

RANDOM FOREST IN FORECASTING RAIN-INDUCED LANDSLIDES

A Thesis

Presented to the Faculty of the
College of Information Technology
University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos

In Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Bachelor of Science in Computer Science

Bachelor of Science in
COMPUTER
SCIENCE

by

Erik A. Agabon

Daniel Jun S. Lamaton

Ranmie G. Montecalvo

2025

The thesis entitled:

RANDOM FOREST IN FORECASTING RAIN-INDUCED LANDSLIDES

submitted by Erik A. Agabon, Daniel Jun S. Lamaton, and Ranmie G. Montecalvo have been examined and are recommended for Oral Defense.

Date of Graduation: July 2026

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researchers would like to express their gratitude to the following individuals for their assistance and support for the completion of the thesis project.

- To Mr. Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D., the course adviser, for his unwavering guidance, patience and dedication, ensuring the team remained motivated and always stayed positive whenever setbacks strike. His constructive feedback every consultation opens a lot of doors leading to new ideas, helping the researchers achieve this great feat of study completion.
- To Ms. Mehreen E. Dolendo, MSCS, Mr. Reymund L. Sabay, MBE, D.B.M, and Mr. Joshua Dela Cruz, MIT Candidate, the panel members, for their exceptional technical expertise and insightful feedback that enhanced the impact of the study.
- To the Interpellators, for their candid feedback, constructive criticism, and suggestions to the output of the team.
- To the Parents and friends of the Researchers, for the boundless support, love, care, patience, and understanding, through financial assistance and encouragement throughout the development of the project.

Above all, the researchers expressed their heartfelt gratitude to the Almighty God for the wisdom, strength, courage, guidance, and hope. Through Him, all things were made possible and given excellence.

The Faculty of the College of Information Technology of the University of Negros Occidental - Recoletos accepts the thesis entitled

RANDOM FOREST IN FORECASTING RAIN-INDUCED LANDSLIDES

submitted by Erik A. Agabon, Daniel Jun S. Lamaton, and Ranmie G. Montecalvo in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Computer Science.

MEHREEN E. DOLENDO, MSCS
Panel Member

JOSHUA E. DELA CRUZ, MIT Candidate
Panel Member

Bachelor of Science in
ELMER T. HARO, Ph.D.
Dean, College of Information Technology

Grade: Very Good

Date: May 30, 2025

Random Forest in Forecasting Rain-Induced Landslides

Erik A. Agabon
University of Negros
Occidental-Recoletos
College of Information Technology
Bacolod City, Philippines
erikagabon125@gmail.com

Daniel Jun S. Lamaton
University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos
College of Information Technology
Bacolod City, Philippines
lamatond444@gmail.com

Ranmie G. Montecalvo
University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos
College of Information Technology
Bacolod City, Philippines
ranmiem@gmail.com

Elmer T. Haro Ph. D.
University of Negros Occidental-Recoletos
College of Information Technology
Bacolod City, Philippines
haroelmer@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Recent studies in the Philippines on landslides have primarily focused on susceptibility mapping and generation of hazard maps. However, research on landslide forecasting remains less explored. As artificial intelligence continues to progress, forecasting methods used have also become more advanced. The study focuses on rainfall, a primary triggering factor of landslides, examining its relationship with environmental variables such as slope, soil type, and soil moisture to predict potential landslide events. The study applies the random forest model to forecast landslides using a minimized yet significant set of predictors (rainfall, slope, soil moisture, slope). One-Way ANOVA was conducted to assess differences in model performance under various combinations of input variables, followed by post hoc tests to determine the most effective predictive variables. The researchers found out that combining rainfall and environmental variables as predictors yielded the highest accuracy at 90%, outperforming models that use only individual variable inputs. These findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the random forest model in forecasting landslides even with limited resources and data, highlighting its potential as a practical and adaptable tool for early warning systems in areas such as the mountainous regions of the Philippines.

COMPUTER SCIENCE CONCEPTS

- Machine Learning • Hyperoptimization
- Supervised Algorithm

KEYWORDS

Forecasting, Random Forest Model, One-Way ANOVA, Post Hoc, Machine Learning

ACM Reference format:

Erik A. Agabon, Daniel Jun S. Lamaton, Ranmie G. Montecalvo, and Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D. 2025. Random Forest in Forecasting Rain-Induced Landslides

1 INTRODUCTION

Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11) and Life on Land (SDG 15) from the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDG), emphasizes the importance of building safe and disaster-prepared communities and promotes sustainable land management practices, protecting forests, and mitigating land degradation to reduce the risk of disasters in vulnerable areas^[1].

Among the many threats to achieving SDG 11 and SDG 15, landslides stand out as a particularly dangerous and unpredictable hazard. Landslides are the downslope movement of earth elements such as rock, debris, and soil with varying speeds from a few inches per year to tens of miles per hour. Ranging from small to large-scale areas, landslides pose a critical threat that is devastating to the environment, infrastructure, and human life^[2]. Factors like rainfall, melting of snow, stream erosion, groundwater changes, earthquakes, volcanic activities, or disturbances by human activities, initiates a slopes downward movement leading to landslide occurrence^[3]. Among the various causes of landslides, the researchers focused on rainfall, one of the most prevalent factors leading to landslides in the Philippines.

To address the challenge of forecasting landslide occurrences, the model used for this study is the machine learning-based random forest model developed by Breiman^[4]. It is the ensemble of decision trees where each tree is trained on the subset of chosen features randomly and independently across the overall trees in the model. This randomness reduces correlation among trees and allows the forest to make near accurate predictions by voting across all trees. By selecting features at random for each split, the model minimizes error rates and achieves comparable performance to other similar boosting methods^[5]. This study focuses on how the random forest model performs well in forecasting rain-induced landslides to elevate community awareness and prevent large-scale casualties.

1.1 Scope of the Study

The goal of this study is to forecast landslides caused by rainfall in the Philippines, a nation regularly hit by natural calamities that endanger towns, infrastructure, and human life. In building safe and resilient communities, it addresses Sustainable Development Goals 11 and 15, and the research used a predictive model that assesses landslide risk based on key environmental factors. By integrating rainfall data with other environmental variables, the model provides more accurate and timely predictions. The study covers dataset from reports such as National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC), and the Mines and Geosciences Bureau (MGB), while other historical landslide data is sourced from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Dataset.

2 METHODOLOGY

To achieve the goal of the study, certain measures are done and this includes the approaches needed to meet that demand. The section highlights the significant methods used and how it was utilized. This includes research design, dataset, data preparation procedures, data analysis, and statistical treatment.

2.1 Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative experimental research design using the random forest model to predict the occurrence of rain-induced landslides. Quantitative research consists of a range of numeric data that is used in a wide field, such as relations among the data, aggregate the data, and compare across aggregated data^[6]. In experimental design, one or more independent variables are manipulated to assess their effect on dependent variables, with the goal of understanding their influence on the latter. Through the means of experimentation, researchers further evaluate if the hypothesis holds true in various cases and is verifiable under certain circumstances.

2.2 Dataset

The study covers data from two primary sources: the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Global Landslide Catalog (GLC) and the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC) of the Philippines (see Tables 1 and 2). The GLC was a global inventory of rainfall-induced landslide events developed at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center since 2007. As shown in Table 1, it includes reports of large-scale movements triggered by rainfall, as

documented in media outlets, disaster databases, scientific literature, and other sources^[7]. The NASA dataset is composed of international sources, therefore, measures were taken to extract and exclusively use data originating from the Philippines.

Dataset	NASA GLC
Type	Historical Landslide Data
Trigger	Rainfall
Total Events	10,000
Filtered Landslide Data	400
Generated Non-landslide Data	400
Total	800

Table 1. Dataset from NASA.

The NDRRMC dataset as seen in Table 2 maintains a valuable and publicly accessible database that consists of detailed annual incident reports of landslides across the country. From this source, the researchers meticulously filtered and extracted only rainfall-induced landslide events from the extensive source, which typically included the date and the time of occurrence.

Dataset	NDRRMC
Type	Historical Landslide Data
Trigger	Rainfall
Total Events	800
Generated Non-landslide Data	800
Total	1600

Table 2. Dataset from NDRRMC.

To determine the performance of the model, particularly in its performance metric and accuracy against the chosen performance metrics, the data was split into two distinct parts namely: the training set (80%) and the test set (20%). The specific distribution of data points assigned to each subset of training and testing is shown in Table 3. This learning process is important for the model to recognize predictive features.

Activity	Percentage Distribution	Number of Data
Training	80%	1930
Test	20%	470
Total	100%	2400

Table 3. Model Training Percentage Distribution.

2.3 Measures and Statistical Treatment

To provide comprehensive and reputable results, this study relies significantly on measurements and statistical approaches for data analysis. In this study, statistical

tools were used to analyze the research objectives. Ultimately, these methods allowed for an assessment of whether to accept or reject the proposed hypotheses.

In this study, logistic regression was utilized as an inferential statistical analysis technique to investigate and quantify the association between the occurrence of landslides, expressed as a binary response, and potential predictor variables (e.g., rainfall and certain environmental conditions). Based on Formula 1, an Odds Ratio (OR) increases above one, it implies a positive relationship. Conversely, an OR less than one indicates a negative relationship, suggesting that an increase in the variable reduces the probability of a landslide. Although logistic regression was used for classification tasks as well, its main objective in this study was to determine how changes in the predictor variables relate to the likelihood of the outcome.

$$P = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_N * X_N))}$$

Formula 1. Logistic Regression.

In this study, a one-way ANOVA as seen in Formula 2 was employed to examine whether there is a statistically significant difference in the accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score of the random forest model when trained using different sets of input variable. The researchers determined whether incorporating multiple variable types leads to an improvement in model performance, or whether certain types of variables contribute more significantly to accurate landslide prediction.

$$F = MSB/MSW$$

Formula 2. One-Way ANOVA.

In this study, the Tukey Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test was utilized. It is one of the common post hoc methods used to perform all possible pair comparisons and provides an adjusted p-value that accounts for all the numerous tests and this is usually done alongside the use of ANOVA. To determine which specific model comparisons indicated statistically significant differences in their respective performance measures, pairwise comparisons among the models that are trained on different sets of input variables are needed using Formula 3 as reference.

$$HSD = \frac{M_i - M_j}{\sqrt{(MSw/nh)}}$$

Formula 3. Tukey HSD.

In this study, the researchers employed a Confusion Matrix to evaluate the performance of the random forest model in landslide prediction. The confusion matrix compares actual and predicted values across target classes, providing a detailed view of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives. Figure 6 shows an example of a 2 x 2 matrix for a binary classification problem.

		Actual Class	
		P	N
Predicted Class	P	TP	FP
	N	FN	TN

Figure 6. Confusion Matrix Diagram.

Accuracy is one of the basic metrics for classification problems that measures the correct predictions made by the model. It is calculated by dividing the total number of correct predictions by the total number of predictions (see Formula 4)^[8]. In this study, accuracy was used as an indicator of how well the model performed.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN}$$

Formula 4. Accuracy.

The precision metric determines the proportion of correctly classified positive samples to the total number of samples predicted as positive which includes both correct and incorrect predictions (see Formula 5). Precision measures the ability of the model to accurately identify a sample as positive^[9]. In this study, this metric helped in understanding the total of actual landslides predicted by the model.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Formula 5. Precision.

The Recall metric calculates the ratio of correctly classified positive samples to the total number of actual positive samples (see Formula 6). It measures the ability of the model in detecting all positive samples in the dataset. The higher the recall, the better the model in identifying most of the actual positive samples^[9].

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

Formula 6. Recall.

The F1-Score represents the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall. It is an important metric for evaluating a classification model with imbalanced data, as it considers both types of errors, such as false positive and false negative, rather than focusing only on the total number of incorrect predictions^[10]. As shown in Formula 7, F1-Score was used alongside precision, recall, and accuracy to identify the overall predictive performance of the model.

$$F1 = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Formula 7. F1-Score.

2.4 Procedures

As illustrated in Figure 3, through various steps, the goal of this study was to forecast landslides. To achieve this, the research used a comprehensive dataset containing historical landslide events and their associated variables. Specifically, a random forest model was implemented using this data to predict the occurrence of landslides.

Figure 3. Operational Framework.

The methodological process began with essential data preprocessing steps, which included cleaning the raw data to address inconsistencies and missing values within the dataset, followed by splitting the cleaned dataset into distinct training and testing sets for the model to use. To explore the relationships between rainfall and environmental variables with landslide occurrences, appropriate tools and models are needed. Moreover, logistic regression was used to examine the influence of categorical and continuous factors such as slope, soil type, and soil moisture on landslide probability. To improve the predictive performance of the random forest model, bayesian optimization was employed for

hyperparameter tuning. Finally, the effectiveness of the model was evaluated using performance metrics such as accuracy, F1-score, precision, and recall, ensuring its reliability in predicting landslide events. Furthermore, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine whether significant differences existed between the performances of various predictive models considered in the study. Lastly, the Tukey HSD (Honest Significant Difference) was used to evaluate which of the predictive models performed better.

2.5 Data Preparation

The dataset collected from various sources were then converted into an applicable format that are used to train the model. Here, a preprocessing phase was undertaken to guarantee both quality and consistency. This phase encompassed the cleaning of the data by eliminating irrelevant, missing, or erroneous entries and concentrating solely on rainfall-induced landslides occurring within the Philippines, utilizing both the NASA GLC and NDRRMC datasets. Categorical attributes, such as soil type and slope, were converted into numerical and binary formats to render them appropriate for machine learning applications. Specific class numerals were assigned to various soil types, while slope values were categorized into discrete ranges that denote differing levels of steepness. To mitigate the data imbalance between landslide and non-landslide instances, the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) was employed to generate synthetic samples for the underrepresented category, thereby enhancing the efficacy of the model in accurately predicting both outcomes. Furthermore, 80% of the dataset was designated for model training and 20% for testing purposes, thereby ensuring a fair evaluation and generalization of the model performance.

3 RESULTS

This chapter analyzes the prediction of rainfall-induced landslides using the random forest model, focusing on the relationship between landslide occurrences and various rainfall and environmental variables. It evaluates the model predictive capability by comparing its accuracy across different input datasets: rainfall-only, environmental-only, and a combination of both. To ensure the reliability of these results, the performance is validated using five-fold cross-validation, mitigating the risk of overfitting. The findings are discussed in relation to the hypotheses of the study to provide insights into the significance of these factors in landslide initiation and the effectiveness of the model for prediction.

3.1 Correlation Between Landslide Occurrence and Rainfall Variables

The results of the L2 Penalized Logistic Regression presented in Table 4 revealed a statistically significant and complex relationship between rainfall and the likelihood of a landslide. The findings show a distinct pattern based on the duration of rainfall: while very short-term rainfall (measured at 3 and 12-hour intervals) was surprisingly associated with a decreased risk, medium to long-term rainfall (measured over 6 hours to 5 days) showed a strong positive correlation with an increased risk of landslides. The most critical factor identified was sustained rainfall over a 3-day period, with 3-day cumulative rainfall being the strongest predictor, increasing the odds of a landslide by 70.1% for each unit increase. The study concludes that the total accumulated rainfall over several days is a more crucial trigger than short, intense bursts, as it leads to the soil saturation and increased pore water pressure that destabilize slopes.

Variable	Coefficient	Odds Ratio	P-value
Cumulative_3hr	-0.228	0.795	0.001
Cumulative_6hr	0.351	1.400	0.001
Cumulative_12hr	-0.104	0.889	0.001
Cumulative_1d	0.251	1.297	0.001
Cumulative_3d	0.525	1.701	0.001
Cumulative_5d	0.380	1.498	0.001
Intensity_3hr	-0.224	0.810	0.001
Intensity_6hr	0.356	1.436	0.001
Intensity_12hr	-0.101	0.900	0.001
Intensity_1d	0.249	1.288	0.001
Intensity_3d	0.523	1.676	0.001
Intensity_5d	0.363	1.399	0.000

Table 4. L2 Penalized Logistic Regression for Rainfall Variables.

3.2 Correlation Between Landslide Occurrence and Environmental Variables

In the analysis derived from the logistic regression (see Table 5) it identified slope steepness and soil moisture as the two most critical environmental factors driving landslide risk. Both variables showed a strong and statistically significant relationship with landslide

occurrence. The model indicates that steeper slopes and higher soil moisture levels dramatically and reliably increase the likelihood of a landslide.

Specifically, the model confirmed that as slope steepness increases, the predicted risk of a landslide rises substantially. Likewise, higher soil moisture content is consistently linked to elevated landslide probability, a trend validated by the concentration of actual landslides at higher moisture levels in the data.

In contrast, after accounting for the dominant effects of slope and moisture, soil type was not found to be a statistically significant predictor of landslide occurrence in this analysis. While different soil types showed some variation in associated risk, this factor was not a reliable indicator compared to the powerful influence of the steepness and saturation of the terrain.

Variable	Odds Ratio	95% CI for Odds Ratio	P-value
Slope	2.671	[2.460, 2.900]	0.000
Soil_Type	1.198	[1.049, 1.369]	0.008
Soil_Moisture	11.670	[3.013, 45.195]	0.000

Table 5. Logistic Regression for Environmental Variables.

3.3 Assessment of the Random Forest Model Performance Across Different Variables

This section evaluates the performance of the random forest model in predicting landslide occurrences using performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score. For further explanation, precision indicates the accuracy of positive predictions for that class, recall measures the models ability to find all positive instances of that class, and the f1-score is a balanced measure of both. Additionally, accuracy was included as a metric.

3.4.1 Random Forest Model Assessment with Rainfall Variables Only. This section of the study focused on using only rainfall variables to train the random forest model. As seen in Table 6 it demonstrated consistent performance during five-fold cross-validation with accuracy, F1, precision, and recall scores primarily between 73% and 79%. The average score was approximately 76%, indicating that rainfall characteristics are a significant predictor of landslide events, correctly identifying outcomes about three-quarters of the time.

Metrics	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	Avg
Accuracy	0.734	0.772	0.790	0.751	0.767	0.763
F1-Score	0.732	0.772	0.790	0.75	0.766	0.763
Precision	0.743	0.773	0.791	0.753	0.772	0.767
Recall	0.734	0.772	0.790	0.751	0.767	0.763

Table 6. Five-Fold Cross Validation for Rainfall Variables Only.

3.4.2. *Random Forest Model Assessment with Environmental Variables Only.* In this section, the researchers conducted a five-fold cross-validation using only environmental factors (soil moisture, soil type, slope) as inputs for the random forest model. The performance metrics, as shown in Table 7, indicated an accuracy and recall range of 81% to 83%. This performance is slightly lower compared to using only rainfall variables, suggesting that environmental variables provide comparable predictive information during the cross-validation phase.

Metrics	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	Avg
Accuracy	0.834	0.833	0.826	0.813	0.842	0.830
F1-Score	0.834	0.833	0.826	0.812	0.842	0.829
Precision	0.838	0.834	0.827	0.819	0.845	0.833
Recall	0.834	0.833	0.826	0.813	0.842	0.830

Table 7. Five-Fold Cross Validation for Environmental Variables Only.

3.4.3 *Random Forest Model Assessment with the Combined Rainfall and Environmental Variables.* The Researchers combined rainfall and environmental variables to train the random forest model, resulting in an improved performance. As shown in Table 8, the five-fold cross validation showed accuracy, F1-score, precision, and recall between 84% and 87%, with an average of 86% across folds. This indicates that both variable types enhance the predictive reliability of the model compared to using either type alone.

Metrics	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	Avg
Accuracy	0.849	0.875	0.859	0.857	0.862	0.861
F1-Score	0.849	0.875	0.859	0.857	0.862	0.86
Precision	0.851	0.875	0.859	0.859	0.867	0.862
Recall	0.849	0.875	0.859	0.857	0.862	0.861

Table 8. Five-fold Cross Validation for Environmental and Rainfall Variables.

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter highlights the solution to the outlined problem statements, discussing detailed findings, and presenting the outcomes of the experimentation process. It discusses the performance of the random forest model in predicting landslides, confirms the hypothesis of the study and suggests possible improvements and future research directions to enhance landslide forecasting systems.

4.1 Conclusion

This section presents a summary of the research findings, highlighting the key predictors of rainfall-induced landslides. It compares the effects of rainfall intensity and cumulative rainfall over various durations, along with environmental factors such as soil moisture, slope, and soil type. The section also evaluates the validity of the study hypotheses and concludes with an assessment of the effectiveness of the random forest model in predicting landslide occurrences using the given variables.

4.1.1 *The Role of Rainfall Variables in Landslide Prediction.* The study concludes that rainfall variables present a complex but significant relationship with landslide occurrences, which varies on various time durations. Sustained, or long-term duration rainfall emerged as the dominant positive predictor, with cumulative rainfall and rainfall intensity over longer durations (6-hour, 1-day, 3-day, and 5-day) showing strong, statistically significant positive correlations with landslide likelihood. Among these, 3-day cumulative rainfall was identified as the most powerful predictor (Odds Ratio = 1.701), closely followed by 3-day rainfall intensity (Odds Ratio = 1.676), indicating that prolonged rainfall saturation is the primary driver of landslide risk.

In contrast, short-term rainfall measures (3-hour and 12-hour) showed negative associations, likely reflecting the model adjustment for the stronger influence of long-term rainfall. Consequently, the hypothesis which proposed a positive correlation between rainfall and landslides, supports the hypothesis which holds for medium- to long-term rainfall but not for very short-term durations. Overall, the findings highlight that longer rainfall duration, rather than brief intense rainfall, are the critical factors that lead to landslide occurrence.

4.1.2 *The Role of Environmental Variables in Landslide Prediction.* The study found that environmental factors

play a critical role in predicting landslide occurrences. This confirms the hypothesis, which proposed a positive correlation between these variables and landslide occurrence. Both soil moisture (1-day) and slope present statistically significant positive relationships. The model also captured differences in landslide probability across soil types, indicating sensitivity to inherent soil properties. However, soil type showed a negative correlation with a p-value of 0.114, suggesting a less significant relationship with landslide. Overall, the results highlight that soil moisture and slope are key environmental determinants of landslide occurrence, reinforcing the importance of incorporating topographic conditions into predictive models and enhancing the overall performance of the random forest model.

4.1.3 Overall Predictive Performance of the Random Forest Model. The utilization of the random forest model demonstrated high performance in predicting rainfall-induced landslides, integrating both rainfall and environmental variables effectively. The analysis presents high accuracy with some misclassifications, which confirms the ability of the model to account for both triggering factors (rainfall) and predisposing conditions (environmental variables). Models trained on rainfall or environmental variables alone achieved an accuracy of (80–86%), indicating that each set provides substantial but limited predictive performance. However, combining both variable feature sets significantly improved performance, achieving high accuracy scores between 86% and 91% during cross-validation.

The use of Bayesian optimization through Optuna increased model accuracy by 3–5%, reaching 91%, highlighting the significant effect of hyperparameter tuning. Statistical analyses using ANOVA and Tukey HSD tests confirmed that the combined model significantly outperformed individual variable models across accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. These results validated the hypothesis that indicates significant difference in model performance depending on variable combinations. Overall, the study highlights the effectiveness of an optimized random forest model for landslide prediction and presents the importance of integrating both rainfall and environmental factors, along with optimization techniques.

4.2 Recommendations

Based on the study findings, several recommendations are proposed by the researchers to improve rainfall-induced landslide forecasting. These include integration of additional predictive variables, the use of

alternative machine learning models, and the improvement of the quality of landslide inventories. Future studies should incorporate the use of other predisposing variables such as land vegetation, soil depth, and terrain attributes like aspect, curvature, elevation, and proximity to rivers or roads. These are gathered through Geographic Information System (GIS) and remote sensing tools. The addition of these variables further enhances the accuracy of the model, making it more reliable on different kinds of mountain terrain.

The integration of the random forest model showed promising results, however future researchers could compare it with other algorithms such as LSTM, Gradient Boosting, Support Vector Machines, and Deep Learning models. The use of hybrid models is also another option, as the performance of one model could be further improved with the aid of another model.

Furthermore, improving landslide inventories is essential for model reliability. Future work should focus on expansion of datasets, accurately mapping landslide occurrences and timing, and integrating remote sensing and ground-based sensor data. Collaboration with government agencies and classification of landslides by type are recommended to ensure more detailed, precise datasets. A high-quality inventory will improve model training, validation, and the overall effectiveness of landslide prediction systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The researchers would like to acknowledge the indispensable contribution of Elmer Haro, Ph.D., the researcher adviser, for the vital support and guidance in accomplishing this milestone of finishing undergraduate research.

The proponents would also like to express their gratitude to their parents for their unwavering support and the benefactors who have helped and accompanied them throughout the project.

REFERENCES

- [1] THE 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development. (n.d.). <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
- [2] UNISDR. (2017). Words into Action Guidelines: National Disaster Risk Assessment - Hazard Specific Risk Assessment - Landslide Hazard and Risk Assessment. https://www.unisdr.org/files/52828_03landslidehazardandriskassessment.pdf
- [3] U.S. Geological Survey. (2017). What is a landslide and what causes one? U.S. Department of the Interior. Retrieved February 19, 2025, from <https://www.usgs.gov/faqs/what-a-landslide-and-what-causes-one>

- [4] Breiman, L. (2001). Random forests. *Machine Learning*, 45(1), 5–32. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010933404324>
- [5] Freund, Y., & Schapire, R. E. (1996, July). Experiments with a new boosting algorithm. In *icml* (Vol. 96, pp. 148-156).
- [6] Coghlan, D., & Brydon-Miller, M. (2014). *The SAGE encyclopedia of action research* (Vols. 1-2). London: SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446294406>
- [7] Kirschbaum, D. B., Adler, R., Hong, Y., Hill, S., & Lerner-Lam, A. (2010). A global landslide catalog for hazard applications: method, results, and limitations. *Natural Hazards*, 52(3), 561–575. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-009-9401-4>
- [8] Bressler, N. (2024, June 10). How to Check the Accuracy of Your Machine Learning Model. Deepchecks. Retrieved from <https://www.deepchecks.com/how-to-check-the-accuracy-of-your-machine-learning-model/>
- [9] Gad, A. F., & Skelton, J. (2024, August 28). Evaluating deep learning models: The confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, and recall. DigitalOcean. www.digitalocean.com/community/tutorials/deep-learning-metric-precision-recall-accuracy#accuracy-precision-and-recall
- [10] Sharma, N. (2023, June 6). Understanding and applying F1 Score: AI evaluation essentials with hands-on coding example. Arize. arize.com/blog-course/f1-score

LIST OF FIGURES

1. Type of Rainfall Induced Landslides.....	18
2. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework.....	28
3. Operational Framework.....	38
4. Sample Soil Types.....	40
5. Random Forest Model Process.....	44
6. Confusion Matrix Diagram.....	49
7. System Decomposition Chart.....	56
8. Landing Page.....	60
9. Dynamic Map Page.....	61
10. Dynamic Map Page (Forecasting).....	62
11. Prediction Report Page.....	63
12. Dashboard Page.....	64
13. User Guide Page.....	65
14. Training Result Page.....	66
15. Soil Moisture Result.....	79
16. Slope Result.....	80
17. Soil Type Result.....	81
18. Confusion Matrix.....	85

LIST OF TABLES

1. Dataset from NASA.....	33
2. Dataset from NDRRMC.....	34
3. Classification of Variables Used.....	35
4. Model Training Percentage Distribution.....	36
5. Soil Type Classification.....	41
6. Slope Ranking Classification.....	42
7. Survey Results Interpretation.....	70
8. Summary of Survey Results.....	71
9. L2 Penalized Logistic Regression for Rainfall Variables.....	77
10. Logistic Regression for Environmental Variables.....	78
11. Five-Fold Cross Validation for Rainfall Variables Only.....	83
12. Five-Fold Cross Validation for Environmental Variables Only.....	84
13. Five-Fold Cross Validation for Environmental and Rainfall Variables.....	84
14. ANOVA Result.....	87
15. Post-hoc for Accuracy Result.....	87
16. Post-hoc for F1-score Result.....	88
17. Post-hoc for Precision Result.....	89
18. Post-hoc for Recall Result.....	89
19. Random Forest Model Evaluation Result.....	90

LIST OF FORMULAS

1. Logistic Regression.....	46
2. One-Way ANOVA.....	47
3. Tukey HSD.....	48
4. Accuracy.....	50
5. Precision.....	51
6. Recall.....	51
7. F1- Score.....	52

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGMENT.....	iv
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	v
LIST OF FIGURES.....	xiii
LIST OF TABLES.....	xiv
LIST OF FORMULAS.....	xv

Chapter

I. INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 Statement of the Problem.....	2
1.2 Hypothesis.....	3
1.3 Assumption.....	4
1.4 Scope of the Study.....	5
1.4.1 Sources of Data.....	5
1.4.2 Rainfall and Environmental Variables.....	6
1.4.3 Random Forest Model.....	6
1.4.4 Performance Metrics.....	7
1.5 Significance of the Study.....	8
1.5.1 Mines and Geosciences Bureau (MGB).....	8
1.5.2 National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC).....	8
1.5.3 Communities Near Mountainous Areas.....	9
1.5.4 Future Researchers.....	9
II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE.....	11
2.1 Machine Learning.....	11
2.1.1 Supervised Learning.....	12
2.1.2 Machine Learning Models in Forecasting Landslide.....	13
2.2 The Random Forest Model.....	14
2.2.1 Random Forest Model and Its Process.....	14
2.2.2 Random Forest Model Hyperparameters.....	15
2.2.3 Hyperparameter Tuning.....	15

2.3	Soil Erosion Theory.....	16
2.4	Landslides and Triggering Factors.....	17
2.4.1	Types of Landslides.....	18
2.4.2	Common Triggering Factors.....	19
2.4.3	Factors Affecting Landslide Susceptibility.....	19
2.5	Rainfall as a Key Trigger.....	20
2.6	The Influence of Spatial and Temporal Variables on Landslides.....	22
2.6.1	Spatial Variables.....	22
2.6.2	Temporal Variables.....	23
2.7	Case Studies on Landslide Occurrence in the Philippines.....	24
2.8	Random Forest Model in Landslide Forecasting.....	25
2.8.1	Spatial and Temporal Forecasting.....	26
2.9	Theoretical and Conceptual Framework.....	27
2.10	Synthesis.....	29
III.	METHODOLOGY.....	31
3.1	Research Design.....	32
3.2	Dataset Collection and Characterization.....	32
3.3	Procedures.....	37
3.3.1	Data Preparation.....	39
3.3.2	Data Preprocessing.....	39
3.3.3	Model Training.....	43
3.3.4	Hyperparameter Optimization.....	44
3.4	Statistical Treatment.....	45
3.4.1	Logistic Regression.....	45
3.4.2	Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).....	47
3.4.3	Tukey Honest Significant Difference (HSD).....	48
3.5	Performance Metrics.....	49
3.5.1	Confusion Matrix.....	49
3.5.2	Accuracy.....	50
3.5.3	Precision.....	50
3.5.4	Recall.....	51
3.5.5	F1-Score.....	51
3.6	Ethical Consideration.....	52
3.7	APIs and Development Tools.....	53
IV.	SOLUTION.....	55
4.1	System Decomposition Chart.....	55
4.1.1	Data Entry.....	56
4.1.2	Forecasting.....	57
4.1.3	Analytics.....	57
4.2	Technology/Development Tools.....	58

4.2.1	Frontend Development.....	58
4.2.2	Backend Development.....	59
4.2.3	Jupyter Notebook.....	59
4.3	User Interfaces.....	60
4.3.1	Dynamic Map (Data Entry).....	61
4.3.2	Dynamic Map (Forecasting).....	62
4.3.3	Prediction Report Summary (Analytics).....	63
4.3.4	Dashboard (Analytics).....	64
4.3.5	User Guide.....	65
4.3.6	Training Result.....	66
4.4	System Validation.....	66
4.4.1	Unit Testing.....	67
4.4.2	Integration Testing.....	68
4.4.3	System Testing.....	68
4.4.4	Acceptance Testing.....	69
V.	RESULTS, ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION.....	74
5.1	Correlation Between Landslide Occurrence and Rainfall Variables.....	74
5.1.1	Rainfall Intensity (3, 6, 12 hours, and 1, 3, 5 days).....	75
5.1.2	Cumulative Rainfall (3, 6, 12 hours, and 1, 3, 5 days).....	76
5.2	Correlation between Landslide Occurrence and Environmental Variables.....	77
5.2.1	Soil Moisture (1 day).....	78
5.2.2	Slope.....	80
5.2.3	Soil Type.....	81
5.3	Assessment of the Random Forest Model Performance Across Different Variables.....	82
5.3.1	Random Forest Model Assessment with Rainfall Variables Only.....	82
5.3.2	Random Forest Model Assessment with Environmental Variables Only.....	83
5.3.3	Random Forest Model Assessment with the Combined Rainfall and Environmental Variables.....	84
5.3.4	Confusion Matrix.....	85
5.4	Hypothesis Testing.....	86
5.4.1	Post-hoc Test for Model Accuracy.....	87
5.4.2	Post-hoc Test for Model F1-score.....	88
5.4.3	Post-hoc Test for Model Precision.....	88
5.4.4	Post-hoc Test for Model Recall.....	89
5.5	Evaluation of Random Forest Model with Bayesian Optimization.....	90
VI.	CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION.....	92
6.1	Conclusion.....	92
6.1.1	The Role of Rainfall Variables in Landslide Prediction.....	93

6.1.2	The Role of Environmental Variables in Landslide Prediction.....	94
6.1.3	Overall Predictive Performance of the Random Forest Model.....	95
6.2	Recommendation.....	97
6.2.1	Integration of Additional Predictive Variables.....	98
6.2.2	Exploration of Alternative Predictive Models.....	98
6.2.3	Development of a More Comprehensive Landslide Inventory.....	99
6.2.4	Automated Collection of Landslide Data.....	100
PROJECT MANAGEMENT.....		101
A.	Hardware Recommendation.....	101
B.	Software Recommendation.....	102
C.	Peopeware Recommendation.....	103
D.	System Budget.....	104
E.	Time Management.....	105
GLOSSARY.....		106
LIST OF SCREENSHOTS.....		111
USERS' MANUAL.....		112
APPENDICES.....		125
A.	Mutual Agreement Form for Co-Authorship.....	125
B.	Concept Paper.....	126
C.	PERT Table.....	130
D.	PERT Diagram.....	131
E.	System Budget.....	132
F.	Minutes of the Thesis Project Proposal Defense.....	133
G.	Minutes of the Thesis Final Defense.....	135
H.	Landslide Dataset.....	137
I.	Artificial Intelligence Tools Used.....	202
J.	Product Logo.....	204
K.	Team Logo.....	205
L.	Product Poster.....	206
M.	Product Packaging.....	207
N.	Grammarly Results.....	208
O.	Turnitin Results.....	209
REFERENCES.....		210
CURRICULUM VITAE.....		220

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11) and Life on Land (SDG 15) from the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDG) emphasize the importance of building safe and disaster-prepared communities and promoting sustainable land management practices, protecting forests, and mitigating land degradation to reduce the risk of disasters in vulnerable areas [SD2024]. Between 1998 and 2017, landslides killed over 18,000 people and affected 4.8 million worldwide, significantly hindering progress towards this goal. Their destructive impacts on communities are worsened by their disruption of vital utilities, including communication networks, water supplies, energy, and healthcare systems [WH2019]. In addition to their harm to communities, landslides severely impact the environment. Landslides degrade forests and habitats and damage aquatic ecosystems, while the widespread loss of forest cover threatens biodiversity and wildlife [GM2008]. These impacts highlight the urgent need for sustainable land management practices to protect and restore terrestrial ecosystems.

Among the many threats to achieving SDG 11 and SDG 15, landslides stand out as particularly hazardous and unpredictable. Landslides are the downslope movement of earth materials such as rock, debris, and soil, with speeds ranging from a few inches per year to tens of miles per hour. From small to large-scale areas, landslides pose a critical threat, devastating the environment, infrastructure, and human life [UN2017]. Factors such as rainfall, snowmelt, stream erosion, groundwater changes, earthquakes, volcanic activity, or disturbances from human activities initiate a downward movement of the slope, leading to

landslide occurrence [US2017]. Landslides occur gradually or suddenly, unexpectedly. The most dangerous are sudden landslides, which happen in an instant, leaving little to no time to react before one is buried beneath the debris.

To address the challenge of forecasting landslide occurrences, this study uses a machine-learning-based random forest model developed by Breiman [BL2001]. It is the ensemble of decision trees where each tree is trained on a subset of chosen features randomly and independently across all the trees in the model. This randomness reduces correlation among trees and allows the forest to make near-accurate predictions by voting across all trees. By selecting features at random for each split, the model minimizes error rates and achieves performance comparable to other boosting methods [FY1996]. Furthermore, the random forest model provides built-in methods for monitoring error rates, feature importance, and correlations, making them valuable for both classification and regression tasks. This approach has evolved from earlier methods such as bagging, random split selection, and the random subspace method, all of which introduce randomness to improve prediction accuracy [BL2001].

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Rainfall-induced landslides are among the most common types of landslides. Forecasting these landslides involves analyzing both spatial and temporal variables. However, forecasting landslides is challenging due to the numerous factors that is considered. This study focuses on rainfall, the primary triggering factor for predicting landslide occurrences. Environmental variables are utilized to examine their significant

relationship with landslide occurrences. By analyzing the role of rainfall and environmental variables in landslide initiation, the researchers assess the random forest model capability to predict landslides. Specifically, the study addresses the following research questions:

1.1.1 The correlation between landslide occurrence and the rainfall variables measured over the following durations (3 hrs, 6 hrs, 12 hrs, 1 day, 3 days, 5 days), which include:

1.1.1.1 Rainfall Intensity

1.1.1.2 Cumulative Rainfall

1.1.2 The correlation between landslide occurrence and environmental variables, which include:

1.1.2.1 Soil Moisture (1 day)

1.1.2.2 Slope

1.1.2.3 Soil Type

1.1.3 The difference in the performance metrics of the random forest model in predicting landslide events, using:

1.1.3.1 Rainfall Variables (rainfall intensity, cumulative rainfall)

1.1.3.2 Environmental Variables (soil moisture, slope, soil type)

1.1.3.3 Both Rainfall and Environmental Variable

1.2 Hypothesis

Based on the formulation of problem statements, the following hypotheses have been established to explore the relationship between landslide occurrence and various

environmental factors. Through evaluation of these hypotheses, this study aimed to provide a deeper understanding of the factors influencing landslides. Furthermore, in its contribution to the creation of accurate predictive models.

1.2.1 There is a positive correlation between the rainfall variables and landslide occurrence.

1.2.2 There is a positive correlation between environmental variables and the landslide occurrence.

1.2.3 There is a significant difference in the performance metrics of the random forest model in predicting landslide events using the rainfall and environmental variables.

1.3 Assumption

This section presents the assumptions that the researchers are likely to encounter that affect the development and effectiveness of the study and system. These assumptions address potential areas for refinement, guide the study scope, and set realistic expectations for its outcomes. By defining them early in the research process, the researchers narrow the scope of the study, set realistic expectations, and identify critical factors that influence the performance of the system. This study is based on the following assumptions:

1.3.1 That the model performs effectively in the Philippines across different terrains and regions prone to landslides;

1.3.2 That environmental factors used as variables have a significant influence on predicting landslide occurrences;

1.3.3 That the accuracy of the random forest model is affected by the quantity of datasets, and;

1.3.4 That short-term rainfall accumulation variables (3, 6, and 12 hours) are not significant.

1.4 Scope of the Study

The goal of this study is to forecast landslides caused by rainfall in the Philippines, a nation regularly hit by natural calamities that endanger towns, infrastructure, and human life. In building safe and resilient communities, it addresses Sustainable Development Goals 11 and 15, and the research used a predictive model that assesses landslide risk based on key environmental factors. By integrating rainfall data with other environmental variables, the model provides more accurate and timely predictions.

1.4.1 Sources of Data

Geographically, the study collects data on recent landslides, spanning from 2017 to the present, from sources such as news sites, reports or articles from the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH), National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC), and the Mines and Geosciences Bureau (MGB), while other historical landslide data is sourced from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Global Landslide Dataset [KD2010]. By combining data from various sources, the researchers ensure a more robust landslide inventory repository that spans a wide timeframe. This approach targets landslide-prone areas across multiple terrains in the Philippines, focusing on regions

with a recorded history of landslides. To identify significant trends in rainfall-induced landslides, the study analyzed historical landslide data from recent years. To improve the forecasting accuracy of the model, rainfall data from days or weeks before events is examined. For other variables in the study, different sources were used to improve data quality, including the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO).

1.4.2 Rainfall and Environmental Variables

This study focuses on rainfall as the primary landslide trigger, and its sub-variables, such as rainfall intensity and cumulative rainfall, were specifically evaluated to determine their relationship to landslide occurrences and their role in landslide risk. Other environmental factors, such as soil moisture, slope, and soil type, were also assessed. These variables were gathered through various resources. By clearly defining and focusing on these variables, the study aimed to deepen understanding of the relationship between rainfall and environmental factors in landslide-occurrence prediction.

1.4.3 Random Forest Model

This model is a machine learning ensemble technique that was used in the modeling approach to predict landslides based on temporal and spatial data. This was specifically chosen because of its ability to utilize both numerical and categorical variables without making any assumptions about the statistical distribution of the data and because it assesses its own predictive performance during the training process without requiring separate validation steps or manual intervention as one of its many

benefits, which contribute to its popularity [NN2023]. Furthermore, a study applied the random forest model for landslide prediction because the model is commonly used in classification methods and does not require assumptions on the distribution of explanatory factors highlighting its utility [CY2021]. Moreover, the model examined the correlation between certain environmental variables and landslide occurrences, enabling the ranking of feature relevance and the identification of the most predictive components. To ensure the model is used successfully in different parts of the Philippines, its accuracy and dependability were monitored and improved through rigorous validation, cross-regional testing, and parameter tuning that made the model more accurate.

1.4.4 Performance Metrics

The effectiveness of this model was evaluated using metrics such as accuracy, F1-score, precision, and recall to gauge its accuracy and reliability, especially in distinguishing between high and low risk conditions. These metrics were used to ensure that the model detects landslide risks while minimizing false alarms and to assess its performance. Collectively, these quantitative measures provide a comprehensive framework for determining the operational readiness and predictive validity of the model.

Despite valuable findings, the study faced limitations that impacted generalization and precision. Key assumptions included the belief that environmental variables like slope, soil moisture, and rainfall intensity were reliable predictors of landslide occurrence. The

focus on rainfall-induced landslides excluded other trigger types, limiting model applicability in regions with different influential factors. Additionally, the performance of the random forest model was assumed effective across the diverse topography and geology of the Philippines, yet regional climatic and geological variations affect accuracy. Adjustments or retraining of the model are necessary for regions with distinct environmental traits.

1.5 Significance of the Study

Landslides pose a serious threat to ecosystems, infrastructure, and human safety, particularly under conditions of heavy rainfall. This study contributes to society by providing insights into landslide susceptibility and early warning capabilities, this research holds the potential to mitigate risks, inform disaster preparedness strategies, and contribute to the safety and resilience of vulnerable communities. The following persons and organizations are expected to benefit from this study:

1.5.1 Mines and Geosciences Bureau (MGB)

The findings of this study benefit the MGB, an organization responsible for landslide susceptibility mapping and assessment. By integrating the findings, the bureau enhances the accuracy of its creation of landslide susceptibility maps in the Philippines. Additionally, it helps the bureau identify and add the high-risk areas that are not yet present in their repository.

1.5.2 National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC)

The findings of this study are able to be utilized by NDRRMC to improve its plans and strategies for dealing with landslide incidents. By incorporating the

findings, the agency enhances its early warning systems, thereby reducing the impact of landslides by providing accurate information to communities and responders. Additionally, this helps the agency implement precautionary measures in the areas identified as high-risk. Moreover, the conclusions formulated by this study serves as a scientific reference for updating national disaster protocols and formulating stricter land-use policies in landslide-prone regions.

1.5.3 Communities Near Mountainous Areas

These communities benefit from this study as it promotes risk awareness and education regarding areas that are prone to landslides. Furthermore, with the early warning information, residents in high-risk areas are able to evacuate sooner, preventing potential casualties. The study also provides insights to locals on where to build homes and infrastructure, reducing their exposure to landslide hazards.

1.5.4 Future Researchers

The outcomes of this study serve as a foundation for future researchers in using the random forest model in landslide forecasting in the Philippines. Future researchers benefit from expanding its application by incorporating additional environmental variables and training it on larger datasets. Furthermore, this study guides future researchers in evaluating the potential of the random forest model for integration into early warning systems.

In conclusion, this chapter outlined the significance of landslide forecasting in relation to Sustainable Development Goals 11 and 15 and signifies the urgency in having

predictive models to help mitigate landslide risks, especially for the landslide prone regions of the Philippines. While focusing on rainfall and environmental variables, this research strengthened the understanding of the relationship between these factors and the incidence of landslides. This study adopted the random forest model in predicting landslide events to determine the accuracy of the model in the context of landslide forecasting and providing an opportunity for better and reliable identification of landslide susceptibility.

Furthermore, the findings of this study emphasize the importance of collaboration among government agencies, local communities, and scientific institutions in addressing landslide hazards. By providing data-driven insights that support landslide susceptibility mapping, early warning systems, and disaster preparedness planning, this research strengthens institutional capacities and community resilience. The practical applicability of the results enables decision-makers to adopt proactive risk reduction measures, while empowering vulnerable communities with timely and reliable information. Ultimately, this study highlights the value of integrating scientific modeling approaches into national and local disaster risk management frameworks, contributing to sustainable development and long-term environmental protection in landslide-prone areas of the Philippines.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter provides an overview of the existing literature on landslide prediction, particularly rainfall-induced landslides, and the utilisation of machine learning models, such as random forest, in this challenge. It seeks to understand the factors leading to landslide formation, the methods for predicting landslides, and why these spatial and temporal variables are significant for predicting landslides. The discussion begins by outlining the theory behind machine learning and emphasizes the effectiveness of the random forest model in classification and regression tasks. Further on, discussions about landslides are examined and, in particular, about their classification, triggering factors, and variables affecting susceptibility, with a focus on rainfall as a critical driver of such events. Case studies on landslides in the Philippines have been incorporated to contextualize the discussion within a more specific or regional framework. Furthermore, the chapter highlights the intersection of spatial and temporal variables in landslide forecasting, underscoring the importance of integrating them to improve predictive accuracy.

2.1 Machine Learning

It is a computational approach that enables systems to improve by learning from experience, representing experience as data. It therefore allows making predictions for new observations by building algorithms that generate models from this data. It is an approach that mirrors human learning, where experience-based patterns guide decision-making. For example, predicting favorable weather based on past occurrences [ZZ2021].

The theory behind machine learning is derived from statistics, where learning is referred to as estimation, and inference is the process of moving from specific observations, known as the sample, to broad descriptions of the population. A developing area of computer algorithms called machine learning aims to mimic human intelligence by learning from its surroundings. The objective is to create computer programs that learn to perform better through experience, where experience means past data, such as previous trials, and better means optimizing a performance criterion. From the perspective of a programmer, this improvement arises from changing decision-making mechanisms so that, as the amount of data to be processed increases, the program delivers higher performance according to the defined criterion [AE2021].

2.1.1 Supervised Learning

Machine learning, a branch of artificial intelligence, involves using algorithms to analyze data and identify patterns, making predictions. It is typically categorized into two main approaches. The first is supervised learning, which relies on labeled data for training, and the second is unsupervised learning, which uncovers patterns in unlabeled data [BI2024].

One of the most crucial aspects of machine learning is supervised learning, the theory and practice of algorithms that, given current independent and dependent variables, identify patterns in data and forecast future values of dependent variables. This approach involves training algorithms on labeled datasets. With applications across a variety of fields, supervised learning is a widely used machine learning technique [TA2022].

In machine learning, regression is considered a kind of supervised learning. In this kind of learning, the researchers have the input and the intended result for every example. In this context, learning is the process of adjusting the parameters of the model to enable it to predict the data with the highest possible accuracy. Moreover, the performance of the regression model is determined by how well the predictions match the observed output values in the training data. In the general case, learning is defined as improving based on a performance criterion [AL2021].

2.1.2 Machine Learning Models in Forecasting Landslide

They are widely used for forecasting landslides. A survey conducted, identified the random forest model, decision tree, and support vector machine as among the most commonly used machine learning models in spatial forecasting [TF2022]. Meanwhile, in recent years, several studies have compared various machine learning models to evaluate their effectiveness in predicting rainfall-induced landslides. A study compared five machine learning classification algorithms: logistic regression, support vector machine, k-nearest neighbor, extreme gradient boosting, and random forest [JK2024]. Through a comprehensive analysis, the researchers have revealed that the random forest model combined with a landslide susceptibility map outperformed the other forecasting models.

Moreover, it was concluded that supervised learning achieves higher prediction accuracy than unsupervised learning because it leverages recorded landslides as prior knowledge during training and testing of landslide susceptibility models, enabling algorithms to make more informed decisions and accurate

predictions. Meanwhile, the low accuracy of unsupervised machine learning models has been attributed in large part to the absence of prior knowledge and target guidance [CZ2020].

2.2 The Random Forest Model

Among supervised algorithms, the random forest model has emerged as a powerful and reliable method that enhances accuracy while mitigating overfitting by aggregating the results of multiple decision trees. This algorithm proves effective for both classification and regression tasks by employing techniques such as bootstrapping and randomly selecting features during tree construction. The random forest method includes processes such as bagging and result aggregation, with essential components such as feature randomness and data sampling, as well as tunable hyperparameters [G2024b]. These elements collectively demonstrate the flexibility of the model and efficacy in addressing challenging supervised learning problems.

2.2.1 Random Forest Model and Its Process

The model falls under the supervised learning approach category, widely used in machine learning tasks. It is an ensemble of decision trees where each tree is built using a data sample made out of a training set with a replacement, often referred to as the bootstrap sample. This resampling technique helps prevent overfitting. About one-third of this training sample is not used to train the tree and is stored as test data, called the out-of-bag (OOB) sample [IB2024]. Randomness is further introduced through features such as bagging, which considers only a subset of features at each

split, enhancing diversity among decision trees and reducing correlation between them. The method for determining predictions depends on the task. In regression, the predictions from all trees are averaged, while in classification, a majority vote determines the predicted class. Lastly, the OOB sample is used for cross-validation to estimate model performance and refine the final prediction [IB2024].

2.2.2 Random Forest Model Hyperparameters

The model has several hyperparameters that were adjusted to enhance its performance. Key parameters include `n_estimators`, which specifies the number of decision trees in the forest, where more trees improve accuracy but increase training time; `max_features`, which determines the number of features considered for splitting nodes, balancing accuracy and the risk of overfitting; `min_samples_split`, which sets the minimum samples needed to split a node, affecting reliability and underfitting; `min_samples_leaf`, the minimum samples in a leaf node, influencing model conservativeness; and `max_depth`, which limits the depth of the tree to prevent overfitting. Additionally, `random_state` controls the random seed for reproducibility. Other tunable aspects include the splitting criterion and methods for handling missing values [VM2023].

2.2.3 Hyperparameter Tuning

It is a parameter that is set before running a machine learning algorithm. Unlike regular parameters, which are fixed, hyperparameters are adjusted during training to optimize the model. Examples of hyperparameters include the number of features considered for each split in a random forest model, the number of boosting

iterations in gradient boosting, the value of k in k -nearest neighbors, the regularization weights in lasso and ridge regression within elastic net, and the kernel function in support vector machines [PP2019]. Machine learning models require selecting certain hyperparameters tailored to both the dataset and the model during training. These hyperparameters, which guide the learning process of the model, needs to be fine-tuned to achieve optimal performance. The process is known as hyperparameter tuning, which involves systematically testing different combinations to find the best fit. This process was done manually or automated using specialized techniques. Each experiment runs the model with a new configuration, and the outcomes are analyzed to determine which setup performs best. Metrics such as a loss function are often used to measure effectiveness [AW2024]. Hyperparameter tuning methods include grid search, which tests all possible parameter combinations; randomized search, which samples parameter values randomly; and Bayesian optimization, which uses statistical models to identify optimal values and the best configuration for a random forest model [VM2023]. With in-depth understanding of hyperparameters and the identification of optimal values, overfitting and accuracy issues are mitigated [G2021].

2.3 Soil Erosion Theory

Theoretical and applied research on landslides examines the processes and factors that drive the movement and instability of various types of soil and sediment on slopes. A study on soil erosion theory found that the main causes of soil erosion and crusting are the

disintegration of soil aggregates and the separation of soil particles by precipitation. The stability of soil aggregates is directly related to this process, which increases soil erosion. Aggregate breakdown is caused by a range of processes that vary with soil conditions and rainfall patterns. These mechanisms, along with the physical and chemical characteristics of the soil, provide a means to evaluate its vulnerability to erosion and crusting across a range of scenarios. However, it was concluded that other factors also influence erosion processes, even if aggregate stability is a crucial feature [LY2016].

Meanwhile, in a study on cohesive soil erosion theory, it is stated that the process is complex and influenced by chemical reactions between the eroding fluid and soil pore water, as well as soil characteristics and flow hydraulics. Soil particle bonding is specifically crucial because cohesive soils (e.g., clay, silty clay, organic clay, etc.) erode as aggregates. In contrast, non-cohesive soils (e.g., sand, gravel, silt) erode as individual grains. Changes in the quantity and physical condition of soil pore water also affect cohesive soil resistance to erosion. Moreover, the magnitude of water-induced forces acting on soil forecasts the rate of soil erosion [UB2008].

2.4 Landslides and Triggering Factors

A landslide is a natural phenomenon in which rock, soil, and/or debris move downward due to gravity, and the interaction of geological agents and processes with the geo-materials controls the process. Consequently, identifying specific triggering mechanisms is essential for predicting slope instability. Factors such as mass movements, floods, tsunamis, cyclones, and earthquakes are the most common natural hazards and have

disastrous impacts [PS2019]. Because landslides are complex, it is crucial to understand how factors interact to develop effective risk assessment and mitigation plans.

2.4.1 Types of Landslides

Landslides have been classified based on their mode of movement and the material involved. The authors identified seven primary types of movement, namely: fall, topple, slide, spread, flow, slope deformation, and complex movements. Moreover, the authors classified the landslide materials into two categories: soil and rock. Together, these categories define the specific nature and behavior of the geological hazard [HO2013].

However, for this study, the focus narrowed to rainfall-induced landslides. As seen in Figure 1, very strong rainfall, particularly that delivering very high precipitation over just a few hours, which tends to add more moisture to the soil, is usually what causes rapid debris flows. In contrast, deep-seated landslides, which involve the gradual failure of subsurface material, are associated with periods of almost continuous rainfall or cumulative rainfall that last from a few weeks to several months [ZJ2015].

Figure 1. Type of Rainfall Induced Landslides.

Meanwhile, shallow landslides typically occur in red-bed terrains with steep topography and soil remnants of degradable strength due to heavy rainfall [WL2018]. Additionally, studies have shown that landslide types exhibit different distributions, with rainfall-induced shallow landslides accounting for the largest percentage (38.3%) of the incidents examined. In contrast, deep-seated landslides account for a smaller percentage (4.7%). Moreover, some studies have also focused on specific types of landslides, such as earth flows (3.9%), rockslides (2.3%), and debris flows (25.8% of cases) [SS2018]. This high prevalence validates the prioritization of rainfall parameters in predictive modeling.

2.4.2 Common Triggering Factors

Landslides are caused by external stimuli known as trigger factors. Rainfall, snowmelt, temperature changes, earthquake activity, and human activity are a few of them. Causal variables include internal parameters such as stress, shear strength, and pore water pressure that affect soil stability [JA2024].

A study done in the Philippines emphasizes that landslides result from a combination of more stable geological and physical factors, such as slope steepness, soil composition, and weathering. These are compounded by triggering mechanisms. Moreover, these mechanisms include heavy rainfall, seismic activity, and volcanic eruptions [BM2016].

2.4.3 Factors Affecting Landslide Susceptibility

Landslide susceptibility is the extent to which terrain is affected by future slope changes; it is viewed as a prediction of where landslides are most likely to

occur [GF2006]. The scale of the anticipated landslide and the temporal probability of failure are not accounted for in susceptibility. Key ecological factors are most commonly used in landslide susceptibility mapping [BM2024]. The researchers highlighted that slope, precipitation, and soil type/texture were among the most frequently used criteria in the reviewed literature.

Furthermore, based on the landslide susceptibility assessment, five factors were identified as having the greatest impact on landslide occurrence in the area. These specific variables are the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), soil texture, slope degree, altitude, and height above the nearest drainage. Finally, rather than human-related factors, such as residential areas and proximity to roads, it is thought that a complex environmental collection of causes is more responsible for the susceptibility to landslides in the area [HH2018].

2.5 Rainfall as a Key Trigger

Rainfall alters the dynamics of surface and groundwater, weakening slope stability and increasing the risk of landslides. Such events seriously threaten infrastructures and populations. The prediction of rainfall-induced landslide likelihood is therefore crucial [GF2022]. Moreover, short-term heavy rainfall events are most important for triggering landslides when their cumulative amounts occur within two days. They provide sufficient time for pore water pressure to build to an adequate level for slope failure [NN2023].

The influence of long-term rainfall is minimal, particularly for shallow landslides, which are more effectively affected by short-duration events. Seasonal variations also play a

major role, especially in wet months, when the landslide is more prone to occur due to partially saturated soils. Even lesser-intensity rainfall is insufficient to overcome the dry soil status in dry seasons, which require higher intensity to surpass the dry soil status. However, it is important to understand that while measuring rainfall in terms of hours achieved high performance, daily data also yielded similar results, and the uncertainties associated with hourly data cancel out its advantages [LE2020].

Intensity-Duration (ID) thresholds have been analyzed and found that rainfall patterns influence the occurrence of slope failures [GF2007]. Intense, short-duration rainfall often triggers shallow landslides in highly permeable soils, while prolonged, moderate rainfall causes both shallow and deep-seated landslides in less permeable soils. Meanwhile, shorter rainfall events showed consistent minimum intensities for landslide initiation, whereas longer events exhibited greater variability, influenced by factors such as soil moisture, antecedent rainfall, and evapotranspiration.

Additionally, it was demonstrated that antecedent precipitation, rather than one-day rainfall, was more strongly linked to landslide occurrence. The significance of sustained moisture accumulation in slope instability was highlighted by a comparison that showed five-day antecedent cumulative rainfall had a greater impact on landslide occurrence than single-day rainfall [KM2020]. This suggests that in many geological settings, deep soil saturation is a prerequisite for failure. However, a study conducted in Hong Kong found that rolling rainfall factors are also significant for predicting landslides, as most landslides in the area are shallow and are primarily influenced by recent intense rainfall rather than prolonged accumulation [NC2021].

2.6 The Influence of Spatial and Temporal Variables on Landslides

Landslide susceptibility research usually involves both spatial and temporal variables to identify where and when landslides occur. Consequently, studies that capture both types of variables offer an in-depth understanding of how they interact in similar environments, thereby making them highly relevant for landslide prediction and risk management. The assessment of landslide prediction models and establishing thresholds for early warning systems is made easier by understanding the spatial and temporal distributions of landslides and their relationships to triggering causes [GD2023].

2.6.1 Spatial Variables

The spatial depiction of characteristics deemed significant for forecasting future landslide occurrences is necessary to establish appropriate landslide susceptibility, hazard, and risk assessments [VC2008]. Moreover, slope is a crucial variable, as its displacement and tilting behavior are reliable indicators for detecting and predicting shallow landslides across varying conditions [XJ2019]. The slope is a major factor in the occurrence of disasters, and the greater the slope angle increases, the greater the damage. Additionally, the slope angle is the most important static component among the affecting factors ([KM2020]; [NC2021]).

Landslides caused by rainfall are related to the intensity and pattern of the rainfall, the slopes, and the soils. Higher-intensity rainfall or steeper slopes trigger landslides earlier and with higher sediment yield, resulting in more severe landslides. Changes in the soil behavior under rainfalls, particularly in silty and sandy soils, thus tend to increase susceptibility to early failures. These findings underscore the

importance of potential rainfall characteristics, soil properties, and slope gradients in assessing and mitigating landslide risk [LY2021].

2.6.2 Temporal Variables

These variables are considered important for understanding and predicting rainfall-induced landslides. Several studies made on the Philippines have used Typhoons as their basis and other extreme weather events to investigate this phenomenon. These research efforts specifically underline the role of rainfall as a primary triggering factor ([JJ2023]; [AC2024]; [ND2017]).

It has also been observed that soil moisture plays a crucial role in the onset of landslides. A Philippine study highlights the importance of soil moisture in triggering landslides in the region [AC2021]. To better depict subsurface conditions, a novel approach incorporates real-time subsurface hydrologic monitoring and uses actual soil moisture data [MB2018]. This method creates a visually interpretable and extremely accurate threshold by fusing current and predicted rainfall data with real-time soil moisture readings.

Furthermore, climate trends show that temperature and precipitation are on the rise, indicating the effects of climate change. As atmospheric temperatures rise, the capacity for water vapor retention increases, leading to more frequent and intense extreme rainfall events. The correlation between landslide incidence and climatic characteristics indicates that a major contributing component is high rainfall, especially at lower elevations. This correlation highlights significant concerns regarding the rising incidence of landslides [NR2021].

2.7 Case Studies on Landslide Occurrence in the Philippines

Landslides pose a significant threat to communities in the Philippines, particularly in areas with steep terrain and frequent heavy rainfall. As climate change increases the frequency and intensity of rainfall events, the need for effective forecasting and early warning systems has become even more critical. This section explores case studies that highlight the role of rainfall and soil conditions in landslide occurrences, focusing on past events in the Philippines.

On February 17, 2006, a colossal landslide struck the village of Guinsaigon in the Philippines and destroyed more than 350 houses and a nearby school, claiming more than 1,100 lives. The landslide struck suddenly, leaving the residents of the village no time to prepare or evacuate. Although no specific trigger that warned of the possible risk of a landslide, unusually heavy rainfall that poured and saturated the mountainous site was one of the several causes, as experts implied [ES2007]. In February 2024, a massive landslide hit the mining town in the Southern island of Mindanao in the Philippines, claiming nearly 100 lives, burying about 55 houses and a government office, and affecting 7,000 people. According to the local government, the destructive landslide followed a nonstop heavy rainfall that began on February 2 [FK2024].

Global trends indicate that landslide frequency is rising due to heavy and frequent rainfall, as a causal effect of climate change [JM2023]. While intense precipitation acts as the immediate trigger, it is the pre-existing saturation of the ground that often determines the scale of the failure. Besides rainfall, another factor that has a significant impact on landslide occurrence is soil moisture. As these incidents become more frequent, there is an urgent need

for greater preparedness, early warning systems, and mitigation efforts to reduce the devastating impacts on communities at risk. To achieve this, developing spatial forecasting models that accurately integrate these hydrological variables is essential.

2.8 Random Forest Model in Landslide Forecasting

Several models have been designed to predict landslides by looking at temporal as well as spatial factors. In this framework, temporal prediction predicts when the landslide occurs by analyzing patterns such as seasonal rainfall, recent storms, and cumulative precipitation, which act as triggers. Spatial prediction identifies where landslides are most likely to occur, focusing on vulnerable areas influenced by environmental and topographic factors. Consequently, spatial models are primarily utilized for long-term hazard mapping and urban planning, whereas temporal models form the backbone of real-time early warning systems.

Numerous studies have utilized the random forest model to forecast rainfall-induced landslides, leveraging a wide range of variables and diverse methodologies. Rainfall is consistently identified as a primary trigger for temporal prediction, with studies analyzing variations such as antecedent rainfall, rainfall intensity, and cumulative or rollover rainfall ([NC2021]; [KM2020]; [MM2018]). These differences are essential for determining the likelihood of landslides. Spatial prediction, on the other hand, aims to pinpoint susceptible areas, and the variables employed vary widely across research. Geological, hydrological, and topographical datasets are considered useful conditioning factors. However, the significance of each factor varies across studies [AH2019].

2.8.1 Spatial and Temporal Forecasting

Many studies use random forest to predict rainfall-induced landslides, drawing on a wide range of variables and multiple methodologies. In rainfall-induced landslide forecasting, both landslides caused by brief and extremely severe rainstorms is considered by common early warning systems. Usually, a threshold indicates the rainfall conditions that, when met or surpassed, are likely to cause a landslide [TF2022]. Moreover, a study on landslide spatial forecasting in Sicily, Italy, examined two models: logistic regression and random forest. The results showed that the random forest model performed the best. Meanwhile, the most important explanatory variables for landslide susceptibility in both models were slope angle, land use, and plan curvature [TA2015].

Among the various models and algorithms used in landslide prediction, the random forest model showed promising results. In a study that utilized five machine learning techniques: logistic regression, random forest, adaboost tree, support vector machine, and multilayer perceptron. The random forest model performed best in terms of predictive accuracy, accurately capturing the likelihood of landslides based on rainfall distribution and intensity [NC2021]. Furthermore, another study that compared random forest, support vector machine, and logistic regression showed that the random forest model outperforms the other models in terms of predicting susceptibility, and it performed better in predicting the temporal probability of landslide occurrence when rainfall intensity duration was taken into consideration [HF2022].

2.9 Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

As seen in Figure 2, the study is grounded in two primary theoretical frameworks that guide the research approach. The machine learning framework explores a comprehensive examination of supervised learning, reviewing a spectrum of algorithms commonly utilized for predictive modeling and forecasting. Within this domain, the framework places specific emphasis on the random forest model, offering an analysis of its internal mechanics. Specifically, it emphasizes the random forest model by detailing its functionality as an ensemble technique, forecasting role, and the various methods that it uses such as bagging and decision tree aggregation.

Hyperparameters and hyperparameter tuning were then highlighted pertaining to the random forest model to further discuss their importance in influencing the performance and accuracy of the model. This tuning process is important for balancing model complexity and generalization, thereby avoiding common issues such as overfitting. Furthermore, the discussion elaborated on the different methods utilized in optimizing these parameters, highlighting their significance in the predictive capabilities of the model. Beyond optimization, the ability of the model to handle non-linear data allows it to effectively capture the intricate dependencies and environmental dynamics described by this framework. Furthermore, the inherent feature importance mechanism of the random forest model complements the theoretical approach by quantifying the relative impact of each variable. This capability enables researchers to validate the capability of the model in areas that are applicable, ensuring that the identified dominant drivers align with established hydrological and geological principles as seen in this study.

Figure 2. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework.

The soil erosion theory framework explains landslide occurrence and susceptibility by analyzing the complex interrelationships among spatial and temporal variables. It states that the physical degradation of soil aggregates decreases shear strength, making slopes more prone to failure under hydraulic stress. Within this analysis, specific emphasis is placed on rainfall as the primary triggering mechanism. This theoretical foundation establishes the environmental context necessary to justify the application of the random forest model for landslide prediction.

2.10 Synthesis

This chapter reviews literature relevant to the study, beginning with an overview of machine learning, specifically supervised learning. It explores various forecasting models, emphasizing the random forest model as a key supervised learning technique. The chapter details how the random forest model works, its application in the study, and its ability to handle diverse datasets. It highlights methods to mitigate overfitting, including bagging, hyperparameter tuning, and Bayesian optimization, ensuring accurate model predictions.

The study then turns to the theoretical framework of landslides, specifically focusing on soil erosion theory, to give an understanding of the mechanisms, fundamentals, and principles behind landslide events. After discussing soil erosion theory, the research examines various types of landslides, particularly those induced primarily by rainfall. It also addresses common triggers and other factors that affect landslide susceptibility mapping, thereby helping select the appropriate variables for the study. The conceptual framework for landslide forecasting was then discussed by identifying the influence of key spatial and temporal variables, with particular attention to slope, soil type, and soil moisture, which are also critical to the accuracy of landslide susceptibility and prediction.

The literature then highlights rainfall as a primary triggering factor that destabilizes slopes by altering soil dynamics, and especially short-term, intense rainfall and cumulative rainfall are identified as variables to observe. Case studies, especially in the Philippines, underscore the destructive impact of rainfall-induced landslides, underscoring the need for more precise predictive models to better manage the associated risk. Through these environmental and meteorological factors, the random forest model has shown greater

accuracy than other machine learning models, particularly for temporal and spatial predictions.

This synthesis aligns with the goal of the study by correlating rainfall variables with landslide occurrence, examining the effect of rainfall on soil and environmental factors, and evaluating the accuracy of the random forest model in landslide forecasting scenarios. The findings of this review of related literature emphasize the importance of these factors in building a dependable predictive model and in formulating an effective early warning system in the face of a rapidly growing threat from rainfall-induced landslides.

In conclusion, the chapter reviewed significant literature on the use of machine learning models, particularly the random forest model, for landslide forecasting, with a focus on rainfall-induced landslides. The review also highlighted the theories and concepts behind machine learning and landslides, which help support the study in landslide forecasting by enabling understanding and integration of numerous spatial and temporal factors and by informing model selection. It also highlighted the importance of hyperparameter tuning in improving the random forest model performance. The chapter further focused on the various types and causes of landslides, with emphasis on rainfall as a primary cause. While synthesizing these studies, the development of the landslide prediction system benefits from an integrated approach combining machine learning with environmental variables and geographic data.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlined a comprehensive methodology for rainfall-induced landslide forecasting in the Philippines using the random forest model. The study begins by following a systematic approach to collecting data, ensuring the sources are reliable for environmental and geospatial data. Some key steps in preprocessing include ensuring the data is ready for analysis by eliminating common issues such as missing values, irrelevant information, and potential imbalances that affect model performance. These steps were crucial in order to maintain the balance of the dataset, which significantly affects the training phase as well as the implementation stage.

The researchers highlight the implementation of a random forest model designed to analyze critical variables associated with landslide occurrence. This implementation also involves refining the model through optimization techniques to improve its predictive accuracy. It uses relevant environmental factors, such as rainfall patterns, soil conditions, and terrain characteristics, to capture the complex relationships that contribute to landslides.

An important part of this research is an accurate and efficient evaluation procedure. This procedure uses robust statistical methods to assess the reliability and accuracy of the model. The methodology, therefore, takes into account a comprehensive and data-driven approach in dealing with the urgent need for effective and reliable landslide prediction systems for disaster preparedness and risk reduction in the Philippines. Ultimately, this methodological design ensures that the findings presented in the subsequent chapter are scientifically valid and reproducible.

3.1 Research Design

It is defined as the foundation for a refined answer to a research problem [GC2021]. It serves as a bridge to fill the gap between the known and unknown in a research topic. This study employed a quantitative experimental research design using a random forest model to predict landslide occurrence. Quantitative research uses numerical data across a wide range of fields, such as analyzing relations among data, aggregating data, and comparing aggregated data [CD2014].

In experimental design, one or more independent variables are manipulated to assess their effects on dependent variables and to understand their influence. The researcher attempts to control all other factors that affect the results, thereby enabling predictions about the potential outcomes [ZA2022]. Through an experimental design, this study evaluated the applicability of machine learning to landslide prediction. Moreover, this examined the relationship and influences of rainfall and environmental variables on landslides using the random forest model. The researchers maintained objectivity throughout the analysis to ensure reliable findings and eliminate biases.

3.2 Dataset Collection and Characterization

The study utilized data from two primary sources: the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Global Landslide Catalog (GLC) and the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC) of the Philippines (see Tables 1 and 2). The GLC was a global inventory of rainfall-induced landslide events developed at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center since 2007. It included reports of large-scale movements

triggered by rainfall, as documented in media outlets, disaster databases, scientific literature, and other sources [KD2010]. The catalog contained over 10,000 landslide events worldwide, providing information such as location, source, date of occurrence, country, and other relevant details. For this study, only events that occurred in the Philippines were considered, along with selected relevant data fields. The dataset focused solely on landslide occurrences and did not include contributing environmental or geological factors.

Additional data were obtained from the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC). This Philippine government agency is primarily responsible for disaster preparedness, mitigation, and response. Furthermore, it serves as the principal adviser to the President regarding response operations and rehabilitation efforts coordinated between the government and the private sector (S1).

Dataset	NASA Global Landslide Catalog
Type	Historical Landslide Data
Trigger	Rainfall
Total Events	10,000
Filtered Landslide Data	400
Generated Non-landslide Data	400
Total	800

Table 1. Dataset from NASA.

The NDRRMC dataset, as seen in Table 2, maintains a valuable and publicly accessible database that consists of detailed annual incident reports of landslides across the

country. As an official government source, this dataset provides a reliable and standardized baseline for historical landslide events. From this source, the researchers meticulously filtered and extracted only rainfall-induced landslide events, typically including the date and, in some cases, the time of occurrence. This filtering process was crucial for isolating the specific phenomenon under investigation and avoiding confounding variables from other triggers, such as earthquakes. To ensure the resulting dataset had enough entries for extensive analysis and to train a reliable model, these two datasets were combined to create a more comprehensive and sufficient dataset for the study.

Dataset	NDRRMC
Type	Historical Landslide Data
Trigger	Rainfall
Total Events	800
Generated Non-landslide Data	800
Total	1600

Table 2. Dataset from NDRRMC.

Environmental data, such as rainfall and soil moisture, were collected from Open-Meteo [OM2025]. This open-source weather platform provides historical and forecasted meteorological data, including rainfall intensity, cumulative rainfall, and soil moisture. This platform was selected for its high temporal resolution and Application Programming Interface (API) accessibility, enabling the efficient retrieval of hourly historical time-series data, crucial for analyzing landslide triggers. Meanwhile, data on slope and soil

type were obtained from two different organizations, as these data were not available on the Open-Meteo website. Slope information was provided directly to the researchers by an engineer from the Department of Agriculture Bureau of Soils and Water Management (BSWM) in response to a formal request made by the researchers. On the other hand, soil type data were accessed publicly through the FAO-UNESCO Soil Map. These environmental factors are essential for understanding the physical characteristics of the landscape, which directly influence landslide occurrence as seen in Table 3.

Variable	Unit	Classes	Form	Sources	Data Type
Rainfall	mm	<2.5 in/ hr; 2.5 in to 7.5 in /hr; > 7.5 in/hr	Datasheet	Open-meteo (https://open-meteo.com/0)	Continuous
Soil Moisture	Percentage (%)	< 0.2; 0.4 - 0.6; >0.9	Datasheet	Open-meteo (https://open-meteo.com/)	Continuous
Slope	Degrees(°)	0° - 5°; 10° - 15°; 30° - 45°	Grid	BSMW	Discrete
Soil Type	None	1 - loam, 2 - clay_loam, 3 - sandy_loam, 4 - clay	Vector	Fao UNESCO (https://www.fao.org/soils-portal/data-hub/soil-maps-and-databases/faunesco-soil-map-of-the-world/en/)	Discrete

Table 3. Classification of Variables Used.

To determine the performance of the model, particularly in its performance metric and accuracy against the chosen performance metrics, the data was split into two distinct parts, namely, the training set and the test set. The distribution of data points across the training and test subsets is shown in Table 4. As observed, the training phase uses 80% of the data to train and learn the model from past landslide occurrence data. This learning process is important for enabling the model to recognize predictive features and build an effective decision boundary. Meanwhile, the testing phase uses 20% of the data for performance and accuracy evaluation to evaluate the performance, accuracy, and generalization capability of the model on unseen data.

Activity	Percentage Distribution	Number of Data
Training	80%	1930
Test	20%	470
Total	100%	2400

Table 4. Model Training Percentage Distribution.

The dataset used for training and testing consisted of 2,400 landslide events, distributed across different phases. Of these, 1,930 events were allocated to the training set, while 470 were reserved for testing. To avoid bias and improve the accuracy of landslide prediction, an equal number of non-landslide data points were included. These non-landslide instances were collected from the exact locations of the landslide events, but during periods when no landslides occurred.

For model evaluation, the researchers applied an alternative testing method using cross-validation to assess the performance of the model on unseen data. In this method, the training set was split into multiple smaller subsets. During each iteration of the cross-validation process, one fold was set aside as the validation set, while the remaining folds were used to train the model. This cycle was repeated several times, ensuring that every data point was used in both training and validation. This technique evaluated the generalizability of the model and prevented overfitting by ensuring it performed well not only on known data but also on new, unseen samples. Cross-validation is an essential procedure for ensuring that trained models are reliable and effective when applied to unknown data. By systematically dividing the dataset into training and validation groups, the method provides a more accurate measure of model performance [G2025a]. While cross-validation helps fine-tune and evaluate the model during training, the test set is reserved for the final, unbiased assessment of the real-world performance of the model. The test set remains untouched throughout the training and validation process and is used only at the end to simulate how the model performs on completely unseen data.

3.3 Procedures

As shown in Figure 3, the objective of this study was to forecast landslides. This objective was achieved by utilizing a comprehensive dataset of historical landslide events and associated variables, primarily via the random forest model for forecasting landslide occurrence. The model was trained on 80% of the dataset for training and tested on the remaining 20% for validation, which eventually led to the development of the web

application. The methodological process began with essential data preprocessing steps, including cleaning the raw data to address inconsistencies and missing values, followed by splitting the cleaned dataset into distinct training and testing sets for the model. To explore the relationships between rainfall and environmental variables with landslide occurrences, appropriate tools and models are needed. Moreover, logistic regression was used to examine the influence of categorical and continuous factors, including slope, soil type, and soil moisture, on landslide probability. To improve the predictive performance of the random forest model, bayesian optimization was employed for hyperparameter tuning. Finally, the effectiveness of the model was evaluated using performance metrics such as accuracy, f1-score, precision, and recall, reliability in predicting landslide events. Furthermore, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine whether significant differences existed in the performance of the various predictive models considered in the study.

Figure 3. Operational Framework.

3.3.1 Data Preparation

In this study, rainfall and soil moisture data were collected from Open-Meteo, an open-source weather data platform that provides reliable meteorological information in Comma-Separated Values (CSV) format. The dataset spans from 2008 to 2024, covering 16 years. Meanwhile, slope data was provided by the Department of Agriculture – Bureau of Soils and Water Management (BSWM) in shapefile format. In contrast, soil type data were obtained from the FAO-UNESCO Soil Map, derived from vectorization of a 1:200,000 geological map. Unlike rainfall and soil moisture, which were already in numeric form, the slope and soil type data needed to be converted to CSV format to extract usable numerical values. To accomplish this, the researchers utilized Quantum Geographic Information System (QGIS), a free and open-source application that allows users to generate, modify, visualize, analyze, and export geospatial data [QG2009]. The slope shapefile was imported into QGIS and rendered as a Digital Elevation Model (DEM), from which values were extracted and exported as a CSV file. Similarly, the soil type vector data were processed in QGIS and converted into CSV format for integration into the dataset of the study.

3.3.2 Data Preprocessing

Once all the relevant data were collected and converted into a usable format, the next step in data preprocessing was data cleaning. It involved evaluating, filtering, and manipulating the data to improve its quality and suitability for model training. In this study, raw data from various sources were processed to ensure consistency and to eliminate irrelevant or redundant information.

The GLC dataset contained landslide events from multiple countries, but this study focused specifically on landslides within the Philippines. Therefore, any landslide data from outside the Philippines was removed to ensure the dataset was geographically relevant. Additionally, irrelevant entries, such as missing or erroneous data, were addressed by either inputting missing values or eliminating incomplete records.

The dataset from NDRRMC was collected manually, filtering only rain-induced landslides with a specific time for each event to reduce erroneous data. Next, the dataset underwent feature transformation, which involved converting categorical variables such as soil type and slope into a format suitable for machine learning algorithms. For soil type as seen in Figure 4 (e.g., "clay", "sand", "loam", "silt"), each was converted into a separate binary feature (see Table 5). Similarly, slope values were divided into discrete ranges (e.g., 0° – 10° , 10° – 20° , $>30^{\circ}$) and also turned them into binary features representing whether a particular slope range applied to the data point.

Figure 4. Sample Soil Types.

The soil type data were converted from their original descriptive categories to numerical representations to prepare them for the machine learning models. This process, often referred to as label encoding, is required because the model cannot process raw string variables. As shown in Table 5, each soil type was assigned a unique numerical identification between 1 and 4. Loam was allocated to Class 1, clay_loam to Class 2, sandy_loam to Class 3, and clay to Class 4. By processing categorical soil data through numerical mapping, the model spots trends, correlations, and variations in the expected results across these soil texture types, which ultimately helps them learn and generate predictions. This ensures that the physical properties associated with each soil category are represented in the model.

Class	Description
1	clay
2	sandy_loam
3	clay_loam
4	loam

Table 5. Soil Type Classification.

The slope data were also transformed from their original continuous angle values into discrete categorical classes based on ranges. These ranges were assigned numerical classes between 1 and 6, which refer to differing steepness (e.g., Class 1 for '<10°' or 'Flat', Class 6 for '> 50°' or 'Very Steep Slope'), as the table provided shows. To make this variable ready for inclusion in the models alongside the

transformed soil type data, the categorical representation was typically converted into a set of binary features, each indicating whether a given slope range was present or not in a data point.

Class	Slope Range	Description
1	<10°	Flat
2	10°-20°	Gentle Slope
3	20°-30°	Moderate Slope
4	30°-40°	Substantial Slope
5	40°-50°	Steep Slope
6	> 50°	Very Steep Slope

Table 6. Slope Ranking Classification.

To address class imbalance in the dataset, a data balancing process was performed. Initially, the dataset contained only landslide occurrence records, with minimal non-landslide instances. To prevent the model from being biased toward predicting only landslide events, the dataset was balanced to ensure equal representation of both landslide and non-landslide cases. To achieve this, the researchers employed the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE), a widely used method for generating synthetic data for the underrepresented class. SMOTE works by creating new, plausible non-landslide data points based on the existing samples, effectively enhancing the diversity of the dataset while preserving its original structure. This method is essential for training the model to forecast

possible landslide occurrences accurately. It helped the model learn to predict both landslide and non-landslide outcomes with equal effectiveness.

3.3.3 Model Training

For training, 80% of the dataset was used, with the remaining 20% as test set to evaluate performance on unseen data. This step ensures the model generalizes and makes accurate predictions beyond the training phase. This separation is important for evaluating the true predictive capabilities of the model on unseen data to ensure the model does not overfit.

3.3.3.1 Cross Validation

In addition to this train-test split, the researchers also employed cross-validation within the training data. One method for evaluating the performance of a machine learning model on unknown data is cross-validation. The data is divided into multiple segments, and the model is trained on some and tested on the others. This process is repeated several times. A more precise estimate of the performance of the model is obtained by averaging the outcomes of each validation phase [G2025a]. Through this method, the training set was split into multiple folds to systematically assess the performance of the model and fine-tune its parameters. Cross-validation helps prevent overfitting by ensuring models perform consistently across different subsets of the data. The overall workflow of the model, including training, validation, and testing phases, is seen in Figure 5. This shows the overall process from dataset training to final prediction output.

Figure 5. Random Forest Model Process.

3.3.4 Hyperparameter Optimization

To optimize the performance of the random forest model, bayesian optimization was used to fine-tune its hyperparameters. The key parameters that were

optimized include: `n_estimators` (number of trees in the forest), `max_depth` (maximum depth of each tree), `min_samples_split` (minimum number of samples required to split a node), and `min_samples_leaf` (minimum number of samples required at a leaf node). Bayesian optimization iteratively updates these parameters based on the performance of the model, balancing exploration of new configurations and exploitation of existing good configurations. This helps avoid overfitting while maximizing the performance of the model. The best hyperparameter configuration was chosen based on validation accuracy and f1-score.

3.4 Statistical Treatment

An essential part of this study is the use of measurements and statistical methods for data analysis to ensure reliable results. In this study, the researchers utilized statistical tools to investigate the research objectives and evaluate the acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses. These methods helped determine the strength and direction of relationships between variables and identify the most critical factors contributing to landslides.

3.4.1 Logistic Regression

In this study, it was used as an inferential statistical analysis technique to investigate and quantify the association between landslide occurrence and the predictive variables used in the study. Although it was used for classification tasks as well, its main objective in this study was to determine how changes in the predictor variables relate to the likelihood of the outcome. This process is similar to how correlation evaluates relationships, but to a categorical dependent variable.

Logistic regression models the relationship between the predictor variables and the logarithm of the odds (logit or log-odds) of a landslide event. Odds Ratios (OR) derived from the model coefficients quantify the direction and magnitude of the association for each predictor variable. Through the use of Formula 1 as reference, when an odds ratio increases above one, it implies a positive relationship, i.e., the higher the chance of a landslide occurring is associated with a rise in the predictor variable. Conversely, an OR less than one indicates a negative relationship, suggesting that an increase in the variable reduces the probability of a landslide.

Conversely, a negative correlation is represented by an odds ratio less than one indicating that an increase in the predictor variable corresponds to a lower likelihood of a landslide. Notably, if statistically adjusted for the effects of other predictors in the model, an odds ratio close to one indicates little independent association between that predictor and landslide likelihood. To develop an understanding of the factors that affect landslide susceptibility rather than focusing on predicting future occurrences, the researchers applied logistic regression to assess the strength and direction of relationships among the variables used and the probability of landslide occurrence [G2025b]. By isolating these contribution levels, the study distinguishes specific causal factors.

$$P = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_N * X_N))}$$

Formula 1. Logistic Regression.

3.4.2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

It is a statistical technique used to compare the means of three or more groups, essential for identifying differences and relationships across various fields of study. ANOVA assesses the impact of different factors by comparing the means of multiple groups or samples. It tests the null hypothesis that all group means are equal against the alternative that at least one group mean differs significantly [G2024a].

In this study, a one-way ANOVA was employed to examine whether there is a statistically significant difference in the accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score of the random forest model when trained using different sets of input variables. The researchers determined whether incorporating multiple variable types improves model performance or whether certain variable types contribute more significantly to accurate landslide prediction. As shown in Formula 2, the F-value is calculated by dividing the mean square between groups (MSB) by the mean square within groups (MSW), providing a measure of variance among group means relative to variance within the groups. A high F-value indicates that the variability in performance is driven by the differences in input datasets rather than random error, thereby confirming the statistical significance of feature selection in model optimization which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

$$F = MSB/MSW$$

Formula 2. One-Way ANOVA.

3.4.3 Tukey Honest Significant Difference (HSD)

A post-hoc test is conducted to identify which specific pairs exhibit statistically significant differences in their group means after a relevant result from the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) indicates a difference among the group means. One standard post-hoc method for pairwise comparisons of all possible group means while controlling the family-wise error rate (FWER) is the Tukey Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test as shown in Formula 3. When multiple pairwise comparisons are performed without adjustment, the probability of a significant difference occurring by chance (Type I error) increases [LD2010].

While the ANOVA confirms that there are differences in overall model performance, it does not pinpoint exactly where these differences lie. This limitation is addressed by employing the Tukey HSD test, which conducts all possible pairwise comparisons and provides adjusted p-values that account for multiple comparisons. Due to significant one-way ANOVA results for the accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score metrics, the Tukey HSD test was applied in this research. To determine which specific model comparisons show statistically significant differences in their respective performance measures, pairwise comparisons among models trained on different input sets are needed.

$$HSD = \frac{M_i - M_j}{\sqrt{(MSw/nh)}}$$

Formula 3. Tukey HSD.

3.5 Performance Metrics

They are essential because they are used to evaluate the performance and effectiveness of the model [JA2024b]. They helped the researchers understand how well the model performs across various tasks and ensure that its predictions are reliable and accurate. The researchers employed several metrics relevant to measuring, validating, and fine-tuning the performance of the random forest model.

3.5.1 Confusion Matrix

The performance of the random forest model was evaluated using a confusion matrix, which is an N by N structure comparing actual and predicted values across target classes. As seen in Figure 6 it categorizes outcomes into four components: True Positive (TP) and True Negative (TN) for correctly identified positive and negative cases, respectively; False Positive (FP) for negative cases incorrectly labeled as positive; and False Negative (FN) for positive cases incorrectly labeled as negative [BA2023]. This tool provides insights in evaluating the model performance.

		Actual Class	
		P	N
Predicted Class	P	TP	FP
	N	FN	TN

Figure 6. Confusion Matrix Diagram.

3.5.2 Accuracy

It is one of the basic metrics for classification problems that measures the correct predictions made by the model. It is calculated by dividing the total number of correct predictions by the total number of predictions (see Formula 4) [BN2024]. In the context of this study, accuracy was used as an indicator of how well the random forest model performs in predicting both landslides and non-landslides.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN}$$

Formula 4. Accuracy.

3.5.3 Precision

This metric determines the proportion of correctly classified positive samples relative to the total number of samples predicted as positive, including both correct and incorrect predictions (see Formula 5). Precision is a metric that evaluates how effectively a model identifies positive samples. It declines when the model has a high number of incorrect positive classifications relative to the correct ones. In contrast, precision is deemed high when there are many correct positive classifications and fewer erroneous ones. [GA2024]. In this study, this metric helped in understanding the total amount of actual landslides predicted by the model which is useful for forecasting landslides or early warning systems.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Formula 5. Precision.

3.5.4 Recall

It is a metric that calculates the ratio of correctly classified positive samples to the total number of actual positive samples (see Formula 6). It measures the ability of the model to detect all positive samples in the dataset. The higher the recall, the better the model in identifying most of the actual positive samples [GA2024].

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

Formula 6. Recall.

3.5.5 F1-Score

Another metric used to evaluate the performance of the random forest model is the f1-score. The f1-score represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It is an important metric for evaluating a classification model with imbalanced data, as it considers both types of errors, such as false positives and false negatives, rather than focusing only on the total number of incorrect predictions [SN2023]. As shown

in Formula 7, f1-score was used alongside precision, recall, and accuracy to identify the overall predictive performance of the model. Consequently, this metric provides a more rigorous assessment of the reliability of the model than accuracy alone because it imposes a penalty on the score if either precision or recall is low.

$$F1 = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Formula 7. F1- Score.

3.6 Ethical Consideration

There are minimal issues considered in this study as it focuses primarily on environmental and geospatial information, avoiding direct interaction with human participants, personal data, or interventions in natural environments. Since the methodology relies entirely on computational modelling rather than physical fieldwork, there is no ecological footprint or physical disturbance to the study areas. Researchers used publicly available datasets, such as landslide events and rainfall and soil data from platforms like the NASA Global Landslide Catalog and the geoportal PH, to ensure ethical compliance. Proper authorization was obtained to access these datasets, ensuring responsible data use and alignment with data-sharing policies. This approach reduces concerns related to consent and privacy; it also avoids intrusive data collection techniques and direct contact with at-risk groups, which in itself reduces many of the ethical concerns generated by issues of consent

and privacy. Furthermore, the study adheres to principles of academic integrity by ensuring transparency in data processing and correctly attributing all intellectual property.

The study adheres to responsible data usage principles, ensuring compliance with data-sharing policies and appropriate attribution to source organizations. It contributes to reducing disaster risk by fostering safer, more resilient communities and supporting the protection and sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems. The results are made available to the public, benefiting future policymakers, local communities, and researchers. The study demonstrates strong adherence to ethical research principles while safeguarding the integrity and social value of its results.

3.7 APIs and Development Tools

This section outlines the development and Application Programming Interface (API) tools used in the research. To maintain transparency and academic integrity, the researchers formally acknowledge the integration of Generative AI tools, specifically ChatGPT and Gemini. These AI chatbots were primarily utilized to improve the structure and coherence of the text, as well as to assist in sentence expansion. It is important to note that they were not used to generate references or fabricate content. For complete transparency and accountability, the table in Appendix I provides a detailed breakdown of the application of each tool, describing their specific purposes, results, and locations within the study.

In conclusion, this chapter has detailed the methodological framework employed to develop and validate the random forest model. After defining the research design and

characterizing the dataset, a strict procedural workflow was followed, including data preparation, preprocessing, and model training with hyperparameter optimization. It also discussed the statistical tools used in the study, including Logistic Regression, ANOVA, and Tukey HSD, along with a comprehensive set of performance metrics to ensure objective evaluation.

Finally, the inclusion of ethical considerations ensures the study adheres to the required standards of data privacy and integrity. Moreover, the methodological approach adopted in this study ensures the reliability of the predictive outcomes of the model. The integration of machine learning techniques with conventional statistical analyses strengthens the interpretability and validity of the results, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of landslide susceptibility patterns for future research and practical applications in landslide forecasting.

CHAPTER IV

SOLUTION

To address the underlying issues and objectives in this study, the researchers developed a machine learning-based system. This chapter outlines the system decomposition, user interface, and technologies used in the development of the application. The system decomposition demonstrates the usability and main functions provided by the application. The user interface section, meanwhile, shows the application that was made based on the findings presented in this study. It provides users a friendly interface for data input, data output, and results interpretation. The application was also designed for users to interact with a dynamic map and view results generated by the system. Furthermore, it offers a dynamic dashboard that presents landslide forecasting information, including risk levels and mapping of areas that are prone to landslides.

4.1 System Decomposition Chart

The system is decomposed into three primary modules: data entry, forecasting, and analytics as shown in Figure 7. The process begins with the data entry module, which gathers user-defined parameters and environmental data. This module acts as the entry point of the system, validating inputs to ensure data integrity before they are passed further downstream. This information is then processed by the forecasting module to generate a landslide prediction and its confidence score. The output of the landslide prediction shows a binary result and the confidence score is used as a nuanced assessment of the resulting landslide prediction.

Figure 7. System Decomposition Chart.

Finally, the analytics module contextualizes this result by providing a detailed analysis of the contributing factors. These include variables such as rainfall, soil conditions, and historical data, offering a comprehensive view of the potential risk. This final stage is crucial for decision making, as it translates the raw prediction into actionable insights.

4.1.1 Data Entry

This is where the user first interacts with the system which collects the fundamental parameters needed to make a prediction. This stage entails defining a specific geographic location, the desired time range for the analysis, and the target time and date for the forecast. After setting these user-specified parameters, the

system automatically retrieves the required environmental data to carry out the Variable Assignment. Moreover, the system retrieves rainfall data from outside sources and accesses static data, such as soil type and slope category, from a local database to prepare a full set of inputs for the forecasting model.

4.1.2 Forecasting

This module uses the random forest model to process the required parameters after they have been gathered from the Data Entry stage. The two main outputs it produces are a prediction regarding the probability of a landslide and a confidence score determination that measures the level of confidence of the model in that result. When combined, these findings offer a numerical evaluation of the possible landslide risk for the given parameters.

4.1.3 Analytics

The module provides a comprehensive analysis of the variables contributing to a landslide forecast. It combines static and dynamic data to provide the prediction result with more context. The module provides context to factors like rainfall intensity and cumulative rainfall to evaluate recent weather impacts against historical norms and it also incorporates important geospatial data, such as slope category, soil type, and soil moisture. It also shows historical landslides, which analyzes data from previous events to pinpoint vulnerable areas and long-term trends, to give historical context. This visualization ensures that users interpret the predictions of the model within a complete environmental and historical framework. This transforms raw data into actionable insights for disaster preparedness.

4.2 Technology/Development Tools

The system architecture is built upon a specific stack of technologies carefully selected to handle the frontend, backend, and data analysis phases. The frontend utilizes Bootstrap [BO2025] for responsive design and mapping services like Mapbox [MA2025] and OpenStreetMap [OS2025] for data visualization. The backend is powered by the Python Flask framework [FL2025] for API handling, integrated with the Open-Meteo API for data acquisition. Finally, the machine learning component was developed using Jupyter Notebook [JU2025] and other essential libraries, most notably scikit-learn [SC2025], for model training and statistical validation. These tools play a critical role in developing the system that is crucial for implementation of research results.

4.2.1 Frontend Development

A variety of tools was used in the frontend development process to produce a user interface that is interactive, responsive, and a visually appealing user interface. Bootstrap was used to build the main structure and layout, it is an efficient framework that provides a consistent and mobile-first design across all devices. Additionally, custom JavaScript was implemented to manage client-side behavior. The Mapbox platform was utilized for the interactive mapping features of the application. Specifically, it renders a map of the Philippines on the Dashboard Page to visualize locations where landslides have occurred. Meanwhile, OpenStreetMap was used for its rich and open-source geographic data which serves as the basis for the mapping functionality of the Dynamic Map Page because of its dependable and affordable basis for all location-based features and visualizations. It allows the users to be able

to search for a location using a search bar or through clicking the map. These tools ensure that the interface remains intuitive and responsive across different devices.

4.2.2 Backend Development

The backend architecture was built on a solid and efficient stack designed to handle data processing and machine learning tasks. Python Flask, a lightweight web framework, is used to handle API requests and coordinate server-side tasks. The scikit-learn library was used to create and execute machine learning models that extract insightful information for sophisticated data analysis and predictive modeling of landslide occurrence. This library was where the random forest model was derived from and was used in the study. Furthermore, the application integrates with the Open-Meteo API, which was used to gather consistent historical and real-time weather data every hour to feed the model with the necessary data it needs. This ensures that the model is able to perform well with enough data.

4.2.3 Jupyter Notebook

This tool served as the primary interactive environment for the machine learning development, analysis, and validation phases. It was used in training the random forest model for the purpose of the study. The environment enabled the use of various essential libraries for data preprocessing, feature engineering, and model implementation. It was also the main tool used for data visualization to explore datasets and understand feature correlations. This was also used for methods such as logistic regression and one-way ANOVA for hypothesis testing and validating statistical assumptions. It details generating and analyzing comprehensive model

performance results, noting key metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC AUC curve to assess the effectiveness of the classifier.

4.3 User Interfaces

The application developed is a public web platform designed to generate landslide predictions for locations within the Philippines. The application is openly accessible at www.twostepsahead.site and does not require users to log in. Upon visiting the site, users are first greeted by the landing page (shown in Figure 8). From there, they explore all sections of the website using the links in the top navigation bar. Users are also able to click the Learn How button to access the user guide page or the Start Predicting button to proceed directly to the Data Entry section as seen in the decomposition chart.

Figure 8. Landing Page.

The web application was designed with a user-friendly interface to ensure intuitive navigation. It functions as an accessible platform where users forecast landslides by either selecting coordinates on an interactive map or using the search feature. The layout includes a navigation bar and a dashboard that visualizes environmental data and model performance metrics to support decision-making.

4.3.1 Dynamic Map (Data Entry)

The interface, shown in Figure 9, serves as the main feature for users to explore landslide prediction based on the geographical location of the Philippines. The interface consists of a control panel where data entry occurs. This is where a user searches for a specific location, and assigns date, time, and time range for forecasting. Besides typing the specific name of the place, a map at the right allows searching of location by clicking on the map. Once the location has been specified, the system fetches the static variables, soil type and slope, from its internal database.

Figure 9. Dynamic Map Page.

The calendar interface entails users to select a date from today up to five days in the future. The time is selected in a 12-hour (AM/PM) format. Finally, a dropdown menu allows users to choose a prediction time range of 3, 6, 12, or 24 hours. These parameters enable users to accurately control the prediction timeframe while internally assigning variables as the system retrieves rainfall, soil moisture values, soil type, and slope from the Open-Meteo service.

4.3.2 Dynamic Map (Forecasting)

As shown in Figure 10, once the “Predict Landslide Risk” button is clicked, the prediction results are displayed. These results include the classification output, indicating whether the prediction is “No Landslide” or “Landslide,” along with a confidence score that indicates the level of certainty of the model. The generated output is derived from the variable values as based on the data entry.

Figure 10. Dynamic Map Page (Forecasting).

4.3.3 Prediction Report Summary (Analytics)

As seen in Figure 11, the Prediction Report Page is an aggregated analytics summary which includes report details, environmental variables, and rainfall analysis. Within the report details, it displays the location name, coordinates, as well as date and time of the prediction. It also includes prediction output of the model along with a confidence score. Below the report details, environmental variables (slope, soil type, and soil moisture) are presented. Moreover, the rainfall analysis section shows the visual representation of rainfall data depicting the past hourly (12 hours) and daily (5 days) cumulative and rainfall intensity.

Figure 11. Prediction Report Page.

4.3.4 Dashboard (Analytics)

As visually presented in Figure 12, the dashboard page serves as a central hub for a visually intuitive and comprehensive representation of landslide history and related information. A key component of this interface features several charts that summarize different aspects of landslide data. At the top are charts for the History of Landslide Occurrence (Yearly), the History of Landslide Occurrence (Monthly), and Regions with the Most Landslide Occurrence, along with a region selection dropdown. Another element is a detailed map, which utilizes a heatmap overlay with a legend to clearly and quickly visualize the geographical locations of identified landslide occurrences. This feature presents analytical results of accumulated landslide occurrences in the Philippines over the years. It serves as a foundation for understanding how related variables contribute to the probability of landslides.

Figure 12. Dashboard Page.

4.3.5 User Guide

As seen in Figure 13, the user guide interface helps the user navigate and use the web application. It provides clear instructions on how to operate the application, including steps for using the dynamic map, making predictions, and understanding the results. The guide also features a Quick Navigation panel on the left side for easy access to different sections of the web page. It also offers detailed explanations of system components, including rainfall data, soil moisture, terrain analysis, and soil composition, ensuring that users fully understand how each factor contributes to landslide prediction. Additionally, it includes a Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) section that provides guidance and answers to common inquiries that users have while navigating the system. The section addresses topics such as the nature of the model and the software as a whole.

Figure 13. User Guide Page.

4.3.6 Training Result

The interface presents the results of the random forest model during training on landslides dataset. As seen in Figure 14, the interface provides visuals that highlights the performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, f1-score, and roc curve. The confusion matrix shows the accuracy of the random forest model in distinguishing landslide events. Additionally, the feature importance chart visualizes the contribution of each variable in predicting landslide occurrences using the model.

Figure 14. Training Result Page.

4.4 System Validation

A proper testing of the system is critical to ensure reliability, effectiveness, and adherence in meeting high quality standards. This process is essential for mitigating errors

and verifying stability prior to user deployment. To achieve this, the researchers implemented a variety of testing strategies consisting of unit, integration, system, and acceptance testing. These tests evaluated the system as a whole which included the application interface, external APIs, backend server, and the integration of the random forest model. This systematic approach ensured the system was fully functional upon release and further established a baseline for subsequent improvements. Documentation of these testing procedures further serves to validate and provide a clear framework for future scalability.

4.4.1 Unit Testing

The process includes testing each function on individual system components ensuring that they worked properly and did not cause bugs. A major obstacle in doing unit testing for the system was the reliance on external services such as APIs, the random forest model, and data files. To overcome this and maintain isolation, frameworks such as pytest and pytest-mock frameworks were used. This involved making sure tests were quick, repeatable, and unaffected by outside variables by substituting controlled, simulated objects for actual dependencies. The unit testing was primarily applied to test core features, including location and weather data retrieval, the prediction making process of the random forest model, and report generation.

On the Javascript frontend, it involved the client-side logic which acted as the intermediary between the user and the backend. The development of mock tests was also a part of this process and its goal was to validate the client-server communication layer. The process involved how the frontend code handled a wide range of possible

responses, from successful data payloads to network and server errors, by simulating the API calls to the backend.

4.4.2 Integration Testing

After unit testing, integration testing was done which focused on confirming the separate parts of the system functioned as a whole properly. The main objective was to validate the crucial communication channels, beginning with the interface between the Python backend and the Javascript frontend. The Python framework `pytest` was used again in this scenario which allowed the server to run in a test environment, live API and random forest model calls were executed to ensure the client, server, and the model correctly had the appropriate data formats and handled both successful and unsuccessful interactions.

Furthermore, the ability of the backend to integrate with its external dependencies was examined, including databases and third-party APIs. This phase involved live connections to test versions of these services that ensured the application accurately fetches, processes, and stores data in a real-world scenario. This allows the identification of errors such as data format mismatches, network configuration issues, and flawed API logic.

4.4.3 System Testing

The purpose of this testing phase was for the application to be examined from the viewpoint of an end user as a whole. The developers acted as testers replicating actual user workflows in a production-like staging environment where it was already hosted and accessible in the cloud. A typical test included the automation of the

entire process of a user entering location data, initiating a prediction from the random forest model, obtaining a final report, and then confirming the accuracy of the data presented in the user interface. This approach provided the highest level of confidence in the readiness of the system for release by confirming that all system components from the frontend, backend, and external services functioned properly to meet the specified system requirements.

4.4.4 Acceptance Testing

The final phase of testing was used to confirm that the system aligns with the requirements and functions properly for end users. For this project, it focuses on verifying that the landslide forecasting system satisfied end user requirements and performed as intended. The collected feedback serves as the guide for the refinement of the system and helps verify its usability in real-life scenarios. The system evaluation was conducted with a group of 54 respondents which includes 23 respondents from the College of Information Technology, 29 respondents from other courses, one respondent from the university faculty, and one respondent from other institutions or agencies. The respondents interacted with the system through a combination of a demonstration and hands-on use. Their feedback was then collected through a survey conducted via Google Forms. Lastly, all gathered data remains confidential and used only for system evaluation.

The acceptance testing was conducted based on 54 criteria, covering aspects such as accuracy, auditability, communication commonality, completeness, conciseness, consistency and understandability, controllability, data commonality,

decomposability, error tolerance, execution efficiency, expandability, generality, hardware independence, instrumentation, modularity, observability, operability, security, self-documentation, functional simplicity, structural simplicity, code simplicity, software system independence, traceability, and training. As shown in Table 7, each criterion was rated on a scale of 1 to 5, with the corresponding interpretation indicating the overall performance. A higher mean score reflects better performance, where a score between 4.21 and 5.00 is considered Very Good, while a score between 1.00 and 1.80 is interpreted as Very Poor. This scale ensures a standardized assessment for all criteria, allowing for consistent and objective evaluation.

Mean Score	Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Very Good
3.41 – 4.20	Good
2.61 – 3.40	Average
1.81 – 2.60	Poor
1.00 – 1.80	Very Poor

Table 7. Survey Results Interpretation.

Table 8 summarizes the survey results, presenting criteria, mean scores, and interpretations. Fifty-four respondents evaluated each criterion through hands-on system use, from which overall operational acceptability and key performance aspects were determined. The interpretation column offers qualitative insights into user

experience, while the criteria column outlines the specific quality attributes measured by user sentiment.

Criteria	Mean Score	Interpretation
Accuracy	4.80	Very Good
Auditability	4.57	Very Good
Communication commonality	4.72	Very Good
Completeness	4.63	Very Good
Conciseness	4.70	Very Good
Consistency and understandability	4.68	Very Good
Controllability	4.60	Very Good
Data commonality	4.65	Very Good
Decomposability	4.60	Very Good
Error tolerance	4.61	Very Good
Execution efficiency	4.78	Very Good
Expandability	4.74	Very Good
Generality	4.69	Very Good
Hardware independence	4.67	Very Good
Instrumentation	4.61	Very Good
Modularity	4.61	Very Good
Observability	4.65	Very Good
Operability	4.67	Very Good
Security	4.67	Very Good
Self-documentation	4.69	Very Good
Functional simplicity	4.72	Very Good
Structural simplicity	4.70	Very Good
Code simplicity	4.69	Very Good
Software system independence	4.70	Very Good
Traceability	4.69	Very Good
Training	4.76	Very Good

Table 8. Summary of Survey Results.

The top three criteria with highest scores are accuracy (4.80), execution efficiency (4.78), and training (4.76). Accuracy measures the precision of computations and control. This high score means the system is highly reliable as a tool for end users. Execution efficiency refers to the runtime performance of the program. The high score indicates that the software operates with minimal latency and high responsiveness. This is critical in disaster risk management, where large datasets, such as real-time rainfall levels, soil moisture readings, and slope angle metrics, needs to be processed instantly. Finally, training assesses the degree to which the software assists in enabling new users to utilize the system. The high score on training suggests that the system is user-friendly and easy to adopt.

In contrast, the criteria with relatively low scores are auditability (4.57), controllability (4.60), and decomposability (4.60). Auditability is defined as the ease with which conformance to standards are to be checked. The low score suggests that while the system is functional, verifying its compliance with coding standards or safety protocols is more difficult than necessary, indicating a need for clearer code documentation. Controllability denotes all possible outputs that are generated through some combination of input. The relatively lower score suggests that the system does not allow users or developers to easily produce all desired outputs or control system behavior fully, indicating potential limitations in flexibility or responsiveness that are to be addressed in future updates. Finally, decomposability means that the software is built from independent modules. The relatively lower score highlights an area for architectural improvement where the system components are further decoupled to

ensure that updating one feature, like the dynamic map, does not risk disrupting the core data processing logic.

In conclusion, this chapter has presented the architecture, technology, and user interface of the landslide prediction system. It has presented the core modules of the system such as data entry, forecasting, and analytics. Fundamentally, this chapter demonstrates the successful translation of the theoretical framework of the study into a tangible, functional web application. Furthermore, it details the comprehensive validation process employed to verify system stability, which includes unit, integration, system, and acceptance testing. These tests ensured the operational readiness of the system while highlighting areas for refinement based on user feedback. This process of development and verification phase confirms that the application is robust, reliable, and technically prepared to support the core features of the system.

CHAPTER V

RESULTS, ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents a detailed analysis and discussion of the findings related to the prediction of rainfall-induced landslides using the random forest model. The analysis directly addresses the relationship between landslide occurrences and the specified variables. Key elements examined include the correlation between landslide events and rainfall variables, as well as the correlation with environmental variables. Furthermore, the chapter evaluates the predictive capability of the random forest model by comparing its accuracy when utilizing different input datasets, such as rainfall variables only, environmental variables only, and a combination of both. The results are analyzed and discussed in the context of the hypotheses of the study, aiming to provide insights into the significance of these factors in landslide initiation and the effectiveness of the random forest approach for prediction.

5.1 Correlation Between Landslide Occurrence and Rainfall Variables

This section examines the relationship between landslide occurrence and various rainfall metrics based on the results from a logistic regression analysis, presented in Table 9. The analysis specifically evaluated the association between different measures of rainfall and the likelihood of a landslide occurring. The researchers used rainfall intensity and cumulative rainfall, each measured over the one, three, and five days before a potential landslide event.

Logistic regression models this relationship on the log-odds scale, providing coefficients that estimate the direction and magnitude of the association between each rainfall variable and the log-odds of a landslide. To make these results more interpretable, the

researchers focus on the Odds Ratios (OR), which indicate how the odds of a landslide occurring multiply for each one-unit increase in the rainfall variable, holding other variables constant. An Odds Ratio greater than one indicates a positive association (increased odds), while an Odds Ratio less than one indicates a negative association (decreased odds). The p-value assesses the statistical significance of this relationship, with a value below the conventional threshold of 0.05 indicating strong evidence that the observed relationship is not due to random chance [DN2005].

The results of the L2 Penalized Logistic Regression presented in Table 9 demonstrate that rainfall variables have a complex, yet statistically significant, relationship with the likelihood of landslide occurrence. Crucially, all associated p-values are substantially below 0.05, confirming that these relationships are not due to chance. The analysis reveals a distinct pattern: short-duration rainfall metrics (3-hour and 12-hour) are negatively associated with landslide likelihood (Odds Ratios < 1), whereas medium to longer-term metrics (6-hour, 1-day, 3-day, and 5-day) show a strong positive association (Odds Ratios > 1). The most powerful predictors are the 3-day cumulative rainfall (OR = 1.7012) and 3-day rainfall intensity (OR = 1.6764), suggesting that sustained rainfall over several days is the most critical factor in elevating landslide risk in this study context.

5.1.1 Rainfall Intensity (3, 6, 12 hours, and 1, 3, 5 days)

The analysis of rainfall intensity across the different durations revealed a mixed but statistically significant pattern. The 6-hour (OR = 1.4363), one-day (OR = 1.2877), three-day (OR = 1.6764), and five-day (OR = 1.3990) intensity variables all showed strong positive associations with landslide likelihood. In contrast, the

three-hour (OR = 0.8102) and 12-hour (OR = 0.8996) intensity variables exhibited a significant negative association.

To interpret these Odds Ratios, a one-unit increase in three-day rainfall intensity is associated with a 67.6% increase in the odds of a landslide. Conversely, a one-unit increase in three-hour intensity is associated with a 19.0% decrease in the odds. This suggests that while sustained high-intensity rainfall over days is a major risk factor, very recent, short-term intensity is negatively correlated with landslide occurrence within this model.

5.1.2 Cumulative Rainfall (3, 6, 12 hours, and 1, 3, 5 days)

The logistic regression results for cumulative rainfall strongly echo the findings for intensity, demonstrating a complex association with landslide occurrence. The six-hour (OR = 1.4003), one-day (OR = 1.2972), three-day (OR = 1.7012), and five-day (OR = 1.4981) cumulative rainfall variables all had a significant positive relationship with landslide risk. As with intensity, the three-hour (OR = 0.7950) and twelve-hour (OR = 0.8887) durations showed a significant negative relationship.

Through the interpretation of these Odds Ratios, the strongest positive association among all rainfall variables was observed for the three-day cumulative rainfall (OR = 1.7012), indicating that for each unit increase in three-day accumulated rainfall, the odds of a landslide increase by 70.1%. In contrast, a one-unit increase in three-hour cumulative rainfall is associated with a 20.5% decrease in the odds. This reinforces the conclusion that the total accumulated volume of rainfall over several days, particularly a three-day period, is a much more critical predisposing condition

for landslides than isolated, short-term rainfall events. This suggests that the total accumulated rainfall over periods up to three to five days capture critical conditions related to soil saturation and pore water pressure more strongly than intensity alone, leading to a significantly higher likelihood of landslides.

Variable	Coefficient	Odds Ratio	P-value
cumulative_rainfall_3hr	-0.2275	0.7950	0.00051
cumulative_rainfall_6hr	0.3506	1.4003	0.00071
cumulative_rainfall_12hr	-0.1039	0.8887	0.00063
cumulative_rainfall_1d	0.2506	1.2972	0.00060
cumulative_rainfall_3d	0.5248	1.7012	0.00093
cumulative_rainfall_5d	0.3797	1.4981	0.00062
rainfall_intensity_3hr	-0.2235	0.8102	0.00051
rainfall_intensity_6hr	0.3557	1.4363	0.00046
rainfall_intensity_12hr	-0.1014	0.8996	0.00063
rainfall_intensity_1d	0.2492	1.2877	0.00060
rainfall_intensity_3d	0.5219	1.6764	0.00094
rainfall_intensity_5d	0.3633	1.3990	0.00005

Table 9. L2 Penalized Logistic Regression for Rainfall Variables.

5.2 Correlation between Landslide Occurrence and Environmental Variables

The logistic regression analysis revealed statistically significant relationships between landslide occurrence and two of the environmental variables: slope and soil moisture. The results seen in Table 10 indicate that slope has a statistically significant positive association

with the likelihood of landslide occurrence with an Odds Ratio of 1.682 and p less than 0.001, meaning that for every one-unit increase in slope, the odds of a landslide are estimated to increase by 68.2%, holding soil type and soil moisture constant. Similarly, soil moisture also showed a statistically significant positive association with an Odds Ratio of 1.4179 and p less than 0.001, where each one-unit increase in soil moisture is associated with an estimated 41.8% increase in the odds of a landslide, holding other factors constant. In contrast, the soil type variable did not exhibit a statistically significant association with landslide occurrence after accounting for slope and soil moisture. Although the estimated odds ratio for soil type suggests a potential 6.6% decrease in odds per unit increase but failed to reach statistical significance ($p = 0.114$), suggesting that, after accounting for slope and soil moisture, there is no reliable evidence of an association between this specific soil measure and landslide occurrence within the dataset.

Variable	Coefficient	Odds Ratio	95% CI for Odds Ratio	P-value
slope	0.9826	2.6713	[2.4596, 2.9008]	0.000
soil_type	0.1807	1.1980	[1.0492, 1.3689]	0.008
soil_moisture	2.4571	11.6698	[3.013, 45.1953]	0.000

Table 10. Logistic Regression for Environmental Variables.

5.2.1 Soil Moisture (1 day)

As seen on the displayed scatter plot on Figure 15, there is a clear and generally positive correlation between increasing soil moisture levels and the

corresponding predicted probability. The figure provides a visualization of this relationship, plotting individual predictions against soil moisture and overlaying a binned mean to summarize the central trend. This overarching relationship is effectively captured by the upward trajectory of the binned mean line, which, despite some localized volatility such as a notable dip around the 0.2 moisture level, demonstrates a definitive positive trend for all moisture values above this point.

The data distribution exhibits a clear upward trend, moving from the lower-left to the upper-right as soil moisture increases. While moisture levels below 0.2 yield varied predictions, values above 0.3 consistently correspond to elevated probabilities, often exceeding 0.6. This relationship is validated by the color-coding: actual Class 1 events (blue) cluster in these high-probability zones, whereas Class 0 non-events (red) remain predominantly in the lower bands.

Figure 15. Soil Moisture Result.

5.2.2 Slope

The variable had exhibited a significant positive relationship with predicted events, indicated by a p-value of less than 0.001 as seen in Figure 16. A one-unit increase in slope ranking elevates the log-odds of the event, with predicted probabilities rising from approximately 0.18 at the lowest rank (1) to about 0.96 at the highest (6). Variability in predictions is greatest at intermediate slope ranks, suggesting higher uncertainty, while ranks 5 and 6 show narrower distributions indicative of high model consensus at elevated probability levels. These results provide solid support for the underlying hypothesis that links increased slope steepness to a higher probability of the event. The model not only captures this fundamental relationship but also effectively ranks risk across the different slope categories stated in the study.

Figure 16. Slope Result.

5.2.3 Soil Type

The figure compares the predicted probabilities across four soil types: Loam, Clay Loam, Clay, and Sandy Loam. Loam shows the highest median predicted probability at about 0.8. Clay Loam has a median around 0.4, whereas Clay and Sandy Loam have much lower median probabilities, both near 0.2. The plot as seen in Figure 17 reveals distinct differences in how predictions are distributed across soil types. Loam, Clay Loam, and Clay show a wide spread of values, indicating high variability in the predictions of the model. Loam is notable for its high median prediction, despite a distribution that extends into lower values. In contrast, sandy loam predictions are tightly clustered in a low-probability range, though extreme outliers reaching 1.0 exist. This indicates that while the model generally views sandy loam as low-risk, it identifies specific high-confidence anomalies.

Figure 17. Soil Type Result.

5.3 Assessment of the Random Forest Model Performance Across Different Variables

This section evaluates the performance of the random forest model in predicting landslide occurrences using performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score. For further explanation, precision indicates the accuracy of positive predictions for that class, recall measures the models ability to find all positive instances of that class, and the f1-score is a balanced measure of both. Additionally, the metric also includes the accuracy metric which is the total percentage of correct predictions done by the model.

5.3.1 Random Forest Model Assessment with Rainfall Variables Only

The researchers only used rainfall variables that were stated in the study to train the model. The data shown in Table 11 shows how it performed during the five-fold cross-validation. The scores for accuracy, F1, precision, and recall mostly hover in the lower to middle 0.76s (73% to 79%).

The results were reasonably close together across the five folds, suggesting the performance was considered to be consistent on different parts of the training data. To conclude, using just rainfall gives a decent baseline performance. It gets the correct predictions at around 73% to 79% of the time according to these metrics during these internal tests and with an average of 76%.

The analysis shows that a model relying solely on rainfall data achieves a respectable baseline performance, with an average score of approximately 76% across the primary metrics. This indicates the importance of the hydrological input to the researchers found out that rainfall characteristics, in isolation, are a significant and powerful predictor of landslide events. This confirms that precipitation intensity and

duration are critical determinants of slope instability. It correctly identifies the outcome roughly three-quarters of the time during these internal validation tests.

Metrics	first fold	second fold	third fold	fourth fold	fifth fold	average
Accuracy	0.7344	0.7721	0.7902	0.7508	0.7668	0.7629
f1-score	0.7321	0.7720	0.7901	0.7503	0.7657	0.7628
precision	0.7434	0.7728	0.7908	0.7533	0.7721	0.7669
recall	0.7344	0.7721	0.7902	0.7508	0.7668	0.7629

Table 11. Five-Fold Cross Validation for Rainfall Variables Only.

5.3.2 Random Forest Model Assessment with Environmental Variables Only

In this section, the five-fold cross-validation process was repeated, using only the environmental factors (soil moisture, soil type, slope) as inputs. Based on table 12, the performance was mostly in the 81% to 83% range for accuracy, recall, and the other metrics. Compared to rainfall variables only, performance metrics were marginally lower, showing minimal deviation from the rainfall-only model. Overall, it suggests that the environmental variables on their own provide a comparable level of predictive information as the rainfall variables. This indicates that inherent terrain characteristics play a substantial role in defining landslide susceptibility, independent of immediate rainfall triggers. This parity suggests that combining these static conditions with dynamic triggers is essential for maximizing predictive performance.

metrics	first fold	second fold	third fold	fourth fold	fifth fold	average
Accuracy	0.8344	0.8328	0.8262	0.8131	0.8424	0.8298
f1-score	0.834	0.8327	0.8261	0.8123	0.8422	0.8294
precision	0.8384	0.8337	0.8274	0.8192	0.8445	0.8327
recall	0.8344	0.8328	0.8262	0.8131	0.8424	0.8298

Table 12. Five-Fold Cross Validation for Environmental Variables Only.

5.3.3 Random Forest Model Assessment with the Combined Rainfall and Environmental Variables

In this section, the model was trained using a combination of rainfall and environmental variables. As shown in Table 13, five-fold cross-validation results demonstrate a noticeable improvement. Accuracy, F1-score, precision, and recall consistently ranged between 84% and 87%, with a stable average of 86%. This confirms that integrating both variable types significantly enhances the learning and predictive capability of the model.

metrics	first fold	second fold	third fold	fourth fold	fifth fold	average
Accuracy	0.8492	0.8754	0.8590	0.8574	0.8621	0.8606
f1-score	0.8490	0.8754	0.8589	0.8573	0.8616	0.8601
precision	0.8510	0.8754	0.8593	0.8585	0.8672	0.8623
recall	0.8492	0.8754	0.8590	0.8574	0.8621	0.8606

Table 13. Five-Fold Cross Validation for Environmental and Rainfall Variables.

5.3.4 Confusion Matrix

Figure 18 illustrates the classification performance of the model in distinguishing between landslide and non-landslide events. The model correctly identified 270 landslides (True Positives) and 257 non-landslides (True Negatives). Conversely, it generated 39 False Positives and 44 False Negatives. This balanced accuracy demonstrates the strong capability of the model to differentiate between classes. While minor misclassifications occurred, their low frequency still confirms the high reliability of the model in this task. Collectively, these findings derived using the confusion matrix as a tool, validates the random forest model approach as an effective decision-support tool for forecasting.

		Predicted	
		non-landslide(0)	landslide[1]
Actual	non-landslide(0)	257	39
	landslide[1]	44	270

Figure 18. Confusion Matrix.

5.4 Hypothesis Testing

The researchers employed ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) as a formal statistical test to evaluate whether the performance differences observed during the five-fold cross-validation of the three models (rainfall only, environmental only, combination of both) were significant or due to random chance in data splits. ANOVA works by comparing variations in average performance scores among distinct groups against variation within individual groups, using the F-statistic. A high F-score indicates significant differences among groups, and the F-value is compared to a critical F-value from an F-distribution table for evaluation. [AK2024].

In this study, a high F-statistic is determined to be above the value 3.89 based on the F-distribution table. Meanwhile, the result of the p-values were all approximately 0.002 or lower. Since these p-values are substantially below the conventional significance threshold of 0.05, it provides strong statistical evidence to accept the alternative hypothesis which assumes that there is difference between the groups. Therefore, the analysis validates the presence of distinct underlying characteristics that separate these groups within the dataset.

For every performance metric assessed such as accuracy, f1-score, precision, and recall, the corresponding ANOVA test as shown in Table 14 yielded very high F-statistics, ranging from 54.2 to 68.8. However, while the ANOVA test indicated an overall significant difference, it does not identify which specific pairs of models are different. Therefore, the researchers utilized the Tukey HSD post-hoc test (Honestly Significant Difference) to perform pairwise comparisons. This tool identifies which specific pairs of models have a statistically significant difference [AH2010].

Metric	F-statistic	p-value	Result
Accuracy	56.637695	0.00000077	TRUE
F1-score	54.233518	0.00000098	TRUE
Precision	68.789328	0.00000027	TRUE
Recall	56.637695	0.00000077	TRUE

Table 14. ANOVA Result.

5.4.1 Post-hoc Test for Model Accuracy

For accuracy, the initial ANOVA test confirms there is a statistically significant difference somewhere among the three models. To find out exactly where the differences lie, a post-hoc test was conducted, with the results displayed in Table 15. Based on the pairwise comparisons, the test reveals that the difference between Model 1 and Model 2 is statistically significant. This confirms that rainfall and environmental variables contribute uniquely to model performance. Likewise, the differences between Model 1 and Model 3 and between Model 2 and Model 3 are also statistically significant. In terms of accuracy, these results indicate that the performance of all three models was significantly different from each other.

group1	group2	meandiff	p-adj	lower	upper	reject
Model 1	Model 2	0.0669	0.0000	0.0419	0.0920	True
Model 1	Model 3	0.0977	0.0000	0.0727	0.1228	True
Model 2	Model 3	0.0308	0.0167	0.0058	0.0559	True

Table 15. Post-hoc for Accuracy Result.

5.4.2 Post-hoc Test for Model F1-score

As based on the F1-scores, the ANOVA indicates a significant overall difference between the models. The Tukey HSD post-hoc test clarifies this as seen in Table 16. The comparison between Model 1 and Model 2 shows a significant difference. Moreover, the comparisons show that the F1-score of the Model 3 is significantly different from Model 1 and also significantly different from Model 2. The pattern is consistent with the accuracy results.

group1	group2	meandiff	p-adj	lower	upper	reject
Model 1	Model 2	0.0674	0.0000	0.0416	0.0932	True
Model 1	Model 3	0.0984	0.0000	0.0726	0.1242	True
Model 2	Model 3	0.0310	0.0190	0.0052	0.0568	True

Table 16. Post-hoc for F1-score Result.

5.4.3 Post-hoc Test for Model Precision

For the precision metric, the ANOVA test established an overall significant difference among the models as shown in Table 17. The subsequent Tukey HSD pairwise comparisons show that Model 1 and Model 2 are significantly different in their precision. Furthermore, Model 3 demonstrates significantly different precision compared to Model 1 and compared to Model 2. These results confirm that each model exhibits a distinct level of precision that is distinguishable from the others. This identifies the specific model configuration that minimizes false positive errors.

group1	group2	meandiff	p-adj	lower	upper	reject
Model 1	Model 2	0.0662	0.0000	0.0439	0.0885	True
Model 1	Model 3	0.0958	0.0000	0.0735	0.1181	True
Model 2	Model 3	0.0296	0.0105	0.0073	0.0519	True

Table 17. Post-hoc for Precision Result.

5.4.4 Post-hoc Test for Model Recall

The ANOVA results indicated a statistically significant overall difference in mean recall across the models. This significant finding suggests that the recall performance of the three models is not all equal. To determine which specific pairs of models differed significantly, a post-hoc Tukey Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test was performed as seen in Table 18. The outcomes of the Tukey HSD test for recall were consistent with the findings previously observed for model accuracy. This alignment across metrics reinforces the validity of the combined variable approach. Specifically, the test revealed a statistically significant difference in recall between Model 1 and Model 2. Moreover, the recall of Model 3 was found to be also statistically significantly different from both Model 1 and Model 2.

group1	group2	meandiff	p-adj	lower	upper	reject
Model 1	Model 2	0.0669	0.0000	0.0419	0.092	True
Model 1	Model 3	0.0977	0.0000	0.0727	0.1228	True
Model 2	Model 3	0.0308	0.0167	0.0058	0.0559	True

Table 18. Post-hoc for Recall Result.

5.5 Evaluation of Random Forest Model with Bayesian Optimization

This section highlights the strong performance of the random forest model after hyperparameter tuning using bayesian optimization via Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) of optuna as shown in the Table 19 below. It efficiently searched for the best hyperparameter combinations, with trial 12 yielding the highest weighted F1-score of approximately 0.9066 using 63 estimators and a maximum depth of 23. The final model, trained with these optimized settings and tested on unseen data, achieved consistent results with both overall accuracy and weighted F1-score at around 0.91. It performed equally well in predicting landslide and non-landslide events, showing slightly higher recall for non-landslides (0.94) and slightly higher precision for landslides (0.93), indicating a well-balanced and generalizable model.

category	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.88	0.94	0.91	304
1	0.93	0.88	0.90	306
accuracy	0.91	0.91	0.91	610

Table 19. Random Forest Model Evaluation Result.

In conclusion, the analysis confirms that both rainfall and environmental factors are critical for predicting landslides with sustained multi-day rainfall, in particular, identifying 3-day cumulative rainfall and intensity as the most potent predictors. Alongside this, slope and soil moisture were confirmed as highly significant environmental contributors, whereas

certain soil types did not show a statistically significant influence. Consequently, these high-impact variables are prioritized to maximize model accuracy.

The study statistically proves through the use of ANOVA and Tukey HSD post-hoc tests that a random forest model integrating both rainfall and environmental variables achieved a significantly higher predictive accuracy (averaging 86%) than models using either rainfall (76%) or environmental variables (81-83%) alone. After final tuning with Bayesian optimization, the model achieved a high accuracy of approximately 91%. This demonstrates its strong potential as a reliable tool for landslide forecasting.

Furthermore, these findings highlight the advantage of using ensemble machine learning techniques such as random forest for complex forecasting, where nonlinear interactions between variables play a crucial role. The random forest model effectively captured the combined influence of rainfall and environmental variables, resulting in improved predictive performance and model stability. The substantial increase in accuracy after Bayesian optimization further demonstrates the importance of systematic hyperparameter tuning in enhancing model reliability. Overall, the results affirm the suitability of the proposed model for integration into landslide early warning systems, providing a data-driven basis for more accurate risk assessment and timely decision-making in landslide-prone regions in the Philippines.

CHAPTER VI

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter provides the conclusion of the study by summarizing the solutions to the initial problems identified and their resolution. The chapter offers a detailed description of the experimentation process, illustrates key findings, concludes the hypothesis, and the general performance of the random forest model when applied for landslide prediction. In addition, this section hints at possible future directions on how the model is to be enhanced and the uses of landslide forecasting systems expanded. The objective of this chapter is to summarize the findings of the research and present recommendations that guide future studies in this area.

6.1 Conclusion

This section provides a concluding overview of the research, summarizing the primary findings to address the core objectives related to identifying key predictors of rainfall-induced landslides. It specifically shows the results concerning the differential influence of rainfall intensity versus cumulative rainfall over multiple durations, and the significance of environmental factors such as soil moisture, slope, and soil type. Based on this evidence, the section evaluates the extent to which the hypotheses of the study were supported and offers a final assessment of the capability of the random forest model to effectively predict landslide occurrences using the investigated variables. Ultimately, this conclusion validates the research framework and confirms the potential of the system as a tool for forecasting landslides.

6.1.1 The Role of Rainfall Variables in Landslide Prediction

The study concludes that rainfall variables have a complex, yet highly significant, relationship with landslide occurrence, which is not uniformly positive across all time scales. The model identifies a critical distinction between the effects of short-term and long-term rainfall. The results strongly confirm that sustained rainfall is a dominant positive predictor. Specifically, both cumulative rainfall and rainfall intensity measured over longer durations, namely 6-hours, 1-day, 3-days, and 5-days, all demonstrated strong, statistically significant positive correlations with landslide likelihood. The coefficients for these variables indicate a considerable increase in predicted risk per unit increase. The most powerful positive predictor among all variables was three-day cumulative rainfall (OR = 1.7012), followed very closely by three-day rainfall intensity (OR = 1.6764). This indicates that sustained rainfall over a three-day period, whether measured by total volume or average intensity, is the most critical factor driving landslide risk in this model.

In contrast, the model revealed a significant negative association for very short-term rainfall metrics. Both the 3-hour and 12-hour cumulative and intensity variables yielded negative coefficients and odds ratios less than one. This counter-intuitive finding does not imply that recent rain prevents landslides. Rather, it is likely a statistical artifact of the model accounting for the overwhelming influence of the long-term variables. Once the powerful effect of sustained saturation (e.g., from three-day rainfall) is factored in, the negative coefficients for short-term rain likely act as correction factors, suggesting that a long, steady soaking is more

dangerous than a pattern with a very recent, intense burst. Consequently, deep infiltration of moisture in soil appears more critical of a variable than immediate surface intensity.

Therefore, these findings only accept Hypothesis 1.2.1, which suggests a positive correlation between rainfall and landslide occurrence. The hypothesis holds true for medium to long-term rainfall (6-hours to 5-days) but is rejected for the very short-term (3-hour and 12-hour) metrics within this multivariate context. The results strongly suggest that while both intensity is important, the duration of the rainfall event is paramount. The critical factor is the total accumulated water input over several days, which leads to the soil saturation and elevated pore water pressure that ultimately trigger slope failure.

6.1.2 The Role of Environmental Variables in Landslide Prediction

Environmental factors were found to be crucial predictors of landslide susceptibility, strongly supporting Hypothesis 1.2.2, which posited a positive correlation between these variables and landslide occurrence. Higher levels of one-day soil moisture and steeper slope gradients both showed clear, statistically significant positive associations with increased predicted landslide probability. Furthermore, the analysis demonstrated that landslide likelihood varied significantly across different soil types, indicating the model successfully captured the influence of inherent soil properties on susceptibility. These findings suggest the importance of integrating site-specific environmental conditions into landslide prediction models.

Therefore, these findings accept Hypothesis 1.2.2, which states that there is a positive correlation between environmental variables and landslide occurrence. Furthermore, both soil moisture and slope showed a strong positive relationship with landslide occurrence, however, soil type showed a negative correlation but had a p-value of 0.114 which suggests that there is no reliable evidence of a correlation between the occurrence of landslides in the dataset and this particular soil metric once slope and soil moisture have been taken into consideration. This confirms that environmental factors like soil moisture and slope significantly influence landslide susceptibility, providing spatial context and enhancing the predictive capability of the random forest model.

6.1.3 Overall Predictive Performance of the Random Forest Model

The random forest model demonstrated strong overall capability in predicting rainfall-induced landslides when utilizing the combined set of rainfall and environmental variables. The analysis indicated a high degree of accuracy in distinguishing between landslide and non-landslide events, as evidenced by the relatively low number of misclassifications (false positives and false negatives) observed in the confusion matrix. This suggests that the random forest model effectively integrates the complex influences of both triggering factors (rainfall) and predisposing conditions (environmental variables) to produce reliable predictions, implicitly supporting Hypothesis 1.2.3 by showing the utility of combining variable sets for effective prediction.

6.1.3.1 Individual and Combined Variable Set Performance Comparison

The results indicated that models trained solely on rainfall variables or solely on environmental variables achieved comparable and moderate performance levels, with performance metrics generally ranging between approximately 80% and 86%. This indicates that both current triggering conditions (rainfall) and underlying environmental conditions contain substantial, but relatively equal amounts of, predictive information if taken individually in the internal validation step. However, an improvement was observed when both rainfall and environmental features were combined. This combined approach consistently yielded higher performance across all metrics, typically falling between 86% and 91% during cross-validation.

6.1.3.2 Impact of Bayesian Optimization on the Performance of the Model

The findings strongly suggest the collective effect of integrating both triggering and preparatory factors, allowing the model to capture a more holistic understanding of landslide prerequisites than either feature set provides alone. With the utilization of bayesian algorithm using optuna the model significantly increases by 3% to 5% having an accuracy of 0.91. This indicates a well-tuned model configuration poised for effective generalization.

6.1.3.3 Statistical Comparison of Models Derived

Furthermore, additional detailed statistical comparisons using ANOVA followed by Tukey HSD post-hoc tests were performed to pinpoint specific differences between the models derived from the different approaches. While ANOVA consistently confirmed significant overall differences across all

metrics, the Tukey HSD tests provided pairwise comparisons. By synthesizing the results from the different statistical test outputs provided, the most effective finding was that the model using combined features consistently demonstrated statistically significant performance advantages over models using only rainfall or only environmental factors across accuracy, F1-score, precision, and recall. Although the statistical significance of the difference between Model 2 and Model 3 varied slightly depending on the specific metric or test run illustrated, the superiority of the combined feature model was confirmed by these post-hoc analyses. Therefore, these findings accept Hypothesis 1.2.3 which states that there is a significant difference in the performance of the model when utilizing different variables

In conclusion, this study demonstrated the effectiveness of a random forest model, optimized using optuna bayesian methods, for landslide prediction. The final optimized model exhibited strong and balanced predictive capability on unseen test data. This study result highlights the importance of considering multiple facets of landslide causality and utilizing automated optimization techniques to develop an effective predictive model.

6.2 Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, this section proposes recommendations for future research and practical application aimed at advancing rainfall-induced landslide prediction. Key directions include the incorporation of additional influential environmental and

triggering variables, the comparative evaluation of different predictive algorithms, and the critical development of more comprehensive and precise landslide inventories. Furthermore, integrating these models into real-time early warning systems could significantly enhance community preparedness and disaster response times.

6.2.1 Integration of Additional Predictive Variables

Future research needs to use a greater diversity of features aside from those variables discussed here in this study to improve the accuracy and resilience of the model in predicting rainfall-triggered landslides. This includes comprehensive land use or land cover mapping that integrates specific vegetation types and how they influence root cohesion and hydrology. Geological data (lithology, structure, weathering, depth to soil) that are needed in the interpretation of material strength and permeability were employed in other explorations. Aspect, curvature, elevation, and distance to rivers or roads are some illustrative geomorphological parameters capable of recording small-scale water movement and stress concentration. Predictive models are improved in accuracy and physical basis by adding these numerous factors, which are often derived from remote sensing and GIS.

6.2.2 Exploration of Alternative Predictive Models

While the random forest model performed well, it is recommended to compare it with other modeling techniques for methodological strength and other improvements. Given the various strengths of algorithms, researchers should compare alternatives like Gradient Boosting, which often achieve high accuracy by progressively correcting errors from previous steps. Support Vector Machines are to

be explored as they are good at detecting clear boundaries between landslide and non-landslide conditions. Additionally, although complex, deep learning models are very insightful when applied to understanding time sequences like rainfall or detecting patterns in geographical map data.

In addition to using hybrid models that integrate machine learning and physical models, interpretable statistical models like Generalized Additive Models facilitate much better understanding of how each factor affects the hazard of a landslide. The application of standardized criteria to contrast these different methods allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the optimal modeling approach for rainfall-induced landslide prediction. Furthermore, this comparison provides a pathway towards enhanced predictive accuracy and the generation of new scientific knowledge.

6.2.3 Development of a More Comprehensive Landslide Inventory

Future research needs to enhance the quality, accuracy, and quantity of data within the landslide inventory because it is crucial to the reliability of the model. As bigger datasets generally allow models to learn more solid patterns and improve generalization, adding more landslide occurrences to the inventory is an important factor to consider. In addition, in order to link landslides to their triggers, it is also important to map landslide locations correctly, preferably as polygons showing their actual geometry and not merely points, and establish an accurate date and time of occurrence. The accuracy and timeliness of inventory revisions are significantly enhanced by incorporating information from remote sensing platforms.

Further collaboration with government agencies such as geological surveys, disaster management agencies, or public works agencies is also highly recommended since they often possess data that are highly relevant to the study and assists in developing more accurate and comprehensive inventories. Landslides were classified by type since different types of landslides have different triggers and sensitivities, enabling more detailed or type-specific modeling. A high-quality landslide inventory enhances model training and assessment and, ultimately, leads to more reliable predictions.

6.2.4 Automated Collection of Landslide Data

To further enhance the random forest model and ensure its applicability in real-world scenarios, future works are to prioritize the automation of data acquisition. This objective is achieved by establishing formal collaborations with government agencies or by leveraging publicly available data from reputable sources, such as the public reports done by the NDRRMC. Specifically, implementing data mining and web scraping techniques allows for the automated extraction of critical information from situational reports, ensuring the dataset remains current without the need for manual input.

This chapter concludes that the Bayesian-optimized random forest model achieves high accuracy by effectively combining environmental factors with rainfall data. Crucially, the research identifies sustained, long-term rainfall as a more significant predictor of slope failure than short-term intensity. To enhance real-world applicability, future studies should

focus on integrating diverse variables, refining landslide inventories, and establishing automated data collection to enable continuous model learning.

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

This study is created concerning the project management aspect for planned and organized operations to ensure a successful development of the rainfall-induced landslide prediction model through the random forest model utilization. The strategy applies proper hardware and software, clear role definition, budgeting, and time management. The researchers are able to prepare against associated risks, maximize usage of resources, and achieve deadlines, thus fulfilling the goals of the project effectively.

A. Hardware Recommendation

In this study, training the random forest model requires appropriate hardware configurations with performance considerations, appropriate storage, and reliability. While less computationally intensive than other deep learning models, the random forest model still requires specific hardware. These specifications are required for large datasets with regard to efficient data processing, feature selection, and hyperparameter optimization.

1. Model Training and Data Processing

The training of a random forest model requires handling huge amounts of environmental and landslide datasets demanding efficient data preprocessing and parallel computation. Therefore, appropriate hardware is crucial for handling these demands effectively. The suggested hardware specifications in this study are:

Processor: Intel Core i5 or AMD Ryzen 5 (2.5 GHz or higher) for the efficient processing of data and executing models.

Memory: 8GB RAM or greater for seamless processing of multiple decision trees together.

Storage: 512GB SSD. This is great for fast access of large sets of data, especially for storing results, models, and logs.

Internet Connectivity: Reliable connectivity to enable data retrieval, training resources for the model, and collaboration tools.

2. Testing of Application

The prediction application across various devices was tested ensuring usability and compatibility. Additionally, this process helps identify potential performance bottlenecks on lower-specification systems. This approach ensures a seamless user experience regardless of device. The recommended testing hardware includes:

2.1 Desktop/ Laptop: Intel Core i3 or AMD Ryzen 3 (2.0 GHz or higher) with 4GB RAM, and a 256GB SSD.

2.2 Mobile Devices: Qualcomm Snapdragon 665 or equivalent, with 2GB RAM and 32GB storage to test mobile-friendly interfaces for the potential end-user accessibility.

B. Software Recommendation

This project consists of software tools and libraries that support data preprocessing, model training, evaluation, and visualization. These are based on open-source frameworks as the cost is supposed to be low, although still flexible and scalable. The project is open-source

to ensure transparency and reproducibility, enabling others to verify and build upon the work.

1. Python: It includes important features of a vast library ecosystem and friendly nature.

Machine Learning Frameworks:

- 1.1 Scikit-learn: A very flexible library that helps implement and fine-tune a random forest model.
- 1.2 Pandas and NumPy: For data manipulation and numerical operations.
2. Development Environment: Jupyter Notebook, for its interactivity and ease with code documentation and testing, alongside Visual Studio Code for structured coding, debugging, and deployment preparation.
3. Visualization Tools: Matplotlib and Seaborn for plot generation and model performance metric visualization.
4. Cloud support: Vercel, utilized for optimized frontend hosting, and Google Cloud Run, employed for managing scalable, containerized backend services.

C. Peopleware Recommendation

The project involves researchers primarily in, developing the model, testing, and analyzing it, and there is an opportunity in the future to work with policymakers or disaster response teams as the primary users. Researchers are important in improving the accuracy of the model and identifying its limitations through testing and analysis. The project is essential for future development of a comprehensive management system that benefits a lot of the local communities that are present in the Philippines. The goal of this is to provide policy

makers and disaster response teams with the appropriate tools to improve disaster prediction efforts. Through this, the community disaster preparedness plans are able to enhance further.

1. Researcher:

They are responsible for dataset acquisition, model training, hyperparameter tuning, and performance evaluation. They develop interpretive visualizations to analyze results and optimize the model. The researchers utilized their experience in utilizing the model to enhance the performance.

2. End-users/Government Agencies

Along with susceptibility mapping development, providing the system for real-time landslide prediction and risk assessment to policymakers or concerned local government units is also being facilitated. The real time capabilities of the system enable proactive mitigation efforts, minimizing the impact of potentially dangerous landslides. By providing timely and accurate information the system contributes in enhancing the public safety and resilience of local communities that are prone to landslide occurrences.

D. System Budget

The estimated budget for this research totals ₱44,719.37. The largest portion of the budget is allocated to hardware, with ₱35,000.00 designated for a mid-range laptop that satisfies all recommended technical specifications. An additional ₱5,000.00 is reserved for miscellaneous expenses, including internet connectivity, storage backups, and other incidental operational needs. Newly included in the budget are system usage and

computational service costs incurred during the implementation phase of the study. These include ₱294.58 and ₱677.52 for request-based processing beyond 1,000 requests per load, as well as ₱3,317.76 and ₱352.51 for time-based computational usage over a total duration of 2,073,600 seconds (24 days). Collectively, these operational expenses ensure uninterrupted system performance throughout the research period.

E. Time Management

Proper time management is required in a project so that all the objectives are achieved in time. In total, the project has been divided into four major phases for proper workflow. The first phase is Data Acquisition and Preparation, which consists of the gathering and preprocessing of data from reliable sources such as NASA, DRRMC, and Open Meteo such that the datasets are properly prepared for training the model. The second phase, Model Training and Optimization (Weeks 9–20) focuses on training the random forest model, careful tweaking of its hyperparameters, and evaluation of its performance to ensure that the predictive accuracy of the model is optimized. The third phase, System Development and Testing (Weeks 21–30), aims to build the predictive framework and test it on different devices to ensure that the system is compatible and functional. The fourth phase, Documentation and Finalization (Weeks 31–40), finally involves preparing the final version of the thesis document that integrates results, discussions, and insights acquired across the study. Such a systematic timeline allows for efficient progress toward the timely completion of the study.

GLOSSARY

A. ANTECEDENT RAINFALL

It refers to the total amount of rainfall measured over the days leading up to an event, providing an insight into prior moisture levels in the soil and environment [DM2024].

B. CUMULATIVE RAINFALL

It is the total amount of rainfall recorded over a certain period in a specific location [WA2024].

D. DURATION

In this study, it refers to the specific length of time (e.g., one day, three days, or five days) that elapses immediately prior to a potential event. Throughout the entire duration, rainfall parameters (e.g., total accumulation or mean intensity) are calculated. A 1-day rainfall duration, for instance, includes data from the entire 24-hour period prior to the event, including any periods of no rain. The term describes the period of time used in calculation, but not necessarily the quantity of rain that fell consistently over that period.

E. FOLDS

This indicates the number of groups into which the dataset is split. This figure establishes the amount of testing iterations the model goes through, guaranteeing that every segment is utilized as a testing set only once [CV2024].

F. F-STATISTIC

A value derived from statistical tests like ANOVA or regression to determine if a group of variables is jointly significant. Generally, a higher F-statistic means the results are significant, allowing the null hypothesis to be rejected [GS2009].

G. HYPERPARAMETERS

It refers to the configuration of variables set before the training process of the model begins. Unlike parameters that the model learns during training, hyperparameters are set by the user or determined through techniques like hyperparameter tuning. [G2023].

H. LANDSLIDE EVENTS

In this study, these are defined as instances categorized into two outcomes: landslide occurrence and no landslide occurrence.

I. LANDSLIDE OCCURRENCE

In this study, it refers to the presence or the actual event of a landslide taking place. The study uses this definition to differentiate itself from the term landslide events as two separate definitions.

J. LOG-ODDS

In logistic regression, these are crucial because they change the logistic regression model from a probability-based model to a likelihood-based model. While both probability

and log odds have their own set of characteristics, log odds facilitates output interpretation. Log odds are therefore somewhat better than probability [G2025c].

K. ODDS RATIO

It is a statistical metric used in logistic regression to assess the degree and direction of a relationship between a predictor variable and an outcome variable is the odds ratio (OR). For a one-unit increase in the predictor variable, it shows the ratio of the odds of the result occurring in one group to the odds of the outcome occurring in another group [G2025c].

L. PERFORMANCE METRICS

It helps evaluate and compare various machine learning models by having quantitative measures of a model's accuracy, f1-score, precision, and recall.

N. POST-HOC ANALYSIS

This is also known as posteriori comparisons, made after the data have been obtained. Upon the rejection of an analysis of variance (ANOVA) model null hypothesis, post-hoc tests are applied in order to detect the population means that differ [CS2022].

M. RAINFALL INTENSITY

It is defined as the ratio of the total amount of rain (rainfall depth) falling during a given period to the duration of the period It is expressed in depth units per unit time, usually as mm per hour (mm/h) [CW1991].

O. RAINFALL AND ENVIRONMENTAL VARIABLES

In this study, the first term is used to encompass rainfall intensity and cumulative rainfall, in order to be collectively referred to as rainfall variables. Meanwhile, the other term refers to variables such as soil moisture, slope, and soil type.

P. SLOPE

This refers to the steepness or incline of a surface, typically measured in degrees from the horizontal [SA2024]. This is one of the key indicators that landslides are most likely to occur.

Q. SOIL MOISTURE

It is the water stored in the soil, it is a key variable influenced by a complex interplay of factors and is affected by precipitation, temperature, soil characteristics, and more [ES2024].

R. SOIL TYPE

It refers to the classification of soil based on its texture, proportions of particles, and the presence of organic and mineral compositions [BY2024].

S. SPATIAL AND TEMPORAL FORECASTING

The former predicts the locations of future landslides in a specific area without taking into account their frequency or timing [TF2022]. The latter, meanwhile, describes the process

of predicting the occurrence of landslides over time, including the prediction of changes in important parameters that affect slope stability and safety over time [TF2022].

T. SUPERVISED LEARNING

A category of machine learning that involves training algorithms on labeled datasets to identify patterns and make predictions [GC2024].

U. TEMPORAL AND SPATIAL VARIABLES

The former is referred to as time-stamped or time-related information , which makes it possible to monitor changes across predetermined time periods. It is useful for making well-informed decisions about the way variables change over time [TD2024]. The latter, meanwhile, contain information about the actual locations and properties of objects on Earth and are frequently referred to as geospatial data [AT2023].

V. TIME PERIOD

Refers to the particular time frame or forecast horizon that was employed in the research. It defines the duration of time into the future for which the forecast is valid. For instance, a 6-hour time period indicates that the model predicts the probability of a landslide occurring within the subsequent six hours.

LIST OF SCREENSHOTS

1. Homepage Display Interface.....	113
2. Dynamic Map Interface.....	115
3. Forecast Settings.....	116
4. Prediction Result Display.....	117
5. Prediction Report Summary Interface.....	118
6. Report Summary Analysis and PDF Generation.....	119
7. User Guide Section.....	120
8. Historical Landslides Dashboard Interface.....	121
9. Training Results Interface.....	123

USERS' MANUAL

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Homepage.....	113
2. Dynamic Map Interface.....	114
3. Forecast Setting.....	116
4. Prediction Result Display.....	117
5. Prediction Report Summary.....	118
6. Report Summary Analysis and PDF Generation.....	119
7. User Guide.....	120
8. Historical Landslide Dashboard.....	121
9. Training Result.....	122

Bachelor of Science in
COMPUTER
SCIENCE

USERS' MANUAL

This section details the modules of TwoStepsAhead, guiding disaster management agencies like LGUs and the NDRRMC on effective system utilization. The manual ensures that users, regardless of technical experience, are able to navigate the interface with ease. Users require only a standard web browser and stable internet to access twostepsahead.site.

1. Homepage

As shown in Screenshot 1, the homepage interface displays the introductory page of the system. The navbar is used for the navigation of the different parts of the website. The body of the homepage displays the tagline and description of the system, along with its main features. Users proceed by clicking either the “Learn How” or “Start Predicting” button. The footer lists different sources of data utilized by researchers.

Screenshot 1. Homepage Display Interface.

- A. Learn How Button - When clicked, it directs the user to the User Guide page.
- B. Start Predicting Button - When clicked, it directs the user to the Dynamic Map page. This is the main feature.
- C. Home - This is a navigation link that returns the user to the landing page.
- D. Dynamic Map - This is a navigation link that directs users to the dynamic map which is the page for the forecasting tool.
- E. User Guide - This is a navigation link in the navbar that directs the user to the system tutorial or manual.
- F. Dashboard - This is a navigation link to the historical data analysis of landslides.
- G. Training Result - This is a navigation link that displays the visual presentation of the training result and performance of the machine learning model used which is the random forest model.
- H. Weather and Soil Moisture Data - This is a footer credit which links to the source of meteorological data that includes rainfall and soil moisture.
- I. DEM Data - This is a footer credit which links the source of the slope data.
- J. Soil Data - This is a footer credit which links the source of the soil variable data.
- K. Landslide Data - This is a footer credit which links to the source of the historical landslide occurrences.

2. Dynamic Map Interface

As seen in Screenshot 2, the dynamic map is the main feature of the system for visualizing the geographical data and selecting the specific areas to forecast landslides. This

also includes the integration of interactive map of the Philippines which allows the user to view and explore various characteristics of each location through clicking or searching. This also has a sidebar that includes a search bar for location search. Below this, are the interfaces date, time, and time duration selection. This interface serves as the platform for generating prediction by linking the data fetched from the map location to the random forest model.

Screenshot 2. Dynamic Map Interface.

A. Zoom in and Zoom out Button - This control is located at the top left of the map allowing the user to adjust the visual scale of the map view.

B. Location Search - This is an input field where users search for specific locations limited only to places in the Philippines. After searching it pinpoints the exact location on the map.

- C. Location Information Display - This is a panel that displays the exact coordinates of the location currently selected at the map.
- D. Clickable Map of the Philippines - The main interactive visual area where users click at any specific point of the map to drop a pin that pinpoints the location.
3. Forecast Setting

As shown in Screenshot 3, it allows users to define the specific temporal parameters for landslide forecasting. This provides input fields to select for specific date, time, and time period. The time period indicates the duration that the forecasting takes place, for instance, a 24 hrs window from the chosen date and time. Once all the parameters have been set, the “Predict Landslide Risk” button initiates the model to process the data and generate a result.

Screenshot 3. Forecast Settings.

- A. Select Date - A calendar input field for choosing a specific date to forecast.
 - B. Select Time - A clock input field for choosing specific starting time to forecasts.
 - C. Time Period Selection - A dropdown menu to choose duration range to forecasts.
 - D. Predict Landslide Risk Button - The button that triggers the system to process the selected data and generate a forecasting result.
4. Prediction Result Display

The Screenshot 4 shown below presents the immediate outcome of the forecasting directly on the map interface. A pop-up window appears at the selected location, clearly stating the prediction classification, such as whether there is a probability of landslide or none. It also displays a confidence score percentage, giving users insight into the certainty of the model output. From this window, users then choose to delve deeper into the data by clicking the button to view the full report summary.

Screenshot 4. Prediction Result Display.

- A. Prediction Result Information - A modal window showing the binary prediction such as “No Landslide” , and the model confidence percentage.
- B. View Report Summary Button - A clickable button that redirects the user to a detailed page containing comprehensive analysis of all the generated data from input to forecasting result.
5. Prediction Report Summary

This offers a comprehensive breakdown of the factors which influence landslide prediction. As shown in Screenshot 5, it organizes significant data into sections, including specific report details like coordinates and dates, alongside environmental variables such as slope, soil type, and moisture levels. The page features visual graphs for rainfall analysis, allowing users to compare cumulative rainfall against intensity over time. A navigation aid is included to help users quickly return to the top of this detailed information page.

Screenshot 5. Prediction Report Summary Interface.

A. Result Summary Display - This is the main content area which lists specific data points such as coordinates, slope degrees, soil type, soil moisture percentages.

B. Scroll up Button - This is a navigation button that quickly brings the user back to the top of the page.

6. Report Summary Analysis and PDF Generation

This section shown in Screenshot 6, visualizes cumulative rainfall and intensity based on the selected date and time. Below the charts, users manually input a description or utilize AI to automatically generate a report summary. Finally, the system allows the complete findings to be exported as a downloadable PDF for offline use and reporting.

Screenshot 6. Report Summary Analysis and PDF Generation.

A. Rainfall Graph - A bar and line charts that visualize cumulative rainfall and intensity rainfall over the selected time period.

B. Report Summary Analysis - This is a text input box where users write detailed reports or where AI generated analysis appears.

C. Generate AI Report Button - This is a button that uses AI to automatically write a summary of the findings based on the data available.

D. Reset Button - A control that clears all inputs and text, reverting the interface to the dynamic map.

E. Download PDF Button - This feature compiles all charts and findings into a PDF document for immediate download.

7. User Guide

This module acts as an instructional resource, this module assists users in effectively using the application. As shown in Screenshot 7, it features a sidebar for categorized navigation and a main display for detailed feature explanations. This layout ensures clarity for all users, making the system accessible even to those with limited technical skills.

Screenshot 7. User Guide Section.

A. User Guide Sections - This is a sidebar menu that contains clickable categories to hover for different topics and tutorials in navigating and exploring the system.

B. Display of Informations - This is the reading pane where the instructional texts are displayed along with detailed explanation on technical topics.

8. Historical Landslide Dashboard

This section offers a visual analytics platform for analyzing historical landslide occurrences across the Philippines, as seen in Screenshot 8. It employs bar graphs to break down data by year, month, and region, alongside an interactive map that plots events color-coded by recency. Additionally, users filter the dataset via a region dropdown to focus their analysis on specific locations.

Screenshot 8. Historical Landslides Dashboard Interface.

- A. Choose Region Dropdown - This field allows users to filter the overall view to specific regions displaying specific landslide occurrences on the map from that region only.
- B. History of Landslides in Yearly Format - This is a bar chart displaying the aggregate count of landslides for each year.
- C. History of Landslides in Monthly Format - This is a bar chart showing seasonal trends by counting landslides per month.
- D. Lists of Regions with most Landslides Occurrences - A horizontal bar chart ranking regions from highest to lowest landslide occurrences.
- E. Legend of Landslides Recency - A small panel explaining the color coding of map dots based on the year the landslide occurred.
- F. Zoom Button - Controls for changing the magnification level of the historical map either to zoom in or zoom out.
- G. Map of the Philippines that Contains Landslide Occurrences - This is a geospatial view with dots representing individual recorded landslide events, along with the date it occurred.

9. Training Result

The page shown in Screenshot 9 offers full transparency into the performance and reliability of the machine learning model used in this system. It highlights key performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, and F1-score to allow for a quick assessment of model quality. The interface details the model behavior through visual graphs like learning curves

and confusion matrix, as well as a tabular classification report. Furthermore, a feature importance chart ranks which environmental variables most significantly influence the prediction outcomes.

Screenshot 9. Training Results Interface.

A. Performance Metrics in numeric format - These are colored cards displaying the high-level scores for Accuracy, Average Precision, and F1-Score.

B. Learning Curve and Confusion Matrix - These graphs illustrate visually how the model improved over time and how it categorized true/false positives and negatives.

C. Classification Report - Table that provides a detailed report of the model performance.

D. Feature Importance - A bar chart that ranks input variables by how they contribute to forecasting accuracy.

To successfully conclude the landslide forecasting workflow, users reach the Report Summary Analysis and PDF Generation interface. At the end of the activity, the assessment is finalized using either the Generate AI Report feature or manual report input to summarize the results. For official documentation and offline distribution to relevant agencies, users are able to utilize the Download PDF button to export the comprehensive charts and analysis. Lastly, users click the Reset button to end the session or start a new forecast for a different location. This clears all current inputs and returns the interface to the Dynamic Map.

APPENDIX A

Mutual Agreement Form for Co-Authorship.
(Adopted from Philippine Association of Institutions for Research (PAIR), Inc.)

WE, the researcher, and research adviser/consultant, have worked together in a thesis project from January 2024 to August 2025.

WE have used various forms of contact during the thesis work such as Microsoft Teams, Facebook and other means of communication.

WE agree that :

- The academic partnership leads to publication of the manuscript with the research consultant as the author and the researcher, the primary author.
- the paper be presented in a public forum by the researcher if available at such an opportunity or by the research adviser/consultant if the researcher is no longer around.
- only the name of the oral presenter shall be submitted to the Conference organizer.

WE agree to dress formally and prepare adequately for the formal oral presentation in both the oral defense panel and the public presentations.

Signed this 27th of July in the year of our Lord 2025 in Bacolod City, Philippines.

ERIK A. AGABON
Researcher

ELMER T. HARO, Ph.D.
Technical Consultant / Adviser

DANIEL JUN S. LAMATON
Researcher

CHRISTIAN L. DE LA TORRE
Witness

RANMIE G. MONTECALVO
Researcher

APPENDIX B

Concept Paper.

Research Concept Title	Landslide Risk Prediction System for Mountain Communities in Negros Using LSTM		
Concept Author and Collaborator(s)	Erik Agabon	Daniel Jun Lamaton	Ranmie Montecalvo
	Main Author	Collaborator #1	Collaborator #2
Rationale of the Research Concept			
<p>The research aims to develop an RNN-based system, specifically the LSTM model, for predicting landslides in mountainous areas in Negros. The system will use real-time weather and environmental data, improving preparedness and reducing disaster-related casualties. It helps rural communities by issuing warnings, especially during the rainy season, thus reducing risks posed by natural hazards, aligning with UN SDGs for climate resilience and sustainable cities.</p>			
Main Features and Functionalities			

Analyze using LSTM-based Time Series - This model will analyze sequential environmental data such as rainfall, soil moisture levels, and terrain slopes over time to predict when a landslide might occur. By identifying patterns that precede landslides, the LSTM can provide reliable forecasts.

Real-Time Data Processing - The system will use live data streams from weather APIs, such as rainfall data from PAGASA and soil moisture levels from NASA SMAP. It will integrate with cloud-based systems to process the data in real time, delivering immediate predictions.

Automated Early Warning System - The model's output will trigger automated alerts via SMS or mobile apps to notify local communities of potential landslide risks. This will provide enough lead time for evacuation or preventive measures.

Model(s) to Use

LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) of RNN

LSTM is a special type of RNN designed to handle time series data, which is crucial for this project as the system needs to predict landslide risks based on past environmental conditions.

Dataset Source

PAGASA - This will provide localized weather data, such as rainfall levels, which are critical for identifying landslide triggers.

NASA SMAP - SMAP will offer soil moisture data, helping the model track saturation levels in the soil.

USGS - Terrain and slope maps are vital for determining landslide-prone areas.

PHIVOLCS - Historical records of landslides will be used to train and validate the model.
Project Usability / Benefit Justification
<p>Early Warning for Early Preparations - deliver early warnings that can save lives and reduce property damage in vulnerable mountain communities. Local governments and residents will be better prepared for landslides, with real-time alerts giving them ample time to evacuate or implement safety measures.</p> <p>Scalability - this system can be adapted to other regions in the Philippines or other countries facing similar landslide risks due to deforestation, climate change, or other environmental factors.</p>
Relevance to the Theme
<p>SDG 13 (Climate Action) - By predicting landslide risks, the system directly addresses climate-related disasters, allowing for proactive disaster management.</p> <p>SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) - The project promotes safer, more resilient communities in disaster-prone mountainous areas, aligning with the goal of creating sustainable and safe living environments.</p>
Technology Deployment
<p>Platform - The model will be hosted on cloud-based platforms like AWS, Google Cloud, or Microsoft Azure to enable real-time data processing and scalability.</p> <p>Software - Machine learning frameworks like TensorFlow or PyTorch will be used for model training and deployment. These will integrate with APIs for real-time data acquisition from external sources such as OpenWeather or PAGASA.</p>

Hardware - The system can be enhanced with IoT devices (e.g., soil moisture sensors) for on-the-ground data collection, but these are optional. The real-time data can also come solely from public APIs if on-site sensors are not feasible.

Anticipated Challenges

Data Availability - In some remote areas, real-time data may be difficult to collect. This challenge can be mitigated by using satellite data or predictive models to fill gaps.

Community Engagement - Ensuring that local communities trust and respond to the system's alerts will be critical to its success. This may require educational initiatives alongside technical development.

Infrastructure Limitations - In rural areas with poor internet connectivity, delivering real-time alerts may be a challenge. The system will need to include offline functionality, such as SMS-based alerts that can be transmitted via low-bandwidth networks.

References

Huang, Yan, et al. "Landslide susceptibility mapping based on self-adaptive LSTM neural network and GIS." *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 5, 2020, pp. 1786-1803. DOI: 10.3390/su12051786.

Pham, Binh Thai, et al. "A novel hybrid approach of landslide susceptibility modelling using deep learning and swarm intelligence." *Geomorphology*, vol. 362, 2020, pp. 107221. DOI: 10.1016/j.geomorph.2020.107221.

Kamp, Ulrich, et al. "Landslide susceptibility mapping in the Himalayas of Nepal using random forest and logistic regression." *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, vol. 18, no. 5, 2018, pp. 929-956. DOI: 10.5194/nhess-18-929-2018.

Sameen, Muhammad Iqbal, and Muhammad Pradhan. "Landslide susceptibility assessment using convolutional neural networks, residual networks, and long short-term memory networks." *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 765, 2021, pp. 142320. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142320.

APPENDIX C

PERT Table.

Activity	Description	Predecessor	a	m	b	ET	ES	EF	LS	LF	Slack
A	Title Proposal System Planning	None	7	8	9	8	0	8	0	8	0
B	Identify Sytem Requirements and Functionalities	A	1	1	2	1	8	9	8	9	0
C	Literature Review	B	2	3	3	3	9	12	14	17	5
D	Data Gathering and Preprocessing	B	7	8	9	8	9	17	9	17	0
E	Training, Valldating, and Testing the Model	C,D	5	6	7	6	17	23	17	23	0
F	Data Analysis	E	2	3	4	3	23	26	32	35	9
G	Application Development and Testing	E	11	12	13	12	23	35	23	35	0
H	Documentation	F,G	4	5	6	5	35	40	35	40	0

APPENDIX D

PERT Diagram.

APPENDIX E

System Budget.

Components	Brief Description Model	Cost
Acer Aspire 3	AMD Ryzen 5 7520U; 4 Cores 8 Threads; 8 GB RAM; 512 GB SSD	₱ 35, 000.00
Domain Name	GoDaddy Domain 1 year Duration (twostepsahead.site)	₱ 77.00
Mapbox API	Mapbox GLS, Map loads for web; Search Box API - Session	₱ 294.58 for over 1000 request/load ₱ 677.52 for over 1000 request/load
Google Cloud Run	CPU - First 180,000 vCPU-seconds free per month; RAM - First 360,000 GB-seconds free per month; Requests - 2 million requests free per month	₱ 3,317.76 for 2,073,600 seconds ₱ 0.00017.00 for 2,073,600 seconds ₱ 352.51 for over 2,000,000 request
Miscellaneous Expenses	Internet, subscriptions, backups, other incidental operations needs	₱ 5,000.00
Total Costs		₱ 44,719.37

APPENDIX F

Minutes of the Thesis Project Proposal Defense.

December 19, 2024 | 8:30 AM – 10:00 AM

College of Information Technology

University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos

Thesis Proposal Title	Random Forest In Forecasting Rain-Induced Landslides In The Philippines
Group Members	Erik A Agabon Daniel Jun S. Lamaton Ranmie G. Montecalvo
Panel Members	Reymund L. Sabay, MBE Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D. Mehreen E. Dolendo, MSCS
Interpolators	Karen Kaye T. Alfonso Shane Michael D. Magallanes Josef Komanchi D. Javier

1. The conference started with a prayer led by Erik A. Agabon.
2. The group members were introduced by Erik A. Agabon.
3. The oral presentation was delivered by Erik A. Agabon.
4. After the presentation, the following are the suggestions and recommendations of the interpellators and the panel members:

Chapter/Selection	Recommendation/Suggestions	Proponent	Actions Taken
-------------------	----------------------------	-----------	---------------

Statement of the Problem	Add a time element for the variables	Mehreen E. Dolendo Reymund L. Sabay	The researches added time elements in the cumulative and rainfall variables
Statement of the Problem	Clarify the variables used	Mehreen E. Dolendo	Revised the structure of the SOP to further define the variables
Statement of the Problem	Revise the structure of the problem statement	Mehreen E. Dolendo Elmer T. Haro	Further revision added to the structure of the SOP
Review of Related Literature	Include or define the thresholds	Mehreen E. Dolendo Elmer T. Haro	The researchers gathered landslide datasets from the NDRRMC
Review of Related Literature	Add references to the stated functionality	Elmer T. Haro	The researchers added more references to the various functionalities of the random forest model
Review of Related Literature	Include Project NOAH in the references	Reymund L. Sabay	The researchers included references to project NOAH
Dataset	Find and include more datasets from national government agencies	Mehreen E. Dolendo Reymund L. Sabay	The researchers gathered landslide datasets
Dataset	Include a time element for the datasets in the landslide	Mehreen E. Dolendo Reymund L. Sabay	The researchers identified landslide datasets that included only the time of occurrence
Dataset	Clarify clearly what is inside the dataset	Mehreen E. Dolendo Reymund L. Sabay	Added more descriptions in the dataset

5. After the deliberation of the interpellators and panel members, the proposal is

- considered accepted with revisions in the documentation and in the prototype.
- The conference ended at 10:00 AM.

Transcribed by: Daniel Jun S. Lamaton

Noted by: Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D.

APPENDIX G

Minutes of the Thesis Final Defense.

May 30, 2025 | 10:30 AM – 12:00 PM

College of Information Technology

University of Negros Occidental – Recoletos

Thesis Proposal Title	Random Forest In Forecasting Rain-Induced Landslides In The Philippines
Group Members	Erik A. Agabon Daniel Jun S. Lamaton Ranmie G. Montecalvo
Panel Members	Joshua E. Dela Cruz, MIT Candidate Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D. Mehreen E. Dolendo, MSCS
Interpolators	Karen Kaye T. Alfonso Shane Michael D. Magallanes Josef Komanchi D. Javier

- The conference started with a prayer led by Erik A. Agabon.
- The group members were introduced by Erik A. Agabon.
- The oral presentation was delivered by Erik A. Agabon.
- After the presentation, the following are the suggestions and recommendations of the interpellators and the panel members:

Chapter/Selection	Recommendation/Suggestions	Proponent	Actions Taken
Application	Enumerate the rainfall variables so that the user can see the data properly	Josef Komanchi D. Javier Joshua E. Dela Cruz,	The researchers enumerated the rainfall variables that were present leading up to the landslide after the user has made a prediction
Application	Address naming inconsistencies	Karen Kaye T. Alfonso Mehreen E. Dolendo	Changed the name of the dashboard from Landslide forecasting dashboard to historical landslide dashboard
Application	Provide the user with additional details with how the researchers categorized high, medium, low risks in the dashboard map	Joshua E. Dela Cruz, Mehreen E. Dolendo	Instead of a risk categorization, the researchers emphasised it to just be a landslide historical dashboard map instead
Application	Provide the user with a graphical timeline UI of the rainfall variables leading to prediction	Mehreen E. Dolendo Joshua E. Dela Cruz	The users utilized chart.js in order to better show graphically the rainfall data prediction
Application	Add hourly data if possible	Mehreen E. Dolendo Joshua E. Dela Cruz	The researchers integrated hourly data into the model through
Application	Allow the users to create a detailed report for the users to download	Mehreen E. Dolendo	The researchers made it possible for the user to download the detailed report made and allow them to make comments or allow AI to give them a template and download it as pdf for printing

5. After the deliberation of the interpellators and panel members, the proposal is considered accepted with revisions on the prototype.
6. The conference ended at 12:00 AM

Transcribed by: Daniel Jun S. Lamaton

Noted by: Elmer T. Haro, Ph.D.

APPENDIX H

Landslide Dataset.

LEGEND	
A = cumulative_rainfall_3hr	G = rainfall_intensity_3hr
C = cumulative_rainfall_12hr	I = rainfall_intensity_12hr
E = cumulative_rainfall_3d	K = rainfall_intensity_3d
M = soil_moisture	N = slope
B = cumulative_rainfall_6hr	H = rainfall_intensity_6hr
D = cumulative_rainfall_1d	J = rainfall_intensity_1d
F = cumulative_rainfall_5d	L = rainfall_intensity_5d
O = soil_type	P = target_classification

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P
0.4331	1.2048	5.4764	7.8268	8.8465	9.1378	0.1444	0.2008	0.4564	0.3262	0.1229	0.0762	0.3731	2	4	1
0.7126	1.0079	1.0197	1.0355	2.1457	2.2008	0.2376	0.168	0.085	0.0432	0.0299	0.0184	0	5	1	1
0.3189	0.6536	1.5945	1.8386	7.2441	8.3544	0.1063	0.109	0.1329	0.0767	0.1007	0.0697	0	1	1	1
0.0079	0.2363	1.2166	2.0867	6.7048	7.6418	0.0027	0.0394	0.1014	0.087	0.0932	0.0637	0.489	4	1	1
0.9134	1.4213	3.4607	5.1615	7.2953	7.8308	0.3045	0.2369	0.2884	0.2151	0.1014	0.0653	0.3603	4	4	1
0.2126	0.6063	0.6772	0.8898	4.3662	5.4213	0.0709	0.1011	0.0565	0.0371	0.0607	0.0272	0.494	4	3	1
0.2756	0.7796	0.8977	1.0512	4.7717	5.7008	0.0919	0.13	0.0749	0.0438	0.0663	0.0476	0.3886	2	3	1
0.8426	1.0591	3.0237	7.1851	9.6772	9.9489	0.2809	0.1766	0.252	0.2994	0.1345	0.083	0.2521	5	4	1
0.0788	0.3504	0.9646	3.7914	6.7599	7.9016	0.0263	0.0584	0.0804	0.158	0.0939	0.0659	0.5136	6	1	1
0.0985	0.1615	0.6221	3.689	9.1063	9.8032	0.0329	0.027	0.0519	0.1538	0.1265	0.0817	0.2454	4	4	1
0.0158	0.063	0.1654	1.1182	5.0552	6.0394	0.0053	0.0105	0.0138	0.0466	0.0703	0.0504	0.5176	4	3	1
0.063	0.2481	1.0197	7.1457	13.2323	14.1654	0.021	0.0414	0.085	0.2978	0.1838	0.1181	0.4609	4	3	1
0.126	0.1772	0.2796	1.1693	2.9567	4.256	0.042	0.0296	0.0233	0.0488	0.0411	0.0355	0.472	5	3	1
0.0197	0.0197	0.0197	0.067	2.8308	3.0355	0.0066	0.0033	0.0017	0.0028	0.0394	0.0253	0.5161	1	3	1
0	0.1221	2.3308	6.7717	6.815	6.9804	0	0.0204	0.1943	0.2822	0.0947	0.0582	0.336	6	3	1
0.315	1.9882	6.6812	7.4528	7.6772	8.0749	0.105	0.3314	0.5568	0.3106	0.1067	0.0673	0.414	6	4	1
0.1339	0.9292	6.7284	8.7363	8.8347	9.126	0.0447	0.1549	0.5607	0.3641	0.1228	0.0761	0.5033	5	3	1
0.063	0.0945	0.1024	0.1063	2.0749	3.2875	0.021	0.0158	0.0086	0.0045	0.0289	0.0274	0.426	6	4	1
0.0315	0.3859	3.3583	4.4292	4.5749	5.9213	0.0105	0.0644	0.2799	0.1846	0.0636	0.0494	0.5117	6	3	1
0.0237	0.0276	0.0394	0.1339	0.4804	0.63	0.0079	0.0046	0.0033	0.0056	0.0067	0.0053	0.4766	4	1	1
0.0119	0.0512	0.0985	0.1969	0.6851	0.7284	0.004	0.0086	0.0083	0.0083	0.0096	0.0061	0.382	4	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.0473	0.0473	0	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0	5	1	1
0.0591	0.1851	0.6575	1.1418	3.067	3.7008	0.0197	0.0309	0.0548	0.0476	0.0426	0.0309	0.508	1	3	1

0.0473	0.0827	0.126	0.4528	1.2638	1.9489	0.0158	0.0138	0.0105	0.0189	0.0176	0.0163	0.5126	1	3	1
0.0394	0.0788	0.1339	0.3071	1.0867	1.6221	0.0132	0.0132	0.0112	0.0128	0.0151	0.0136	0.5132	5	3	1
0.315	0.6536	1.7402	3.2756	3.8189	4.878	0.105	0.109	0.1451	0.1365	0.0531	0.0407	0.5146	5	3	1
0	0	0.3386	0.3544	1.756	2.2087	0	0	0.0283	0.0148	0.0244	0.0185	0.3618	1	1	1
0	0.0079	0.0158	0.0158	0.689	0.9095	0	0.0014	0.0014	0.0007	0.0096	0.0076	0.393	6	3	1
0.004	0.0158	0.0591	0.3701	4.878	7.0709	0.0014	0.0027	0.005	0.0155	0.0678	0.059	0.4155	5	1	1
0	0.0079	0.1772	0.2048	1.3032	1.6733	0	0.0014	0.0148	0.0086	0.0181	0.014	0.469	4	3	1
0.004	0.1024	0.2087	0.2205	1.2835	1.563	0.0014	0.0171	0.0174	0.0092	0.0179	0.0131	0.341	5	4	1
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0512	0.3662	0.5158	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0022	0.0051	0.0043	0.321	4	3	1
0.3819	0.5158	0.8819	2.3268	7.193	15.4056	0.1273	0.086	0.0735	0.097	0.1	0.1284	0.43	4	3	1
0.1497	0.2205	0.3859	0.5473	3.7284	5.5276	0.0499	0.0368	0.0322	0.0229	0.0518	0.0461	0.514	3	1	1
0.0788	0.63	0.6654	0.6851	2.4292	3.1378	0.0263	0.105	0.0555	0.0286	0.0338	0.0262	0.4548	5	3	1
0.0276	0.1024	0.2008	0.9961	3.3741	3.6339	0.0092	0.0171	0.0168	0.0416	0.0469	0.0303	0.5153	5	3	1
0.0749	0.2048	0.2953	0.7638	1.6575	2.5906	0.025	0.0342	0.0247	0.0319	0.0231	0.0216	0.5083	6	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.1142	0.3583	0	0	0	0	0.0016	0.003	0.487	6	3	1
0	0	0.1103	1.5709	3.563	4.6024	0	0	0.0092	0.0655	0.0495	0.0384	0.5169	6	3	1
0.0158	0.0512	0.2875	0.3898	2.8071	4.5315	0.0053	0.0086	0.024	0.0163	0.039	0.0378	0.5168	6	3	1
0.1378	0.1497	0.1812	0.3859	2.9725	4.7245	0.046	0.025	0.0151	0.0161	0.0413	0.0394	0.517	6	3	1
0.0276	0.0355	0.2363	0.3544	3.0158	4.5788	0.0092	0.006	0.0197	0.0148	0.0419	0.0382	0.5172	5	3	1
0.0394	0.1536	0.5	0.7914	2.878	4.5079	0.0132	0.0256	0.0417	0.033	0.04	0.0376	0.517	6	3	1
0	0	0.0906	0.6024	2.9134	3.9331	0	0	0.0076	0.0251	0.0405	0.0328	0.4169	4	3	1
0	0	0.0906	0.8583	3.2205	5.3071	0	0	0.0076	0.0358	0.0448	0.0443	0.423	4	3	1
0.0119	0.0906	0.13	0.3426	2.9213	4.6142	0.004	0.0151	0.0109	0.0143	0.0406	0.0385	0.4121	1	3	1
0	0	0.0394	0.1339	1.7245	2.7402	0	0	0.0033	0.0056	0.024	0.0229	0.4131	6	4	1
0.004	0.0119	0.0237	0.0552	0.7993	1.4056	0.0014	0.002	0.002	0.0023	0.0112	0.0118	0	4	1	1
0.2678	0.5945	2.2756	3.5394	4.4371	4.4646	0.0893	0.0991	0.1897	0.1475	0.0617	0.0373	0.4596	4	3	1
0.0591	0.1024	1.1221	3.6497	4.6221	4.878	0.0197	0.0171	0.0936	0.1521	0.0642	0.0407	0.3854	5	3	1
0.0197	0.5079	1.5709	2.4252	2.6339	2.6851	0.0066	0.0847	0.131	0.1011	0.0366	0.0224	0.335	1	3	1
0.0237	0.2087	0.7756	2.4686	3.4174	3.6103	0.0079	0.0348	0.0647	0.1029	0.0475	0.0301	0.5031	4	4	1
0.3859	0.7284	1.1772	1.6536	2.1418	2.2875	0.1287	0.1214	0.0981	0.0689	0.0298	0.0191	0.36	4	4	1
0.3386	0.815	1.5119	1.9764	2.6693	2.8032	0.1129	0.1359	0.126	0.0824	0.0371	0.0234	0.392	4	4	1
0.0788	0.256	0.9607	2.1772	2.7441	2.941	0.0263	0.0427	0.0801	0.0908	0.0382	0.0246	0.3602	4	4	1
0.0079	0.0119	0.3819	1.752	2.7008	2.8544	0.0027	0.002	0.0319	0.073	0.0376	0.0238	0.4833	4	4	1
0.0788	0.1812	0.5237	0.7914	3.0315	3.4961	0.0263	0.0302	0.0437	0.033	0.0422	0.0292	0.3684	4	4	1
0.004	0.0276	0.0945	0.2087	1.9016	2.4725	0.0014	0.0046	0.0079	0.0087	0.0265	0.0207	0.331	4	4	1
0	0	0.0079	0.1221	0.5079	2.0394	0	0	0.0007	0.0051	0.0071	0.017	0.355	3	3	1
0	0	0.1103	0.6615	2.6969	5.7756	0	0	0.0092	0.0276	0.0375	0.0482	0.4167	6	3	1
0	0.0158	0.3111	0.8583	4.4095	7.0315	0	0.0027	0.026	0.0358	0.0613	0.0586	0.5158	6	3	1
0	0	0.0473	0.8347	2.2087	6.2953	0	0	0.004	0.0348	0.0307	0.0525	0.4652	6	3	1
0.004	0.0473	0.4922	0.9804	4.6812	6.2953	0.0014	0.0079	0.0411	0.0409	0.0651	0.0525	0.4645	6	3	1
0.13	0.2875	0.9489	4.8544	7.7796	8.4016	0.0434	0.048	0.0791	0.2023	0.1081	0.0701	0.3851	6	3	1
0.1497	0.5749	1.5512	2.8623	10.0119	12.5985	0.0499	0.0959	0.1293	0.1193	0.1391	0.105	0.4001	6	4	1
0.0512	0.2008	1.2993	2.5749	9.5591	12.6497	0.0171	0.0335	0.1083	0.1073	0.1328	0.1055	0.4011	6	3	1
0.0276	0.0945	0.7875	1.8662	2.4056	2.5276	0.0092	0.0158	0.0657	0.0778	0.0335	0.0211	0.4713	4	3	1
0.0276	0.0945	0.7875	1.8662	2.4056	2.5276	0.0092	0.0158	0.0657	0.0778	0.0335	0.0211	0.4713	4	3	1
0.1024	0.4213	1.3111	2.252	2.7284	2.8662	0.0342	0.0703	0.1093	0.0939	0.0379	0.0239	0.4636	5	3	1
0.0867	0.1063	0.1457	0.193	0.3071	0.3426	0.0289	0.0178	0.0122	0.0081	0.0043	0.0029	0.344	5	3	1
0.004	0.0079	0.2402	1.4922	2.1457	2.3189	0.0014	0.0014	0.0201	0.0622	0.0299	0.0194	0.4713	4	3	1

0.0276	0.0749	0.9489	1.7638	2.3111	2.4489	0.0092	0.0125	0.0791	0.0735	0.0321	0.0205	0.436	4	4	1
0.2481	0.3426	0.6339	0.6378	0.7756	1.3189	0.0827	0.0571	0.0529	0.0266	0.0108	0.011	0.483	4	4	1
0.2756	0.4134	0.9252	1.4292	4.8859	5.0237	0.0919	0.0689	0.0771	0.0596	0.0679	0.0419	0.4911	4	3	1
0.3268	0.815	2.0512	3.3898	11.1221	11.8701	0.109	0.1359	0.171	0.1413	0.1545	0.099	0.4275	6	4	1
0.1024	0.2875	0.4607	0.4804	0.5906	0.9449	0.0342	0.048	0.0384	0.0201	0.0083	0.0079	0.345	5	3	1
0.0985	0.3662	0.7717	1.6654	5.8111	5.9016	0.0329	0.0611	0.0644	0.0694	0.0808	0.0492	0.3468	5	3	1
0.004	0.0158	0.0276	0.0276	0.7087	2.1063	0.0014	0.0027	0.0023	0.0012	0.0099	0.0176	0.494	5	3	1
0.2481	0.4371	1.0867	2.2953	6.6378	6.9725	0.0827	0.0729	0.0906	0.0957	0.0922	0.0582	0.5175	6	4	1
0.2008	0.626	1.1693	1.6221	5.2835	5.3229	0.067	0.1044	0.0975	0.0676	0.0734	0.0444	0.3429	6	3	1
0.6497	1.2363	1.7441	2.5473	5.8583	5.8938	0.2166	0.2061	0.1454	0.1062	0.0814	0.0492	0.4224	6	4	1
0.2205	0.4095	0.7323	1.0591	4.2087	4.2717	0.0735	0.0683	0.0611	0.0442	0.0582	0.0356	0.4488	4	3	1
0.3347	0.3701	0.8741	1.2008	4.3347	4.7087	0.1116	0.0617	0.0729	0.0501	0.0603	0.0393	0.4073	6	3	1
0	0.0473	0.2756	0.2953	4.6457	8	0	0.0079	0.023	0.0124	0.0646	0.0667	0.429	6	4	1
0.0434	0.0512	0.0591	0.2048	1.7875	4.1575	0.0145	0.0086	0.005	0.0086	0.0249	0.0347	0.339	4	4	1
0.1457	0.8623	1.6182	2.7166	5.9922	6.0985	0.0486	0.1438	0.1349	0.1132	0.0833	0.0509	0.5113	5	3	1
0.3504	0.4961	1.7481	2.9095	6.3308	6.4489	0.1168	0.0827	0.1457	0.1213	0.088	0.0538	0.5132	5	3	1
1.2914	2.6457	4.4843	6.9016	7.5945	9.0906	0.4305	0.441	0.3737	0.2876	0.1055	0.0758	0.5093	4	3	1
0.0906	0.3504	2.7205	6.2245	8.2363	9.689	0.0302	0.0584	0.2268	0.2594	0.1144	0.0808	0.513	4	3	1
0.7048	1.3898	2.3111	2.5512	3.0945	4.63	0.235	0.2317	0.1926	0.1063	0.043	0.0386	0.5074	4	3	1
0.4331	1.0906	2.3583	4.0827	12.9725	13.5788	0.1444	0.1818	0.1966	0.1702	0.1802	0.1132	0.519	4	3	1
0.1457	0.4882	1.1654	1.5749	4.6024	4.7166	0.0486	0.0814	0.0972	0.0657	0.064	0.0394	0.5184	5	3	1
1.0945	1.1182	1.2008	1.6103	3.4961	3.6024	0.3649	0.1864	0.1001	0.0671	0.0486	0.0301	0.3652	5	3	1
0.5788	0.6654	1.2835	2.0512	5.2402	5.3583	0.193	0.1109	0.107	0.0855	0.0728	0.0447	0.5183	5	3	1
0.0315	0.1969	0.5552	1.378	2.9174	3.3544	0.0105	0.0329	0.0463	0.0575	0.0406	0.028	0.4153	4	3	1
0.4252	0.5119	1.563	2.1339	4.6063	5.0394	0.1418	0.0854	0.1303	0.089	0.064	0.042	0.4202	4	3	1
0.4725	1.3662	1.5	1.7835	3.6339	3.6615	0.1575	0.2277	0.125	0.0744	0.0505	0.0306	0.272	5	3	1
0.0434	0.0985	0.256	0.8465	2.5473	2.6339	0.0145	0.0165	0.0214	0.0353	0.0354	0.022	0.235	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0158	0.0315	0.8623	0.9528	1.0119	0.004	0.0027	0.0027	0.036	0.0133	0.0085	0.238	5	3	1
0.0473	0.1142	0.2953	0.9489	3.063	3.2993	0.0158	0.0191	0.0247	0.0396	0.0426	0.0275	0.3365	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.6772	1.7205	2.3662	0	0	0	0.0283	0.0239	0.0198	0.374	5	1	1
0.2008	0.4252	0.8189	1.6457	5.1182	5.4646	0.067	0.0709	0.0683	0.0686	0.0711	0.0456	0.4081	4	4	1
0.189	0.2796	0.4174	0.4489	0.6497	1.9764	0.063	0.0466	0.0348	0.0188	0.0091	0.0165	0.3765	3	3	1
0.067	0.2166	0.5276	1.3898	6.1615	7.0591	0.0224	0.0361	0.044	0.058	0.0856	0.0589	0.517	4	3	1
0.0315	0.0788	0.2796	0.7875	4.4646	5.9804	0.0105	0.0132	0.0233	0.0329	0.0621	0.0499	0.416	4	3	1
0.0276	0.0552	0.063	0.189	2.4528	5.378	0.0092	0.0092	0.0053	0.0079	0.0341	0.0449	0.517	3	3	1
0.0394	0.0906	0.0985	0.1457	2.5473	5.2993	0.0132	0.0151	0.0083	0.0061	0.0354	0.0442	0.3955	3	3	1
0.0867	0.13	0.4607	0.8268	1.5552	3.2678	0.0289	0.0217	0.0384	0.0345	0.0216	0.0273	0.395	4	3	1
0.0355	0.0591	0.0867	0.4174	1.1969	2.756	0.0119	0.0099	0.0073	0.0174	0.0167	0.023	0.3956	4	4	1
0.0394	0.1103	1.1693	3.9331	4.4371	4.7914	0.0132	0.0184	0.0975	0.1639	0.0617	0.04	0.4064	4	2	1
0.0512	0.1812	0.2008	0.6812	1.4764	2.8111	0.0171	0.0302	0.0168	0.0284	0.0206	0.0235	0.4045	4	2	1
0	0.0119	0.0434	0.1693	0.7756	1.4134	0	0.002	0.0037	0.0071	0.0108	0.0118	0.394	4	3	1
0	0	0.1182	0.3268	0.9567	2.1654	0	0	0.0099	0.0137	0.0133	0.0181	0.504	6	4	1
0.0788	0.1418	0.6378	1.1772	1.5591	1.8465	0.0263	0.0237	0.0532	0.0491	0.0217	0.0154	0.4745	6	3	1
0.063	0.1142	0.2638	0.5473	1.3583	1.4449	0.021	0.0191	0.022	0.0229	0.0189	0.0121	0.463	6	3	1
0.0197	0.1851	1.3662	2.9252	3.1733	3.2835	0.0066	0.0309	0.1139	0.1219	0.0441	0.0274	0.338	1	3	1
0.1103	0.2756	0.8386	1.3898	2.9213	3.6418	0.0368	0.046	0.0699	0.058	0.0406	0.0304	0.4724	5	1	1
0.0827	0.2599	0.63	1.5985	3.1024	3.815	0.0276	0.0434	0.0525	0.0667	0.0431	0.0318	0.3665	4	1	1
0.1063	0.2245	0.7678	1.3977	2.9607	3.7245	0.0355	0.0375	0.064	0.0583	0.0412	0.0311	0.4734	5	1	1

0.1654	0.3229	0.6615	1.4764	3.2599	4.2048	0.0552	0.0539	0.0552	0.0616	0.0453	0.0351	0.405	3	3	1
0.067	0.2245	1.2678	3.0158	7.0197	9.0985	0.0224	0.0375	0.1057	0.1257	0.0975	0.0759	0.4907	4	3	1
0.1497	0.3032	0.3268	0.5315	1.878	2.2048	0.0499	0.0506	0.0273	0.0222	0.0261	0.0184	0.407	4	3	1
0.1024	0.3386	0.4922	0.7166	1.6497	2.0788	0.0342	0.0565	0.0411	0.0299	0.023	0.0174	0.404	4	3	1
0.0355	0.2363	0.4764	1.2953	2.0315	2.2717	0.0119	0.0394	0.0397	0.054	0.0283	0.019	0.393	4	3	1
0.0355	0.2363	0.4764	1.2953	2.0315	2.2717	0.0119	0.0394	0.0397	0.054	0.0283	0.019	0.393	5	3	1
0.0276	0.0906	0.441	1.2008	1.9371	2.2441	0.0092	0.0151	0.0368	0.0501	0.027	0.0188	0.393	4	3	1
0.0355	0.2363	0.4764	1.2953	2.0315	2.2717	0.0119	0.0394	0.0397	0.054	0.0283	0.019	0.393	4	3	1
0.0158	0.0394	0.8229	1.4922	2.4528	2.752	0.0053	0.0066	0.0686	0.0622	0.0341	0.023	0.4517	4	3	1
0.1142	0.2993	0.6418	1.4528	3.0315	3.8623	0.0381	0.0499	0.0535	0.0606	0.0422	0.0322	0.306	4	3	1
0.0434	0.4371	0.7481	0.9174	2.7087	3.5709	0.0145	0.0729	0.0624	0.0383	0.0377	0.0298	0.334	2	3	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.0394	1.1142	6.2008	11.8465	0.0027	0.0014	0.0033	0.0465	0.0862	0.0988	0.3792	3	3	1
0.6851	1.2245	2.1851	3.7835	8.6575	11.1536	0.2284	0.2041	0.1821	0.1577	0.1203	0.093	0.4215	4	3	1
0.0119	0.0315	0.0906	0.2323	0.4016	1.1339	0.004	0.0053	0.0076	0.0097	0.0056	0.0095	0.472	5	1	1
0.0119	0.0512	0.2599	0.6103	0.8386	1.6733	0.004	0.0086	0.0217	0.0255	0.0117	0.014	0.303	1	1	1
0	0	0	0	0.5552	2.3111	0	0	0	0	0.0078	0.0193	0.474	2	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.4174	1.3977	0	0	0	0	0.0058	0.0117	0.361	4	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.4174	1.3977	0	0	0	0	0.0058	0.0117	0.361	2	3	1
0.4095	1.0788	1.9371	2.4449	6.0591	7.6575	0.1365	0.1798	0.1615	0.1019	0.0842	0.0639	0.3061	6	4	1
0.0867	0.1457	0.2323	0.7678	3.4528	4.1812	0.0289	0.0243	0.0194	0.032	0.048	0.0349	0.5085	5	4	1
0.0749	0.0906	0.2441	0.8347	1.8741	2.5237	0.025	0.0151	0.0204	0.0348	0.0261	0.0211	0.4705	5	3	1
0.0788	0.1497	0.3229	0.756	3.2796	3.8071	0.0263	0.025	0.027	0.0315	0.0456	0.0318	0.4863	5	3	1
0	0.0276	0.0276	0.0276	0.6142	0.7323	0	0.0046	0.0023	0.0012	0.0086	0.0062	0.38	6	4	1
0	0.0197	0.5276	0.5315	2.1063	3.5552	0	0.0033	0.044	0.0222	0.0293	0.0297	0.401	3	3	1
0.0158	0.0315	0.193	0.5827	2.6772	3.4843	0.0053	0.0053	0.0161	0.0243	0.0372	0.0291	0.401	4	1	1
0.1654	0.3741	0.8662	1.504	2.7796	3.567	0.0552	0.0624	0.0722	0.0627	0.0387	0.0298	0.3759	4	1	1
0.3938	0.5906	1.3623	1.7441	2.4489	3.2126	0.1313	0.0985	0.1136	0.0727	0.0341	0.0268	0.3573	4	1	1
0.1378	0.3898	0.6063	1.1182	3.4489	4.1103	0.046	0.065	0.0506	0.0466	0.048	0.0343	0.4586	1	3	1
0.0119	0.0158	0.0276	0.067	1.4528	2.9016	0.004	0.0027	0.0023	0.0028	0.0202	0.0242	0.4742	5	3	1
0.1339	0.1575	0.2717	0.7008	0.9804	2.0827	0.0447	0.0263	0.0227	0.0292	0.0137	0.0174	0.4418	4	4	1
0.0788	0.4882	0.8111	1.8426	2.2008	2.7481	0.0263	0.0814	0.0676	0.0768	0.0306	0.023	0.3531	6	3	1
0.2835	0.4882	1.3229	3.2993	7.4174	7.8662	0.0945	0.0814	0.1103	0.1375	0.1031	0.0656	0.2714	2	4	1
0.3347	0.5709	1.3623	3.2835	7.5237	7.9725	0.1116	0.0952	0.1136	0.1369	0.1045	0.0665	0.2715	2	4	1
0.1575	0.4567	1.0473	2.4764	8.0591	8.5079	0.0525	0.0762	0.0873	0.1032	0.112	0.0709	0.2718	3	4	1
0.0237	0.067	0.2717	0.6024	4.2284	5.4567	0.0079	0.0112	0.0227	0.0251	0.0588	0.0455	0.4021	2	3	1
0.0197	0.1615	0.3347	1.067	3.3386	6.5709	0.0066	0.027	0.0279	0.0445	0.0464	0.0548	0.4013	2	3	1
0.2166	0.2796	0.5434	1.0434	1.4607	1.5906	0.0722	0.0466	0.0453	0.0435	0.0203	0.0133	0.46	5	3	1
0.0276	0.0355	0.0512	0.2678	2.4607	5.1536	0.0092	0.006	0.0043	0.0112	0.0342	0.043	0.3484	4	1	1
0.3819	0.9095	1.3819	2.3426	4.256	4.6142	0.1273	0.1516	0.1152	0.0977	0.0592	0.0385	0.347	6	3	1
0.3111	1.0355	1.6221	2.3623	4.3701	4.7914	0.1037	0.1726	0.1352	0.0985	0.0607	0.04	0.4562	6	3	1
0.0315	0.0788	0.0788	0.193	0.4213	0.6733	0.0105	0.0132	0.0066	0.0081	0.0059	0.0057	0.4762	5	3	1
0.067	0.2245	1.0394	1.7402	4.7205	5.0197	0.0224	0.0375	0.0867	0.0726	0.0656	0.0419	0.352	6	3	1
0.1812	0.3426	1.4567	2.0945	2.7166	3.3462	0.0604	0.0571	0.1214	0.0873	0.0378	0.0279	0.312	4	4	1
0.0867	0.1063	0.1063	0.2087	1.315	2.4646	0.0289	0.0178	0.0089	0.0087	0.0183	0.0206	0.3812	6	3	1
0	0.004	0.0906	0.7087	2.3859	2.8071	0	0.0007	0.0076	0.0296	0.0332	0.0234	0.489	6	3	1
0.0158	0.0158	0.0197	0.1733	0.3977	1.189	0.0053	0.0027	0.0017	0.0073	0.0056	0.01	0.4058	5	4	1
0.1024	0.2126	0.2363	0.3071	0.9764	1.4056	0.0342	0.0355	0.0197	0.0128	0.0136	0.0118	0.388	6	4	1
0.0827	0.252	0.315	0.3859	2.3859	3.2717	0.0276	0.042	0.0263	0.0161	0.0332	0.0273	0.503	6	4	1

0.0945	0.1063	0.1182	0.2048	0.4882	1.1615	0.0315	0.0178	0.0099	0.0086	0.0068	0.0097	0.4121	6	3	1
1.1969	1.756	2.0985	2.1103	3.5709	4.7402	0.399	0.2927	0.1749	0.088	0.0496	0.0396	0.395	6	3	1
0.0315	0.0906	0.8071	1.0591	1.4016	1.6221	0.0105	0.0151	0.0673	0.0442	0.0195	0.0136	0.413	5	3	1
0.3583	0.7638	1.4056	2.1418	3.6024	3.6812	0.1195	0.1273	0.1172	0.0893	0.0501	0.0307	0.403	5	3	1
0.1733	0.6418	1.13	1.5394	2.8386	2.9922	0.0578	0.107	0.0942	0.0642	0.0395	0.025	0.403	5	3	1
0.2835	0.4528	0.6418	0.8032	1.2205	1.2993	0.0945	0.0755	0.0535	0.0335	0.017	0.0109	0.4811	3	1	1
0.5079	0.9174	1.756	5.1772	8.5079	8.9016	0.1693	0.1529	0.1464	0.2158	0.1182	0.0742	0	5	3	1
0.504	0.8662	1.5276	2.693	4.63	5.2245	0.168	0.1444	0.1273	0.1123	0.0644	0.0436	0.4226	4	3	1
0.2284	0.3898	0.8268	1.1221	2.2126	2.9134	0.0762	0.065	0.0689	0.0468	0.0308	0.0243	0.5035	4	3	1
0	0.0315	0.1339	0.4213	1.3859	2.4725	0	0.0053	0.0112	0.0176	0.0193	0.0207	0.3891	5	3	1
0.063	0.252	1.6812	3.378	5.7402	7.3111	0.021	0.042	0.1401	0.1408	0.0798	0.061	0.5189	1	3	1
0.2835	0.3938	0.6772	2.2953	3.0079	3.4725	0.0945	0.0657	0.0565	0.0957	0.0418	0.029	0.4996	6	3	1
0.2402	0.441	1.6536	2.756	3.756	4.7638	0.0801	0.0735	0.1378	0.1149	0.0522	0.0397	0.5025	5	3	1
0.1182	1.315	1.6812	4.7205	6.2245	6.7796	0.0394	0.2192	0.1401	0.1967	0.0865	0.0565	0.5	5	3	1
0.0434	0.5158	1.6812	3.3741	6.4449	8.5197	0.0145	0.086	0.1401	0.1406	0.0896	0.071	0.5189	5	3	1
0.063	0.252	1.6812	3.378	5.7402	7.3111	0.021	0.042	0.1401	0.1408	0.0798	0.061	0.5189	4	3	1
0.7599	1.189	1.5079	2.2284	2.6536	3.5552	0.2533	0.1982	0.1257	0.0929	0.0369	0.0297	0.5	4	3	1
0.1182	0.2953	0.5788	0.6733	1.2126	1.9095	0.0394	0.0493	0.0483	0.0281	0.0169	0.016	0.498	3	3	1
0.0355	0.0906	0.126	0.4213	2.2166	2.3662	0.0119	0.0151	0.0105	0.0176	0.0308	0.0198	0.504	4	3	1
0.193	0.3465	0.8938	1.626	2.1575	2.2756	0.0644	0.0578	0.0745	0.0678	0.03	0.019	0.4138	5	4	1
0.2441	0.5276	0.7875	0.9922	1.5434	2.2717	0.0814	0.088	0.0657	0.0414	0.0215	0.019	0.423	6	4	1
0.0591	0.13	0.4725	3.067	4.2717	4.9686	0.0197	0.0217	0.0394	0.1278	0.0594	0.0415	0.5135	5	3	1
0.1418	0.2323	0.2796	0.5591	4.0237	4.5867	0.0473	0.0388	0.0233	0.0233	0.0559	0.0383	0.516	4	3	1
0	0.0119	0.2796	1.4174	1.8623	5.1024	0	0.002	0.0233	0.0591	0.0259	0.0426	0.5034	4	3	1
0.0158	0.0552	0.1969	1.6812	3.3032	6.9922	0.0053	0.0092	0.0165	0.0701	0.0459	0.0583	0.4296	6	3	1
0.0788	0.0985	0.2678	1.3977	1.8032	5.0197	0.0263	0.0165	0.0224	0.0583	0.0251	0.0419	0.498	4	3	1
0.1615	0.1654	0.3623	1.5749	1.9371	5.9725	0.0539	0.0276	0.0302	0.0657	0.027	0.0498	0.4125	5	3	1
0.0394	0.0512	0.1772	1.1378	1.7481	8.0315	0.0132	0.0086	0.0148	0.0475	0.0243	0.067	0.5136	6	3	1
0.3347	0.4804	0.7363	1.0079	1.9174	2.2835	0.1116	0.0801	0.0614	0.042	0.0267	0.0191	0.507	6	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.1418	1.9528	2.4961	2.6378	0.0014	0.0007	0.0119	0.0814	0.0347	0.022	0.408	5	4	1
0.1851	0.2953	0.8268	1.1812	2.8938	4.5276	0.0617	0.0493	0.0689	0.0493	0.0402	0.0378	0.511	5	3	1
0.2875	0.3504	0.5906	1.4331	3.4134	5.7205	0.0959	0.0584	0.0493	0.0598	0.0475	0.0477	0.513	5	3	1
0.2245	0.9528	3.3898	9.2717	10.1575	10.9056	0.0749	0.1588	0.2825	0.3864	0.1411	0.0909	0.5008	5	1	1
0.8662	2.3347	5.6378	7.4489	8.4922	9.6772	0.2888	0.3892	0.4699	0.3104	0.118	0.0807	0.5022	4	1	1
0.0827	0.2717	1.4292	10.441	14.6142	15.4331	0.0276	0.0453	0.1191	0.4351	0.203	0.1287	0.3829	5	4	1
0.5355	1.1772	4.256	6.5158	6.5749	7.2835	0.1785	0.1962	0.3547	0.2715	0.0914	0.0607	0.385	1	1	1
2.2087	4.0355	8.878	12.9252	13.3386	14.1772	0.7363	0.6726	0.7399	0.5386	0.1853	0.1182	0.3941	4	1	1
0.2048	1.0473	2.3583	3.3308	4.4686	5.0985	0.0683	0.1746	0.1966	0.1388	0.0621	0.0425	0.5082	4	3	1
0.3977	0.7756	1.3938	3.8032	4.6772	5.7914	0.1326	0.1293	0.1162	0.1585	0.065	0.0483	0.4182	5	4	1
0.3071	1.4804	1.9843	2.8032	3.4804	5.8111	0.1024	0.2468	0.1654	0.1168	0.0484	0.0485	0.5133	2	3	1
0.0237	0.1142	0.1693	0.2284	3.4725	4.441	0.0079	0.0191	0.0142	0.0096	0.0483	0.0371	0.45	4	3	1
0.0197	0.1024	0.1772	0.5906	4.3938	5.1536	0.0066	0.0171	0.0148	0.0247	0.0611	0.043	0.361	5	4	1
0.004	0.0079	0.189	0.8898	3.815	5.2717	0.0014	0.0014	0.0158	0.0371	0.053	0.044	0.4681	4	4	1
0.0906	0.1693	0.3071	0.8308	3.8504	5.1654	0.0302	0.0283	0.0256	0.0347	0.0535	0.0431	0.365	4	4	1
0.0276	0.1733	0.2875	1.0158	3.6339	4.6772	0.0092	0.0289	0.024	0.0424	0.0505	0.039	0.45	6	4	1
0.0749	0.4252	1.2717	2.4489	3.4646	4.9843	0.025	0.0709	0.106	0.1021	0.0482	0.0416	0.365	5	4	1
0.1103	0.3465	1.8111	2.4213	3.8977	4.6969	0.0368	0.0578	0.151	0.1009	0.0542	0.0392	0.4681	4	4	1
0.1339	0.5315	1.6063	2.3111	3.2835	4.0827	0.0447	0.0886	0.1339	0.0963	0.0457	0.0341	0.45	6	3	1

0.2638	1.0079	1.504	2.7835	3.8426	4.6693	0.088	0.168	0.1254	0.116	0.0534	0.039	0.361	4	4	1
0.4686	1.3229	1.5985	2.9371	3.7599	4.5906	0.1562	0.2205	0.1333	0.1224	0.0523	0.0383	0.361	6	3	1
1.2205	1.5591	1.7087	2.2402	3.6654	4.5709	0.4069	0.2599	0.1424	0.0934	0.051	0.0381	0.4681	4	3	1
0.0512	0.2087	0.2756	0.5315	1.9213	3.0197	0.0171	0.0348	0.023	0.0222	0.0267	0.0252	0.384	5	4	1
0.004	0.1536	0.2363	0.3977	2.3268	3.6575	0.0014	0.0256	0.0197	0.0166	0.0324	0.0305	0.472	4	3	1
0.0473	0.0552	0.5237	1.0158	1.5906	2.5079	0.0158	0.0092	0.0437	0.0424	0.0221	0.0209	0.4681	6	3	1
0.0394	0.0434	0.4292	0.6339	1.3701	1.9686	0.0132	0.0073	0.0358	0.0265	0.0191	0.0165	0.451	6	3	1
0.0197	0.0434	0.1378	0.4016	1.9213	3.4331	0.0066	0.0073	0.0115	0.0168	0.0267	0.0287	0.365	5	4	1
0.004	0.063	0.1812	0.5197	1.3426	2.4213	0.0014	0.0105	0.0151	0.0217	0.0187	0.0202	0.3613	2	4	1
0.0119	0.0945	0.252	1.1418	5.2914	8.4607	0.004	0.0158	0.021	0.0476	0.0735	0.0706	0.429	6	4	1
0.3347	0.4134	0.5276	0.6221	2.0434	4.6851	0.1116	0.0689	0.044	0.026	0.0284	0.0391	0.4056	4	3	1
0.0749	0.2126	0.2402	0.63	2.9567	3.4686	0.025	0.0355	0.0201	0.0263	0.0411	0.029	0.4869	6	3	1
0.1182	0.1339	0.1536	0.3583	0.9095	2.6103	0.0394	0.0224	0.0128	0.015	0.0127	0.0218	0.391	6	3	1
0.3386	0.3623	0.3623	0.3623	8.9725	10.9252	0.1129	0.0604	0.0302	0.0151	0.1247	0.0911	0.3858	1	3	1
0	0	0.004	0.004	0.0079	0.0315	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.0002	0.0003	0.443	5	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0119	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	0.433	5	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.0158	0.0158	0.0591	0.13	0.0014	0.0007	0.0014	0.0007	0.0009	0.0011	0.4636	6	3	1
0	0	0	0	0	0.0119	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.3431	5	3	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.05	6	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.0355	0.1693	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0015	0.351	5	4	1
0.0591	0.13	0.7993	1.2363	2.1063	3.4725	0.0197	0.0217	0.0667	0.0516	0.0293	0.029	0.2923	5	3	1
0.0197	0.1457	0.5945	0.6103	2.2363	4.693	0.0066	0.0243	0.0496	0.0255	0.0311	0.0392	0.4277	4	3	1
0.4882	1.4804	2.7008	3.2363	4.5	5.0906	0.1628	0.2468	0.2251	0.1349	0.0625	0.0425	0.4269	4	3	1
0.8662	1.4095	2.4016	3.004	3.8977	4.6536	0.2888	0.235	0.2002	0.1252	0.0542	0.0388	0.4394	6	4	1
0.126	0.2835	0.5788	1.1851	2.2717	3.5355	0.042	0.0473	0.0483	0.0494	0.0316	0.0295	0.4309	2	1	1
0.1536	0.4607	0.9371	1.8426	2.3623	2.6969	0.0512	0.0768	0.0781	0.0768	0.0329	0.0225	0.3585	2	4	1
0.0315	0.1693	0.7756	1.4764	2.0945	2.6182	0.0105	0.0283	0.0647	0.0616	0.0291	0.0219	0.3613	4	4	1
0.0512	0.193	0.3465	0.5276	1.756	2.4095	0.0171	0.0322	0.0289	0.022	0.0244	0.0201	0.352	4	4	1
0.0158	0.3111	1.1339	1.4646	1.9725	2.3544	0.0053	0.0519	0.0945	0.0611	0.0274	0.0197	0.3926	2	3	1
0	0.004	0.004	0.3229	5.0473	5.3462	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0135	0.0702	0.0446	0.5184	5	3	1
0.0591	0.063	0.063	0.0906	8.1182	8.6733	0.0197	0.0105	0.0053	0.0038	0.1128	0.0723	0.518	5	3	1
0.0473	0.0473	0.0867	0.0985	0.2205	6.5473	0.0158	0.0079	0.0073	0.0042	0.0031	0.0546	0.5153	4	3	1
0.2087	0.7914	1.8347	2.626	3.315	3.8032	0.0696	0.1319	0.1529	0.1095	0.0461	0.0317	0.4161	4	1	1
0.0906	0.1182	0.1339	0.1497	0.5237	0.756	0.0302	0.0197	0.0112	0.0063	0.0073	0.0063	0.4296	5	2	1
0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.0434	0.2048	0.3898	0.0053	0.0027	0.0014	0.0019	0.0029	0.0033	0.5094	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.0237	0.5355	1.1536	0	0	0	0.001	0.0075	0.0097	0.5035	3	3	1
0	0	0.004	0.0827	0.7678	1.0473	0	0	0.0004	0.0035	0.0107	0.0088	0.5106	3	3	1
0.0276	0.0512	0.2048	0.3229	1.5552	2.1969	0.0092	0.0086	0.0171	0.0135	0.0216	0.0184	0.5073	5	3	1
0.004	0.0237	0.1339	0.1457	0.3504	0.504	0.0014	0.004	0.0112	0.0061	0.0049	0.0042	0.5027	3	3	1
0.004	0.0315	0.1221	0.1457	0.4252	0.7087	0.0014	0.0053	0.0102	0.0061	0.006	0.006	0.5058	1	3	1
0.0276	0.0512	0.2048	0.3229	1.5552	2.1969	0.0092	0.0086	0.0171	0.0135	0.0216	0.0184	0.5073	4	3	1
0.004	0.0315	0.1221	0.1457	0.4252	0.7087	0.0014	0.0053	0.0102	0.0061	0.006	0.006	0.5058	3	3	1
0.0434	0.063	0.1497	0.1575	0.3426	0.5276	0.0145	0.0105	0.0125	0.0066	0.0048	0.0044	0.5057	3	3	1
0	0.0394	0.0552	0.0552	0.4567	1.0985	0	0.0066	0.0046	0.0023	0.0064	0.0092	0.3809	2	3	1
0	0	0	0.0749	0.252	0.6969	0	0	0	0.0032	0.0035	0.0059	0.5104	6	1	1
0	0.004	0.0119	0.0119	0.9292	1.193	0	0.0007	0.001	0.0005	0.013	0.01	0.404	3	3	1
0.1339	0.3071	0.3189	0.3426	1.4371	2.5709	0.0447	0.0512	0.0266	0.0143	0.02	0.0215	0.414	5	1	1
0	0	0	0.1103	0.8465	2.3898	0	0	0	0.0046	0.0118	0.02	0.515	5	3	1

0	0	0	0.1103	0.8465	2.3898	0	0	0	0.0046	0.0118	0.02	0.515	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.0079	1.5158	2.4725	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0211	0.0207	0.5152	5	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0197	0.0276	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0003	0.0003	0.495	4	3	1
0	0.1063	0.1378	0.1418	0.4292	0.8426	0	0.0178	0.0115	0.006	0.006	0.0071	0.4547	4	3	1
0	0.0473	0.0827	0.0827	0.4607	0.8544	0	0.0079	0.0069	0.0035	0.0064	0.0072	0.449	4	3	1
0	0.1654	0.3938	0.3938	0.8111	1.315	0	0.0276	0.0329	0.0165	0.0113	0.011	0.363	6	4	1
0	0	0.0197	0.1024	0.6457	0.8819	0	0	0.0017	0.0043	0.009	0.0074	0.348	6	3	1
0.0867	0.1339	0.4922	0.7402	1.7638	3.2875	0.0289	0.0224	0.0411	0.0309	0.0245	0.0274	0.3892	5	4	1
0	0	0.0197	0.1024	0.6457	0.8819	0	0	0.0017	0.0043	0.009	0.0074	0.348	4	3	1
0	0	0.0119	0.0985	0.2993	0.626	0	0	0.001	0.0042	0.0042	0.0053	0.349	4	4	1
0	0	0.0197	0.1024	0.6457	0.8819	0	0	0.0017	0.0043	0.009	0.0074	0.348	4	3	1
0.0867	0.1339	0.4922	0.7402	1.7638	3.2875	0.0289	0.0224	0.0411	0.0309	0.0245	0.0274	0.3892	4	4	1
0.0355	0.0434	0.4016	0.5827	0.6733	0.9804	0.0119	0.0073	0.0335	0.0243	0.0094	0.0082	0.415	5	4	1
0.0355	0.0434	0.4016	0.5827	0.6733	0.9804	0.0119	0.0073	0.0335	0.0243	0.0094	0.0082	0.415	4	4	1
0	0	0.4134	0.4725	0.9843	1.4095	0	0	0.0345	0.0197	0.0137	0.0118	0.3761	4	3	1
0.063	0.3386	0.4882	0.7245	2.1654	4.1851	0.021	0.0565	0.0407	0.0302	0.0301	0.0349	0.3964	1	3	1
0	0	0.067	0.1575	1.4961	1.7638	0	0	0.0056	0.0066	0.0208	0.0147	0.388	2	3	1
0	0	0.1497	0.2087	0.5276	1.067	0	0	0.0125	0.0087	0.0074	0.0089	0.393	4	4	1
0.004	0.2599	0.3229	0.3465	0.4213	0.5867	0.0014	0.0434	0.027	0.0145	0.0059	0.0049	0.4	4	3	1
0.0237	0.1457	0.4016	0.4882	1.1418	2.5315	0.0079	0.0243	0.0335	0.0204	0.0159	0.0211	0.401	4	3	1
0.0867	0.1339	0.4922	0.7402	1.7638	3.2875	0.0289	0.0224	0.0411	0.0309	0.0245	0.0274	0.3892	4	4	1
0	0	0.004	0.13	0.6142	0.7402	0	0	0.0004	0.0055	0.0086	0.0062	0	4	3	1
0	0.004	0.0119	0.9804	2.7205	7.9882	0	0.0007	0.001	0.0409	0.0378	0.0666	0	4	3	1
0	0.004	0.063	1.0276	3.7678	9.4882	0	0.0007	0.0053	0.0429	0.0524	0.0791	0.518	3	3	1
0	0.004	0.0473	1.0079	2.8268	7.6339	0	0.0007	0.004	0.042	0.0393	0.0637	0.5151	1	3	1
0.0394	0.1103	0.1221	0.2166	0.4371	0.8426	0.0132	0.0184	0.0102	0.0091	0.0061	0.0071	0.271	6	3	1
0.0119	0.0119	0.0434	0.2284	1.2835	1.4449	0.004	0.002	0.0037	0.0096	0.0179	0.0121	0.407	3	1	1
0.126	0.1339	0.1378	1.378	6.8544	7.4764	0.042	0.0224	0.0115	0.0575	0.0952	0.0624	0.3978	2	3	1
0	0	0.0512	0.2126	4.7717	6.5709	0	0	0.0043	0.0089	0.0663	0.0548	0.5177	5	3	1
0.2914	0.315	0.315	0.3189	0.6969	0.9371	0.0972	0.0525	0.0263	0.0133	0.0097	0.0079	0.3998	5	4	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.1536	3.378	4.1615	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0064	0.047	0.0347	0.4978	4	3	1
0.0315	0.0315	0.0315	0.1457	2.7245	3.2284	0.0105	0.0053	0.0027	0.0061	0.0379	0.027	0.4932	3	3	1
0.0355	0.441	1.7008	2.2914	6.7363	9.1418	0.0119	0.0735	0.1418	0.0955	0.0936	0.0762	0.5187	4	3	1
0.0512	0.0788	0.2008	0.3938	5.2678	7.7717	0.0171	0.0132	0.0168	0.0165	0.0732	0.0648	0.4292	4	4	1
0.0355	0.063	0.2166	0.3465	7.2481	11.1378	0.0119	0.0105	0.0181	0.0145	0.1007	0.0929	0.5175	4	4	1
0.0355	0.063	0.2166	0.3465	7.2481	11.1378	0.0119	0.0105	0.0181	0.0145	0.1007	0.0929	0.5175	5	4	1
0.0512	0.0788	0.2008	0.3938	5.2678	7.7717	0.0171	0.0132	0.0168	0.0165	0.0732	0.0648	0.4292	4	4	1
0.0512	0.0788	0.2008	0.3938	5.2678	7.7717	0.0171	0.0132	0.0168	0.0165	0.0732	0.0648	0.4292	5	4	1
0	0.004	0.1693	0.4528	2.7048	5.0079	0	0.0007	0.0142	0.0189	0.0376	0.0418	0.3783	6	4	1
0.2678	0.2756	0.4095	0.9449	2.3583	4.2008	0.0893	0.046	0.0342	0.0394	0.0328	0.0351	0.4344	4	3	1
0.1103	0.2323	0.5945	0.9922	2.4764	3.0197	0.0368	0.0388	0.0496	0.0414	0.0344	0.0252	0.3962	4	3	1
0	0.1142	0.126	0.189	0.7441	1.3189	0	0.0191	0.0105	0.0079	0.0104	0.011	0.4908	4	3	1
0.0119	0.0197	0.1221	0.6772	5.7481	6.2678	0.004	0.0033	0.0102	0.0283	0.0799	0.0523	0.4317	4	3	1
0.0197	0.0197	0.0197	0.189	0.9646	2.2363	0.0066	0.0033	0.0017	0.0079	0.0134	0.0187	0.428	6	4	1
0	0	0.067	0.0827	0.6103	1.5788	0	0	0.0056	0.0035	0.0085	0.0132	0.426	6	4	1
0.0079	0.0158	0.2914	0.3071	1.2087	2.2756	0.0027	0.0027	0.0243	0.0128	0.0168	0.019	0.512	4	3	1
0.0276	0.0276	0.063	0.4567	1.1457	2.4174	0.0092	0.0046	0.0053	0.0191	0.016	0.0202	0.4197	4	1	1
0.0079	0.0158	0.0473	0.4646	6.9331	7.6497	0.0027	0.0027	0.004	0.0194	0.0963	0.0638	0.4297	5	4	1

0	0	0	0.2008	2.0276	2.6378	0	0	0	0.0084	0.0282	0.022	0.4053	5	4	1
0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.0197	0.9607	1.4843	0.004	0.0027	0.0014	0.0009	0.0134	0.0124	0.401	2	1	1
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	2.2284	2.8583	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.031	0.0239	0.478	1	1	1
0.0355	0.0512	0.0591	0.0591	2.5512	3.7756	0.0119	0.0086	0.005	0.0025	0.0355	0.0315	0.358	1	1	1
2.8544	4.1812	5.5434	6.5394	7.1142	7.8229	0.9515	0.6969	0.462	0.2725	0.0989	0.0652	0.4718	4	1	1
0.5434	1.4134	3.0985	5.7166	6.6733	10.6654	0.1812	0.2356	0.2583	0.2382	0.0927	0.0889	0.4263	4	1	1
0.004	0.0197	0.063	0.1812	2.6339	4.8462	0.0014	0.0033	0.0053	0.0076	0.0366	0.0404	0.5182	5	3	1
0.0315	0.0512	0.1063	0.2638	2.3623	4.626	0.0105	0.0086	0.0089	0.011	0.0329	0.0386	0.5174	5	3	1
0.2245	0.9922	3.2363	5.0315	5.5985	6.6536	0.0749	0.1654	0.2697	0.2097	0.0778	0.0555	0.4221	3	4	1
0	0.0079	0.0158	0.0158	1.4449	2.1575	0	0.0014	0.0014	0.0007	0.0201	0.018	0.342	4	4	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0197	1.4292	1.9449	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0009	0.0199	0.0163	0.3991	4	4	1
0	0	0.0079	0.0079	1.4252	2.1024	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0198	0.0176	0.3909	4	4	1
0.0276	0.0276	0.0276	0.0276	1.3583	1.8977	0.0092	0.0046	0.0023	0.0012	0.0189	0.0159	0.4021	5	4	1
0	0.0473	0.2205	0.2245	1.2835	1.6615	0	0.0079	0.0184	0.0094	0.0179	0.0139	0.4911	5	4	1
0.0119	0.3071	0.3268	0.3347	1.2953	2.689	0.004	0.0512	0.0273	0.014	0.018	0.0225	0.5029	5	1	1
0	0.1654	0.2008	0.2008	1.3426	1.9804	0	0.0276	0.0168	0.0084	0.0187	0.0166	0.4875	1	1	1
0.9056	2.193	5.1615	7.5079	8.8504	10.0945	0.3019	0.3655	0.4302	0.3129	0.123	0.0842	0	3	4	1
0.3386	0.5512	1.2087	1.3701	2.1812	8.6063	0.1129	0.0919	0.1008	0.0571	0.0303	0.0718	0.5143	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.004	1.1969	2.2048	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0167	0.0184	0.4025	5	4	1
0.0276	0.0867	0.1221	0.1221	10.4213	12.1063	0.0092	0.0145	0.0102	0.0051	0.1448	0.1009	0.5167	4	3	1
0	0.0276	0.0434	0.0434	12.13	12.8386	0	0.0046	0.0037	0.0019	0.1685	0.107	0.5167	1	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.6693	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0056	0.321	4	4	1
0.315	0.3504	0.3741	1.5945	3.2323	6.2048	0.105	0.0584	0.0312	0.0665	0.0449	0.0518	0.4129	6	1	1
0.0355	0.0434	0.1024	1.626	3.0394	6.8741	0.0119	0.0073	0.0086	0.0678	0.0423	0.0573	0.515	3	1	1
0.189	0.3977	0.626	1.2914	2.6575	3.8032	0.063	0.0663	0.0522	0.0539	0.037	0.0317	0.3189	1	1	1
0.0985	0.3308	0.7993	2.8898	4.3347	5.2441	0.0329	0.0552	0.0667	0.1205	0.0603	0.0438	0.4268	2	4	1
0.1772	0.2087	0.2441	0.7993	1.5906	4.7087	0.0591	0.0348	0.0204	0.0334	0.0221	0.0393	0.505	1	1	1
0.6457	1.3898	2.8268	4.2993	6.1733	8.2402	0.2153	0.2317	0.2356	0.1792	0.0858	0.0687	0.3951	5	3	1
0.0709	0.2402	0.4489	3.9804	6.1339	8.2008	0.0237	0.0401	0.0375	0.1659	0.0852	0.0684	0.4298	5	3	1
0.193	0.2914	1.1024	2.878	2.9882	3.6339	0.0644	0.0486	0.0919	0.12	0.0416	0.0303	0.3964	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0473	0.1851	0.4961	1.0079	2.9371	0.004	0.0079	0.0155	0.0207	0.014	0.0245	0.4242	6	3	1
0.0788	0.2363	1.1457	2.563	3.7914	4.9449	0.0263	0.0394	0.0955	0.1068	0.0527	0.0413	0.5177	6	4	1
0.0394	0.1575	0.3504	1.1182	2.0512	2.9371	0.0132	0.0263	0.0292	0.0466	0.0285	0.0245	0.508	5	4	1
0	0.0276	0.5276	1.8189	4.9095	6.1457	0	0.0046	0.044	0.0758	0.0682	0.0513	0.5185	5	4	1
0	0.0394	0.1615	1.7993	6.9213	8.5906	0	0.0066	0.0135	0.075	0.0962	0.0716	0.4298	6	3	1
0.0591	0.2166	0.504	1.6063	2.5197	4.126	0.0197	0.0361	0.042	0.067	0.035	0.0344	0.3583	4	3	1
0.0079	0.0355	0.3938	4.7638	10.563	12.0473	0.0027	0.006	0.0329	0.1985	0.1468	0.1004	0.5126	1	1	1
0.0709	0.1378	0.3308	2.0158	6.752	8.126	0.0237	0.023	0.0276	0.084	0.0938	0.0678	0.494	4	1	1
0.0237	0.0552	0.13	1.3701	4.4489	5.126	0.0079	0.0092	0.0109	0.0571	0.0618	0.0428	0.488	5	1	1
0.0315	0.0473	0.8741	2.126	7.7914	9.0394	0.0105	0.0079	0.0729	0.0886	0.1083	0.0754	0.4913	5	1	1
0	0.0079	0.3859	2.2756	7.9449	9.3977	0	0.0014	0.0322	0.0949	0.1104	0.0784	0.4063	3	4	1
0.4331	0.8268	1.7678	4.8898	8.5197	10.8268	0.1444	0.1378	0.1474	0.2038	0.1184	0.0903	0.3747	3	4	1
0	0.0119	0.0315	0.1103	7.4449	9.9016	0	0.002	0.0027	0.0046	0.1035	0.0826	0.3472	1	4	1
0	0.0394	0.4174	7.8623	15.4095	17.0552	0	0.0066	0.0348	0.3276	0.2141	0.1422	0.3957	6	4	1
0.0867	0.1457	0.5945	4.2756	11.2875	12.1615	0.0289	0.0243	0.0496	0.1782	0.1568	0.1014	0.2983	6	4	1
0.0079	0.0394	0.5237	8.8623	16.0867	17.5945	0.0027	0.0066	0.0437	0.3693	0.2235	0.1467	0.4384	4	4	1
0.9489	1.5945	3.0827	3.8859	7.4252	10.8308	0.3163	0.2658	0.2569	0.162	0.1032	0.0903	0.4188	4	3	1
0.1536	0.1536	1.2796	3.6221	7.5237	8.0512	0.0512	0.0256	0.1067	0.151	0.1045	0.0671	0.497	5	1	1

0.5512	1.7441	3.9095	7.6654	10.6142	11.1812	0.1838	0.2907	0.3258	0.3194	0.1475	0.0932	0.4414	4	3	1
0.689	1.4292	3.8623	9.6654	12.2323	12.441	0.2297	0.2382	0.3219	0.4028	0.1699	0.1037	0.3803	6	4	1
0.9686	2.7678	6.5434	10.1851	12.6378	13.0749	0.3229	0.4613	0.5453	0.4244	0.1756	0.109	0.4344	4	3	1
0.5945	2.7481	8.0434	12.2441	15.2363	15.5552	0.1982	0.4581	0.6703	0.5102	0.2117	0.1297	0.383	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.004	0.004	0.0985	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0001	0.0009	0.4581	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.0158	0.1221	0.1497	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0017	0.0013	0.365	5	3	1
0.0394	0.1142	0.13	0.189	0.2875	0.3268	0.0132	0.0191	0.0109	0.0079	0.004	0.0028	0.469	5	3	1
0.1418	0.2835	0.315	0.4607	0.6733	0.8071	0.0473	0.0473	0.0263	0.0192	0.0094	0.0068	0.4769	5	1	1
0.1615	0.2245	0.6221	1.1536	3.9961	6.6654	0.0539	0.0375	0.0519	0.0481	0.0556	0.0556	0	4	3	1
0.256	0.9213	1.7993	4.2008	5.6693	7.5355	0.0854	0.1536	0.15	0.1751	0.0788	0.0628	0.5179	4	3	1
0.0276	0.0945	0.1969	0.7126	1.8032	7.6536	0.0092	0.0158	0.0165	0.0297	0.0251	0.0638	0.5152	5	3	1
0.0276	0.0945	0.1969	0.7126	1.8032	7.6536	0.0092	0.0158	0.0165	0.0297	0.0251	0.0638	0.5152	5	3	1
0.0276	0.0945	0.1969	0.7126	1.8032	7.6536	0.0092	0.0158	0.0165	0.0297	0.0251	0.0638	0.5152	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0552	0.2363	0.5079	1.3347	6.3623	0.004	0.0092	0.0197	0.0212	0.0186	0.0531	0.5139	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0552	0.2363	0.5079	1.3347	6.3623	0.004	0.0092	0.0197	0.0212	0.0186	0.0531	0.5139	5	3	1
0.0906	0.2363	0.4292	1.0119	2.5237	8.567	0.0302	0.0394	0.0358	0.0422	0.0351	0.0714	0.516	5	3	1
0.0276	0.0945	0.1969	0.7126	1.8032	7.6536	0.0092	0.0158	0.0165	0.0297	0.0251	0.0638	0.5152	4	3	1
0.0473	0.1772	0.3701	1.004	2.5394	8.3662	0.0158	0.0296	0.0309	0.0419	0.0353	0.0698	0.517	4	3	1
0.0473	0.1772	0.3701	1.004	2.5394	8.3662	0.0158	0.0296	0.0309	0.0419	0.0353	0.0698	0.517	5	3	1
0.0473	0.1772	0.3701	1.004	2.5394	8.3662	0.0158	0.0296	0.0309	0.0419	0.0353	0.0698	0.517	5	3	1
0.0906	0.2363	0.4292	1.0119	2.5237	8.567	0.0302	0.0394	0.0358	0.0422	0.0351	0.0714	0.516	5	3	1
0	0	0.0079	1.315	4.0985	8.5355	0	0	0.0007	0.0548	0.057	0.0712	0.5187	4	3	1
0	0	0.0079	1.315	4.0985	8.5355	0	0	0.0007	0.0548	0.057	0.0712	0.5187	4	3	1
0	0	0.0079	1.315	4.0985	8.5355	0	0	0.0007	0.0548	0.057	0.0712	0.5187	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.0119	0.0473	0.1693	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0007	0.0015	0.345	6	3	1
0	0	0.0079	0.0158	0.2166	0.8583	0	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0031	0.0072	0	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.9252	1.3268	1.4213	0	0	0	0.0386	0.0185	0.0119	0.483	4	3	1
0.1654	0.315	0.7323	1.941	5.3111	8.5119	0.0552	0.0525	0.0611	0.0809	0.0738	0.071	0.43	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.2087	0.815	1.0394	0	0	0	0.0087	0.0114	0.0087	0.443	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.0512	0.1142	0.2363	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0016	0.002	0.4581	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.2953	1	1.4843	0	0	0	0.0124	0.0139	0.0124	0.339	6	4	1
0	0	0.0394	0.7875	4.189	9.7796	0	0	0.0033	0.0329	0.0582	0.0815	0.4295	5	3	1
0	0	0.0473	0.2205	0.6654	0.8977	0	0	0.004	0.0092	0.0093	0.0075	0.419	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.252	1.067	1.2599	0	0	0	0.0105	0.0149	0.0105	0.4021	6	3	1
0	0	0.0434	0.2717	0.4725	0.7481	0	0	0.0037	0.0114	0.0066	0.0063	0.352	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.1969	0.4607	2.441	0	0	0	0.0083	0.0064	0.0204	0.4255	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.193	0.6418	2.7678	0	0	0	0.0081	0.009	0.0231	0.4259	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.193	0.6418	2.7678	0	0	0	0.0081	0.009	0.0231	0.4259	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.193	0.4725	2.2993	0	0	0	0.0081	0.0066	0.0192	0.4258	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.1654	0.6654	2.7245	0	0	0	0.0069	0.0093	0.0228	0.509	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.1969	0.4607	2.441	0	0	0	0.0083	0.0064	0.0204	0.4255	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.5276	1.3386	3.3583	0	0	0	0.022	0.0186	0.028	0.4238	4	3	1
0.0158	0.0237	0.0709	1.0434	4.0079	5.6221	0.0053	0.004	0.006	0.0435	0.0557	0.0469	0.518	1	3	1
0.063	0.1812	0.2481	0.756	1.5552	3.7875	0.021	0.0302	0.0207	0.0315	0.0216	0.0316	0.5123	4	3	1
0.1378	0.2481	0.3504	0.9646	1.5237	3.5906	0.046	0.0414	0.0292	0.0402	0.0212	0.03	0.5131	5	3	1
0.1378	0.2481	0.3504	0.9646	1.5237	3.5906	0.046	0.0414	0.0292	0.0402	0.0212	0.03	0.5131	5	3	1
0.2008	0.256	0.3189	0.8544	1.5434	3.4252	0.067	0.0427	0.0266	0.0356	0.0215	0.0286	0.5145	5	3	1
0.1103	0.1378	0.2087	0.626	2.2993	5.3898	0.0368	0.023	0.0174	0.0261	0.032	0.045	0.5156	4	3	1

0	0	0.0079	0.3504	0.5394	0.693	0	0	0.0007	0.0146	0.0075	0.0058	0.419	5	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.0158	0.1063	0.4489	0.7875	0.0014	0.0007	0.0014	0.0045	0.0063	0.0066	0.197	4	3	1
0.1024	0.1142	0.126	0.8465	2.5276	5.8701	0.0342	0.0191	0.0105	0.0353	0.0352	0.049	0.3633	1	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.0197	0.3308	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0028	0.341	5	3	1
0.0079	0.0197	0.067	0.3189	0.9252	1.7441	0.0027	0.0033	0.0056	0.0133	0.0129	0.0146	0.314	5	3	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.0237	0.2717	2.3898	4.4056	0.0027	0.0014	0.002	0.0114	0.0332	0.0368	0.5163	4	3	1
0.0591	0.0591	0.1142	0.5512	2.8071	5.9922	0.0197	0.0099	0.0096	0.023	0.039	0.05	0.5178	5	3	1
0	0.0079	0.0473	0.067	1.567	3.0827	0	0.0014	0.004	0.0028	0.0218	0.0257	0.5153	4	3	1
0	0.0197	0.0512	0.0985	1.2284	2.7441	0	0.0033	0.0043	0.0042	0.0171	0.0229	0.2092	5	3	1
0	0.004	0.0867	0.1182	1.8308	2.9489	0	0.0007	0.0073	0.005	0.0255	0.0246	0.517	5	3	1
0	0	0.0079	0.0709	0.4567	0.5788	0	0	0.0007	0.003	0.0064	0.0049	0	5	4	1
0	0	0.13	1.13	3.3071	4.5945	0	0	0.0109	0.0471	0.046	0.0383	0.3594	5	4	1
0	0.0079	0.1378	1.3268	2.8623	4.4489	0	0.0014	0.0115	0.0553	0.0398	0.0371	0.3908	5	1	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.0434	0.2756	2.8623	5.1063	0.0027	0.0014	0.0037	0.0115	0.0398	0.0426	0.5139	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0394	0.0827	0.4292	2.6693	2.7796	0.004	0.0066	0.0069	0.0179	0.0371	0.0232	0.335	1	3	1
0.5906	2.3898	3.2993	4.4882	4.6103	4.6339	0.1969	0.3983	0.275	0.1871	0.0641	0.0387	0.3062	6	3	1
0.4489	1.256	1.8583	2.5591	2.7717	2.7993	0.1497	0.2094	0.1549	0.1067	0.0385	0.0234	0.314	1	3	1
0.4489	1.256	1.8583	2.5591	2.7717	2.7993	0.1497	0.2094	0.1549	0.1067	0.0385	0.0234	0.314	5	3	1
0.4489	1.256	1.8583	2.5591	2.7717	2.7993	0.1497	0.2094	0.1549	0.1067	0.0385	0.0234	0.314	6	2	1
0.0119	0.0473	0.1536	0.567	7.5197	7.6693	0.004	0.0079	0.0128	0.0237	0.1045	0.064	0.5183	6	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0788	0.567	5.7717	6.0315	0.0014	0.0033	0.0066	0.0237	0.0802	0.0503	0.5186	5	3	1
0	0	0.0512	0.5434	3.3229	3.5591	0	0	0.0043	0.0227	0.0462	0.0297	0.4741	6	3	1
0	0	0.063	0.6575	4.6812	5.0355	0	0	0.0053	0.0274	0.0651	0.042	0.4117	6	3	1
0.0119	0.0473	0.1536	0.567	7.5197	7.6693	0.004	0.0079	0.0128	0.0237	0.1045	0.064	0.5183	6	3	1
0.0119	0.0473	0.1536	0.567	7.5197	7.6693	0.004	0.0079	0.0128	0.0237	0.1045	0.064	0.5183	6	2	1
0	0.0158	0.0827	0.7363	2.1615	9.3583	0	0.0027	0.0069	0.0307	0.0301	0.078	0.5155	4	4	1
0	0.0119	0.2678	0.6103	5.3623	5.4371	0	0.002	0.0224	0.0255	0.0745	0.0454	0.3402	4	4	1
1.067	2.0552	2.4764	2.9371	3.0552	3.0985	0.3557	0.3426	0.2064	0.1224	0.0425	0.0259	0.34	4	3	1
0.6497	1.6812	2.2441	3.1615	3.3347	3.378	0.2166	0.2802	0.1871	0.1318	0.0464	0.0282	0.4451	5	3	1
0	0.0197	0.0906	0.4056	2.2245	2.3544	0	0.0033	0.0076	0.0169	0.0309	0.0197	0.351	1	3	1
0.0079	0.0394	0.0867	0.378	4.9607	5.004	0.0027	0.0066	0.0073	0.0158	0.0689	0.0417	0.306	6	3	1
0.004	0.0158	0.1615	0.5709	6.8189	6.8898	0.0014	0.0027	0.0135	0.0238	0.0948	0.0575	0.416	1	3	1
0.0079	0.0473	0.0906	0.3977	3.2205	3.3308	0.0027	0.0079	0.0076	0.0166	0.0448	0.0278	0.4581	5	3	1
0.004	0.0158	0.1615	0.5709	6.8189	6.8898	0.0014	0.0027	0.0135	0.0238	0.0948	0.0575	0.416	5	3	1
0	0	0.004	0.2914	1.1142	3.9371	0	0	0.0004	0.0122	0.0155	0.0329	0.4581	6	3	1
1.8189	4.8701	6.8229	7.1378	7.2717	7.3229	0.6063	0.8117	0.5686	0.2975	0.101	0.0611	0.4983	6	3	1
1.3229	4.4016	6.5709	7.0591	7.2756	7.3462	0.441	0.7336	0.5476	0.2942	0.1011	0.0613	0.5045	5	3	1
0.941	4.0197	6.004	6.815	7.0237	7.1142	0.3137	0.67	0.5004	0.284	0.0976	0.0593	0.5098	6	3	1
1.9804	4.3071	5.3819	5.4922	5.5709	5.5827	0.6602	0.7179	0.4485	0.2289	0.0774	0.0466	0.336	6	3	1
1.378	3.7323	5.9292	6.4213	6.5276	6.5749	0.4594	0.6221	0.4941	0.2676	0.0907	0.0548	0.4959	4	3	1
0	0	0.0158	0.626	1.752	5.7756	0	0	0.0014	0.0261	0.0244	0.0482	0.4173	6	4	1
0	0.004	0.1378	0.5827	4.8662	5.0473	0	0.0007	0.0115	0.0243	0.0676	0.0421	0.3492	6	4	1
0	0	0.0158	0.2599	1.7481	6.0315	0	0	0.0014	0.0109	0.0243	0.0503	0.352	5	3	1
0.2481	0.563	1.2008	1.9331	8.5079	9.4371	0.0827	0.0939	0.1001	0.0806	0.1182	0.0787	0.5185	5	3	1
0.2245	0.5906	1.0788	1.6851	7.5394	8.7953	0.0749	0.0985	0.0899	0.0703	0.1048	0.0733	0.5188	4	3	1
0.2245	0.5906	1.0788	1.6851	7.5394	8.7953	0.0749	0.0985	0.0899	0.0703	0.1048	0.0733	0.5188	4	3	1
0.2481	0.563	1.2008	1.9331	8.5079	9.4371	0.0827	0.0939	0.1001	0.0806	0.1182	0.0787	0.5185	4	3	1
0.2481	0.563	1.2008	1.9331	8.5079	9.4371	0.0827	0.0939	0.1001	0.0806	0.1182	0.0787	0.5185	4	3	1

0.2245	0.5906	1.0788	1.6851	7.5394	8.7953	0.0749	0.0985	0.0899	0.0703	0.1048	0.0733	0.5188	5	3	1
0.2284	0.5394	1.0512	2.0158	8.7599	10.0985	0.0762	0.0899	0.0876	0.084	0.1217	0.0842	0.4159	5	3	1
0.2481	0.563	1.2008	1.9331	8.5079	9.4371	0.0827	0.0939	0.1001	0.0806	0.1182	0.0787	0.5185	5	3	1
0.6221	1.6969	2.8426	3.5749	4.2599	4.4331	0.2074	0.2829	0.2369	0.149	0.0592	0.037	0.506	5	3	1
0.0276	0.0434	0.256	0.941	4.6182	4.9252	0.0092	0.0073	0.0214	0.0393	0.0642	0.0411	0.4944	6	3	1
0.9134	2.8465	4.4804	5.8426	6.5591	6.752	0.3045	0.4745	0.3734	0.2435	0.0911	0.0563	0.4021	6	3	1
0.5591	1.4134	2.4686	2.9725	3.4449	3.7166	0.1864	0.2356	0.2058	0.1239	0.0479	0.031	0.4735	1	3	1
0.0473	0.067	0.1182	0.4371	2.2796	2.7048	0.0158	0.0112	0.0099	0.0183	0.0317	0.0226	0.4083	4	4	1
0.0473	0.067	0.1182	0.4371	2.2796	2.7048	0.0158	0.0112	0.0099	0.0183	0.0317	0.0226	0.4083	1	3	1
0	0	0.0276	0.3308	3.5119	6.0355	0	0	0.0023	0.0138	0.0488	0.0503	0.3686	6	4	1
0.4056	1.0788	1.4567	2.1024	3.6812	3.8189	0.1352	0.1798	0.1214	0.0876	0.0512	0.0319	0.3599	3	4	1
0.4371	1.0945	2.0237	3.0945	4.1378	4.1654	0.1457	0.1825	0.1687	0.129	0.0575	0.0348	0.3414	3	3	1
0	0	0	0.0158	0.0591	0.0749	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0009	0.0007	0.4133	1	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.0276	0.0906	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0008	0.242	6	3	1
0	0.0079	0.0552	0.5473	3.193	6.8583	0	0.0014	0.0046	0.0229	0.0444	0.0572	0.2983	6	4	1
0	0.0119	0.0473	0.4056	2.5473	5.7008	0	0.002	0.004	0.0169	0.0354	0.0476	0.348	6	4	1
0	0.004	0.0276	0.2796	2.5749	5.7993	0	0.0007	0.0023	0.0117	0.0358	0.0484	0.3934	6	4	1
0.004	0.0158	0.1182	0.7678	4.9567	9.1812	0.0014	0.0027	0.0099	0.032	0.0689	0.0766	0.2872	6	4	1
0	0.0079	0.0552	0.5473	3.193	6.8583	0	0.0014	0.0046	0.0229	0.0444	0.0572	0.2983	6	4	1
0	0	0.0119	0.3623	2.5	6.13	0	0	0.001	0.0151	0.0348	0.0511	0.4241	6	4	1
0	0.0119	0.0473	0.4056	2.5473	5.7008	0	0.002	0.004	0.0169	0.0354	0.0476	0.348	6	3	1
0	0.0119	0.0473	0.4056	2.5473	5.7008	0	0.002	0.004	0.0169	0.0354	0.0476	0.348	6	3	1
0	0.0079	0.0552	0.5473	3.193	6.8583	0	0.0014	0.0046	0.0229	0.0444	0.0572	0.2983	6	4	1
0	0.0079	0.0552	0.5473	3.193	6.8583	0	0.0014	0.0046	0.0229	0.0444	0.0572	0.2983	3	1	1
0.0906	0.4252	1.1457	2.2048	3.6536	4.941	0.0302	0.0709	0.0955	0.0919	0.0508	0.0412	0.238	2	1	1
0.0906	0.4252	1.1457	2.2048	3.6536	4.941	0.0302	0.0709	0.0955	0.0919	0.0508	0.0412	0.238	4	4	1
0.1418	0.2402	0.4252	1.0709	1.2481	4.063	0.0473	0.0401	0.0355	0.0447	0.0174	0.0339	0.2359	4	3	1
0.2756	0.6103	1.63	2.9764	6.1221	7.3623	0.0919	0.1018	0.1359	0.1241	0.0851	0.0614	0.3891	2	3	1
0.2756	0.6103	1.63	2.9764	6.1221	7.3623	0.0919	0.1018	0.1359	0.1241	0.0851	0.0614	0.3891	4	4	1
0.0119	0.193	1.3189	1.6497	3.6969	5.2284	0.004	0.0322	0.11	0.0688	0.0514	0.0436	0.27	6	4	1
0.0119	0.0197	0.0552	0.1536	3.3544	6.4174	0.004	0.0033	0.0046	0.0064	0.0466	0.0535	0.3264	4	3	1
0.0394	0.126	0.4371	1.567	4.4567	5.6969	0.0132	0.021	0.0365	0.0653	0.0619	0.0475	0.3078	4	3	1
0	0	0.0158	0.1733	2.1457	4.1575	0	0	0.0014	0.0073	0.0299	0.0347	0.4128	4	3	1
0.0394	0.193	0.4174	0.7441	4.9174	6.2008	0.0132	0.0322	0.0348	0.0311	0.0683	0.0517	0.4583	6	4	1
0	0	0.004	0.0355	2.6339	5.1497	0	0	0.0004	0.0015	0.0366	0.043	0.3168	5	4	1
0.3347	0.7402	1.1339	1.3268	1.5473	1.6024	0.1116	0.1234	0.0945	0.0553	0.0215	0.0134	0.232	3	4	1
0	0.0079	0.1182	0.2323	2.5394	4.0119	0	0.0014	0.0099	0.0097	0.0353	0.0335	0.3564	2	3	1
0	0.1615	0.7756	7.5079	12.7678	12.8741	0	0.027	0.0647	0.3129	0.1774	0.1073	0.383	3	3	1
0.0079	0.3623	0.9882	6.7756	11.4528	11.6575	0.0027	0.0604	0.0824	0.2824	0.1591	0.0972	0.3791	3	3	1
0.0079	0.3623	0.9882	6.7756	11.4528	11.6575	0.0027	0.0604	0.0824	0.2824	0.1591	0.0972	0.3791	4	1	1
0	0.1615	0.7756	7.5079	12.7678	12.8741	0	0.027	0.0647	0.3129	0.1774	0.1073	0.383	4	1	1
0.0158	0.2796	1.0237	5.3426	12.0709	12.4095	0.0053	0.0466	0.0854	0.2227	0.1677	0.1035	0.4534	4	3	1
0.004	0.0276	0.0867	0.4292	2.2835	2.8662	0.0014	0.0046	0.0073	0.0179	0.0318	0.0239	0.408	5	4	1
0.0945	0.1378	0.8465	2.441	6.8229	6.9371	0.0315	0.023	0.0706	0.1018	0.0948	0.0579	0.5175	4	4	1
0.1772	0.3465	0.9567	1.6733	5.1457	5.1575	0.0591	0.0578	0.0798	0.0698	0.0715	0.043	0.3457	5	3	1
0.1221	0.2993	0.9016	1.7323	5.6733	5.7087	0.0407	0.0499	0.0752	0.0722	0.0788	0.0476	0.3446	6	3	1
0.2284	0.2717	0.9607	2.9016	7.6063	7.7756	0.0762	0.0453	0.0801	0.1209	0.1057	0.0648	0.5179	6	3	1
0.0197	0.0355	0.7441	1.9371	5.3662	5.4843	0.0066	0.006	0.0621	0.0808	0.0746	0.0458	0.5186	2	3	1

0.004	0.0119	0.4528	2.0394	4.5709	4.63	0.0014	0.002	0.0378	0.085	0.0635	0.0386	0.324	5	3	1
0.1103	0.252	0.2953	0.3623	1.1182	1.2914	0.0368	0.042	0.0247	0.0151	0.0156	0.0108	0.447	5	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.3308	1.5079	3.815	3.8308	0.0014	0.0033	0.0276	0.0629	0.053	0.032	0.276	1	3	1
0.004	0.2717	0.2993	0.5237	1.6378	3.189	0.0014	0.0453	0.025	0.0219	0.0228	0.0266	0.3995	1	3	1
0	0.2048	0.2284	0.5	1.7835	3.4961	0	0.0342	0.0191	0.0209	0.0248	0.0292	0.3962	1	3	1
0	0.2048	0.2284	0.5	1.7835	3.4961	0	0.0342	0.0191	0.0209	0.0248	0.0292	0.3962	1	3	1
0	0.2048	0.2284	0.5	1.7835	3.4961	0	0.0342	0.0191	0.0209	0.0248	0.0292	0.3962	1	3	1
0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0.0512	0.2993	1.2402	0.0027	0.002	0.001	0.0022	0.0042	0.0104	0.4921	1	3	1
0	0.0867	0.0906	0.3583	1.4922	2.7835	0	0.0145	0.0076	0.015	0.0208	0.0232	0.4973	1	3	1
0.1497	0.4567	0.7638	1.626	4.8859	5.0788	0.0499	0.0762	0.0637	0.0678	0.0679	0.0424	0.5181	1	2	1
0.004	0.063	0.063	0.1812	0.8977	2.7914	0.0014	0.0105	0.0053	0.0076	0.0125	0.0233	0.4045	1	3	1
0.0197	0.0237	0.2756	1.2638	5.4371	5.5355	0.0066	0.004	0.023	0.0527	0.0756	0.0462	0.3708	4	3	1
0.0119	0.0394	0.1693	0.3426	2.5552	3.7008	0.004	0.0066	0.0142	0.0143	0.0355	0.0309	0.5184	4	3	1
0	0.2087	0.3859	0.7166	3.5	4.6457	0	0.0348	0.0322	0.0299	0.0487	0.0388	0.5063	4	3	1
0	0.3111	0.5	0.7914	3.6497	4.4882	0	0.0519	0.0417	0.033	0.0507	0.0375	0.518	2	4	1
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.1693	2.1182	5.8623	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0071	0.0295	0.0489	0.4008	6	3	1
0	0	0.004	0.9016	3.6339	3.689	0	0	0.0004	0.0376	0.0505	0.0308	0.502	4	4	1
0.0827	0.1221	0.2441	2.4292	3.8347	4.0473	0.0276	0.0204	0.0204	0.1013	0.0533	0.0338	0.3761	1	3	1
0.0119	0.1615	0.5158	2.1418	3.7717	3.8977	0.004	0.027	0.043	0.0893	0.0524	0.0325	0.3565	1	3	1
0.0079	0.063	0.6103	1.7245	3.5276	3.5906	0.0027	0.0105	0.0509	0.0719	0.049	0.03	0.4021	1	3	1
0	0	0.004	0.1536	4.0709	4.1457	0	0	0.0004	0.0064	0.0566	0.0346	0.293	1	3	1
0.0827	0.1378	0.1772	0.4449	2.8347	4.9016	0.0276	0.023	0.0148	0.0186	0.0394	0.0409	0.5163	6	3	1
0.3662	0.4095	0.5709	3.189	3.9371	4.4528	0.1221	0.0683	0.0476	0.1329	0.0547	0.0372	0	4	4	1
0	0	0	1.8268	4.6733	6.3032	0	0	0	0.0762	0.065	0.0526	0.348	5	4	1
0	0	0	1.8268	4.6733	6.3032	0	0	0	0.0762	0.065	0.0526	0.348	4	3	1
0.1221	0.2796	0.7284	1.2993	2.9252	3.8544	0.0407	0.0466	0.0607	0.0542	0.0407	0.0322	0.4251	4	3	1
0.1221	0.2796	0.7284	1.2993	2.9252	3.8544	0.0407	0.0466	0.0607	0.0542	0.0407	0.0322	0.4251	4	3	1
0.3741	0.4882	1.6221	2.3504	4.441	5.4607	0.1247	0.0814	0.1352	0.098	0.0617	0.0456	0.348	6	3	1
0	0	0	4.9567	7.7796	9.3898	0	0	0	0.2066	0.1081	0.0783	0.4294	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0197	0.0867	1.4567	2.1063	2.2717	0.004	0.0033	0.0073	0.0607	0.0293	0.019	0.433	4	3	1
0.4213	0.5827	1.3111	1.8701	3.2402	3.6024	0.1405	0.0972	0.1093	0.078	0.0451	0.0301	0.459	4	3	1
0.3111	0.5788	0.6772	0.7599	3.0315	3.4528	0.1037	0.0965	0.0565	0.0317	0.0422	0.0288	0.302	4	4	1
0.3268	0.5788	1.0709	1.7166	2.4961	2.941	0.109	0.0965	0.0893	0.0716	0.0347	0.0246	0.314	5	1	1
0.0276	0.0355	0.252	0.4686	1.1536	1.6378	0.0092	0.006	0.021	0.0196	0.0161	0.0137	0.464	5	1	1
0.3504	0.5434	0.8977	1.4804	2.3583	3.4922	0.1168	0.0906	0.0749	0.0617	0.0328	0.0292	0.498	4	1	1
0.3268	0.4646	0.7245	1.0473	1.8071	2.4922	0.109	0.0775	0.0604	0.0437	0.0251	0.0208	0.464	5	1	1
0	0	0	0	0.0315	0.2914	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0025	0.465	1	4	1
0.0237	0.0749	0.1497	0.5237	2.6812	3.0237	0.0079	0.0125	0.0125	0.0219	0.0373	0.0252	0.369	1	4	1
0	0	0	0.1812	0.3465	0.4843	0	0	0	0.0076	0.0049	0.0041	0.42	3	2	1
0.0552	0.2717	0.4095	0.567	1.3741	1.4449	0.0184	0.0453	0.0342	0.0237	0.0191	0.0121	0.371	4	3	1
0.004	0.0237	0.0749	0.5158	2.3071	2.5276	0.0014	0.004	0.0063	0.0215	0.0321	0.0211	0.324	4	3	1
0.004	0.0237	0.0749	0.5158	2.3071	2.5276	0.0014	0.004	0.0063	0.0215	0.0321	0.0211	0.324	4	3	1
0.0788	0.1851	0.4607	0.6024	1.0867	1.4016	0.0263	0.0309	0.0384	0.0251	0.0151	0.0117	0.479	5	3	1
0	0	0.0158	0.1457	0.9686	1.3465	0	0	0.0014	0.0061	0.0135	0.0113	0.47	4	3	1
0	0	0.0158	0.1457	0.9686	1.3465	0	0	0.0014	0.0061	0.0135	0.0113	0.47	4	3	1
0	0	0.0158	0.1457	0.9686	1.3465	0	0	0.0014	0.0061	0.0135	0.0113	0.47	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0276	0.0827	0.2087	0.9174	1.1615	0.004	0.0046	0.0069	0.0087	0.0128	0.0097	0	6	3	1
0.4292	0.5945	1.063	2.3662	3.9528	5.2008	0.1431	0.0991	0.0886	0.0986	0.0549	0.0434	0.5107	6	3	1

0.2914	0.8426	1.4371	3.5749	7.2796	9.6103	0.0972	0.1405	0.1198	0.149	0.1012	0.0801	0.4026	5	3	1
0.2008	0.6733	0.9607	2.6339	5.8662	7.6693	0.067	0.1123	0.0801	0.1098	0.0815	0.064	0.4035	5	4	1
0.0749	0.2441	0.3741	1.0552	3.0355	3.4961	0.025	0.0407	0.0312	0.044	0.0422	0.0292	0.3471	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.252	1.1733	3.2205	0	0	0	0.0105	0.0163	0.0269	0.4354	4	4	1
0.1615	0.2245	0.5355	0.7441	1.4882	2.4725	0.0539	0.0375	0.0447	0.0311	0.0207	0.0207	0.344	5	4	1
0.0119	0.0276	0.1182	0.1615	0.5473	1.9331	0.004	0.0046	0.0099	0.0068	0.0077	0.0162	0.4251	4	3	1
0.0237	0.2402	1	2.2796	2.8898	3.0394	0.0079	0.0401	0.0834	0.095	0.0402	0.0254	0.396	5	3	1
0.4882	1.0473	1.7638	2.9646	5.4292	5.8741	0.1628	0.1746	0.147	0.1236	0.0755	0.049	0.5189	5	3	1
0.2835	0.693	1.2284	2.2481	3.5473	3.693	0.0945	0.1155	0.1024	0.0937	0.0493	0.0308	0.3991	4	3	1
0.7481	1.4174	1.8701	2.5906	3.0237	3.9331	0.2494	0.2363	0.1559	0.108	0.042	0.0328	0.4999	4	3	1
0.4882	0.9922	1.4961	2.0749	2.441	3.2914	0.1628	0.1654	0.1247	0.0865	0.034	0.0275	0.496	6	3	1
0.5276	0.9764	1.7875	3.6812	4.8623	6.941	0.1759	0.1628	0.149	0.1534	0.0676	0.0579	0.3163	6	4	1
0.0119	0.0197	0.1812	1.189	1.693	2.189	0.004	0.0033	0.0151	0.0496	0.0236	0.0183	0	4	4	1
0	0.0079	0.1772	1.0749	1.5709	2.0867	0	0.0014	0.0148	0.0448	0.0219	0.0174	0.414	2	3	1
0.0591	0.1142	0.5197	3.7323	4.5827	4.8426	0.0197	0.0191	0.0434	0.1556	0.0637	0.0404	0.5041	6	4	1
0.067	0.1733	0.6733	3.0827	3.9174	4.2481	0.0224	0.0289	0.0562	0.1285	0.0545	0.0355	0.42	6	4	1
0.067	0.1575	0.5079	2.5945	3.4331	3.8071	0.0224	0.0263	0.0424	0.1082	0.0477	0.0318	0.5145	4	3	1
0.0237	0.1221	0.5709	2.8308	3.7126	3.8386	0.0079	0.0204	0.0476	0.118	0.0516	0.032	0.407	6	3	1
0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.0827	4.0512	4.7402	0.0053	0.0027	0.0014	0.0035	0.0563	0.0396	0.416	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.1851	2.3859	6.0749	0	0	0	0.0078	0.0332	0.0507	0.5037	6	3	1
0	0	0.0158	0.1969	3.1693	7.004	0	0	0.0014	0.0083	0.0441	0.0584	0.4291	4	4	1
0.1536	0.3032	1.1615	3.0591	4.6536	5.189	0.0512	0.0506	0.0968	0.1275	0.0647	0.0433	0.5147	4	4	1
0.1536	0.3032	1.1615	3.0591	4.6536	5.189	0.0512	0.0506	0.0968	0.1275	0.0647	0.0433	0.5147	6	3	1
0.3623	1.2402	2.2756	4.5315	5.7048	6.2441	0.1208	0.2067	0.1897	0.1889	0.0793	0.0521	0.5162	2	4	1
0.2441	0.4725	4.9371	10.7599	12.3544	13.6772	0.0814	0.0788	0.4115	0.4484	0.1716	0.114	0.3975	1	1	1
0.0276	0.315	2.0749	8.9252	11.3741	11.9961	0.0092	0.0525	0.173	0.3719	0.158	0.1	0.3129	2	4	1
0.3308	0.63	1.8504	9.0867	11.3859	11.9371	0.1103	0.105	0.1542	0.3787	0.1582	0.0995	0.3474	2	4	1
0.0788	0.4449	1.7087	9.9804	11.9882	12.4686	0.0263	0.0742	0.1424	0.4159	0.1666	0.104	0.3896	6	4	1
0.2008	0.5709	2.756	6.9449	8.6575	9.2166	0.067	0.0952	0.2297	0.2894	0.1203	0.0769	0.3754	5	4	1
0.0276	0.3426	1.8229	7.7087	10.1772	10.5473	0.0092	0.0571	0.152	0.3212	0.1414	0.0879	0.4122	4	4	1
0.5119	0.9292	1.7914	9.7835	12.5315	13.2875	0.1707	0.1549	0.1493	0.4077	0.1741	0.1108	0.3653	5	3	1
0.13	0.2323	1.2717	4.8819	8.6733	9.8229	0.0434	0.0388	0.106	0.2035	0.1205	0.0819	0.5186	4	1	1
0.0276	0.063	0.6536	3.8426	9.5552	10.7993	0.0092	0.0105	0.0545	0.1602	0.1328	0.09	0.5187	1	1	1
0.0237	0.0867	0.6733	2.7048	6.8898	9.2245	0.0079	0.0145	0.0562	0.1127	0.0957	0.0769	0.5189	5	3	1
0.1733	0.2914	0.4252	0.6418	4.9961	5.7205	0.0578	0.0486	0.0355	0.0268	0.0694	0.0477	0.5027	5	3	1
0.3426	0.8701	1.3977	3.4764	5.0512	5.7993	0.1142	0.1451	0.1165	0.1449	0.0702	0.0484	0.5151	5	3	1
0.3426	0.8701	1.3977	3.4764	5.0512	5.7993	0.1142	0.1451	0.1165	0.1449	0.0702	0.0484	0.5151	5	3	1
0.3426	0.8701	1.3977	3.4764	5.0512	5.7993	0.1142	0.1451	0.1165	0.1449	0.0702	0.0484	0.5151	5	3	1
0	0.0237	0.1575	5.7126	9.1221	9.5945	0	0.004	0.0132	0.2381	0.1267	0.08	0.3797	4	3	1
0.2205	0.4764	1.1851	2.4213	4.004	4.8701	0.0735	0.0794	0.0988	0.1009	0.0557	0.0406	0.4823	1	4	1
0.2245	0.3544	0.4764	0.9252	4.4725	5.7599	0.0749	0.0591	0.0397	0.0386	0.0622	0.048	0.3787	3	3	1
0.0434	0.0591	0.0827	0.2599	4.693	6.5197	0.0145	0.0099	0.0069	0.0109	0.0652	0.0544	0.4119	4	3	1
0.1378	0.2678	0.4213	0.9843	4.2441	5.1733	0.046	0.0447	0.0352	0.0411	0.059	0.0432	0.3278	3	3	1
0.0394	0.0985	0.193	0.3504	1.1654	1.4331	0.0132	0.0165	0.0161	0.0146	0.0162	0.012	0.483	5	3	1
0.0827	0.1812	0.441	0.9764	2.5552	2.7638	0.0276	0.0302	0.0368	0.0407	0.0355	0.0231	0.387	5	3	1
0.0434	0.1103	0.3938	0.9213	2.6142	3.0906	0.0145	0.0184	0.0329	0.0384	0.0364	0.0258	0.479	1	3	1
0.0827	0.1812	0.441	0.9764	2.5552	2.7638	0.0276	0.0302	0.0368	0.0407	0.0355	0.0231	0.387	4	3	1
0.2481	0.2875	0.4843	0.8741	2.5749	2.7363	0.0827	0.048	0.0404	0.0365	0.0358	0.0229	0.493	4	3	1

0.2638	0.3701	0.8229	1.1378	1.752	1.878	0.088	0.0617	0.0686	0.0475	0.0244	0.0157	0.498	5	3	1
0.0394	0.0788	0.1339	1.1969	4.63	6.5158	0.0132	0.0132	0.0112	0.0499	0.0644	0.0543	0.5188	4	3	1
0.4095	0.7284	1.2245	2.6575	3.8741	4.5315	0.1365	0.1214	0.1021	0.1108	0.0539	0.0378	0.4936	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.0276	1.6063	8.4292	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0224	0.0703	0.5164	4	3	1
0.3859	0.7678	1.2678	2.5591	3.7363	4.315	0.1287	0.128	0.1057	0.1067	0.0519	0.036	0.473	4	3	1
0.0079	0.0945	0.4567	0.9489	6.9528	10.3229	0.0027	0.0158	0.0381	0.0396	0.0966	0.0861	0.5015	5	3	1
0.0079	0.0945	0.4567	0.9489	6.9528	10.3229	0.0027	0.0158	0.0381	0.0396	0.0966	0.0861	0.5015	5	3	1
0.0079	0.0945	0.4567	0.9489	6.9528	10.3229	0.0027	0.0158	0.0381	0.0396	0.0966	0.0861	0.5015	4	3	1
0.0079	0.0945	0.4567	0.9489	6.9528	10.3229	0.0027	0.0158	0.0381	0.0396	0.0966	0.0861	0.5015	5	3	1
0	0.0867	0.315	0.6536	6.504	10	0	0.0145	0.0263	0.0273	0.0904	0.0834	0.5163	1	3	1
0	0.0867	0.315	0.6536	6.504	10	0	0.0145	0.0263	0.0273	0.0904	0.0834	0.5163	4	1	1
0.0197	0.0985	0.6142	2.0079	8.3071	10.315	0.0066	0.0165	0.0512	0.0837	0.1154	0.086	0.3558	1	1	1
0.0197	0.0985	0.6142	2.0079	8.3071	10.315	0.0066	0.0165	0.0512	0.0837	0.1154	0.086	0.3558	6	3	1
0.1575	0.2323	0.3465	1.2796	1.6182	2.3859	0.0525	0.0388	0.0289	0.0534	0.0225	0.0199	0.5084	6	3	1
0.2087	0.3071	0.5749	1.8347	2.1575	2.3859	0.0696	0.0512	0.048	0.0765	0.03	0.0199	0.496	4	3	1
0.2087	0.3071	0.5749	1.8347	2.1575	2.3859	0.0696	0.0512	0.048	0.0765	0.03	0.0199	0.496	4	3	1
0.1339	0.2087	0.3504	1.5	1.7363	2.2599	0.0447	0.0348	0.0292	0.0625	0.0242	0.0189	0.5	4	3	1
1.7126	3.2126	4.7717	6.6182	8.7481	10.0119	0.5709	0.5355	0.3977	0.2758	0.1216	0.0835	0.5186	5	3	1
1.1142	2.256	3.0552	4.5237	6.3386	6.756	0.3714	0.376	0.2546	0.1885	0.0881	0.0563	0.4191	6	3	1
1.1142	2.256	3.0552	4.5237	6.3386	6.756	0.3714	0.376	0.2546	0.1885	0.0881	0.0563	0.4191	4	1	1
1.4213	2.441	3.1142	4.9449	6.4134	6.7363	0.4738	0.4069	0.2596	0.2061	0.0891	0.0562	0.3123	4	1	1
0.0749	0.2284	0.4528	1.2599	4.9292	6.0945	0.025	0.0381	0.0378	0.0525	0.0685	0.0508	0.5191	4	3	1
0.0591	0.2205	0.5945	1.563	6.3701	7.6024	0.0197	0.0368	0.0496	0.0652	0.0885	0.0634	0.5163	4	1	1
0.6497	1.2363	1.6418	2.5276	4.3386	4.8583	0.2166	0.2061	0.1369	0.1054	0.0603	0.0405	0.4998	4	1	1
0.6063	1.2441	1.7481	2.5355	3.693	4.2205	0.2021	0.2074	0.1457	0.1057	0.0513	0.0352	0.4215	1	1	1
0.6063	1.2441	1.7481	2.5355	3.693	4.2205	0.2021	0.2074	0.1457	0.1057	0.0513	0.0352	0.4215	6	1	1
0.0394	0.13	0.5867	1.1378	4.4764	5.1969	0.0132	0.0217	0.0489	0.0475	0.0622	0.0434	0.4267	5	1	1
0.0867	0.1693	0.5827	1.5355	5.3977	5.9489	0.0289	0.0283	0.0486	0.064	0.075	0.0496	0	4	1	1
0.0158	0.0749	0.5119	1.1182	4.6497	5.8071	0.0053	0.0125	0.0427	0.0466	0.0646	0.0484	0.4289	4	1	1
0.0158	0.0749	0.5119	1.1182	4.6497	5.8071	0.0053	0.0125	0.0427	0.0466	0.0646	0.0484	0.4289	5	3	1
0	0	0.0197	0.3465	7.0394	14.3623	0	0	0.0017	0.0145	0.0978	0.1197	0.4293	6	3	1
0	0	0.0197	0.3465	7.0394	14.3623	0	0	0.0017	0.0145	0.0978	0.1197	0.4293	4	3	1
0.3859	0.6575	1.1457	1.4804	2.4174	3.0434	0.1287	0.1096	0.0955	0.0617	0.0336	0.0254	0.483	3	2	1
0.0394	0.3977	0.5906	1.3426	5.941	6.7796	0.0132	0.0663	0.0493	0.056	0.0826	0.0565	0.3957	4	3	1
1.2166	2.2323	2.7363	3.5552	4.6693	4.9252	0.4056	0.3721	0.2281	0.1482	0.0649	0.0411	0.475	4	3	1
1.0473	2.0197	2.5473	3.3898	4.7796	5.193	0.3491	0.3367	0.2123	0.1413	0.0664	0.0433	0.4763	6	3	1
1.7756	3.3268	4.1654	5.0079	6.0434	6.7205	0.5919	0.5545	0.3472	0.2087	0.084	0.0561	0.4121	3	3	1
0.9607	1.8977	2.4528	3.1536	4.5394	4.9686	0.3203	0.3163	0.2044	0.1314	0.0631	0.0415	0.4781	4	3	1
1	1.9686	2.4567	3.1851	4.8662	5.6142	0.3334	0.3281	0.2048	0.1328	0.0676	0.0468	0.4584	3	3	1
0.9607	1.8977	2.4528	3.1536	4.5394	4.9686	0.3203	0.3163	0.2044	0.1314	0.0631	0.0415	0.4781	3	3	1
0.9607	1.8977	2.4528	3.1536	4.5394	4.9686	0.3203	0.3163	0.2044	0.1314	0.0631	0.0415	0.4781	3	3	1
1.0473	2.0197	2.5473	3.3898	4.7796	5.193	0.3491	0.3367	0.2123	0.1413	0.0664	0.0433	0.4763	5	3	1
0.7245	1.3347	2.0552	2.7284	5.5394	6.5473	0.2415	0.2225	0.1713	0.1137	0.077	0.0546	0.4208	5	4	1
0	0.0119	0.0276	0.6536	1.4331	2.0237	0	0.002	0.0023	0.0273	0.02	0.0169	0.418	1	3	1
0.4174	0.563	1.2323	1.5119	2.2953	2.6378	0.1392	0.0939	0.1027	0.063	0.0319	0.022	0.378	4	4	1
0.2166	0.5079	1.6024	3.9489	5.2914	6.3623	0.0722	0.0847	0.1336	0.1646	0.0735	0.0531	0.4162	6	4	1
0.1536	0.4292	0.7441	2.5434	4.2284	5.1733	0.0512	0.0716	0.0621	0.106	0.0588	0.0432	0.4681	5	4	1
0.1221	0.63	1.0473	2.9134	5.0473	7.0237	0.0407	0.105	0.0873	0.1214	0.0702	0.0586	0.3661	6	4	1

0.2048	0.6221	0.8701	2.1536	4.3111	5.6418	0.0683	0.1037	0.0726	0.0898	0.0599	0.0471	0.4199	1	3	1
0.0749	0.1772	0.504	1.2638	3.1182	3.9567	0.025	0.0296	0.042	0.0527	0.0434	0.033	0.371	6	3	1
0.193	0.3583	0.5119	1.2717	3.2796	4.563	0.0644	0.0598	0.0427	0.053	0.0456	0.0381	0	5	4	1
0.2126	0.441	0.8859	2	4.2323	5.5827	0.0709	0.0735	0.0739	0.0834	0.0588	0.0466	0.3856	4	3	1
0.126	0.3898	1.7441	4.9843	7.9961	9.3662	0.042	0.065	0.1454	0.2077	0.1111	0.0781	0.3892	5	3	1
0.004	0.0591	0.1182	0.2953	5.0906	7.4371	0.0014	0.0099	0.0099	0.0124	0.0708	0.062	0.5174	4	3	1
0.004	0.0315	0.0749	0.2599	5.0355	7.3898	0.0014	0.0053	0.0063	0.0109	0.07	0.0616	0.4663	4	3	1
0.004	0.0315	0.0749	0.2599	5.0355	7.3898	0.0014	0.0053	0.0063	0.0109	0.07	0.0616	0.4663	4	4	1
0.0119	0.0591	0.1536	0.5158	5.3701	8.5	0.004	0.0099	0.0128	0.0215	0.0746	0.0709	0.3132	4	4	1
0.0119	0.0591	0.1536	0.5158	5.3701	8.5	0.004	0.0099	0.0128	0.0215	0.0746	0.0709	0.3132	6	4	1
0.0119	0.0591	0.1536	0.5158	5.3701	8.5	0.004	0.0099	0.0128	0.0215	0.0746	0.0709	0.3132	4	3	1
0	0	0.004	0.1339	3.1063	5.0512	0	0	0.0004	0.0056	0.0432	0.0421	0.518	5	3	1
0	0	0.0394	0.1457	5.1063	6.8189	0	0	0.0033	0.0061	0.071	0.0569	0.5177	6	4	1
0.0749	0.2087	0.3701	1.13	6.0315	6.63	0.025	0.0348	0.0309	0.0471	0.0838	0.0553	0.3753	5	4	1
0.0315	0.13	0.2008	0.7875	5.9725	6.7953	0.0105	0.0217	0.0168	0.0329	0.083	0.0567	0.3777	1	3	1
0.0315	0.13	0.2008	0.7875	5.9725	6.7953	0.0105	0.0217	0.0168	0.0329	0.083	0.0567	0.3777	4	4	1
0.0591	0.1182	0.4095	1.9371	4.2481	5.3347	0.0197	0.0197	0.0342	0.0808	0.0591	0.0445	0.5166	4	3	1
0	0.004	0.3662	1.7441	3.0434	4.8386	0	0.0007	0.0306	0.0727	0.0423	0.0404	0.5175	5	3	1
0.0237	0.0394	0.126	0.252	0.378	0.8938	0.0079	0.0066	0.0105	0.0105	0.0053	0.0075	0.51	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0197	0.0237	0.0237	0.4843	0.6339	0.004	0.0033	0.002	0.001	0.0068	0.0053	0.3883	4	3	1
0.0119	0.0355	0.0473	0.0552	0.5906	1.4725	0.004	0.006	0.004	0.0023	0.0083	0.0123	0.4121	5	2	1
0.0197	0.0788	0.2008	0.7875	1.1457	1.563	0.0066	0.0132	0.0168	0.0329	0.016	0.0131	0.417	5	1	1
0.0197	0.0788	0.2008	0.7875	1.1457	1.563	0.0066	0.0132	0.0168	0.0329	0.016	0.0131	0.417	1	2	1
0.13	0.1969	0.2599	0.3032	0.6851	0.8308	0.0434	0.0329	0.0217	0.0127	0.0096	0.007	0.396	1	3	1
0.13	0.1969	0.2599	0.3032	0.6851	0.8308	0.0434	0.0329	0.0217	0.0127	0.0096	0.007	0.396	1	2	1
0.1182	0.1536	0.1615	0.2008	0.4331	0.563	0.0394	0.0256	0.0135	0.0084	0.0061	0.0047	0.391	2	2	1
0.13	0.1969	0.2599	0.3032	0.6851	0.8308	0.0434	0.0329	0.0217	0.0127	0.0096	0.007	0.396	4	3	1
0.004	0.0158	0.0158	0.0237	0.3308	0.756	0.0014	0.0027	0.0014	0.001	0.0046	0.0063	0.509	2	3	1
0	0.0197	0.0276	0.2599	0.4134	0.6812	0	0.0033	0.0023	0.0109	0.0058	0.0057	0.497	2	3	1
0	0.0197	0.0276	0.2599	0.4134	0.6812	0	0.0033	0.0023	0.0109	0.0058	0.0057	0.497	4	3	1
0.0079	0.0276	0.0434	0.3819	0.6654	0.9528	0.0027	0.0046	0.0037	0.016	0.0093	0.008	0.495	4	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0315	0.0394	0.7166	1.1497	0.0014	0.0033	0.0027	0.0017	0.01	0.0096	0.507	4	1	1
0.0119	0.0276	0.0552	0.0827	0.6221	1.4331	0.004	0.0046	0.0046	0.0035	0.0087	0.012	0.405	4	3	1
0.004	0.0079	0.0079	0.0197	0.7087	1.2835	0.0014	0.0014	0.0007	0.0009	0.0099	0.0107	0.504	4	1	1
0.0119	0.0276	0.0552	0.0827	0.6221	1.4331	0.004	0.0046	0.0046	0.0035	0.0087	0.012	0.405	1	3	1
0.0237	0.0552	0.0709	0.1024	1.0591	1.63	0.0079	0.0092	0.006	0.0043	0.0148	0.0136	0.5104	4	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.0079	0.0394	0.6378	0.878	0.0014	0.0007	0.0007	0.0017	0.0089	0.0074	0.5124	4	3	1
0	0	0.063	0.0985	0.6615	1.0827	0	0	0.0053	0.0042	0.0092	0.0091	0.5103	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.0709	1.2441	1.4922	0	0	0	0.003	0.0173	0.0125	0.4781	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.0158	1.2953	1.5788	0	0	0	0.0007	0.018	0.0132	0.489	3	3	1
0	0	0	0.0158	1.2953	1.5788	0	0	0	0.0007	0.018	0.0132	0.489	4	3	1
0	0	0.004	0.0355	1.0276	1.315	0	0	0.0004	0.0015	0.0143	0.011	0.4903	3	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0197	0.189	0.5945	1.0985	0.0014	0.0033	0.0017	0.0079	0.0083	0.0092	0.506	4	3	1
0.0197	0.0473	0.0473	0.1457	0.4882	1.0788	0.0066	0.0079	0.004	0.0061	0.0068	0.009	0.497	1	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0197	0.189	0.5945	1.0985	0.0014	0.0033	0.0017	0.0079	0.0083	0.0092	0.506	3	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0197	0.189	0.5945	1.0985	0.0014	0.0033	0.0017	0.0079	0.0083	0.0092	0.506	4	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0197	0.189	0.5945	1.0985	0.0014	0.0033	0.0017	0.0079	0.0083	0.0092	0.506	4	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0197	0.189	0.5945	1.0985	0.0014	0.0033	0.0017	0.0079	0.0083	0.0092	0.506	4	3	1

0.0197	0.0473	0.0473	0.1457	0.4882	1.0788	0.0066	0.0079	0.004	0.0061	0.0068	0.009	0.497	1	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0197	0.189	0.5945	1.0985	0.0014	0.0033	0.0017	0.0079	0.0083	0.0092	0.506	3	3	1
0.0197	0.0473	0.0473	0.1457	0.4882	1.0788	0.0066	0.0079	0.004	0.0061	0.0068	0.009	0.497	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.0119	0.8977	1.1615	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0125	0.0097	0.404	4	4	1
0	0	0	0	8.6772	14.0315	0	0	0	0	0.1206	0.117	0.4292	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.4607	0.4686	0.4922	0	0	0	0.0192	0.0066	0.0042	0.5	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.4607	0.4686	0.4922	0	0	0	0.0192	0.0066	0.0042	0.5	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.4607	0.4686	0.4922	0	0	0	0.0192	0.0066	0.0042	0.5	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.4607	0.4686	0.4922	0	0	0	0.0192	0.0066	0.0042	0.5	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.2599	0.2599	0.2638	0	0	0	0.0109	0.0037	0.0022	0.4083	1	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.8071	1.8544	2.7402	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0337	0.0258	0.0229	0.4273	5	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.8071	1.8544	2.7402	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0337	0.0258	0.0229	0.4273	6	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.8071	1.8544	2.7402	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0337	0.0258	0.0229	0.4273	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.0119	0.0276	0.063	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0004	0.0006	0.411	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.0119	0.0276	0.063	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0004	0.0006	0.411	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.3741	0.3938	0.3938	0	0	0	0.0156	0.0055	0.0033	0.409	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.3741	0.3938	0.3938	0	0	0	0.0156	0.0055	0.0033	0.409	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.126	0.2048	0.2756	0	0	0	0.0053	0.0029	0.0023	0.4035	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.2599	0.2599	0.2638	0	0	0	0.0109	0.0037	0.0022	0.4083	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.0315	0.0355	0.0512	0	0	0	0.0014	0.0005	0.0005	0.4944	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.2599	0.2599	0.2638	0	0	0	0.0109	0.0037	0.0022	0.4083	1	1	1
0	0	0	0.2756	0.7599	0.9764	0	0	0	0.0115	0.0106	0.0082	0.2963	3	1	1
0	0	0	0.2756	0.7599	0.9764	0	0	0	0.0115	0.0106	0.0082	0.2963	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.004	0.0315	0.1221	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0005	0.0011	0.494	5	1	1
0	0	0	0.5945	1.3426	1.626	0	0	0	0.0248	0.0187	0.0136	0.4075	5	4	1
0.2363	0.4725	1.0434	5.0749	5.5355	6.2599	0.0788	0.0788	0.087	0.2115	0.0769	0.0522	0.413	5	4	1
0.315	0.9095	1.9134	7.4843	8.1142	8.4134	0.105	0.1516	0.1595	0.3119	0.1127	0.0702	0.41	5	4	1
0.315	0.9095	1.9134	7.4843	8.1142	8.4134	0.105	0.1516	0.1595	0.3119	0.1127	0.0702	0.41	5	4	1
0.0079	0.0158	0.0355	0.2481	7.5906	7.626	0.0027	0.0027	0.003	0.0104	0.1055	0.0636	0.4294	5	1	1
0.0079	0.0158	0.0355	0.2481	7.5906	7.626	0.0027	0.0027	0.003	0.0104	0.1055	0.0636	0.4294	5	4	1
0.0473	0.0552	0.067	0.2993	1.567	3.1063	0.0158	0.0092	0.0056	0.0125	0.0218	0.0259	0.4293	1	3	1
0	0	0.2126	4.1575	5.7205	6.7993	0	0	0.0178	0.1733	0.0795	0.0567	0.513	4	3	1
0	0.0512	0.1969	0.3189	1.9725	4.4134	0	0.0086	0.0165	0.0133	0.0274	0.0368	0.414	4	3	1
0	0	0.0788	0.3741	1.4528	2.4095	0	0	0.0066	0.0156	0.0202	0.0201	0.415	4	3	1
0	0	0.0788	0.3741	1.4528	2.4095	0	0	0.0066	0.0156	0.0202	0.0201	0.415	4	3	1
0	0.004	0.2126	0.4134	1.378	2.3347	0	0.0007	0.0178	0.0173	0.0192	0.0195	0.423	2	1	1
0.1575	0.189	0.6457	0.7441	1.8898	2.9607	0.0525	0.0315	0.0539	0.0311	0.0263	0.0247	0.319	2	1	1
0	0.004	0.2284	0.378	1.8111	2.6575	0	0.0007	0.0191	0.0158	0.0252	0.0222	0.3182	3	3	1
0	0	0	0.0473	1.1575	1.5	0	0	0	0.002	0.0161	0.0125	0.486	6	4	1
3.5197	6.7205	13.8504	16.2245	17.4174	21.1378	1.1733	1.1201	1.1542	0.6761	0.242	0.1762	0.4295	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.1339	0.8701	2.3583	0	0	0	0.0056	0.0121	0.0197	0.512	1		1
0.0276	0.126	0.3701	1.2245	2.4725	3.4016	0.0092	0.021	0.0309	0.0511	0.0344	0.0284	0.43	5	3	1
0.0276	0.1142	0.189	0.5512	1.6575	1.6812	0.0092	0.0191	0.0158	0.023	0.0231	0.0141	0.415	4		1
0	0.0315	0.2835	1.2796	1.7087	1.7284	0	0.0053	0.0237	0.0534	0.0238	0.0145	0.4204	2	3	1
0	0.0158	0.0355	0.2914	1.7402	3.0552	0	0.0027	0.003	0.0122	0.0242	0.0255	0.429	4	4	1
0.3859	1.1536	4.6024	9.8544	14.0276	15.7835	0.1287	0.1923	0.3836	0.4106	0.1949	0.1316	0.2783	2	3	1
0	0.004	0.1142	0.8189	3.1221	3.2245	0	0.0007	0.0096	0.0342	0.0434	0.0269	0.4334	6	4	1
0.0079	0.0119	0.0158	0.5119	2.9489	4.8583	0.0027	0.002	0.0014	0.0214	0.041	0.0405	0.427	2	3	1

0.0079	0.0079	0.063	0.2008	9.2953	13.063	0.0027	0.0014	0.0053	0.0084	0.1292	0.1089	0.5175	5	4	1
0.7323	1.4056	4.8504	7.2914	7.626	7.9213	0.2441	0.2343	0.4042	0.3039	0.106	0.0661	0.4809	5	4	1
0.5709	1.4489	2.7599	6.6654	13.2993	13.9174	0.1903	0.2415	0.23	0.2778	0.1848	0.116	0.3287	6	4	1
0	0.0197	0.1733	0.7993	3.5788	3.8544	0	0.0033	0.0145	0.0334	0.0498	0.0322	0.4083	4	1	1
0.0119	0.0119	0.0119	0.1378	0.6221	1.0434	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.0058	0.0087	0.0087	0.421	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.0158	0.8898	4.7402	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0124	0.0396	0.4696	6	4	1
0.9331	2.2835	5.4882	6.9489	8.256	9.2126	0.3111	0.3806	0.4574	0.2896	0.1147	0.0768	0.4688	5	3	1
0.0591	0.1221	0.2796	0.5827	2.4489	3.5197	0.0197	0.0204	0.0233	0.0243	0.0341	0.0294	0.4278	1	3	1
0.4567	0.8859	1.7717	4.9764	6.6693	7.504	0.1523	0.1477	0.1477	0.2074	0.0927	0.0626	0.4844	2	3	1
0	0	0	0.689	3.7048	3.7638	0	0	0	0.0288	0.0515	0.0314	0.436	5	3	1
0.6615	1.2678	4.0749	5.626	6.5473	7.5001	0.2205	0.2113	0.3396	0.2345	0.091	0.0626	0.4923	5	4	1
0	0.0197	0.0867	0.8859	1.8347	2.815	0	0.0033	0.0073	0.037	0.0255	0.0235	0.4933	4	1	1
0.0827	0.3938	0.4646	0.8189	1.0276	2.13	0.0276	0.0657	0.0388	0.0342	0.0143	0.0178	0.324	4	3	1
0	0.0237	0.0473	1.2638	5.4882	8.4528	0	0.004	0.004	0.0527	0.0763	0.0705	0.4999	1	3	1
0.0315	0.0473	0.1536	0.5355	2.1615	2.9764	0.0105	0.0079	0.0128	0.0224	0.0301	0.0249	0.511	4	4	1
0	0.0119	0.0315	0.5985	1.7166	2.7481	0	0.002	0.0027	0.025	0.0239	0.023	0.507	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.3189	0.5276	3.9016	0	0	0	0.0133	0.0074	0.0326	0.4624	6	3	1
0.0788	0.2087	0.2993	1.4567	3.2126	3.5906	0.0263	0.0348	0.025	0.0607	0.0447	0.03	0.3805	4	3	1
0.4646	0.752	1.189	1.2953	1.8308	2.2717	0.1549	0.1254	0.0991	0.054	0.0255	0.019	0.161	6	3	1
0.0079	0.0315	0.193	0.5	1.5709	2.4095	0.0027	0.0053	0.0161	0.0209	0.0219	0.0201	0.496	5	4	1
0	0	0	0.0158	0.4095	5.756	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0057	0.048	0.5133	1	3	1
0.0473	0.0985	0.1969	1.0985	2.0709	2.563	0.0158	0.0165	0.0165	0.0458	0.0288	0.0214	0.4888	4	4	1
0	0	0.0355	0.0749	0.1457	0.2323	0	0	0.003	0.0032	0.0021	0.002	0.328	1	3	1
0.0473	0.0749	0.1654	0.4804	3.2008	4.567	0.0158	0.0125	0.0138	0.0201	0.0445	0.0381	0.429	4	4	1
0	0.0158	0.0315	1.6063	6.4056	8.9804	0	0.0027	0.0027	0.067	0.089	0.0749	0.429	1		1
1.2048	1.9567	2.3938	3.8111	6.563	11.9449	0.4016	0.3262	0.1995	0.1588	0.0912	0.0996	0.3713	6	3	1
0.0197	0.063	0.2048	0.7323	5.5985	7.1733	0.0066	0.0105	0.0171	0.0306	0.0778	0.0598	0.4375	2	3	1
0	0	0	0.004	0.7481	1.9252	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0104	0.0161	0.351	4	4	1
0.4686	1.0827	2.2402	4.3544	5.5788	6.2481	0.1562	0.1805	0.1867	0.1815	0.0775	0.0521	0.4358	3	4	1
0.6693	1.189	2.3859	3.5119	8.0394	10.504	0.2231	0.1982	0.1989	0.1464	0.1117	0.0876	0.3885	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.0237	6.8938	7.0985	0	0	0	0.001	0.0958	0.0592	0.427	1	3	1
0.0394	0.1575	0.4292	1.256	2.6851	3.6615	0.0132	0.0263	0.0358	0.0524	0.0373	0.0306	0.238	6	3	1
0.1378	0.2638	0.7166	3.8859	7.189	8.2914	0.046	0.044	0.0598	0.162	0.0999	0.0691	0.4698	5	4	1
0	0.2599	0.5985	0.7481	1.6142	2.0158	0	0.0434	0.0499	0.0312	0.0225	0.0168	0.388	2	1	1
0.1182	0.1615	0.2284	1.3977	4.4252	4.6615	0.0394	0.027	0.0191	0.0583	0.0615	0.0389	0.4697	6	3	1
0.4804	0.5512	0.6497	0.9843	2.6339	3.7756	0.1602	0.0919	0.0542	0.0411	0.0366	0.0315	0.317	1	4	1
0.4292	0.752	1.2048	2.1063	3.6142	4.1339	0.1431	0.1254	0.1004	0.0878	0.0502	0.0345	0.411	5	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.0197	0.4213	2.9252	5.2953	0.0014	0.0007	0.0017	0.0176	0.0407	0.0442	0.4551	1	4	1
0	0	0	0.626	2.878	10.2008	0	0	0	0.0261	0.04	0.0851	0.3876	6	4	1
0.0591	0.1221	0.2796	0.5827	2.4489	3.5197	0.0197	0.0204	0.0233	0.0243	0.0341	0.0294	0.223	6	3	1
0.0827	0.2402	0.3032	0.3544	0.5473	0.6103	0.0276	0.0401	0.0253	0.0148	0.0077	0.0051	0.4179	1	4	1
0	0.0276	0.067	0.2245	0.8583	1.0079	0	0.0046	0.0056	0.0094	0.012	0.0084	0.3684	4	1	1
0.2323	0.3032	0.3859	1.5158	4.6339	5.0709	0.0775	0.0506	0.0322	0.0632	0.0644	0.0423	0.4281	6	4	1
0	0.0197	0.1536	0.4331	1.6575	2.5749	0	0.0033	0.0128	0.0181	0.0231	0.0215	0.3747	1	3	1
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.4804	2.2678	2.7166	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0201	0.0315	0.0227	0.5156	3	1	1
0.3819	0.4922	0.5197	0.6418	1.4725	4.6024	0.1273	0.0821	0.0434	0.0268	0.0205	0.0384	0.5148	5	1	1
0.3111	0.5119	0.756	1.3701	2.2796	3.063	0.1037	0.0854	0.063	0.0571	0.0317	0.0256	0.5036	2	4	1
0.3583	0.63	0.9056	1.441	7	8.2205	0.1195	0.105	0.0755	0.0601	0.0973	0.0686	0.5179	6	3	1

0.0315	0.1378	0.4725	0.8701	2.1536	2.3032	0.0105	0.023	0.0394	0.0363	0.03	0.0192	0.5181	6	3	1
0.0237	0.0394	0.0906	1.0276	2.3465	2.752	0.0079	0.0066	0.0076	0.0429	0.0326	0.023	0.3628	1	3	1
0.3938	1.0355	1.7678	2.6024	3.2914	3.9607	0.1313	0.1726	0.1474	0.1085	0.0458	0.0331	0.459	4	4	1
0.0197	0.0237	0.1103	0.4725	3.0906	4.9646	0.0066	0.004	0.0092	0.0197	0.043	0.0414	0.4906	4	4	1
0.0237	0.0434	0.0473	0.8032	8.3938	9.4567	0.0079	0.0073	0.004	0.0335	0.1166	0.0789	0.431	4	3	1
1.6182	3.1575	4.8071	5.7875	6.4371	9.7914	0.5394	0.5263	0.4006	0.2412	0.0895	0.0816	0.428	5	3	1
0.3623	0.693	0.9252	1.6418	5.4174	7.2993	0.1208	0.1155	0.0771	0.0685	0.0753	0.0609	0.4279	5	4	1
0.067	0.2678	2.0079	5.0867	5.4213	5.5	0.0224	0.0447	0.1674	0.212	0.0753	0.0459	0.4864	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.0197	0.0512	0.2284	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0008	0.002	0.483	5	4	1
0.0276	0.0394	0.0434	0.0827	0.9174	2.6497	0.0092	0.0066	0.0037	0.0035	0.0128	0.0221	0.4087	2	1	1
0	0.0119	0.256	0.3741	0.8544	1.7796	0	0.002	0.0214	0.0156	0.0119	0.0149	0.419	2	4	1
0.5867	1.1733	2.4607	5.2599	9.3111	10.8229	0.1956	0.1956	0.2051	0.2192	0.1294	0.0902	0.468	5	3	1
0.3859	1.1536	4.6024	9.8544	14.0276	15.7835	0.1287	0.1923	0.3836	0.4106	0.1949	0.1316	0.4815	1	3	1
0	0	0.0473	0.1339	2.13	2.5079	0	0	0.004	0.0056	0.0296	0.0209	0.3971	5	4	1
0.4843	1.3504	2.8111	6.563	15.6063	17.193	0.1615	0.2251	0.2343	0.2735	0.2168	0.1433	0.4298	2	3	1
0.067	0.1733	0.3741	2.1221	5.878	6.1812	0.0224	0.0289	0.0312	0.0885	0.0817	0.0516	0.506	5	4	1
0.1339	0.1654	0.1654	0.1812	5.4646	5.9174	0.0447	0.0276	0.0138	0.0076	0.0759	0.0494	0.426	1	2	1
0	0	0.0276	0.0434	0.2953	1.1536	0	0	0.0023	0.0019	0.0042	0.0097	0.411	1	4	1
0.0512	0.2245	0.7363	1.6575	8.5867	13.7363	0.0171	0.0375	0.0614	0.0691	0.1193	0.1145	0.4747	1	4	1
0.1536	0.2481	0.256	0.3386	1.8701	2.0709	0.0512	0.0414	0.0214	0.0142	0.026	0.0173	0.4022	4		1
0	0	0	0.504	1.3386	2.3111	0	0	0	0.021	0.0186	0.0193	0.4133	4	4	1
0.0473	0.0985	0.1969	0.689	1	1.378	0.0158	0.0165	0.0165	0.0288	0.0139	0.0115	0.4221	4	3	1
0.0119	0.0119	0.0237	0.2796	6.4725	6.9567	0.004	0.002	0.002	0.0117	0.0899	0.058	0	6	1	1
0	0	0.0394	0.063	12.8977	27.8662	0	0	0.0033	0.0027	0.1792	0.2323	0.4288	3	4	1
0	0	0	0.689	3.7048	3.7638	0	0	0	0.0288	0.0515	0.0314	0.436	3	3	1
0.0197	0.1615	0.2481	0.7126	2.9843	3.1024	0.0066	0.027	0.0207	0.0297	0.0415	0.0259	0.505	5	1	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.0867	0.0867	0.6772	0.8426	0.0027	0.0014	0.0073	0.0037	0.0095	0.0071	0.4634	6	3	1
0.0552	0.1772	2.3229	5.9016	6.0552	6.2875	0.0184	0.0296	0.1936	0.2459	0.0841	0.0524	0.484	6	4	1
0.0158	0.0709	0.3544	0.7284	1.2441	1.3623	0.0053	0.0119	0.0296	0.0304	0.0173	0.0114	0.493	5	4	1
0.067	0.2402	1.0945	4.3268	5.6457	7.4056	0.0224	0.0401	0.0913	0.1803	0.0785	0.0618	0.4335	1	4	1
0.3662	1.0394	4.4843	9.0827	9.3229	9.441	0.1221	0.1733	0.3737	0.3785	0.1295	0.0787	0.4	4	1	1
0.0119	0.0119	0.0473	0.3741	0.5355	0.6221	0.004	0.002	0.004	0.0156	0.0075	0.0052	0.363	4	4	1
0.1103	0.2756	1.0827	6.2284	11.8111	12.2166	0.0368	0.046	0.0903	0.2596	0.1641	0.1019	0.3893	4	3	1
0.0119	0.0591	0.0709	0.6221	4.4449	5.7402	0.004	0.0099	0.006	0.026	0.0618	0.0479	0.4967	3	4	1
1.1536	2.3977	3.7323	4.3859	12.6418	12.8426	0.3846	0.3997	0.3111	0.1828	0.1756	0.1071	0.4987	5	4	1
0.4449	1.004	4	7.6103	7.9449	8.1615	0.1483	0.1674	0.3334	0.3171	0.1104	0.0681	0.4071	2	1	1
0.0355	0.067	0.5512	4.8504	7.2717	9.4016	0.0119	0.0112	0.046	0.2021	0.101	0.0784	0.4808	2	4	1
0.0749	0.1378	0.1733	0.3898	1.13	5.5867	0.025	0.023	0.0145	0.0163	0.0157	0.0466	0.476	5	1	1
0	0	0.0788	0.4252	0.9174	1.1812	0	0	0.0066	0.0178	0.0128	0.0099	0.4884	1	3	1
0.0355	0.0355	0.0434	0.1851	1.3229	1.8268	0.0119	0.006	0.0037	0.0078	0.0184	0.0153	0.4207	6	4	1
0.0355	0.0867	0.1103	0.6063	2.0158	5.6182	0.0119	0.0145	0.0092	0.0253	0.028	0.0469	0.517	4	3	1
0.1024	0.256	0.7087	3.315	7.3229	8.4567	0.0342	0.0427	0.0591	0.1382	0.1018	0.0705	0.5081	3	3	1
0.3032	0.5315	0.6024	0.756	1.1615	1.6024	0.1011	0.0886	0.0502	0.0315	0.0162	0.0134	0.416	4	3	1
0.1418	0.2363	0.3859	0.7245	1.7363	2.4371	0.0473	0.0394	0.0322	0.0302	0.0242	0.0204	0.5046	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.0552	1.2087	3.9843	0	0	0	0.0023	0.0168	0.0333	0.4682	4	3	1
0.0591	0.1221	0.2796	0.5827	2.4489	3.5197	0.0197	0.0204	0.0233	0.0243	0.0341	0.0294	0.4244	4	4	1
0	0	0.0827	0.4331	0.7166	1.2245	0	0	0.0069	0.0181	0.01	0.0103	0.3852	2	3	1
0.3701	1.004	4.315	8.6812	9.3071	9.4016	0.1234	0.1674	0.3596	0.3618	0.1293	0.0784	0.4131	4	4	1

0	0.004	0.0276	0.2993	3.8741	4.0394	0	0.0007	0.0023	0.0125	0.0539	0.0337	0.3978	4	4	1
0	0.004	0.13	0.5827	3.063	3.1812	0	0.0007	0.0109	0.0243	0.0426	0.0266	0.4703	5	3	1
0	0.0591	0.1221	0.5158	1.3426	2.0394	0	0.0099	0.0102	0.0215	0.0187	0.017	0.393	6	3	1
0	0	0.0119	0.2087	3.6693	4.9174	0	0	0.001	0.0087	0.051	0.041	0.454	1	3	1
0.0315	0.0591	0.1142	0.7323	3.7717	3.9016	0.0105	0.0099	0.0096	0.0306	0.0524	0.0326	0.4429	4	3	1
0.2717	0.6221	2.5827	4.6103	4.815	4.9764	0.0906	0.1037	0.2153	0.1921	0.0669	0.0415	0.409	5	3	1
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.1575	1.5591	2.4016	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0066	0.0217	0.0201	0.506	1	4	1
0.0158	0.0552	0.0906	0.1024	0.126	0.5906	0.0053	0.0092	0.0076	0.0043	0.0018	0.005	0.502	1	3	1
0.1024	0.7323	1.4686	3.4646	12.7796	16.13	0.0342	0.1221	0.1224	0.1444	0.1775	0.1345	0.5126	2	3	1
0.1182	0.2638	0.7717	1.689	2.7914	3.2678	0.0394	0.044	0.0644	0.0704	0.0388	0.0273	0.4233	5	4	1
0.0158	0.0512	0.2953	0.6142	6.9331	7.3071	0.0053	0.0086	0.0247	0.0256	0.0963	0.0609	0.429	5	3	1
0.1024	0.2835	0.6418	2.2205	4.7796	6.1654	0.0342	0.0473	0.0535	0.0926	0.0664	0.0514	0.5135	1		1
0	0	0.0119	0.3111	1.7717	3.0867	0	0	0.001	0.013	0.0247	0.0258	0.4125	2	3	1
0.0119	0.0434	0.0788	0.4528	1.0749	4.1024	0.004	0.0073	0.0066	0.0189	0.015	0.0342	0.514	1	3	1
0	0	0.0788	0.1733	1.7678	3.0355	0	0	0.0066	0.0073	0.0246	0.0253	0.205	5	3	1
0.2993	0.5119	1.1103	2.0709	3.0945	3.3819	0.0998	0.0854	0.0926	0.0863	0.043	0.0282	0.4127	1	4	1
0.1378	0.2638	0.7166	3.8859	7.189	8.2914	0.046	0.044	0.0598	0.162	0.0999	0.0691	0.4698	5	4	1
0	0	0.0591	0.6693	3.0591	4.8662	0	0	0.005	0.0279	0.0425	0.0406	0.499	1	4	1
0.5473	1.0434	2.0158	5.0276	8.2953	8.6536	0.1825	0.1739	0.168	0.2095	0.1153	0.0722	0.4189	4	4	1
0.1615	0.3229	0.7284	1.6772	6.4961	6.5985	0.0539	0.0539	0.0607	0.0699	0.0903	0.055	0.5183	4	4	1
0	0	0.004	0.0434	1.2599	2.0276	0	0	0.0004	0.0019	0.0175	0.0169	0.4392	1	4	1
0.0119	0.0827	0.4292	3.1772	4.6969	6.3859	0.004	0.0138	0.0358	0.1324	0.0653	0.0533	0.4778	5	3	1
0.004	0.0119	0.0434	1.13	6.9686	8.0552	0.0014	0.002	0.0037	0.0471	0.0968	0.0672	0.4245	6	4	1
0.0276	0.1103	0.3189	1.563	4.0197	4.2756	0.0092	0.0184	0.0266	0.0652	0.0559	0.0357	0.4268	2	3	1
0.0355	0.067	0.1418	0.1772	0.4292	0.4292	0.0119	0.0112	0.0119	0.0074	0.006	0.0036	0.4973	2	4	1
0.0906	0.1497	0.2402	0.7048	1.8347	2.2008	0.0302	0.025	0.0201	0.0294	0.0255	0.0184	0.498	2	3	1
0	0	0	0.0867	0.3111	1.0788	0	0	0	0.0037	0.0044	0.009	0.413	3	3	1
0	0.0119	0.0827	0.6221	1.4528	1.5867	0	0.002	0.0069	0.026	0.0202	0.0133	0.4863	3	2	1
0	0	0	0.0237	2.5	3.0749	0	0	0	0.001	0.0348	0.0257	0.3629	1	4	1
0.4331	0.6457	0.756	1.2166	3.4016	6.5119	0.1444	0.1077	0.063	0.0507	0.0473	0.0543	0.5012	3	3	1
0.0276	0.0552	0.1615	0.2481	2.0473	4.4528	0.0092	0.0092	0.0135	0.0104	0.0285	0.0372	0.405	4	4	1
0.0119	0.0512	0.1654	0.756	1.7678	3.4252	0.004	0.0086	0.0138	0.0315	0.0246	0.0286	0.4309	1		1
0.0985	0.2126	0.378	1.0591	2.9804	4.0315	0.0329	0.0355	0.0315	0.0442	0.0414	0.0336	0.4385	6	3	1
0.0552	0.0945	0.1182	0.4686	7.2481	8.9449	0.0184	0.0158	0.0099	0.0196	0.1007	0.0746	0.4795	4	3	1
0.3859	1.1536	4.6024	9.8544	14.0276	15.7835	0.1287	0.1923	0.3836	0.4106	0.1949	0.1316	0.2783	2	3	1
0	0	0	0.8583	7.8701	9.7402	0	0	0	0.0358	0.1094	0.0812	0.4928	6	4	1
0	0.0355	0.1772	0.5276	3.4174	6.0788	0	0.006	0.0148	0.022	0.0475	0.0507	0.4293	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.0749	0.6497	0.756	0	0	0	0.0032	0.0091	0.0063	0.5168	1	4	1
0.0394	0.1024	0.189	2.2284	3.8347	5.5749	0.0132	0.0171	0.0158	0.0929	0.0533	0.0465	0.4613	2	4	1
0	0	0.004	0.1615	0.6024	0.9292	0	0	0.0004	0.0068	0.0084	0.0078	0.4248	5	1	1
0.0709	0.1221	0.2796	1.1024	1.9646	2.8819	0.0237	0.0204	0.0233	0.046	0.0273	0.0241	0.3762	5	4	1
0.0197	0.0355	0.1457	0.3386	1.8701	2.1378	0.0066	0.006	0.0122	0.0142	0.026	0.0179	0.4259	3	3	1
0	0.0079	0.067	0.2245	0.626	1.3623	0	0.0014	0.0056	0.0094	0.0087	0.0114	0.401	5	4	1
0.1654	0.2993	0.5276	1.6418	6.0315	6.5749	0.0552	0.0499	0.044	0.0685	0.0838	0.0548	0.4805	6	3	1
0.0158	0.0276	0.0591	0.4646	1.0552	1.1693	0.0053	0.0046	0.005	0.0194	0.0147	0.0098	0.504	5	4	1
0.0552	0.126	0.126	0.3938	1.4489	2.815	0.0184	0.021	0.0105	0.0165	0.0202	0.0235	0.4268	4	4	1
0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.0197	0.0394	0.004	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0003	0.0004	0.411	6	3	1
0.0119	0.0867	0.3583	1.2048	13.6182	16.7205	0.004	0.0145	0.0299	0.0502	0.1892	0.1394	0.497	4	3	1

0.004	0.0749	0.0867	0.5552	12.4095	16.63	0.0014	0.0125	0.0073	0.0232	0.1724	0.1386	0.429	6	3	1
0.0276	0.1654	0.2914	0.5315	4.1142	5.5315	0.0092	0.0276	0.0243	0.0222	0.0572	0.0461	0.429	2	3	1
0	0	0	0.0985	0.8229	1.3032	0	0	0	0.0042	0.0115	0.0109	0.4989	6	4	1
0	0.0237	0.0315	0.2363	2.3032	2.3504	0	0.004	0.0027	0.0099	0.032	0.0196	0.455	5	3	1
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.256	2.5237	2.7048	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0107	0.0351	0.0226	0.28	3		1
0	0.004	0.004	0.0119	13.5473	25.5552	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0005	0.1882	0.213	0.4291	4	4	1
0.0473	0.0827	0.1969	0.8938	4.8308	5.7205	0.0158	0.0138	0.0165	0.0373	0.0671	0.0477	0.5172	4	3	1
0.0749	0.2008	0.4764	1.7245	3.6536	4.6575	0.025	0.0335	0.0397	0.0719	0.0508	0.0389	0.3338	1	4	1
0.0434	0.1378	0.3111	0.6851	1.7599	3.9528	0.0145	0.023	0.026	0.0286	0.0245	0.033	0.4726	3	3	1
0	0	0.0315	0.7756	2.4567	2.9371	0	0	0.0027	0.0324	0.0342	0.0245	0.5045	4		1
0	0	0.0315	0.2087	0.5434	1.0552	0	0	0.0027	0.0087	0.0076	0.0088	0.414	6	4	1
0	0	0.0394	0.1615	0.7441	1.2993	0	0	0.0033	0.0068	0.0104	0.0109	0.5062	3	4	1
0.567	0.9686	1.9961	3.0788	3.8977	4.4292	0.189	0.1615	0.1664	0.1283	0.0542	0.037	0.362	5	4	1
0.1182	0.1615	0.2284	1.3977	4.4252	4.6615	0.0394	0.027	0.0191	0.0583	0.0615	0.0389	0.438	5	3	1
0	0.0355	0.126	0.2441	1.5434	2.3583	0	0.006	0.0105	0.0102	0.0215	0.0197	0.44	3	3	1
0.0906	0.2678	0.8347	1.6733	3.9095	4.1733	0.0302	0.0447	0.0696	0.0698	0.0543	0.0348	0.4713	5	4	1
0.0079	0.0355	0.0512	0.063	0.5237	0.5237	0.0027	0.006	0.0043	0.0027	0.0073	0.0044	0.446	5	4	1
0.0473	0.6378	0.6575	1.1221	2.0394	2.7993	0.0158	0.1063	0.0548	0.0468	0.0284	0.0234	0.5098	2	1	1
0.004	0.0158	0.1418	0.4804	2.5473	3.7048	0.0014	0.0027	0.0119	0.0201	0.0354	0.0309	0.442	6	4	1
0	0.0079	0.0906	1.1103	2.5512	3.0985	0	0.0014	0.0076	0.0463	0.0355	0.0259	0.467	5		1
0	0	0.0355	0.1378	1.6378	3.0355	0	0	0.003	0.0058	0.0228	0.0253	0.4158	1	3	1
0.189	0.4292	2.0394	3.3386	3.4686	3.6812	0.063	0.0716	0.17	0.1392	0.0482	0.0307	0.4341	4	3	1
0	0	0.0079	0.1339	0.756	1.9449	0	0	0.0007	0.0056	0.0105	0.0163	0.428	3	4	1
0	0	0	0.0315	0.4607	1.5119	0	0	0	0.0014	0.0064	0.0126	0.4351	6	3	1
0.7323	1.4056	4.8504	7.2914	7.626	7.9213	0.2441	0.2343	0.4042	0.3039	0.106	0.0661	0.4697	4	1	1
0.0512	0.1339	0.2126	0.9843	1.4292	2.2245	0.0171	0.0224	0.0178	0.0411	0.0199	0.0186	0.4086	4	4	1
0.0079	0.2441	0.4134	0.6182	0.6457	0.9764	0.0027	0.0407	0.0345	0.0258	0.009	0.0082	0.367	2	3	1
0	0	0	0.4804	0.8465	1.4607	0	0	0	0.0201	0.0118	0.0122	0.346	1	3	1
0.1221	0.2993	1.1969	6.7993	11.4922	11.9134	0.0407	0.0499	0.0998	0.2834	0.1597	0.0993	0.3761	6	4	1
0.0158	0.0237	0.0552	3.2008	7.4331	7.8977	0.0053	0.004	0.0046	0.1334	0.1033	0.0659	0.4033	3	3	1
0	0.0119	0.0473	0.2914	0.9922	1.7914	0	0.002	0.004	0.0122	0.0138	0.015	0.5	5	3	1
0.7205	1.756	3.0591	5.6615	7.3583	8.756	0.2402	0.2927	0.255	0.2359	0.1022	0.073	0.4351	5	1	1
0.2835	0.4528	0.6142	0.7875	2.8229	4.1378	0.0945	0.0755	0.0512	0.0329	0.0393	0.0345	0.4274	5	3	1
0.2323	0.3032	0.3859	1.5158	4.6339	5.0709	0.0775	0.0506	0.0322	0.0632	0.0644	0.0423	0.4469	4	4	1
0.1182	0.1615	0.2323	0.5788	3.3544	3.8741	0.0394	0.027	0.0194	0.0242	0.0466	0.0323	0.5072	5	4	1
0	0.0355	0.0827	0.1063	0.252	2.3268	0	0.006	0.0069	0.0045	0.0035	0.0194	0.439	6	4	1
0.0237	0.0906	0.1182	0.3701	1.9371	3	0.0079	0.0151	0.0099	0.0155	0.027	0.025	0.4293	4	3	1
0.0079	0.0709	0.2953	1.5394	9.3859	20.3189	0.0027	0.0119	0.0247	0.0642	0.1304	0.1694	0.387	1	3	1
0.1024	0.1575	0.1575	0.1693	0.3504	2.063	0.0342	0.0263	0.0132	0.0071	0.0049	0.0172	0.502	6	3	1
0.0749	0.1024	0.1536	0.3347	2.3662	3.9252	0.025	0.0171	0.0128	0.014	0.0329	0.0328	0.5176	1	4	1
0	0	0.0119	0.067	0.9056	1.5867	0	0	0.001	0.0028	0.0126	0.0133	0.5035	4	4	1
0	0	0.004	0.0434	1.2599	2.0276	0	0	0.0004	0.0019	0.0175	0.0169	0.4515	1	4	1
0.0906	0.189	0.189	1.0119	2.4686	3.9134	0.0302	0.0315	0.0158	0.0422	0.0343	0.0327	0.5034	6	4	1
0	0.0276	0.4016	3.7245	5.4646	6.3462	0	0.0046	0.0335	0.1552	0.0759	0.0529	0.4778	4	4	1
0	0	0.0197	0.0749	0.2678	1.752	0	0	0.0017	0.0032	0.0038	0.0146	0.364	6	4	1
0	0	0.0119	0.1497	0.4607	0.9489	0	0	0.001	0.0063	0.0064	0.008	0.2663	6	2	1
0	0	0	0.067	5.4174	9.693	0	0	0	0.0028	0.0753	0.0808	0.4225	6	3	1
0.5276	0.9607	1.252	2.0749	4.0355	5.8583	0.1759	0.1602	0.1044	0.0865	0.0561	0.0489	0.5098	2	3	1

0	0	0.004	0.0827	0.3111	0.5434	0	0	0.0004	0.0035	0.0044	0.0046	0.4116	5	3	1
0.3583	0.7323	1.4449	2.7087	3.4843	3.9449	0.1195	0.1221	0.1205	0.1129	0.0484	0.0329	0.4075	1	4	1
0.4882	0.9371	1.6378	2.2678	2.2953	3.1575	0.1628	0.1562	0.1365	0.0945	0.0319	0.0264	0.4162	1	3	1
0.13	0.2048	0.2953	0.3465	2.4252	4.6103	0.0434	0.0342	0.0247	0.0145	0.0337	0.0385	0.428	6	3	1
0.1221	0.3701	1.1063	2.2599	3.2087	3.9489	0.0407	0.0617	0.0922	0.0942	0.0428	0.033	0.3916	2	1	1
0	0	0	0	0.3071	4.6575	0	0	0	0	0.0043	0.0389	0.4334	5	3	1
0	0	0.004	0.2008	0.8347	1.9764	0	0	0.0004	0.0084	0.0116	0.0165	0.469	4	1	1
0	0.0079	0.0945	1.0315	4.0906	4.1418	0	0.0014	0.0079	0.043	0.0569	0.0346	0.4546	3		1
0.1024	0.7323	1.4686	3.4646	12.7796	16.13	0.0342	0.1221	0.1224	0.1444	0.1775	0.1345	0.4297	4	4	1
0.0315	0.0394	0.0512	0.3111	1.3386	3.8819	0.0105	0.0066	0.0043	0.013	0.0186	0.0324	0.4954	5	4	1
0.0079	0.0355	0.3859	1.189	1.7284	2.2796	0.0027	0.006	0.0322	0.0496	0.0241	0.019	0.4056	4	4	1
0.1103	0.2481	0.9764	5.8462	11.4213	11.5355	0.0368	0.0414	0.0814	0.2437	0.1587	0.0962	0.3781	5		1
0	0	0.0315	0.3898	0.6575	1.5434	0	0	0.0027	0.0163	0.0092	0.0129	0.4448	1	4	1
0.067	0.1575	0.3386	5.8268	8.1182	8.6103	0.0224	0.0263	0.0283	0.2428	0.1128	0.0718	0.4768	5	3	1
0.0315	0.0945	0.0985	0.7048	9.8544	11.9567	0.0105	0.0158	0.0083	0.0294	0.1369	0.0997	0.5191	4	4	1
0.0315	0.0906	0.3426	1.4252	3.6024	3.8741	0.0105	0.0151	0.0286	0.0594	0.0501	0.0323	0.4936	1	3	1
0.0827	0.0945	0.0945	0.2126	1.5945	2.5237	0.0276	0.0158	0.0079	0.0089	0.0222	0.0211	0.5166	5	4	1
0	0.0079	0.0749	0.7126	2.0867	4.7363	0	0.0014	0.0063	0.0297	0.029	0.0395	0.4255	2	1	1
0	0.0158	0.3583	0.7481	2.1733	2.2441	0	0.0027	0.0299	0.0312	0.0302	0.0188	0.508	6	4	1
0.0434	0.1221	0.1772	1.3504	2.9804	4.126	0.0145	0.0204	0.0148	0.0563	0.0414	0.0344	0.4933	2	3	1
0.0197	0.0709	0.3544	1.6969	3.3898	9.4292	0.0066	0.0119	0.0296	0.0708	0.0471	0.0786	0.5154	4	4	1
0.2323	0.2835	0.626	1.6772	1.8504	2.0985	0.0775	0.0473	0.0522	0.0699	0.0257	0.0175	0.4423	6	4	1
0.0315	0.0906	0.3308	0.8386	3.3462	4.6221	0.0105	0.0151	0.0276	0.035	0.0465	0.0386	0.225	5	4	1
0.0119	0.0119	0.0119	0.3386	1.2953	2.0079	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.0142	0.018	0.0168	0.4344	3	3	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0709	1.693	3.4331	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.003	0.0236	0.0287	0.4221	5	4	1
0.004	0.0158	0.1418	0.4804	2.5473	3.7048	0.0014	0.0027	0.0119	0.0201	0.0354	0.0309	0.442	3	3	1
0.0158	0.0237	0.0867	0.189	0.4371	0.4843	0.0053	0.004	0.0073	0.0079	0.0061	0.0041	0.4936	4	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.5591	0.8229	0	0	0	0	0.0078	0.0069	0.392	1	4	1
0.2875	0.6024	1.8741	3.2205	4.9961	5.0552	0.0959	0.1004	0.1562	0.1342	0.0694	0.0422	0.5112	2	1	1
0	0	0	0.3111	0.5158	0.5827	0	0	0	0.013	0.0072	0.0049	0.4739	5	4	1
0.0276	0.0473	1.1142	2.4725	2.9252	3.2126	0.0092	0.0079	0.0929	0.1031	0.0407	0.0268	0.3198	6	3	1
0	0.0709	0.0709	0.1654	0.3898	1.0276	0	0.0119	0.006	0.0069	0.0055	0.0086	0.502	5	3	1
0.0197	0.0197	0.0591	0.3426	2.0119	2.941	0.0066	0.0033	0.005	0.0143	0.028	0.0246	0.4921	4	3	1
0.0237	0.0355	0.0827	0.5945	1.0158	1.378	0.0079	0.006	0.0069	0.0248	0.0142	0.0115	0.4451	3	4	1
0.13	0.252	0.3898	0.752	1.3032	2.3701	0.0434	0.042	0.0325	0.0314	0.0181	0.0198	0.5052	6	3	1
0	0.0158	0.3229	3.5197	4.6339	4.8504	0	0.0027	0.027	0.1467	0.0644	0.0405	0.4871	2	3	1
0.067	0.1457	0.2717	0.5591	1.256	3.0473	0.0224	0.0243	0.0227	0.0233	0.0175	0.0254	0.4186	2	4	1
0.0119	0.0591	0.1063	0.189	0.4449	1.7441	0.004	0.0099	0.0089	0.0079	0.0062	0.0146	0.439	1	3	1
0.1182	0.3701	1.1103	1.5749	2.063	2.2166	0.0394	0.0617	0.0926	0.0657	0.0287	0.0185	0.4727	2	3	1
0.004	0.0394	0.2481	1.2796	3.4804	3.5512	0.0014	0.0066	0.0207	0.0534	0.0484	0.0296	0.4078	1	4	1
0.0237	0.0434	0.13	0.8623	2.7441	5.6221	0.0079	0.0073	0.0109	0.036	0.0382	0.0469	0.5059	3	4	1
0.0749	0.2008	0.4764	1.7245	3.6536	4.6575	0.025	0.0335	0.0397	0.0719	0.0508	0.0389	0.3338	5	1	1
0	0	0.0591	0.0709	0.4567	0.5119	0	0	0.005	0.003	0.0064	0.0043	0.5121	2	3	1
0.1024	0.7481	3.7678	6.3229	7.7875	8.1457	0.0342	0.1247	0.314	0.2635	0.1082	0.0679	0.4478	5	4	1
0.3859	1.1536	4.6024	9.8544	14.0276	15.7835	0.1287	0.1923	0.3836	0.4106	0.1949	0.1316	0.2615	6	3	1
0.0315	0.0591	0.2638	3.1575	7.0867	10.3898	0.0105	0.0099	0.022	0.1316	0.0985	0.0866	0.2525	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.2914	1.6733	2.9095	0	0	0	0.0122	0.0233	0.0243	0.4221	4	4	1
0.0906	0.2284	0.4607	3.7087	7.6969	8.6693	0.0302	0.0381	0.0384	0.1546	0.107	0.0723	0.5108	2	1	1

0.0276	0.0276	0.0512	0.1575	4.4725	7.9567	0.0092	0.0046	0.0043	0.0066	0.0622	0.0664	0.5173	5	4	1
0	0.004	0.0079	0.2756	2.5276	3.2875	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0115	0.0352	0.0274	0.4013	1	1	1
0.004	0.0237	1.1851	5.9016	6.4056	6.6103	0.0014	0.004	0.0988	0.2459	0.089	0.0551	0.4101	3	3	1
0.3229	0.4528	0.4686	0.8386	1.0473	4.5237	0.1077	0.0755	0.0391	0.035	0.0146	0.0377	0.2951	5	3	1
0.0355	0.1497	1.1378	1.689	4.2166	7.5158	0.0119	0.025	0.0949	0.0704	0.0586	0.0627	0.4228	6	4	1
0.0276	0.0827	0.3504	1.7048	3.6693	4.1812	0.0092	0.0138	0.0292	0.0711	0.051	0.0349	0.4784	1	3	1
0.0315	0.0552	0.7993	2.1575	2.3308	2.5827	0.0105	0.0092	0.0667	0.0899	0.0324	0.0216	0.3968	4	4	1
0.0749	0.5394	1.441	2.6733	10.2599	11.9961	0.025	0.0899	0.1201	0.1114	0.1425	0.1	0.4298	5	3	1
0.0237	0.0552	0.0552	0.0788	1.5473	1.6812	0.0079	0.0092	0.0046	0.0033	0.0215	0.0141	0.508	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.2875	0.6615	0.9016	0	0	0	0.012	0.0092	0.0076	0.4213	1	4	1
0.0591	0.2087	1.0827	3.7205	4.2441	4.3544	0.0197	0.0348	0.0903	0.1551	0.059	0.0363	0.484	1	4	1
0	0.0591	0.126	1.2166	5.3229	9.8032	0	0.0099	0.0105	0.0507	0.074	0.0817	0.4363	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.0355	1.6024	2.7284	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0223	0.0228	0.404	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.0394	3.7717	6.9764	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0524	0.0582	0.139	5	4	1
0	0	0	0	3.7993	3.9646	0	0	0	0	0.0528	0.0331	0.391	1	3	1
0.0434	0.0906	0.1733	1.2363	3.4449	3.9489	0.0145	0.0151	0.0145	0.0516	0.0479	0.033	0.4545	3	4	1
0	0	0	0.504	0.8583	2.0985	0	0	0	0.021	0.012	0.0175	0.5	5	4	1
0.1221	0.2363	0.5394	1.5355	2.0355	2.1654	0.0407	0.0394	0.045	0.064	0.0283	0.0181	0.467	1	3	1
0	0.004	0.004	0.0709	1.2717	1.9252	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.003	0.0177	0.0161	0.4451	1		1
0.0079	0.0394	0.0394	0.2402	1.9449	3.563	0.0027	0.0066	0.0033	0.0101	0.0271	0.0297	0.406	2	3	1
0.1142	0.2875	0.6497	0.7993	1.0158	1.4725	0.0381	0.048	0.0542	0.0334	0.0142	0.0123	0.498	3	3	1
0	0.0355	0.1654	0.6378	1.9804	2.1182	0	0.006	0.0138	0.0266	0.0276	0.0177	0.369	6	3	1
0.2914	0.6851	0.9882	1.6221	2.3898	2.5315	0.0972	0.1142	0.0824	0.0676	0.0332	0.0211	0.4862	4	3	1
0.0355	0.1103	0.2284	0.6457	1.0906	1.3662	0.0119	0.0184	0.0191	0.027	0.0152	0.0114	0.4913	3	1	1
0	0	0	0	0	0.0434	0	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.5024	6	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.063	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0006	0.3604	4		1
0.2717	0.3583	0.4961	0.8347	1.2599	1.752	0.0906	0.0598	0.0414	0.0348	0.0175	0.0146	0.4665	4	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0867	0.1063	0.3504	1.2875	0.0014	0.0033	0.0073	0.0045	0.0049	0.0108	0.4259	6	4	1
0	0	0	0.004	0.3347	0.8544	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0047	0.0072	0.4975	4	3	1
0.0079	0.0158	0.0827	0.3859	0.7717	1.1418	0.0027	0.0027	0.0069	0.0161	0.0108	0.0096	0.479	5	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.0945	0.1063	0	0	0	0	0.0014	0.0009	0.4501	6	3	1
0.0473	0.0749	0.1103	0.1812	1.3938	2.3859	0.0158	0.0125	0.0092	0.0076	0.0194	0.0199	0.397	1		1
0	0.0119	0.0119	0.4725	1.5079	4.1969	0	0.002	0.001	0.0197	0.021	0.035	0.4451	5	4	1
0.4567	0.8859	1.7717	4.9764	6.6693	7.504	0.1523	0.1477	0.1477	0.2074	0.0927	0.0626	0.5169	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.0079	0.7284	1.5394	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0102	0.0129	0.496	5	4	1
0.0512	0.1457	0.9134	2.2126	2.7835	2.9804	0.0171	0.0243	0.0762	0.0922	0.0387	0.0249	0.4613	6	4	1
0.0749	0.1772	0.4489	0.8071	4.1063	5.1615	0.025	0.0296	0.0375	0.0337	0.0571	0.0431	0.4294	1	3	1
0.0079	0.0512	0.067	0.067	0.4331	0.6812	0.0027	0.0086	0.0056	0.0028	0.0061	0.0057	0.493	5	4	1
0	0	0	0.2481	0.4843	1.2008	0	0	0	0.0104	0.0068	0.0101	0.414	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.1378	0.4016	1.1693	0	0	0	0.0058	0.0056	0.0098	0.4351	5	4	1
0	0.0158	0.1575	0.2717	3.6615	4.1772	0	0.0027	0.0132	0.0114	0.0509	0.0349	0.4178	1		1
0.0512	0.0827	0.1536	2.378	4.9095	6.1969	0.0171	0.0138	0.0128	0.0991	0.0682	0.0517	0.4815	4		1
0.063	0.1615	0.4961	1.4174	1.7205	3.2245	0.021	0.027	0.0414	0.0591	0.0239	0.0269	0.5126	5	3	1
0.3347	0.756	1.7402	4.8426	8.0237	8.4961	0.1116	0.126	0.1451	0.2018	0.1115	0.0709	0.4158	3	3	1
0.0276	0.0315	0.0394	0.0709	0.3347	0.4528	0.0092	0.0053	0.0033	0.003	0.0047	0.0038	0.245	5	4	1
0	0.0119	0.0197	0.563	1.0473	1.2953	0	0.002	0.0017	0.0235	0.0146	0.0108	0.4983	1	3	1
0	0	0.0276	0.0473	0.3859	0.8741	0	0	0.0023	0.002	0.0054	0.0073	0.49	3	4	1
0	0.0158	0.0158	0.063	1.7048	2.6142	0	0.0027	0.0014	0.0027	0.0237	0.0218	0.4216	1	2	1

0	0.0079	0.689	1.441	2.9292	3.4646	0	0.0014	0.0575	0.0601	0.0407	0.0289	0.5054	1	4	1
0.0079	0.0788	0.0788	0.5197	1.0315	1.3268	0.0027	0.0132	0.0066	0.0217	0.0144	0.0111	0.42	5	3	1
0	0	0.13	0.5512	1.1812	1.3189	0	0	0.0109	0.023	0.0165	0.011	0.34	1	3	1
0.0119	0.0197	0.0197	0.3819	0.9016	2.4449	0.004	0.0033	0.0017	0.016	0.0126	0.0204	0.3661	5	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.0158	0.0788	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0007	0.4823	1	3	1
0	0.1142	0.1497	0.4764	0.6142	1.4174	0	0.0191	0.0125	0.0199	0.0086	0.0119	0.4251	6	3	1
0.0788	0.1418	0.2717	0.9213	1.9252	2.8819	0.0263	0.0237	0.0227	0.0384	0.0268	0.0241	0.404	6	4	1
0	0	0	0.1536	0.4804	1.1457	0	0	0	0.0064	0.0067	0.0096	0.3614	1	3	1
0	0	0.004	0.2756	1.6615	3.815	0	0	0.0004	0.0115	0.0231	0.0318	0.4946	4		1
0.0512	0.193	0.7205	3.8662	5.1812	5.3032	0.0171	0.0322	0.0601	0.1611	0.072	0.0442	0.398	1	4	1
0	0	0	0.2008	0.6418	1.2835	0	0	0	0.0084	0.009	0.0107	0.2044	1	3	1
0.0276	0.0552	0.0906	0.2245	1.0985	2.4449	0.0092	0.0092	0.0076	0.0094	0.0153	0.0204	0.433	5	3	1
0.0591	0.1339	0.2441	0.9449	5.6221	5.9961	0.0197	0.0224	0.0204	0.0394	0.0781	0.05	0.4294	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.1182	0.1812	0.2638	0	0	0	0.005	0.0026	0.0022	0.405	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.004	0.1733	0.3662	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0025	0.0031	0.3211	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.0512	0.1142	0.193	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0016	0.0017	0.4424	1	4	1
0	0	0	0.1024	1.4489	2.7796	0	0	0	0.0043	0.0202	0.0232	0.4683	1	1	1
0	0	0	0.0985	0.567	1.2678	0	0	0	0.0042	0.0079	0.0106	0.4377	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.1142	0.6969	1.0079	0	0	0	0.0048	0.0097	0.0084	0.4248	3	4	1
0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.0709	0.2048	0.4725	0.0079	0.004	0.002	0.003	0.0029	0.004	0.509	6	3	1
0	0.0315	0.0709	0.0788	0.0788	0.1851	0	0.0053	0.006	0.0033	0.0011	0.0016	0.5084	1	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.063	0.13	0	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0011	0.39	4	3	1
0.0237	0.0434	0.2678	0.6733	1.6851	2.2205	0.0079	0.0073	0.0224	0.0281	0.0235	0.0186	0.5026	1		1
0	0	0	0.0197	0.2166	0.3977	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0031	0.0034	0.3802	4	3	1
0	0	0.0985	1.8229	3.8229	4.5355	0	0	0.0083	0.076	0.0531	0.0378	0.4283	6	4	1
0.0276	0.0552	0.0552	0.0867	0.6575	3.6182	0.0092	0.0092	0.0046	0.0037	0.0092	0.0302	0.5002	4	4	1
0	0.004	0.1851	0.6142	2.4449	2.8938	0	0.0007	0.0155	0.0256	0.034	0.0242	0.5024	5	4	1
0.0079	0.0158	0.0237	0.2048	1.4252	1.4646	0.0027	0.0027	0.002	0.0086	0.0198	0.0123	0.4265	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.1497	2.3544	4.9882	0	0	0	0.0063	0.0327	0.0416	0.4788	2	3	1
0	0	0	0	0	0.004	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.4391	4	3	1
0	0.004	0.004	0.1969	1.6339	3.3426	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0083	0.0227	0.0279	0.4221	1	1	1
0	0	0.0985	1.0434	2.7796	5.2126	0	0	0.0083	0.0435	0.0387	0.0435	0.506	1	4	1
0.0906	0.2796	0.5867	0.8544	3.9567	12.5276	0.0302	0.0466	0.0489	0.0356	0.055	0.1044	0.4325	6	4	1
0	0.0985	0.0985	0.1812	0.9213	1.2245	0	0.0165	0.0083	0.0076	0.0128	0.0103	0.297	1	3	1
0.0394	0.0591	0.0749	0.3623	0.9764	1.504	0.0132	0.0099	0.0063	0.0151	0.0136	0.0126	0.271	4		1
0	0	0	0.067	0.4961	0.9725	0	0	0	0.0028	0.0069	0.0082	0.3983	1	2	1
0	0	0.0119	0.2953	0.7717	1.3544	0	0	0.001	0.0124	0.0108	0.0113	0.4234	6	3	1
0.0788	0.1457	0.2481	0.5	2.9056	5.0079	0.0263	0.0243	0.0207	0.0209	0.0404	0.0418	0.429	6	4	1
0.0512	0.063	0.1339	0.8898	1.8662	2.5788	0.0171	0.0105	0.0112	0.0371	0.026	0.0215	0.243	1	2	1
0	0	0.0512	0.8268	2.6024	3.441	0	0	0.0043	0.0345	0.0362	0.0287	0.471	5	4	1
0	0	0	0.8347	2.567	3.0158	0	0	0	0.0348	0.0357	0.0252	0.4193	4	1	1
0.0394	0.0394	0.0434	0.5473	1.2481	2.5985	0.0132	0.0066	0.0037	0.0229	0.0174	0.0217	0.3699	4	3	1
0.0158	0.0158	0.1024	0.6497	1.8662	2.4371	0.0053	0.0027	0.0086	0.0271	0.026	0.0204	0.432	5	4	1
0.2678	1.063	2.1457	4.193	6.4489	9.4252	0.0893	0.1772	0.1789	0.1748	0.0896	0.0786	0.4002	1	1	1
0.0945	0.2323	0.5591	1.2599	3.1615	5.0788	0.0315	0.0388	0.0466	0.0525	0.044	0.0424	0.4203	4	3	1
0	0.0197	0.0985	0.1339	0.7126	1.1575	0	0.0033	0.0083	0.0056	0.0099	0.0097	0.4995	6	4	1
0.0197	0.0197	0.0276	0.13	1.7087	2.3819	0.0066	0.0033	0.0023	0.0055	0.0238	0.0199	0.513	4	1	1
0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.1969	0.7875	1.3504	0.0053	0.0027	0.0014	0.0083	0.011	0.0113	0.5029	3	3	1

0.0276	0.0276	0.0276	0.0512	0.2875	0.9213	0.0092	0.0046	0.0023	0.0022	0.004	0.0077	0.439	6	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.1575	1.4843	0	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0124	0.4947	4	3	1
0.4095	0.6654	0.8977	1.7245	2.752	6.1418	0.1365	0.1109	0.0749	0.0719	0.0383	0.0512	0.427	3	4	1
0.0512	0.0709	0.1536	0.5827	2.3347	4.815	0.0171	0.0119	0.0128	0.0243	0.0325	0.0402	0.502	5	1	1
0.0749	0.0749	0.0749	0.3032	0.7048	0.9607	0.025	0.0125	0.0063	0.0127	0.0098	0.0081	0.503	6	4	1
0	0	0	0.0158	0.0945	0.4843	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0014	0.0041	0.378	5	3	1
0	0	0	0	2.252	2.878	0	0	0	0	0.0313	0.024	0.479	4	3	1
0.0749	0.1497	0.256	0.441	6.8308	8.7126	0.025	0.025	0.0214	0.0184	0.0949	0.0727	0.4045	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.0355	0.1575	0.2166	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0022	0.0019	0.4512	5		1
0	0	0.1575	0.4252	1.7126	3.7048	0	0	0.0132	0.0178	0.0238	0.0309	0.509	5	3	1
0.0788	0.0827	0.0827	0.4056	1.5552	1.6851	0.0263	0.0138	0.0069	0.0169	0.0216	0.0141	0.396	4	3	1
0.004	0.0315	0.0906	0.5119	1.4804	2.5906	0.0014	0.0053	0.0076	0.0214	0.0206	0.0216	0.421	3	4	1
0.0237	0.0591	0.13	0.2126	0.6378	1.0552	0.0079	0.0099	0.0109	0.0089	0.0089	0.0088	0.4478	5	4	1
0.0237	0.0355	0.0355	0.0394	6.7008	6.8544	0.0079	0.006	0.003	0.0017	0.0931	0.0572	0.463	5	4	1
0	0	0	0.0552	0.9134	1.3977	0	0	0	0.0023	0.0127	0.0117	0.4752	1	4	1
0	0	0	0.0119	0.2284	0.5867	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0032	0.0049	0.392	2	3	1
0.0827	0.1339	0.189	0.3859	2.3462	3.4056	0.0276	0.0224	0.0158	0.0161	0.0326	0.0284	0.516	5	3	1
0.0906	0.189	0.2205	0.693	1.2166	1.4331	0.0302	0.0315	0.0184	0.0289	0.0169	0.012	0.3573	4	4	1
0.0315	0.1378	0.3819	2.7402	3.4174	3.752	0.0105	0.023	0.0319	0.1142	0.0475	0.0313	0.4604	2	4	1
0.1418	0.2284	0.5985	1.1221	2.13	5.7914	0.0473	0.0381	0.0499	0.0468	0.0296	0.0483	0	3	3	1
0.2717	0.63	2.7875	4.9843	7.4489	8.8308	0.0906	0.105	0.2323	0.2077	0.1035	0.0736	0.4269	4	4	1
0	0	0.0945	0.3938	0.6063	0.6615	0	0	0.0079	0.0165	0.0085	0.0056	0.4221	1		1
0	0	0	0.0119	0.1063	0.2481	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0015	0.0021	0.454	4		1
0	0.0158	0.0158	0.0749	0.4686	1.2323	0	0.0027	0.0014	0.0032	0.0066	0.0103	0.423	1	1	1
0.0079	0.0197	0.0394	0.2008	0.9725	1.4371	0.0027	0.0033	0.0033	0.0084	0.0136	0.012	0.4287	1	3	1
0.0315	0.1812	0.4331	2.0473	8.2284	9.1497	0.0105	0.0302	0.0361	0.0854	0.1143	0.0763	0.4195	1	4	1
0	0	0.0434	0.1693	0.1851	0.5119	0	0	0.0037	0.0071	0.0026	0.0043	0.426	1	4	1
0.0158	0.0512	0.0512	0.1457	0.2087	0.8229	0.0053	0.0086	0.0043	0.0061	0.0029	0.0069	0.4686	4	3	1
0.0079	0.0788	0.126	0.2441	0.315	0.3977	0.0027	0.0132	0.0105	0.0102	0.0044	0.0034	0.408	1	4	1
0.0355	0.0827	0.1693	0.3308	1.2796	1.3465	0.0119	0.0138	0.0142	0.0138	0.0178	0.0113	0.404	5	4	1
0	0.0315	0.1497	0.4725	1.0394	1.8544	0	0.0053	0.0125	0.0197	0.0145	0.0155	0.5124	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.0119	0.1851	0.441	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0026	0.0037	0.414	6	4	1
0.0276	0.0315	0.1969	0.9607	3.4252	4.5552	0.0092	0.0053	0.0165	0.0401	0.0476	0.038	0.4846	5	4	1
0	0	0.0788	0.8426	1.6378	2.563	0	0	0.0066	0.0352	0.0228	0.0214	0.473	3	4	1
0	0	0	0	0	0.0749	0	0	0	0	0	0.0007	0.444	5		1
0	0	0	0.3268	0.8544	2.3819	0	0	0	0.0137	0.0119	0.0199	0.4792	5	4	1
0.0394	0.067	0.0827	0.5512	3.0788	3.9882	0.0132	0.0112	0.0069	0.023	0.0428	0.0333	0.4075	6	4	1
0.0355	0.0512	0.1103	0.3701	1.2678	2.752	0.0119	0.0086	0.0092	0.0155	0.0177	0.023	0.5013	5	4	1
0.0119	0.0276	0.1733	1	2.6575	3.1733	0.004	0.0046	0.0145	0.0417	0.037	0.0265	0.4137	5	4	1
0	0	0	0	0	0.0158	0	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.398	5	4	1
0.0276	0.1654	0.2914	0.5315	4.1142	5.5315	0.0092	0.0276	0.0243	0.0222	0.0572	0.0461	0.477	1	3	1
0.1418	0.2323	0.2638	0.3701	0.693	1.0749	0.0473	0.0388	0.022	0.0155	0.0097	0.009	0.413	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.0709	1.3859	1.3859	0	0	0	0.003	0.0193	0.0116	0.438	4	3	1
0.3938	0.8819	1.5315	1.6536	1.8583	2.941	0.1313	0.147	0.1277	0.0689	0.0259	0.0246	0.4831	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.0355	1.0394	2.6969	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0145	0.0225	0.4426	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.7284	1.4371	1.4804	0	0	0	0.0304	0.02	0.0124	0.4792	4	3	1
0.0788	0.1103	0.13	0.1654	2.0512	3.5079	0.0263	0.0184	0.0109	0.0069	0.0285	0.0293	0.5159	1	3	1
0	0	0.126	0.3544	0.6536	0.9292	0	0	0.0105	0.0148	0.0091	0.0078	0.397	5	4	1

0.0119	0.067	0.1772	1.2087	6.2756	6.4843	0.004	0.0112	0.0148	0.0504	0.0872	0.0541	0.389	1	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.1497	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0013	0.43	1	3	1
0.0079	0.0434	0.0512	0.2914	3.4961	3.7205	0.0027	0.0073	0.0043	0.0122	0.0486	0.0311	0.4102	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.3504	1	1.2008	0	0	0	0.0146	0.0139	0.0101	0.3983	4	3	1
0	0	0.0079	0.0119	9.693	9.9646	0	0	0.0007	0.0005	0.1347	0.0831	0.4712	6	4	1
0.4764	0.8386	1.9174	3.193	5.3977	8.2166	0.1588	0.1398	0.1598	0.1331	0.075	0.0685	0.5155	1	4	1
0	0	0	0.004	0.2402	0.2402	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0034	0.0021	0.421	1	1	1
0.0079	0.0394	0.2205	0.5591	1.9882	3.7875	0.0027	0.0066	0.0184	0.0233	0.0277	0.0316	0.476	5	4	1
0	0	0	0.1457	1.4607	1.5749	0	0	0	0.0061	0.0203	0.0132	0.4196	1	1	1
0	0.0079	0.0906	0.3347	2.6024	2.8583	0	0.0014	0.0076	0.014	0.0362	0.0239	0.4021	5	4	1
0.1182	0.3189	0.689	1.6733	4.2481	5.5355	0.0394	0.0532	0.0575	0.0698	0.0591	0.0462	0.493	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.0473	2.3189	2.3504	0	0	0	0.002	0.0323	0.0196	0.357	1	3	1
0	0.0119	0.0709	0.3938	1.2678	2.2126	0	0.002	0.006	0.0165	0.0177	0.0185	0.4051	6	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.9016	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0076	0.493	6	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.063	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0006	0.411	4	4	1
0.0827	0.126	0.1575	0.2205	0.2599	0.3189	0.0276	0.021	0.0132	0.0092	0.0037	0.0027	0.495	2		1
0	0	0.0237	0.0552	0.4449	1.1339	0	0	0.002	0.0023	0.0062	0.0095	0.3725	5	3	1
0.193	0.3701	0.8741	1.6221	1.6575	1.9174	0.0644	0.0617	0.0729	0.0676	0.0231	0.016	0.413	1	4	1
0	0	0	0.004	0.0709	0.0709	0	0	0	0.0002	0.001	0.0006	0.3923	5	3	1
0.626	1.1103	1.4095	3.4843	6.5	12.3111	0.2087	0.1851	0.1175	0.1272	0.0903	0.1026	0.4243	1		1
0.0434	0.0749	0.0827	0.1851	3.0512	5.1378	0.0145	0.0125	0.0069	0.0078	0.0424	0.0429	0.426	4	3	1
0.0237	0.0552	0.2756	0.504	2.6969	3.252	0.0079	0.0092	0.023	0.021	0.0375	0.0271	0.4775	5	4	1
0	0	0	0.004	0.0985	0.2245	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0014	0.0019	0	1	3	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3431	1	1	1
0.1221	0.1851	0.3465	1.0394	5.1851	6.0276	0.0407	0.0309	0.0289	0.0434	0.0721	0.0503	0.4248	2	3	1
0.0197	0.0749	0.193	0.3386	1.3544	2.3189	0.0066	0.0125	0.0161	0.0142	0.0189	0.0194	0.3891	1	3	1
0	0.0315	0.0749	0.2166	0.6103	0.6497	0	0.0053	0.0063	0.0091	0.0085	0.0055	0.48	5	3	1
0	0.0197	0.0197	0.0197	0.063	0.1654	0	0.0033	0.0017	0.0009	0.0009	0.0014	0.512	5	3	1
0.0276	0.0591	0.1733	0.4292	1.193	1.5867	0.0092	0.0099	0.0145	0.0179	0.0166	0.0133	0.4381	4	1	1
0	0	0	0.0355	0.1182	0.2126	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0017	0.0018	0.4155	1	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.0197	0.8544	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0072	0.417	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.1221	1.256	1.4252	0	0	0	0.0051	0.0175	0.0119	0.49	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.2087	0.8544	1.5985	0	0	0	0.0087	0.0119	0.0134	0.4252	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.0119	4.4213	7.0473	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0615	0.0588	0.421	1	3	1
0.0788	0.0985	0.2678	0.567	1.9134	2.63	0.0263	0.0165	0.0224	0.0237	0.0266	0.022	0.478	4	4	1
0.067	0.1378	0.2717	0.4016	0.9843	1.3504	0.0224	0.023	0.0227	0.0168	0.0137	0.0113	0.5078	6	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.0749	0.1772	0	0	0	0	0.0011	0.0015	0.484	1	3	1
0.0276	0.0512	0.126	0.2323	0.8032	1.5512	0.0092	0.0086	0.0105	0.0097	0.0112	0.013	0.3914	3	3	1
0	0	0.004	0.0709	0.1103	0.252	0	0	0.0004	0.003	0.0016	0.0021	0.4192	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.6182	1.7087	1.8662	0	0	0	0.0258	0.0238	0.0156	0.4996	5	3	1
0.3347	0.8229	1.6969	2.2756	2.4646	2.5473	0.1116	0.1372	0.1415	0.0949	0.0343	0.0213	0.426	6	3	1
0	0	0.0512	0.4567	2.0749	2.9016	0	0	0.0043	0.0191	0.0289	0.0242	0.474	4	3	1
0	0.1063	0.7402	1.8032	8.2205	12.4528	0	0.0178	0.0617	0.0752	0.1142	0.1038	0.5179	5	4	1
0.7835	1.5079	5.3386	7.0827	7.9056	8.6615	0.2612	0.2514	0.4449	0.2952	0.1098	0.0722	0.4769	6	3	1
0.0079	0.0158	0.0394	0.1772	0.6772	1.7875	0.0027	0.0027	0.0033	0.0074	0.0095	0.0149	0.447	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.0591	0.2875	1.4016	0	0	0	0.0025	0.004	0.0117	0.444	5	3	1
0.067	0.2008	2.6772	5.8071	6	6.1575	0.0224	0.0335	0.2231	0.242	0.0834	0.0514	0.4852	2	3	1
0	0	0.004	0.004	1.5394	1.9449	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.0214	0.0163	0.4955	1	4	1

0	0	0.1812	1.4725	2.2638	3.3938	0	0	0.0151	0.0614	0.0315	0.0283	0.3715	6	4	1
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0119	0.5709	1.1457	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0005	0.008	0.0096	0.484	5	3	1
0.0355	0.189	0.3229	0.7126	1.7245	3.189	0.0119	0.0315	0.027	0.0297	0.024	0.0266	0.3545	2	3	1
0	0	0.0355	0.3268	3.6615	4.8977	0	0	0.003	0.0137	0.0509	0.0409	0.4785	5	3	1
0.193	0.3898	0.752	1.7284	3.6536	4.6024	0.0644	0.065	0.0627	0.0721	0.0508	0.0384	0.5107	6	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.0158	0.0158	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0002	0.465	1	4	1
0.0355	0.2993	1.5394	2.0827	3.2599	4.567	0.0119	0.0499	0.1283	0.0868	0.0453	0.0381	0.5083	5	4	1
0	0.0079	0.2599	1.0512	3.1457	5.8583	0	0.0014	0.0217	0.0438	0.0437	0.0489	0.429	2	4	1
0	0	0	0.2284	0.6693	0.815	0	0	0	0.0096	0.0093	0.0068	0.392	6	4	1
0	0	0	0.3111	1.378	1.8898	0	0	0	0.013	0.0192	0.0158	0.424	1	3	1
0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.0434	0.0552	0.0985	0.0079	0.004	0.002	0.0019	0.0008	0.0009	0.423	3	3	1
0	0.0237	0.1615	0.4489	2.1497	2.6615	0	0.004	0.0135	0.0188	0.0299	0.0222	0.502	6	3	1
0.1339	0.2441	0.2953	0.4882	1.0906	1.2048	0.0447	0.0407	0.0247	0.0204	0.0152	0.0101	0.44	5	4	1
0.0355	0.0394	0.0394	0.1063	1.9371	4.9567	0.0119	0.0066	0.0033	0.0045	0.027	0.0414	0.474	4	2	1
0.0276	0.0315	0.0591	0.1378	0.3662	0.8819	0.0092	0.0053	0.005	0.0058	0.0051	0.0074	0.499	1	3	1
0	0.0237	0.0906	0.4725	0.5315	0.9252	0	0.004	0.0076	0.0197	0.0074	0.0078	0.382	1	3	1
0.0906	0.189	0.2402	0.3347	1.0827	1.7323	0.0302	0.0315	0.0201	0.014	0.0151	0.0145	0.3228	2	4	1
0	0.0158	0.0158	0.0394	1	1.6063	0	0.0027	0.0014	0.0017	0.0139	0.0134	0.4563	1	3	1
0.0394	0.0749	0.1221	0.1654	0.3268	2.063	0.0132	0.0125	0.0102	0.0069	0.0046	0.0172	0.3331	1	3	1
0.063	0.0906	0.1024	0.3347	0.7441	5.2953	0.021	0.0151	0.0086	0.014	0.0104	0.0442	0.41	1	3	1
0	0	0	0	1.3189	1.6142	0	0	0	0	0.0184	0.0135	0.5024	5	4	1
0	0	0	0.1418	0.8032	0.9686	0	0	0	0.006	0.0112	0.0081	0.361	1	3	1
0	0.0079	0.0158	0.0197	0.1575	0.8859	0	0.0014	0.0014	0.0009	0.0022	0.0074	0.4791	3	4	1
0	0	0.0079	0.2284	1.6497	2.4922	0	0	0.0007	0.0096	0.023	0.0208	0.5119	5		1
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0197	0.4371	1.6142	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0009	0.0061	0.0135	0.504	6	4	1
0	0.0079	0.0158	0.1418	0.3347	0.8504	0	0.0014	0.0014	0.006	0.0047	0.0071	0.3573	4	4	1
0.0237	0.0237	0.0434	0.0906	0.2835	0.7914	0.0079	0.004	0.0037	0.0038	0.004	0.0066	0	6	4	1
0.0276	0.0394	0.126	0.1693	1.2402	1.5512	0.0092	0.0066	0.0105	0.0071	0.0173	0.013	0.409	1	1	1
0	0	0	0.2481	0.4489	0.7008	0	0	0	0.0104	0.0063	0.0059	0.41	4	3	1
0	0	0.0197	0.7363	2.4489	2.6654	0	0	0.0017	0.0307	0.0341	0.0223	0.5098	1	4	1
0	0	0.0591	0.0709	0.0709	0.0709	0	0	0.005	0.003	0.001	0.0006	0.4811	3	3	1
0.0394	0.0709	0.0709	0.0985	0.2638	0.563	0.0132	0.0119	0.006	0.0042	0.0037	0.0047	0.419	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.0394	0.3347	0.9095	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0047	0.0076	0.42	5	4	1
0	0.0158	0.0276	0.252	0.5906	1.4016	0	0.0027	0.0023	0.0105	0.0083	0.0117	0.3353	4	1	1
0	0	0	0.0315	0.1063	0.1103	0	0	0	0.0014	0.0015	0.001	0.426	2	3	1
0.4843	1.3504	2.8111	6.563	15.6063	17.193	0.1615	0.2251	0.2343	0.2735	0.2168	0.1433	0.4815	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.2875	0.8426	1.1536	0	0	0	0.012	0.0118	0.0097	0.4698	3	1	1
0.0197	0.0434	0.1772	0.7875	2.2481	2.8977	0.0066	0.0073	0.0148	0.0329	0.0313	0.0242	0.4326	6	4	1
0	0	0.0079	0.0709	1.6378	1.7284	0	0	0.0007	0.003	0.0228	0.0145	0.423	5	4	1
0	0	0.0985	0.9528	2.7126	2.8032	0	0	0.0083	0.0397	0.0377	0.0234	0.28	1	3	1
0.0197	0.0788	0.2993	0.8898	1.2875	1.504	0.0066	0.0132	0.025	0.0371	0.0179	0.0126	0.4355	5	1	1
0	0	0	0	0.1221	0.5709	0	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0048	0.4221	6	4	1
0	0	0	0	0	0.004	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.472	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.2599	0.941	1.0985	0	0	0	0.0109	0.0131	0.0092	0.49	6	4	1
0.6575	1.0315	1.3583	2.0749	2.5158	3.2323	0.2192	0.172	0.1132	0.0865	0.035	0.027	0.492	3	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.0512	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0005	0.4	4	1	1
0	0	0	0.4095	0.6457	0.6497	0	0	0	0.0171	0.009	0.0055	0.4663	1	1	1
0	0.0158	0.2638	0.693	1.1182	3.1221	0	0.0027	0.022	0.0289	0.0156	0.0261	0.507	1	4	1

0	0	0	0.2638	1.0827	1.2363	0	0	0	0.011	0.0151	0.0104	0.461	4	3	1
0	0.0119	0.0158	0.3308	0.7048	1.3189	0	0.002	0.0014	0.0138	0.0098	0.011	0.4911	6	3	1
0.0276	0.0315	0.0315	1.0985	3.256	4.1103	0.0092	0.0053	0.0027	0.0458	0.0453	0.0343	0.4297	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.0315	0.1969	0.3386	0	0	0	0.0014	0.0028	0.0029	0.499	5	4	1
0.0197	0.0197	0.0473	0.1536	1.3032	2.8583	0.0066	0.0033	0.004	0.0064	0.0181	0.0239	0.5117	5	1	1
0.0119	0.0197	0.0197	0.1418	0.3504	0.4882	0.004	0.0033	0.0017	0.006	0.0049	0.0041	0.409	2		1
0.0315	0.0591	0.193	1.256	3.0591	7.0945	0.0105	0.0099	0.0161	0.0524	0.0425	0.0592	0.4666	6	4	1
0.0079	0.0749	0.315	0.3426	0.5394	2.4764	0.0027	0.0125	0.0263	0.0143	0.0075	0.0207	0.5123	1	2	1
0	0	0	0.0512	0.1024	0.3386	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0015	0.0029	0.4123	2	3	1
0	0	0	0.193	2.8898	5.067	0	0	0	0.0081	0.0402	0.0423	0.44	2	4	1
0	0.0079	0.0197	0.189	0.4252	0.5512	0	0.0014	0.0017	0.0079	0.006	0.0046	0.3659	6	4	1
0.0315	0.0945	0.1339	0.563	1.4331	2.6851	0.0105	0.0158	0.0112	0.0235	0.02	0.0224	0.4323	6	3	1
0.0945	0.2008	0.3229	0.6772	1.0827	1.6457	0.0315	0.0335	0.027	0.0283	0.0151	0.0138	0.349	5	3	1
0.2717	0.3032	0.4331	1.5434	3.0237	4.9646	0.0906	0.0506	0.0361	0.0644	0.042	0.0414	0.4407	1	4	1
0	0	0.0552	0.6654	1.2481	2.5985	0	0	0.0046	0.0278	0.0174	0.0217	0.438	4	3	1
0.0158	0.0276	0.0276	0.2481	0.626	1.063	0.0053	0.0046	0.0023	0.0104	0.0087	0.0089	0.5031	6	4	1
0	0	0	0.004	0.2245	0.256	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0032	0.0022	0.384	6	4	1
1.4095	2.5276	6.1693	7.6339	7.9213	8.5749	0.4699	0.4213	0.5142	0.3181	0.1101	0.0715	0.496	4	3	1
0.0434	0.0512	0.0591	0.3504	1.6969	1.9016	0.0145	0.0086	0.005	0.0146	0.0236	0.0159	0.428	6	3	1
0	0	0	1.4371	9.126	11.067	0	0	0	0.0599	0.1268	0.0923	0.429	1	3	1
0.2008	0.5552	0.6103	0.693	1.1733	1.315	0.067	0.0926	0.0509	0.0289	0.0163	0.011	0.481	1		1
0	0	0	0.0237	0.2363	0.8386	0	0	0	0.001	0.0033	0.007	0.447	6	3	1
0	0.0749	0.0867	0.6693	0.9607	1.7796	0	0.0125	0.0073	0.0279	0.0134	0.0149	0.499	6	4	1
0	0	0.0119	0.4056	0.6457	0.9489	0	0	0.001	0.0169	0.009	0.008	0.49	2	4	1
0	0	0.004	0.6221	1.1103	1.6339	0	0	0.0004	0.026	0.0155	0.0137	0.5043	5	4	1
0.0394	0.0394	0.0394	0.0827	1.6182	2.9686	0.0132	0.0066	0.0033	0.0035	0.0225	0.0248	0.4265	1	4	1
0	0	0.0867	0.6693	1.0355	2.2756	0	0	0.0073	0.0279	0.0144	0.019	0.439	1	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.193	0.5867	0	0	0	0	0.0027	0.0049	0.424	4	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.1812	1.2914	0	0	0	0	0.0026	0.0108	0.332	4	3	1
0	0.0119	0.0119	0.0749	2.7796	3.6851	0	0.002	0.001	0.0032	0.0387	0.0308	0.426	4	4	1
0.126	0.1733	0.2363	1.126	5.7363	6.689	0.042	0.0289	0.0197	0.047	0.0797	0.0558	0.429	5	3	1
0.4607	0.7481	0.9528	1.7756	4.8701	6.0473	0.1536	0.1247	0.0794	0.074	0.0677	0.0504	0.5184	1	3	1
0	0.0079	0.0197	0.4095	0.7087	1.8898	0	0.0014	0.0017	0.0171	0.0099	0.0158	0.3899	1	3	1
0	0.004	0.004	0.0709	0.5237	1.3583	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.003	0.0073	0.0114	0.439	1	3	1
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0394	0.1693	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0006	0.0015	0.403	2	3	0
0.0749	0.1182	0.3465	0.4843	0.8386	0.9882	0.025	0.0197	0.0289	0.0202	0.0117	0.0083	0.3957	1	3	0
0	0.0512	0.1063	0.1103	0.2245	0.5	0	0.0086	0.0089	0.0046	0.0032	0.0042	0.428	5	3	0
0	0.0197	0.2717	0.2914	0.9843	1.9252	0	0.0033	0.0227	0.0122	0.0137	0.0161	0.4006	3	3	0
0.1339	0.2717	0.378	0.8032	2.8229	3.5473	0.0447	0.0453	0.0315	0.0335	0.0393	0.0296	0.5185	4	3	0
0.0119	0.0197	0.0315	0.2678	0.6851	0.9646	0.004	0.0033	0.0027	0.0112	0.0096	0.0081	0.499	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.0276	0.0276	0.1024	0.1024	0.0014	0.0007	0.0023	0.0012	0.0015	0.0009	0.469	1	1	0
0.0079	0.1497	0.1654	0.1693	0.2993	0.3229	0.0027	0.025	0.0138	0.0071	0.0042	0.0027	0.43	1	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0276	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0003	0.4406	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.004	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0001	0.254	2	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3343	1	1	0
0.004	0.004	0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0.1693	0.0014	0.0007	0.0007	0.0005	0.0002	0.0015	0.3406	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0276	0.0945	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0004	0.0008	0.335	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.1615	0	0	0	0	0	0.0014	0.3791	1	1	0

0	0	0	0.4016	1.4331	1.6654	0	0	0	0.0168	0.02	0.0139	0.241	1	3	0
0.0906	0.1418	0.3071	0.3898	0.5276	0.5276	0.0302	0.0237	0.0256	0.0163	0.0074	0.0044	0.268	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.004	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.291	1	3	0
0	0.126	0.1654	0.3189	0.8032	1.1693	0	0.021	0.0138	0.0133	0.0112	0.0098	0.432	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.6339	1.2796	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0089	0.0107	0.453	1		0
0	0	0.0276	0.063	0.6418	0.9922	0	0	0.0023	0.0027	0.009	0.0083	0.4281	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.1142	0.2993	4.7599	0	0	0	0.0048	0.0042	0.0397	0.38	1	1	0
0.0079	0.189	0.2008	0.2441	0.7638	2.2481	0.0027	0.0315	0.0168	0.0102	0.0107	0.0188	0.34	1	1	0
0.004	0.0906	0.13	0.1497	0.2599	0.378	0.0014	0.0151	0.0109	0.0063	0.0037	0.0032	0.4173	1		0
0	0.1575	0.1851	0.2205	0.3623	1.126	0	0.0263	0.0155	0.0092	0.0051	0.0094	0.3218	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.5552	0.5552	0	0	0	0	0.0078	0.0047	0.265	1	2	0
0	0.0315	0.0906	0.1851	4.7481	5.7323	0	0.0053	0.0076	0.0078	0.066	0.0478	0.4251	1	3	0
0.0237	0.2599	0.3583	0.4095	0.7756	1.2363	0.0079	0.0434	0.0299	0.0171	0.0108	0.0104	0.3157	3	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0158	0.0591	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0005	0.358	3	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0434	0.0512	0	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0005	0.454	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.354	1	3	0
0.067	0.189	0.689	0.7008	1.0827	2.6339	0.0224	0.0315	0.0575	0.0292	0.0151	0.022	0.4021	1	1	0
0.1969	0.378	0.3819	0.4804	1.9764	5.5788	0.0657	0.063	0.0319	0.0201	0.0275	0.0465	0.386	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0079	0.5197	0.8229	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0004	0.0073	0.0069	0	1	3	0
0.2008	0.4961	0.7953	0.9331	1.9331	2.5315	0.067	0.0827	0.0663	0.0389	0.0269	0.0211	0.3531	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.0394	0.1654	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0006	0.0014	0.432	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.004	0.0827	0.4764	0.7678	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0035	0.0067	0.0064	0.3782	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0512	0.2678	0.3189	0.8701	1.0867	0.0027	0.0086	0.0224	0.0133	0.0121	0.0091	0.439	1	4	0
0.0355	0.0512	0.2166	0.2717	1.3071	2.7363	0.0119	0.0086	0.0181	0.0114	0.0182	0.0229	0.4325	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.0827	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0007	0.388	2	4	0
0	0	0.0158	0.0315	0.067	0.067	0	0	0.0014	0.0014	0.001	0.0006	0.3756	1	4	0
0.1378	0.4449	0.6654	0.6693	0.7205	0.7245	0.046	0.0742	0.0555	0.0279	0.0101	0.0061	0.477	1	4	0
0.189	0.2048	0.3701	1.8189	2.941	3.9331	0.063	0.0342	0.0309	0.0758	0.0409	0.0328	0.4526	1	1	0
0.2363	0.3741	0.3938	0.5394	2.7087	2.8111	0.0788	0.0624	0.0329	0.0225	0.0377	0.0235	0.3585	1	2	0
0.256	0.7284	0.8032	1.3859	1.8347	2.5237	0.0854	0.1214	0.067	0.0578	0.0255	0.0211	0.414	2	4	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	5.6182	6.7717	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0781	0.0565	0.352	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.388	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.2481	0.4016	0	0	0	0	0.0035	0.0034	0.343	1	1	0
0	0	0.004	0.004	0.1497	0.4882	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.0021	0.0041	0.411	1	3	0
0	0.0355	0.0591	0.0709	0.5276	0.7993	0	0.006	0.005	0.003	0.0074	0.0067	0.291	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0276	0.2599	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0022	0.397	1	2	0
0.0079	0.067	0.1733	0.6772	2.2678	4.5552	0.0027	0.0112	0.0145	0.0283	0.0315	0.038	0	1	4	0
0.1654	0.2048	0.4882	0.5197	1.3544	2.3662	0.0552	0.0342	0.0407	0.0217	0.0189	0.0198	0.428	1	4	0
0	0	0.0355	0.0355	0.0985	0.1733	0	0	0.003	0.0015	0.0014	0.0015	0.4006	1	2	0
0.004	0.004	0.0158	0.0237	0.0867	0.2717	0.0014	0.0007	0.0014	0.001	0.0013	0.0023	0.378	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0079	0.1536	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0013	0.358	1	1	0
0	0.0591	0.1063	0.1221	0.1969	0.1969	0	0.0099	0.0089	0.0051	0.0028	0.0017	0.3531	1	1	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0197	0.1418	1.5315	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0009	0.002	0.0128	0.506	1	3	0
0.0434	0.0434	0.0512	0.1378	2.9252	3.252	0.0145	0.0073	0.0043	0.0058	0.0407	0.0271	0.413	1		0
0.0276	0.0276	0.0315	0.063	0.2835	0.4449	0.0092	0.0046	0.0027	0.0027	0.004	0.0038	0.507	1	3	0
0.0197	0.0512	0.0591	0.2087	0.5709	3.4292	0.0066	0.0086	0.005	0.0087	0.008	0.0286	0.405	1		0
0	0	0	0.0512	0.752	0.8819	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0105	0.0074	0.4878	1	3	0
0.0079	0.067	0.0709	0.1457	0.6693	1.3623	0.0027	0.0112	0.006	0.0061	0.0093	0.0114	0.311	1	3	0

0.0591	0.0985	0.2166	1.1693	6.5119	6.9607	0.0197	0.0165	0.0181	0.0488	0.0905	0.0581	0.4252	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0197	0.0394	0.0473	0.1063	1.2796	0.0027	0.0033	0.0033	0.002	0.0015	0.0107	0.2751	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.063	0.1772	0.2481	0	0	0	0.0027	0.0025	0.0021	0.4021	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.3859	0.4764	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0054	0.004	0.426	2	1	0
0	0	0	0.0473	0.7599	0.7993	0	0	0	0.002	0.0106	0.0067	0.4121	1	1	0
0.0158	0.0237	0.0237	0.0473	0.126	1.0512	0.0053	0.004	0.002	0.002	0.0018	0.0088	0.451	1	1	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0749	0.7048	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0011	0.0059	0.4392	2	3	0
0.1378	0.1378	0.1772	1.0197	1.9567	3.7835	0.046	0.023	0.0148	0.0425	0.0272	0.0316	0.222	4	3	0
0.0394	0.0591	0.0749	0.126	2.8032	3.6339	0.0132	0.0099	0.0063	0.0053	0.039	0.0303	0.3086	1	4	0
0.2717	0.3071	0.3268	0.3977	1.2875	2.2402	0.0906	0.0512	0.0273	0.0166	0.0179	0.0187	0.495	2	4	0
0.0749	0.1378	0.3741	0.5867	1.3741	1.4607	0.025	0.023	0.0312	0.0245	0.0191	0.0122	0.421	1	3	0
0.0315	0.063	0.063	0.3977	1.0237	1.1772	0.0105	0.0105	0.0053	0.0166	0.0143	0.0099	0.442	1	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0985	0.9489	1.4528	0	0	0.0007	0.0042	0.0132	0.0122	0.4734	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1654	0.256	0.3229	0	0	0	0.0069	0.0036	0.0027	0.4225	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.322	1	4	0
0.1103	0.2205	0.2638	0.3071	1.0119	1.815	0.0368	0.0368	0.022	0.0128	0.0141	0.0152	0.4843	1	4	0
0	0	0.0552	0.0552	0.0552	0.3977	0	0	0.0046	0.0023	0.0008	0.0034	0.4413	1		0
0.441	0.6063	0.6221	0.7126	1.4725	2.3032	0.147	0.1011	0.0519	0.0297	0.0205	0.0192	0.4028	2	1	0
0	0	0.0945	0.1772	0.3189	0.4016	0	0	0.0079	0.0074	0.0045	0.0034	0.4775	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0237	0.1182	0.6969	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.001	0.0017	0.0059	0.4044	2	3	0
0	0.0079	0.5749	0.7481	1.378	3.1733	0	0.0014	0.048	0.0312	0.0192	0.0265	0.471	1	3	0
0	0.0079	0.0434	0.063	0.126	0.1654	0	0.0014	0.0037	0.0027	0.0018	0.0014	0.415	1	2	0
0.0119	0.0197	0.063	0.2245	0.7166	1.1969	0.004	0.0033	0.0053	0.0094	0.01	0.01	0.4251	1	3	0
0.0315	0.067	0.1339	0.2481	0.4764	0.8426	0.0105	0.0112	0.0112	0.0104	0.0067	0.0071	0.4227	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.126	0.8938	0	0	0	0	0.0018	0.0075	0.4135	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.0512	0.0552	0	0	0	0	0.0008	0.0005	0	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.1536	0.378	0.4567	0	0	0	0.0064	0.0053	0.0039	0.288	5	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0788	0	0	0	0	0	0.0007	0.3405	1	1	0
0.0276	0.0355	0.0355	0.3859	1.6063	2.3504	0.0092	0.006	0.003	0.0161	0.0224	0.0196	0.4021	1	3	0
0.0591	0.1812	0.1812	0.189	0.3504	0.8741	0.0197	0.0302	0.0151	0.0079	0.0049	0.0073	0.34	1	3	0
0.2953	0.3583	0.3662	0.3662	0.815	1.0237	0.0985	0.0598	0.0306	0.0153	0.0114	0.0086	0.2819	1	3	0
0.004	0.0709	0.1142	0.1575	0.7835	2.252	0.0014	0.0119	0.0096	0.0066	0.0109	0.0188	0	1	3	0
0.0315	0.0591	0.0749	0.0867	0.7638	1.4843	0.0105	0.0099	0.0063	0.0037	0.0107	0.0124	0.487	2	1	0
0.004	0.004	0.0473	0.3111	1.7914	2.8701	0.0014	0.0007	0.004	0.013	0.0249	0.024	0.4618	1	1	0
0.0079	0.0158	0.0197	0.0237	0.0434	0.067	0.0027	0.0027	0.0017	0.001	0.0007	0.0006	0.257	2	4	0
0.0079	0.0237	0.0512	0.3229	0.6733	0.8583	0.0027	0.004	0.0043	0.0135	0.0094	0.0072	0.433	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.004	0.0079	0.0394	0.0434	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0004	0.0006	0.0004	0.3504	1	3	0
0	0.0197	0.6142	0.8268	1.6733	1.9371	0	0.0033	0.0512	0.0345	0.0233	0.0162	0.469	6	4	0
0.0158	0.0197	0.0512	0.0749	1.2875	2.067	0.0053	0.0033	0.0043	0.0032	0.0179	0.0173	0.4586	1	3	0
0.2048	0.4095	0.6772	0.8544	1.0355	3.6457	0.0683	0.0683	0.0565	0.0356	0.0144	0.0304	0.369	1	1	0
0.0237	0.1024	0.5276	0.63	0.8347	1.5473	0.0079	0.0171	0.044	0.0263	0.0116	0.0129	0.426	1	3	0
0	0.0355	0.0394	0.0394	0.2205	0.4804	0	0.006	0.0033	0.0017	0.0031	0.0041	0.488	5	4	0
0	0.004	0.2441	0.2441	1.4292	2.1063	0	0.0007	0.0204	0.0102	0.0199	0.0176	0.424	2		0
0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0591	0.0749	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0009	0.0007	0.369	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0119	0.0197	0.0473	0.4607	0.9213	0.004	0.002	0.0017	0.002	0.0064	0.0077	0.4021	3	1	0
0.0749	0.0749	0.0867	0.4213	1.8189	2.504	0.025	0.0125	0.0073	0.0176	0.0253	0.0209	0.5055	2	4	0
0.0237	0.1221	0.1221	0.1418	2.3347	3.8111	0.0079	0.0204	0.0102	0.006	0.0325	0.0318	0.3094	2	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.0788	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0007	0.4458	5	4	0

0	0	0.0355	0.1142	0.5394	0.7245	0	0	0.003	0.0048	0.0075	0.0061	0.4703	2	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0749	1.752	1.7717	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0032	0.0244	0.0148	0.411	1		0
0.3111	0.3111	0.378	0.4804	0.8819	1.563	0.1037	0.0519	0.0315	0.0201	0.0123	0.0131	0.4164	1		0
0.004	0.004	0.1103	0.1575	0.193	0.2402	0.0014	0.0007	0.0092	0.0066	0.0027	0.0021	0.086	1	2	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0315	0.563	1.5749	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0014	0.0079	0.0132	0.4274	1	3	0
0.0315	0.0552	0.0591	0.1339	0.2796	1.4686	0.0105	0.0092	0.005	0.0056	0.0039	0.0123	0.392	1	1	0
0	0.0315	0.3189	0.4016	0.6812	1.1575	0	0.0053	0.0266	0.0168	0.0095	0.0097	0.315	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0079	0.1063	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0009	0.3875	1	3	0
0.004	0.0276	0.2205	0.2993	0.8071	1.7953	0.0014	0.0046	0.0184	0.0125	0.0113	0.015	0.308	1	3	0
0	0.0237	0.0355	0.0552	0.63	0.6418	0	0.004	0.003	0.0023	0.0088	0.0054	0.3833	2	2	0
0.2166	0.6693	0.6969	0.8898	2.3308	2.9213	0.0722	0.1116	0.0581	0.0371	0.0324	0.0244	0.382	1	3	0
0	0	0.0197	0.0827	0.3623	3.2245	0	0	0.0017	0.0035	0.0051	0.0269	0.3522	2	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0315	0.4134	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0005	0.0035	0.3262	2	1	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.0709	0.2008	0	0	0	0.0012	0.001	0.0017	0.3129	1		0
0.0473	0.0552	0.067	0.067	0.315	0.4095	0.0158	0.0092	0.0056	0.0028	0.0044	0.0035	0.437	2	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0512	0.0788	0	0	0	0	0.0008	0.0007	0.415	1	4	0
0.0079	0.0158	0.0237	0.1103	0.5749	1.5473	0.0027	0.0027	0.002	0.0046	0.008	0.0129	0.4978	2	3	0
0	0	0.004	0.0079	0.0394	0.0434	0	0	0.0004	0.0004	0.0006	0.0004	0.482	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.3229	0.4843	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0045	0.0041	0.4482	1		0
0	0	0.0315	0.0355	0.1142	0.4567	0	0	0.0027	0.0015	0.0016	0.0039	0.457	6	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.063	0.7166	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0009	0.006	0.3186	2	1	0
0	0.004	0.1063	0.252	1.2205	4.6418	0	0.0007	0.0089	0.0105	0.017	0.0387	0.428	1	2	0
0	0	0.0945	0.193	0.6103	3.1575	0	0	0.0079	0.0081	0.0085	0.0264	0.5006	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.004	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.4811	1	3	0
0.0079	0.189	0.1969	0.2008	0.256	0.3977	0.0027	0.0315	0.0165	0.0084	0.0036	0.0034	0.287	1	3	0
0.2126	0.2875	0.2875	0.378	2.4804	4.9292	0.0709	0.048	0.024	0.0158	0.0345	0.0411	0.405	1	3	0
0	0.0158	0.0315	0.0315	0.1969	0.3623	0	0.0027	0.0027	0.0014	0.0028	0.0031	0.346	6	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.0394	0.0591	0	0	0	0	0.0006	0.0005	0.4635	1	4	0
0	0.0079	0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.6654	0	0.0014	0.001	0.0007	0.0003	0.0056	0	1	3	0
0.0197	0.0355	0.0394	0.4489	0.6378	2.9725	0.0066	0.006	0.0033	0.0188	0.0089	0.0248	0.4961	1	3	0
0.0591	0.1339	0.1851	0.6142	1.9686	3.1812	0.0197	0.0224	0.0155	0.0256	0.0274	0.0266	0.4272	1		0
0	0	0	0.2402	0.8623	1.0552	0	0	0	0.0101	0.012	0.0088	0.296	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0591	0.0591	0	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0005	0.488	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0473	0.2087	0.256	1.0709	1.0906	0.004	0.0079	0.0174	0.0107	0.0149	0.0091	0.3891	1	2	0
0	0	0.0552	0.067	0.6024	0.6182	0	0	0.0046	0.0028	0.0084	0.0052	0.33	1	3	0
0.0355	0.0355	0.0355	0.0355	0.2993	1.2048	0.0119	0.006	0.003	0.0015	0.0042	0.0101	0.33	1	4	0
0	0	0.0158	0.0394	0.1063	0.2008	0	0	0.0014	0.0017	0.0015	0.0017	0.317	1	1	0
0.1339	0.1378	0.1378	0.252	0.5867	0.7914	0.0447	0.023	0.0115	0.0105	0.0082	0.0066	0.3561	1	3	0
0	0	0.3426	0.3623	0.5	0.6536	0	0	0.0286	0.0151	0.007	0.0055	0.3991	2	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0119	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	0.319	4	3	0
0.2166	0.2481	0.2599	0.2599	0.5867	1.6575	0.0722	0.0414	0.0217	0.0109	0.0082	0.0139	0.5	1	2	0
0.0119	0.0709	0.0788	0.1063	0.5355	1.5827	0.004	0.0119	0.0066	0.0045	0.0075	0.0132	0.397	1	3	0
0.7599	1.1615	1.4646	2.0591	3.2441	3.7008	0.2533	0.1936	0.1221	0.0858	0.0451	0.0309	0.44	1	1	0
0	0.004	0.2441	0.3386	0.5512	2.3898	0	0.0007	0.0204	0.0142	0.0077	0.02	0.298	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.126	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0011	0.055	1	3	0
0.067	0.2126	0.2402	0.5	2.3544	3.6103	0.0224	0.0355	0.0201	0.0209	0.0327	0.0301	0.2885	2	1	0
0	0	0.0355	0.0394	0.1378	0.2245	0	0	0.003	0.0017	0.002	0.0019	0.3867	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0119	0.0749	0.3465	1.7481	3.0394	0.004	0.002	0.0063	0.0145	0.0243	0.0254	0.5155	1	3	0

0.0197	0.0315	0.067	0.1418	0.189	0.2835	0.0066	0.0053	0.0056	0.006	0.0027	0.0024	0.238	1	1	0
0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.1103	0.9095	0.0079	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.0016	0.0076	0.357	1	3	0
0.504	0.504	0.504	0.504	1.4331	1.563	0.168	0.084	0.042	0.021	0.02	0.0131	0.4	1	3	0
0.0276	0.2441	0.2717	0.3662	0.7796	1.1772	0.0092	0.0407	0.0227	0.0153	0.0109	0.0099	0.429	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.3701	1.0788	1.1733	0	0	0	0.0155	0.015	0.0098	0.504	1	3	0
0.004	0.0158	0.4449	0.4449	1.5	1.9764	0.0014	0.0027	0.0371	0.0186	0.0209	0.0165	0.4273	2		0
0.067	0.2245	0.2835	0.3819	0.8701	1.6536	0.0224	0.0375	0.0237	0.016	0.0121	0.0138	0.362	1	3	0
0.0119	0.13	0.1339	0.1339	0.1339	0.1772	0.004	0.0217	0.0112	0.0056	0.0019	0.0015	0.3722	1		0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.1063	0.1418	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0015	0.0012	0.331	2		0
0	0.0512	0.2599	0.3111	1.2402	1.7323	0	0.0086	0.0217	0.013	0.0173	0.0145	0.375	2	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0394	0.2205	0	0	0	0	0.0006	0.0019	0.352	6	3	0
0.1221	0.13	0.13	0.3465	0.6457	1.1733	0.0407	0.0217	0.0109	0.0145	0.009	0.0098	0.319	1	1	0
0	0	0.0158	0.4804	1.0394	1.6221	0	0	0.0014	0.0201	0.0145	0.0136	0.338	1	3	0
0	0	0.2953	0.315	1.2363	2.378	0	0	0.0247	0.0132	0.0172	0.0199	0.4118	1	1	0
0.0315	0.0473	0.0827	0.2245	2.004	2.1024	0.0105	0.0079	0.0069	0.0094	0.0279	0.0176	0.369	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.0079	0.0355	0.2205	0.2678	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0015	0.0031	0.0023	0.215	2	3	0
0.0355	0.0552	0.0552	0.063	0.2087	2.4095	0.0119	0.0092	0.0046	0.0027	0.0029	0.0201	0.395	1	3	0
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0355	0.13	0.2756	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0015	0.0019	0.0023	0.504	1	1	0
0.1615	0.2756	0.5355	0.7796	1.6693	2.4961	0.0539	0.046	0.0447	0.0325	0.0232	0.0209	0.4988	2	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.373	1	3	0
0.0197	0.0906	0.1615	0.3189	0.8189	1.1812	0.0066	0.0151	0.0135	0.0133	0.0114	0.0099	0.2457	1		0
0.0315	0.0434	0.0591	0.063	2.1693	3.626	0.0105	0.0073	0.005	0.0027	0.0302	0.0303	0.5159	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0158	0.1339	0.4764	0.9764	2.0237	0.004	0.0027	0.0112	0.0199	0.0136	0.0169	0.397	1	3	0
0	0.2441	0.8229	0.8386	1.9331	2.2599	0	0.0407	0.0686	0.035	0.0269	0.0189	0.323	1	3	0
0	0	0.0197	0.0276	1.6772	3.1772	0	0	0.0017	0.0012	0.0233	0.0265	0.3543	2		0
0.1654	0.2599	0.2638	0.2678	0.3347	1.0237	0.0552	0.0434	0.022	0.0112	0.0047	0.0086	0.426	2	1	0
0	0	0.004	0.189	0.1969	0.2441	0	0	0.0004	0.0079	0.0028	0.0021	0.4811	1	3	0
1.1063	2.2205	4.0473	5.563	5.8347	7.3347	0.3688	0.3701	0.3373	0.2318	0.0811	0.0612	0.321	1	4	0
0	0.0591	0.126	0.1339	0.4843	0.7363	0	0.0099	0.0105	0.0056	0.0068	0.0062	0.4924	1	3	0
0	0	0.0119	0.0119	0.0473	0.0473	0	0	0.001	0.0005	0.0007	0.0004	0.3784	1	2	0
0.004	0.004	0.1575	0.1615	0.6182	0.6457	0.0014	0.0007	0.0132	0.0068	0.0086	0.0054	0.3891	1	3	0
0	0.0119	0.3977	0.4607	0.6693	1.0945	0	0.002	0.0332	0.0192	0.0093	0.0092	0.371	2		0
0.004	0.0552	0.0945	0.1063	0.2284	0.441	0.0014	0.0092	0.0079	0.0045	0.0032	0.0037	0.417	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0473	0.0985	0.126	0.4725	0.626	0.004	0.0079	0.0083	0.0053	0.0066	0.0053	0.4143	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0158	0.4528	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0038	0.301	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0985	0	0	0	0	0	0.0009	0.3686	1	3	0
0	0.0355	0.7087	0.7087	1.4843	1.5434	0	0.006	0.0591	0.0296	0.0207	0.0129	0.359	2	1	0
0	0.0079	0.0827	0.1063	0.9607	1.2717	0	0.0014	0.0069	0.0045	0.0134	0.0106	0.509	2	3	0
0.0552	0.2953	0.3268	0.3662	1.2441	3.0552	0.0184	0.0493	0.0273	0.0153	0.0173	0.0255	0.3377	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.0552	0.1497	0.7599	1.9686	0	0.0007	0.0046	0.0063	0.0106	0.0165	0.331	2	4	0
0.004	0.1418	0.9371	0.9371	1.441	1.4528	0.0014	0.0237	0.0781	0.0391	0.0201	0.0122	0.406	2	1	0
0.0079	0.0394	0.0394	0.3977	1.0394	1.5355	0.0027	0.0066	0.0033	0.0166	0.0145	0.0128	0.437	4	1	0
0.0079	0.0394	0.189	0.9489	1.2245	7.1536	0.0027	0.0066	0.0158	0.0396	0.0171	0.0597	0.416	1		0
0.0158	0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.2678	0.3347	0.0053	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.0038	0.0028	0.331	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.004	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.387	2	4	0
0	0	0.004	0.004	0.0827	0.13	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.0012	0.0011	0.4909	1	1	0
0.004	0.004	0.0158	0.193	0.6142	1.004	0.0014	0.0007	0.0014	0.0081	0.0086	0.0084	0.275	1	3	0
0.0434	0.0591	0.13	0.315	1.4882	2.6418	0.0145	0.0099	0.0109	0.0132	0.0207	0.0221	0.424	1	1	0

0	0	0	0	0	0.0119	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.493	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.3071	0.3386	0.8504	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0128	0.0048	0.0071	0.4999	2	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.0355	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0003	0.462	1	4	0
0.3938	0.4882	0.4961	0.6812	1.8111	2.3898	0.1313	0.0814	0.0414	0.0284	0.0252	0.02	0.3061	1		0
0	0	0	0.004	0.3347	0.9095	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0047	0.0076	0.5137	1	1	0
0	0.0512	0.6142	1.1457	2.0355	4.1575	0	0.0086	0.0512	0.0478	0.0283	0.0347	0.4133	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	5.2126	5.4134	0	0	0	0	0.0724	0.0452	0.4795	2	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.0434	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0004	0.292	2	3	0
0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0.252	0.8898	1.9056	0.0027	0.002	0.001	0.0105	0.0124	0.0159	0.287	2	1	0
0.004	0.0119	0.0119	0.0197	0.0867	0.441	0.0014	0.002	0.001	0.0009	0.0013	0.0037	0.4688	1	4	0
0.0158	0.067	0.1142	0.3032	0.9764	1.2914	0.0053	0.0112	0.0096	0.0127	0.0136	0.0108	0.4679	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.004	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.3452	1	3	0
0.9725	1	1.2481	1.5827	2.8898	3.3859	0.3242	0.1667	0.1041	0.066	0.0402	0.0283	0.304	1	1	0
0.0237	0.1812	0.1812	0.1812	0.8268	3.0985	0.0079	0.0302	0.0151	0.0076	0.0115	0.0259	0.418	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0827	1.13	1.441	0	0	0	0.0035	0.0157	0.0121	0.462	1	2	0
0.1536	0.4331	0.5827	0.9686	4.067	4.8268	0.0512	0.0722	0.0486	0.0404	0.0565	0.0403	0.3965	1	3	0
0.004	0.0158	0.0434	0.0788	0.3544	0.4174	0.0014	0.0027	0.0037	0.0033	0.005	0.0035	0.381	1	2	0
0.1851	0.6221	0.8465	1.0709	2.2087	3.5315	0.0617	0.1037	0.0706	0.0447	0.0307	0.0295	0.411	3	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0158	0	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.395	1	4	0
0	0.0197	0.0315	0.0315	0.1615	0.1615	0	0.0033	0.0027	0.0014	0.0023	0.0014	0.314	6	4	0
0.004	0.0079	0.0119	0.0315	0.3662	0.8229	0.0014	0.0014	0.001	0.0014	0.0051	0.0069	0.358	1	1	0
0	0.067	0.0709	0.0709	0.0709	0.3859	0	0.0112	0.006	0.003	0.001	0.0033	0.3234	1	3	0
0	0.0867	0.0867	0.0867	0.1339	0.5709	0	0.0145	0.0073	0.0037	0.0019	0.0048	0.446	1	3	0
0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.0906	0.2756	0.4134	0.0079	0.004	0.002	0.0038	0.0039	0.0035	0.4238	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0001	0.4099	1	4	0
0	0.0079	0.0434	0.567	1.0119	1.4134	0	0.0014	0.0037	0.0237	0.0141	0.0118	0.502	6	3	0
0	0	0.0119	0.0827	0.1182	0.7205	0	0	0.001	0.0035	0.0017	0.0061	0	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0119	0.0158	0.126	0.8504	1.4449	0.004	0.002	0.0014	0.0053	0.0119	0.0121	0.429	1		0
0.004	0.0197	0.2599	0.8504	2.0512	3.1182	0.0014	0.0033	0.0217	0.0355	0.0285	0.026	0.3955	1	3	0
0.0355	0.126	0.1339	0.1339	0.5394	0.7441	0.0119	0.021	0.0112	0.0056	0.0075	0.0063	0.4251	1	3	0
0	0.0591	0.0749	0.0749	0.1575	0.2796	0	0.0099	0.0063	0.0032	0.0022	0.0024	0.2868	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0709	0.3268	0	0	0	0.0002	0.001	0.0028	0.324	1		0
0	0.0434	0.0552	0.0827	0.1418	0.2126	0	0.0073	0.0046	0.0035	0.002	0.0018	0.368	1		0
0	0	0	0	0	0.1063	0	0	0	0	0	0.0009	0.334	1	3	0
0	0	0.1536	0.252	0.6024	1.067	0	0	0.0128	0.0105	0.0084	0.0089	0.4115	2	3	0
0	0	0.0394	0.0394	0.0788	0.5197	0	0	0.0033	0.0017	0.0011	0.0044	0.414	1	3	0
0.0315	0.1063	0.1693	0.4056	1.0827	1.2126	0.0105	0.0178	0.0142	0.0169	0.0151	0.0102	0.4221	1	3	0
0	0.0197	0.0394	0.0394	0.1142	0.6182	0	0.0033	0.0033	0.0017	0.0016	0.0052	0.337	1	4	0
0.004	0.0906	0.0906	0.1024	2.6693	2.9252	0.0014	0.0151	0.0076	0.0043	0.0371	0.0244	0.351	1	3	0
0	0	0.0906	0.4134	0.8386	1.2048	0	0	0.0076	0.0173	0.0117	0.0101	0.486	2	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.0355	0.1575	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0014	0.3791	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.0434	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0004	0.369	1		0
0.0867	0.1103	0.1182	0.126	0.7245	1.6182	0.0289	0.0184	0.0099	0.0053	0.0101	0.0135	0.396	1	1	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0237	0.1221	0.3071	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.001	0.0017	0.0026	0.3993	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.1221	0.6418	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0017	0.0054	0.407	1	3	0
0.2914	0.5434	0.5512	0.5749	1.0591	1.752	0.0972	0.0906	0.046	0.024	0.0148	0.0146	0.354	2	4	0
0.004	0.0119	0.1497	0.1851	0.815	1.4607	0.0014	0.002	0.0125	0.0078	0.0114	0.0122	0.482	1	3	0
0.0158	0.0315	0.0355	0.0788	0.126	0.1772	0.0053	0.0053	0.003	0.0033	0.0018	0.0015	0.39	1	1	0

0.004	0.004	0.004	0.1103	0.3977	0.6182	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0046	0.0056	0.0052	0.401	1		0
0.0827	0.256	0.4449	0.4607	0.6142	1.3347	0.0276	0.0427	0.0371	0.0192	0.0086	0.0112	0.289	2	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0394	0.1221	0.2638	0.2835	0.0027	0.0014	0.0033	0.0051	0.0037	0.0024	0.4003	1	4	0
0.2953	0.3071	0.3741	0.4882	1.067	1.8386	0.0985	0.0512	0.0312	0.0204	0.0149	0.0154	0.4108	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.067	0.067	0	0	0	0.0012	0.001	0.0006	0.423	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0315	0.0591	0.0591	0.1378	0.1536	0.004	0.0053	0.005	0.0025	0.002	0.0013	0.292	1	4	0
0	0.0079	0.0119	0.3741	1.0237	1.0591	0	0.0014	0.001	0.0156	0.0143	0.0089	0.415	1	1	0
0.0276	0.2323	0.2323	0.2323	0.3819	0.3819	0.0092	0.0388	0.0194	0.0097	0.0054	0.0032	0.309	1	1	0
0.126	0.1693	0.1772	0.2717	0.7323	1.0197	0.042	0.0283	0.0148	0.0114	0.0102	0.0085	0.328	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.0158	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0002	0.4048	5	3	0
0	0	0.004	0.004	0.7205	0.8898	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.0101	0.0075	0.462	2	4	0
0.2048	0.4882	0.5827	0.7087	2.0512	2.4764	0.0683	0.0814	0.0486	0.0296	0.0285	0.0207	0.3952	1	3	0
0	0	0.0119	0.63	0.7205	0.9804	0	0	0.001	0.0263	0.0101	0.0082	0.369	1		0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.2245	0.2875	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0032	0.0024	0.3367	1	1	0
0	0	0.0197	0.2048	1.3386	4.3268	0	0	0.0017	0.0086	0.0186	0.0361	0.4197	2	4	0
0	0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.1063	0.1536	0	0.002	0.0014	0.0007	0.0015	0.0013	0.3991	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0158	0.0197	0.0394	0.0906	0.0945	0.0027	0.0027	0.0017	0.0017	0.0013	0.0008	0.4041	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0237	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.0002	0.151	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0315	0.0473	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0004	0.36	2	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.0276	0.126	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0011	0.3834	1	3	0
0	0.2048	0.3386	0.378	2.1024	3.3426	0	0.0342	0.0283	0.0158	0.0292	0.0279	0.4148	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.1733	0	0	0	0	0	0.0015	0.367	1	3	0
0	0	0.0355	0.0906	0.2402	0.7993	0	0	0.003	0.0038	0.0034	0.0067	0.4967	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.063	0.0906	0	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0008	0.466	1	3	0
0	0	0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0	0	0.001	0.0007	0.0003	0.0002	0.382	1		0
0	0.0315	0.0867	0.1221	0.5197	0.5197	0	0.0053	0.0073	0.0051	0.0073	0.0044	0.39	2	3	0
0	0.067	0.067	0.067	0.7087	0.9646	0	0.0112	0.0056	0.0028	0.0099	0.0081	0.319	1		0
0	0	0.0079	0.2993	0.5552	0.5788	0	0	0.0007	0.0125	0.0078	0.0049	0.3854	1	4	0
0.0197	0.2678	0.7953	0.8071	1.5749	2.7323	0.0066	0.0447	0.0663	0.0337	0.0219	0.0228	0.5133	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.1851	0.3623	0	0	0	0	0.0026	0.0031	0.334	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.1378	1.3426	1.7245	0	0	0	0.0058	0.0187	0.0144	0.3165	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.0119	0.3544	1.2796	1.5394	0	0.0007	0.001	0.0148	0.0178	0.0129	0.384	4	4	0
0.1103	0.1221	0.13	0.13	0.3938	0.4528	0.0368	0.0204	0.0109	0.0055	0.0055	0.0038	0.4828	1	4	0
0.0434	0.0512	0.0985	0.2363	0.3071	1.0079	0.0145	0.0086	0.0083	0.0099	0.0043	0.0084	0.423	1	3	0
0.0158	0.0315	0.0709	0.0749	0.1378	0.3308	0.0053	0.0053	0.006	0.0032	0.002	0.0028	0.392	1	1	0
0.004	0.004	0.1378	0.1497	0.2323	0.2638	0.0014	0.0007	0.0115	0.0063	0.0033	0.0022	0.294	1		0
0	0	0	0.0315	0.1378	0.1457	0	0	0	0.0014	0.002	0.0013	0.5123	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.0119	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0001	0.417	2	4	0
0	0	0.004	0.0394	0.4646	0.7481	0	0	0.0004	0.0017	0.0065	0.0063	0	4	3	0
0.1221	0.2717	1.1536	1.7835	3.0119	3.3701	0.0407	0.0453	0.0962	0.0744	0.0419	0.0281	0.3431	1	3	0
0.0197	0.0552	0.0552	0.0552	0.1221	0.2048	0.0066	0.0092	0.0046	0.0023	0.0017	0.0018	0.306	1	3	0
0.0434	0.0945	0.189	0.5237	3.4449	4.1103	0.0145	0.0158	0.0158	0.0219	0.0479	0.0343	0.517	1	3	0
0.0315	0.1103	0.4056	0.5394	1.3977	4.4489	0.0105	0.0184	0.0338	0.0225	0.0195	0.0371	0.403	1		0
0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0.2363	0.256	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0033	0.0022	0.477	4	3	0
0	0.0512	0.0788	0.0788	0.1457	0.3426	0	0.0086	0.0066	0.0033	0.0021	0.0029	0.487	1		0
0	0.0119	0.1063	0.1142	0.1339	0.5197	0	0.002	0.0089	0.0048	0.0019	0.0044	0.323	1		0
0	0.0119	0.4489	0.4528	0.8268	1.1221	0	0.002	0.0375	0.0189	0.0115	0.0094	0.438	1	4	0
0	0.0119	0.0119	0.0119	0.0512	0.0512	0	0.002	0.001	0.0005	0.0008	0.0005	0.193	1	3	0

0	0	0.004	0.0158	0.1693	0.1812	0	0	0.0004	0.0007	0.0024	0.0016	0.2804	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.0749	0.1418	0	0	0	0	0.0011	0.0012	0.385	3	3	0
0.0315	0.0315	0.0394	0.0552	0.7953	1.2638	0.0105	0.0053	0.0033	0.0023	0.0111	0.0106	0.438	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.0237	0.3662	0.4528	0	0	0	0.001	0.0051	0.0038	0.416	1	1	0
0.0079	0.0867	0.3819	0.5079	0.7717	1.2284	0.0027	0.0145	0.0319	0.0212	0.0108	0.0103	0.467	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0158	0	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.482	1	3	0
0.0591	0.3662	1.0827	1.3032	3.063	7.5906	0.0197	0.0611	0.0903	0.0543	0.0426	0.0633	0.23	2	3	0
0	0	0.0158	0.1536	1.8544	2.7599	0	0	0.0014	0.0064	0.0258	0.023	0.26	2	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.364	1	1	0
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0237	0.252	0.3544	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.001	0.0035	0.003	0.311	1	1	0
0.0867	0.0867	0.1182	0.1851	0.6851	1.5985	0.0289	0.0145	0.0099	0.0078	0.0096	0.0134	0.4096	1	1	0
0	0.004	0.063	0.067	0.3701	0.6378	0	0.0007	0.0053	0.0028	0.0052	0.0054	0.439	1	3	0
0.0434	0.067	0.067	0.067	0.6733	1.0788	0.0145	0.0112	0.0056	0.0028	0.0094	0.009	0.354	1	4	0
0	0.004	0.2717	0.3189	1.1457	1.1851	0	0.0007	0.0227	0.0133	0.016	0.0099	0.475	1	2	0
0.0158	0.0197	0.1182	0.126	0.315	0.3189	0.0053	0.0033	0.0099	0.0053	0.0044	0.0027	0.4481	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.1182	0.7166	1.0985	1.2166	0.0027	0.0014	0.0099	0.0299	0.0153	0.0102	0.336	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0591	0.3229	0	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0027	0.4074	1	2	0
0.0591	0.0827	0.315	0.6457	0.9292	0.9331	0.0197	0.0138	0.0263	0.027	0.013	0.0078	0.4193	1	1	0
0	0.0749	0.1457	0.3308	1.9252	3.0749	0	0.0125	0.0122	0.0138	0.0268	0.0257	0.3653	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.0749	0.1457	0.4961	0.8071	0	0.0007	0.0063	0.0061	0.0069	0.0068	0.2863	1	3	0
0	0	0.0158	0.0158	0.6457	2.4252	0	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.009	0.0203	0.3943	1	1	0
0.1063	0.1851	0.1851	0.3544	1.0079	1.4646	0.0355	0.0309	0.0155	0.0148	0.014	0.0123	0.421	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.0709	0.0709	0.2678	0.2993	0	0.0007	0.006	0.003	0.0038	0.0025	0.4	1	3	0
0	0.0079	0.067	0.0827	0.1693	1.3938	0	0.0014	0.0056	0.0035	0.0024	0.0117	0.506	1	3	0
0.1536	0.3741	0.8583	1.0237	1.7717	3.941	0.0512	0.0624	0.0716	0.0427	0.0247	0.0329	0.417	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	1.2796	2.441	0	0	0	0	0.0178	0.0204	0.4928	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.1142	0.4449	0.9489	0.004	0.0027	0.0014	0.0048	0.0062	0.008	0.2427	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1457	0.2717	0.4213	0	0	0	0.0061	0.0038	0.0036	0.386	1	3	0
0.0276	0.0788	0.0788	0.0906	0.3032	1.0434	0.0092	0.0132	0.0066	0.0038	0.0043	0.0087	0.502	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0276	0	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.3616	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.2481	0.3229	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0035	0.0027	0.5026	1	4	0
0.0591	0.0749	0.0945	0.6221	1.9016	2.2993	0.0197	0.0125	0.0079	0.026	0.0265	0.0192	0.349	4	3	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.7205	1.3938	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0101	0.0117	0.4581	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0119	0.0276	0.1378	0.2953	0.3938	0.004	0.002	0.0023	0.0058	0.0042	0.0033	0.3271	1	2	0
0.0473	0.067	0.0749	0.0749	0.8819	1.2796	0.0158	0.0112	0.0063	0.0032	0.0123	0.0107	0.2966	1		0
0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0.0276	0.0749	0.0945	0.0027	0.002	0.001	0.0012	0.0011	0.0008	0.2985	1	1	0
0.0315	0.067	0.1457	0.256	1.4961	2.8111	0.0105	0.0112	0.0122	0.0107	0.0208	0.0235	0.245	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.0276	0.0512	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0005	0.3017	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0119	0.0158	0.2875	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0003	0.0024	0.4154	1	1	0
0.0079	0.063	0.2126	0.3701	0.8229	1.1733	0.0027	0.0105	0.0178	0.0155	0.0115	0.0098	0.284	2	4	0
0.0119	0.2166	0.4646	0.5512	0.9371	1.4331	0.004	0.0361	0.0388	0.023	0.0131	0.012	0.371	1	3	0
0	0	0.1575	0.2481	1.7205	3.3308	0	0	0.0132	0.0104	0.0239	0.0278	0.3117	1	4	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0355	0.3071	0.3386	0	0	0.0007	0.0015	0.0043	0.0029	0.288	1	1	0
0.0079	0.0158	0.1103	0.1378	0.2993	0.3189	0.0027	0.0027	0.0092	0.0058	0.0042	0.0027	0.2183	1	4	0
0.0434	0.0434	0.256	0.4371	1.1654	1.9686	0.0145	0.0073	0.0214	0.0183	0.0162	0.0165	0.413	1		0
0	0	0.4567	0.6733	1.5394	1.567	0	0	0.0381	0.0281	0.0214	0.0131	0.405	1	1	0
0.0788	0.2481	0.5119	0.9646	1.9922	2.9016	0.0263	0.0414	0.0427	0.0402	0.0277	0.0242	0.3253	1	4	0
0	0	0.0355	0.5552	2.7008	3.378	0	0	0.003	0.0232	0.0376	0.0282	0	1		0

0.0473	0.4134	0.4213	0.5788	0.7481	0.8938	0.0158	0.0689	0.0352	0.0242	0.0104	0.0075	0.5054	1	3	0
0.1221	0.1693	0.3032	0.4252	0.7717	1.063	0.0407	0.0283	0.0253	0.0178	0.0108	0.0089	0.477	6	4	0
0.0197	0.0237	0.0867	0.256	0.5276	2.9252	0.0066	0.004	0.0073	0.0107	0.0074	0.0244	0.355	1	3	0
0.0867	0.1497	0.2638	0.4371	1.1812	2.7205	0.0289	0.025	0.022	0.0183	0.0165	0.0227	0.417	1	4	0
0	0.004	0.0079	0.0158	0.0867	0.3189	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0007	0.0013	0.0027	0.4918	1	1	0
0	0	0.0119	0.0197	0.193	0.6497	0	0	0.001	0.0009	0.0027	0.0055	0.4008	1	4	0
0.0355	0.1693	0.5158	1.5119	2.1339	2.1497	0.0119	0.0283	0.043	0.063	0.0297	0.018	0.411	1	1	0
0	0.0079	0.0197	0.0197	0.0434	0.2638	0	0.0014	0.0017	0.0009	0.0007	0.0022	0.5028	2	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.1378	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0012	0.276	1	3	0
0.193	0.193	0.193	0.3741	0.6733	0.6733	0.0644	0.0322	0.0161	0.0156	0.0094	0.0057	0.476	1	3	0
0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.878	1.2245	0.0079	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.0122	0.0103	0.404	2	3	0
0.0749	0.1969	0.4489	0.5434	1.6221	1.6536	0.025	0.0329	0.0375	0.0227	0.0226	0.0138	0.284	1	1	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0827	9.9134	10.7756	0	0	0.0007	0.0035	0.1377	0.0898	0.3767	1	1	0
0	0.004	0.0079	0.067	1.0512	1.0985	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0028	0.0146	0.0092	0.4092	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0158	0.0158	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0002	0.4331	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.1812	0.5237	3.2638	3.9016	0	0.0007	0.0151	0.0219	0.0454	0.0326	0.464	1		0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0197	0	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.331	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.004	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.3803	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0158	0.0315	0.6536	1.378	1.8977	0.004	0.0027	0.0027	0.0273	0.0192	0.0159	0	1	2	0
0.315	0.504	0.7481	0.8741	1.8308	2.4843	0.105	0.084	0.0624	0.0365	0.0255	0.0208	0.3401	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0	0.0007	0.002	0.001	0.0004	0.0002	0.317	1		0
0.0197	0.0197	0.0473	0.063	0.1378	0.6418	0.0066	0.0033	0.004	0.0027	0.002	0.0054	0.333	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3824	1	3	0
0.0945	0.1457	0.1693	0.3977	0.6497	0.8032	0.0315	0.0243	0.0142	0.0166	0.0091	0.0067	0.492	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.258	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0276	0.1063	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0004	0.0009	0.4008	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0197	0.5867	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0049	0.225	2	4	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0.4371	0.5079	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0061	0.0043	0.4513	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.0709	0.2678	0	0	0	0.0017	0.001	0.0023	0.407	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.0355	0.0355	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0003	0.331	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0827	0.0827	0.1063	0.5906	0.7008	0.0027	0.0138	0.0069	0.0045	0.0083	0.0059	0.2946	1		0
0.004	0.0119	0.2599	0.4331	0.756	1.7717	0.0014	0.002	0.0217	0.0181	0.0105	0.0148	0.425	2	4	0
0	0	0.0355	0.0709	1.4528	1.6182	0	0	0.003	0.003	0.0202	0.0135	0.466	1	3	0
0.0355	0.1536	0.1654	0.2717	5.9292	6.0355	0.0119	0.0256	0.0138	0.0114	0.0824	0.0503	0.4408	1	1	0
0.0197	0.067	0.067	0.067	0.067	0.067	0.0066	0.0112	0.0056	0.0028	0.001	0.0006	0.4019	3	3	0
0.0355	0.0434	0.1103	0.1378	0.5237	1.0985	0.0119	0.0073	0.0092	0.0058	0.0073	0.0092	0.293	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.4528	1.2166	1.3071	0	0	0	0.0189	0.0169	0.0109	0.4092	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.1575	1.067	1.4292	0	0	0	0.0066	0.0149	0.012	0.492	1	4	0
0.1536	0.1575	0.1575	0.1575	0.378	0.4764	0.0512	0.0263	0.0132	0.0066	0.0053	0.004	0.3877	3	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0552	0	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.4832	1	3	0
0.256	0.378	0.6497	0.8583	1.4882	2.2835	0.0854	0.063	0.0542	0.0358	0.0207	0.0191	0.408	1	4	0
0	0	0.004	0.0079	0.4725	0.7402	0	0	0.0004	0.0004	0.0066	0.0062	0.498	1	1	0
0.0945	0.1103	0.1103	0.2875	0.9489	1.0512	0.0315	0.0184	0.0092	0.012	0.0132	0.0088	0.306	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.13	0.193	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0019	0.0017	0.315	1	3	0
0	0	0.0276	0.0434	0.2796	1.1339	0	0	0.0023	0.0019	0.0039	0.0095	0.511	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0119	0.0749	0.1103	0.3623	1.0158	0.0027	0.002	0.0063	0.0046	0.0051	0.0085	0.311	1		0
0.0119	0.0512	0.1142	0.1536	0.4764	1.4686	0.004	0.0086	0.0096	0.0064	0.0067	0.0123	0.212	1	3	0
0.004	0.0394	0.1851	0.3308	0.9016	1.3898	0.0014	0.0066	0.0155	0.0138	0.0126	0.0116	0.387	1	1	0

0.1024	0.1103	0.1142	0.126	0.3268	0.4095	0.0342	0.0184	0.0096	0.0053	0.0046	0.0035	0.319	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.004	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0001	0.3999	2	2	0
0.004	0.2638	0.2835	0.4686	0.9134	1.2953	0.0014	0.044	0.0237	0.0196	0.0127	0.0108	0.4341	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0749	0.0749	0	0	0	0	0.0011	0.0007	0.341	1	1	0
0.3662	0.5158	0.5197	0.5355	0.9804	1.4843	0.1221	0.086	0.0434	0.0224	0.0137	0.0124	0.3136	3	3	0
0.004	0.0079	0.0079	0.0434	0.9449	1.2481	0.0014	0.0014	0.0007	0.0019	0.0132	0.0105	0.385	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0119	0.0119	0.1851	0.5	0.6221	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.0078	0.007	0.0052	0.498	1	1	0
0.063	0.063	0.252	0.4764	0.5945	0.6812	0.021	0.0105	0.021	0.0199	0.0083	0.0057	0.35	2	1	0
0.0237	0.1063	0.2402	0.2756	0.7441	1.3819	0.0079	0.0178	0.0201	0.0115	0.0104	0.0116	0.304	1		0
0.1063	0.1418	0.1418	0.1575	0.7796	2.8268	0.0355	0.0237	0.0119	0.0066	0.0109	0.0236	0.281	1	3	0
0.1024	0.2638	0.2875	0.4764	2.3426	3.0079	0.0342	0.044	0.024	0.0199	0.0326	0.0251	0.483	1		0
0	0	0.0158	0.0315	0.0591	0.7481	0	0	0.0014	0.0014	0.0009	0.0063	0.3869	4	4	0
0	0	0	0.004	1.252	1.6654	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0174	0.0139	0.385	1	3	0
0.004	0.1418	0.3189	0.6693	1.752	3.9134	0.0014	0.0237	0.0266	0.0279	0.0244	0.0327	0.4288	1	1	0
0.1733	0.1851	0.189	0.3229	0.9134	1.256	0.0578	0.0309	0.0158	0.0135	0.0127	0.0105	0.3187	1	1	0
0.1575	0.3189	0.3819	0.3938	1.3189	1.4882	0.0525	0.0532	0.0319	0.0165	0.0184	0.0125	0.403	1	4	0
0	0	0.4646	0.4843	1.6654	2.4174	0	0	0.0388	0.0202	0.0232	0.0202	0.4938	1	1	0
0.0197	0.0355	0.0434	0.0749	0.2835	0.626	0.0066	0.006	0.0037	0.0032	0.004	0.0053	0.5074	1	1	0
0	0	0.004	0.1497	0.7126	1.3938	0	0	0.0004	0.0063	0.0099	0.0117	0.372	1		0
0	0	0	0.0945	0.4686	0.7835	0	0	0	0.004	0.0066	0.0066	0	1	3	0
0	0	0.0119	0.13	0.4489	0.4528	0	0	0.001	0.0055	0.0063	0.0038	0.4433	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0197	0.378	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0032	0.2974	2	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.301	1	3	0
0	0.0512	0.1575	0.193	0.2441	0.2914	0	0.0086	0.0132	0.0081	0.0034	0.0025	0.2341	1		0
0	0	0	0.0512	1.067	1.9607	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0149	0.0164	0.3243	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0276	0	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.3244	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.126	0.5906	0.7835	0	0	0	0.0053	0.0083	0.0066	0.3357	1		0
0	0	0.004	0.0709	0.815	1.4607	0	0	0.0004	0.003	0.0114	0.0122	0.4072	1	1	0
0.0197	0.0315	0.1654	0.2245	0.3938	0.4607	0.0066	0.0053	0.0138	0.0094	0.0055	0.0039	0.3661	1	1	0
0	0	0.0276	0.0355	0.4095	0.4292	0	0	0.0023	0.0015	0.0057	0.0036	0.4253	1	3	0
0	0	0.1733	1.0434	1.3662	1.5434	0	0	0.0145	0.0435	0.019	0.0129	0.436	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.2126	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0018	0.423	1	1	0
0.0394	0.0867	0.2126	0.5237	3.0276	3.4567	0.0132	0.0145	0.0178	0.0219	0.0421	0.0289	0.4933	4		0
0.0315	0.0473	0.0906	0.7441	1.941	2.8662	0.0105	0.0079	0.0076	0.0311	0.027	0.0239	0.512	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.004	0.0237	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0001	0.0002	0.278	4	3	0
0	0	0.0276	0.3898	1.2678	3.9567	0	0	0.0023	0.0163	0.0177	0.033	0.499	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0197	0.1733	0.8504	1.8111	0.0027	0.0014	0.0017	0.0073	0.0119	0.0151	0.414	1	3	0
0.2363	0.3229	0.6615	0.7717	1.6457	2.2323	0.0788	0.0539	0.0552	0.0322	0.0229	0.0187	0.503	1		0
0	0	0.1063	0.7402	2.0749	2.2717	0	0	0.0089	0.0309	0.0289	0.019	0.3503	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0355	0.1103	0.1497	0.6812	1.5434	0.004	0.006	0.0092	0.0063	0.0095	0.0129	0.489	1		0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0985	0.6772	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0014	0.0057	0.4674	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1418	0.3819	0.9922	0	0	0	0.006	0.0054	0.0083	0.5056	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0237	0.13	0.256	0.4213	1.3347	0.004	0.004	0.0109	0.0107	0.0059	0.0112	0.4251	5	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0709	0.2638	0	0	0	0	0.001	0.0022	0.3561	1	1	0
0.0788	0.1142	0.1693	0.2835	0.5827	0.6851	0.0263	0.0191	0.0142	0.0119	0.0081	0.0058	0.3072	2	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.1142	0.2599	0	0	0	0	0.0016	0.0022	0.3993	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0434	0.6378	0.9252	0	0	0	0.0019	0.0089	0.0078	0.411	3	1	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.0867	0.0867	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0013	0.0008	0.3707	1	3	0

0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0906	0.1693	0.4095	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0038	0.0024	0.0035	0.409	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3608	1	3	0
0.1103	0.1693	0.2796	0.4489	0.9489	1.252	0.0368	0.0283	0.0233	0.0188	0.0132	0.0105	0.419	1	2	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.1103	0.4882	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0016	0.0041	0.332	1		0
0.0315	0.2402	0.3544	0.5355	2.1733	2.3898	0.0105	0.0401	0.0296	0.0224	0.0302	0.02	0.4101	1	1	0
0	0.0512	0.1536	0.567	1.193	1.8111	0	0.0086	0.0128	0.0237	0.0166	0.0151	0.414	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.0197	0.1812	0.2717	2.0473	0.0014	0.0007	0.0017	0.0076	0.0038	0.0171	0.4016	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.1024	0.193	0	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0017	0.472	1	3	0
0	0	0.0394	0.3268	0.5867	0.6615	0	0	0.0033	0.0137	0.0082	0.0056	0.439	1	3	0
0	0.0709	0.1457	0.441	1.0079	1.2166	0	0.0119	0.0122	0.0184	0.014	0.0102	0.404	1	3	0
0.0394	0.2166	0.2835	0.9804	1.9252	2.5237	0.0132	0.0361	0.0237	0.0409	0.0268	0.0211	0.415	2	3	0
0	0.0119	0.0197	0.0315	0.0512	0.1418	0	0.002	0.0017	0.0014	0.0008	0.0012	0.4972	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0945	0.1812	0	0	0	0	0.0014	0.0016	0.493	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.3426	0.9095	4.6142	0	0	0	0.0143	0.0127	0.0385	0.4384	5		0
0	0	0	0	0.0434	0.2402	0	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0021	0.461	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.2087	0.6378	1.1772	1.63	0	0.0007	0.0174	0.0266	0.0164	0.0136	0.289	1		0
0.0237	0.1418	0.2323	0.3977	0.8465	2.756	0.0079	0.0237	0.0194	0.0166	0.0118	0.023	0.357	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.2126	0.4252	0.7245	0	0	0	0.0089	0.006	0.0061	0.264	4	3	0
0	0.1103	0.4252	1.0315	2.0119	4.7402	0	0.0184	0.0355	0.043	0.028	0.0396	0.3898	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0749	0.0749	0.193	0	0	0	0.0032	0.0011	0.0017	0.315	1		0
0	0	0.0119	0.0276	0.8898	2.3898	0	0	0.001	0.0012	0.0124	0.02	0.502	1	3	0
0.0552	0.0788	0.0788	0.2796	0.4725	0.5355	0.0184	0.0132	0.0066	0.0117	0.0066	0.0045	0.418	1	3	0
0.504	1.0985	1.5906	1.6378	2.2796	2.9686	0.168	0.1831	0.1326	0.0683	0.0317	0.0248	0.2632	1	4	0
0	0.0119	0.0119	0.1221	0.4252	0.8465	0	0.002	0.001	0.0051	0.006	0.0071	0.348	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0788	0.4882	1.3741	0	0	0	0.0033	0.0068	0.0115	0.5106	3	4	0
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.2678	0.4095	0.9804	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0112	0.0057	0.0082	0.409	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.067	0.1182	0.1693	0	0	0	0.0028	0.0017	0.0015	0.426	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1103	0.2796	0.4134	0	0	0	0.0046	0.0039	0.0035	0.225	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0827	0.1733	0.3544	0	0	0	0.0035	0.0025	0.003	0.306	2	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0394	0.0394	0	0	0	0	0.0006	0.0004	0.484	1	3	0
0	0	0.0867	0.9095	3.3819	3.7481	0	0	0.0073	0.0379	0.047	0.0313	0.4217	3	3	0
0	0.0079	0.1536	0.3386	0.504	0.7638	0	0.0014	0.0128	0.0142	0.007	0.0064	0.3948	1		0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.488	1		0
0.0237	0.1063	0.1063	0.1182	0.5945	0.6497	0.0079	0.0178	0.0089	0.005	0.0083	0.0055	0.482	1	3	0
0.004	0.0591	0.1182	0.1182	0.1339	0.1536	0.0014	0.0099	0.0099	0.005	0.0019	0.0013	0.293	1	3	0
0.0158	0.0355	0.0394	0.0945	0.878	0.8859	0.0053	0.006	0.0033	0.004	0.0122	0.0074	0	1	4	0
0.1063	0.1418	0.1615	0.4607	0.63	1.0985	0.0355	0.0237	0.0135	0.0192	0.0088	0.0092	0.3933	1		0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.2245	1.5473	2.4567	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0094	0.0215	0.0205	0.3988	5	4	0
0	0.0276	0.0315	0.1693	0.189	0.4489	0	0.0046	0.0027	0.0071	0.0027	0.0038	0.3778	1	1	0
0	0	0.0276	0.0276	0.1733	0.2678	0	0	0.0023	0.0012	0.0025	0.0023	0.4913	1	2	0
0.004	0.0158	0.1969	0.2993	0.7796	1.689	0.0014	0.0027	0.0165	0.0125	0.0109	0.0141	0.411	1	3	0
0.004	0.0158	0.0473	0.0945	0.2363	0.8229	0.0014	0.0027	0.004	0.004	0.0033	0.0069	0.4193	4	4	0
0.0119	0.0197	0.0197	0.0197	0.193	0.1969	0.004	0.0033	0.0017	0.0009	0.0027	0.0017	0.392	3	4	0
0	0.004	0.004	0.0355	0.1575	2.693	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0015	0.0022	0.0225	0.397	1	2	0
0	0	0	0.1851	0.6103	1.5512	0	0	0	0.0078	0.0085	0.013	0.437	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.2323	1.2638	2.3662	0	0	0	0.0097	0.0176	0.0198	0.272	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0119	0.0158	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0002	0.0002	0.3291	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0276	0.5709	4.1142	4.1615	0.0027	0.0014	0.0023	0.0238	0.0572	0.0347	0.4686	1	3	0

0	0	0.0197	0.0276	0.3859	0.5276	0	0	0.0017	0.0012	0.0054	0.0044	0.314	1	0	
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.2087	0.3268	0.4371	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0087	0.0046	0.0037	0.331	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.0985	0.8347	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0014	0.007	0.377	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.4056	0.6654	0	0	0	0	0.0057	0.0056	0.4021	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0276	0.0749	0.4016	0.8898	0.0027	0.0014	0.0023	0.0032	0.0056	0.0075	0.281	1	0	0
0.004	0.004	0.0237	0.315	0.63	0.6339	0.0014	0.0007	0.002	0.0132	0.0088	0.0053	0.3878	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.0079	0.2953	0.8268	0.8268	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0124	0.0115	0.0069	0.467	1	1	0
0.1378	0.2363	0.4607	0.7717	0.8701	1.1575	0.046	0.0394	0.0384	0.0322	0.0121	0.0097	0.341	1	3	0
0	0.0119	0.126	0.3347	1.256	1.3426	0	0.002	0.0105	0.014	0.0175	0.0112	0.471	3	3	0
0	0	0.4016	0.4804	1.7087	1.9686	0	0	0.0335	0.0201	0.0238	0.0165	0.384	2	1	0
0	0	0.0158	0.13	1.756	3.3623	0	0	0.0014	0.0055	0.0244	0.0281	0.4373	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1457	0.6418	1.2717	0	0	0	0.0061	0.009	0.0106	0.18	1	4	0
0	0	0.0158	0.1063	0.5119	1.6575	0	0	0.0014	0.0045	0.0072	0.0139	0.505	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0315	0.0315	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0003	0.428	2	1	0
0	0.004	0.004	0.315	0.4016	0.8859	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0132	0.0056	0.0074	0.4256	1	0	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.004	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0001	0.291	1	4	0
0	0	0.0788	0.0788	0.1812	0.1812	0	0	0.0066	0.0033	0.0026	0.0016	0.273	1	3	0
0	0.0237	0.0788	0.1063	0.2875	1.7914	0	0.004	0.0066	0.0045	0.004	0.015	0.3977	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.0552	0.0552	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0008	0.0005	0.332	2	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.2717	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0023	0.405	1	1	0
0	0	0.1497	0.2599	0.3032	0.504	0	0	0.0125	0.0109	0.0043	0.0042	0.4951	1	1	0
0	0.0158	0.0512	0.0827	0.4056	1.2441	0	0.0027	0.0043	0.0035	0.0057	0.0104	0.442	3	4	0
0	0	0	0.4056	1.3977	1.9804	0	0	0	0.0169	0.0195	0.0166	0.317	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.0394	0.0512	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0006	0.0005	0.4352	1	3	0
0	0.0197	0.0197	0.2756	0.378	0.378	0	0.0033	0.0017	0.0115	0.0053	0.0032	0.39	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.815	2.0119	0	0	0	0	0.0114	0.0168	0.4681	1	0	0
0	0	0	0.1103	0.378	0.5237	0	0	0	0.0046	0.0053	0.0044	0.4933	1	2	0
0	0	0.1339	0.5709	0.9725	2.9331	0	0	0.0112	0.0238	0.0136	0.0245	0.355	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0867	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0008	0.309	1	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.2835	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0024	0.348	1	4	0
0.193	0.2993	0.3898	0.6575	3.2835	5.878	0.0644	0.0499	0.0325	0.0274	0.0457	0.049	0.3416	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0355	0.2245	0.2756	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0015	0.0032	0.0023	0.4913	2	0	0
0.0197	0.0197	0.0749	0.1733	0.6772	1.067	0.0066	0.0033	0.0063	0.0073	0.0095	0.0089	0.438	2	3	0
0.0552	0.1063	0.1969	0.6221	1.5552	2.9449	0.0184	0.0178	0.0165	0.026	0.0216	0.0246	0.3994	1	0	0
0.252	0.4174	0.9764	1.0709	1.5315	1.9764	0.084	0.0696	0.0814	0.0447	0.0213	0.0165	0.195	1	3	0
0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.0276	0.1063	0.13	0.0079	0.004	0.002	0.0012	0.0015	0.0011	0.312	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.1575	0	0	0	0	0	0.0014	0.38	1	0	0
0	0.0079	0.067	0.0945	0.2363	0.8426	0	0.0014	0.0056	0.004	0.0033	0.0071	0.5136	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.063	0.4764	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0009	0.004	0.267	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0315	0.0434	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0004	0.2605	1	3	0
0	0.0315	0.0315	0.0355	0.1142	0.5867	0	0.0053	0.0027	0.0015	0.0016	0.0049	0.417	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.1103	0.2875	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0016	0.0024	0.371	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0237	0.3898	2.3347	0	0	0	0.001	0.0055	0.0195	0.505	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.1615	0.3032	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0023	0.0026	0.4022	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0119	0.3189	0.3819	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0045	0.0032	0.2061	2	3	0
0	0	0.0355	0.4882	0.8071	1.0867	0	0	0.003	0.0204	0.0113	0.0091	0.205	1	1	0
0.004	0.004	0.0079	0.0315	0.1339	0.3898	0.0014	0.0007	0.0007	0.0014	0.0019	0.0033	0.492	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0276	0.0276	0.0473	0.0788	0.0985	0.004	0.0046	0.0023	0.002	0.0011	0.0009	0.46	1	3	0

0	0	0	0	0.0512	0.0512	0	0	0	0	0.0008	0.0005	0.4075	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.13	0.2126	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0019	0.0018	0.4021	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.4121	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.1182	0.1575	1.3229	0	0	0	0.005	0.0022	0.0111	0.501	1	3	0
0.004	0.0827	0.3662	0.6497	2.3583	5.193	0.0014	0.0138	0.0306	0.0271	0.0328	0.0433	0.3874	1	4	0
0.067	0.1418	0.1615	0.3623	0.6654	0.9331	0.0224	0.0237	0.0135	0.0151	0.0093	0.0078	0.408	4	3	0
0	0.0158	0.1103	0.189	0.5906	1.193	0	0.0027	0.0092	0.0079	0.0083	0.01	0.456	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0237	0.1418	0.1615	0	0	0	0.001	0.002	0.0014	0.364	3	2	0
0.0079	0.0276	0.0434	0.0552	0.2087	0.9252	0.0027	0.0046	0.0037	0.0023	0.0029	0.0078	0.293	4	4	0
0.1536	0.2284	0.3426	0.6812	1.4489	2.4095	0.0512	0.0381	0.0286	0.0284	0.0202	0.0201	0.222	1	3	0
0.0119	0.063	0.1457	0.2245	0.3426	0.4843	0.004	0.0105	0.0122	0.0094	0.0048	0.0041	0.429	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0237	0.0355	0.0355	1.193	2.7166	0.0027	0.004	0.003	0.0015	0.0166	0.0227	0.4151	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0119	0.0276	0.2796	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0004	0.0024	0.415	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.0237	1.2835	1.7048	0	0	0	0.001	0.0179	0.0143	0.4041	3	2	0
0.0079	0.0237	0.5197	2.0985	2.9686	3.0394	0.0027	0.004	0.0434	0.0875	0.0413	0.0254	0.3611	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0512	0.3859	0	0	0	0	0.0008	0.0033	0.416	1	1	0
0.004	0.004	0.1182	0.2245	0.4646	1.13	0.0014	0.0007	0.0099	0.0094	0.0065	0.0095	0.266	4	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.063	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0006	0.476	2	4	0
0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.1772	1.0827	2.2599	0.004	0.0027	0.0014	0.0074	0.0151	0.0189	0.2755	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	1.8268	2.189	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0254	0.0183	0.48	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0749	0.3662	0.4528	0	0	0	0.0032	0.0051	0.0038	0.2963	1	4	0
0	0	0.1103	0.1142	0.2205	0.3623	0	0	0.0092	0.0048	0.0031	0.0031	0.3561	4	1	0
0.0119	0.0237	0.0512	0.2008	0.2875	1.063	0.004	0.004	0.0043	0.0084	0.004	0.0089	0.42	1		0
0	0.0237	0.0276	0.5158	0.941	1.2756	0	0.004	0.0023	0.0215	0.0131	0.0107	0.408	1	3	0
0	0	0.0119	1.6733	2.4331	2.9686	0	0	0.001	0.0698	0.0338	0.0248	0.4315	1	3	0
0.0276	0.1063	0.2875	0.7087	1.193	1.4804	0.0092	0.0178	0.024	0.0296	0.0166	0.0124	0.4363	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1615	0.2875	0.3819	0	0	0	0.0068	0.004	0.0032	0.3968	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.13	0.4528	0.7323	0	0	0	0.0055	0.0063	0.0062	0.493	1	1	0
0	0.0079	0.0119	0.6575	5.8111	6.8544	0	0.0014	0.001	0.0274	0.0808	0.0572	0.3849	1	4	0
0.0158	0.0276	0.0434	0.0591	0.1654	0.1851	0.0053	0.0046	0.0037	0.0025	0.0023	0.0016	0.362	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0394	0	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.462	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.13	0.2717	1.1221	0	0	0	0.0055	0.0038	0.0094	0.4251	1	1	0
0	0	0.004	0.067	3.0119	9.0827	0	0	0.0004	0.0028	0.0419	0.0757	0.515	1	4	0
0	0	0.0158	0.0158	0.0906	0.5788	0	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0013	0.0049	0.4581	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0315	0.5	0.6733	0	0	0	0.0014	0.007	0.0057	0.387	2	4	0
0	0.004	0.0079	0.063	0.5827	0.7402	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0027	0.0081	0.0062	0.4662	1		0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0552	0.2993	0.3544	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0023	0.0042	0.003	0.411	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.3308	0.3701	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0046	0.0031	0.367	3	4	0
0.0237	0.0315	0.063	0.7835	2.2678	2.689	0.0079	0.0053	0.0053	0.0327	0.0315	0.0225	0.3661	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.0788	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0007	0.364	5	3	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.2166	0.3071	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0031	0.0026	0.325	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0119	0.0355	0.2008	1.6378	2.2875	0.004	0.002	0.003	0.0084	0.0228	0.0191	0.4207	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.1221	0.189	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0017	0.0016	0.466	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0355	0	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.349	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1851	0.7993	0.8465	0	0	0	0.0078	0.0112	0.0071	0.4266	3	3	0
0	0	0.0906	0.6851	1.9016	3.0355	0	0	0.0076	0.0286	0.0265	0.0253	0.508	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1457	0.3426	2.9882	0	0	0	0.0061	0.0048	0.025	0.3336	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.1575	0.1615	0	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0014	0.424	1		0

0	0	0	0.0394	0.0394	0.0473	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0006	0.0004	0	4	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.1457	0.2796	3.9213	0	0	0.0007	0.0061	0.0039	0.0327	0.5145	1	2	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.0001	0.431	2	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0	2	3	0
0	0.004	0.0079	0.1182	1.004	1.1221	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.005	0.014	0.0094	0.4205	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0788	0.5473	1.6221	0	0	0	0.0033	0.0077	0.0136	0.267	1	1	0
0.0434	0.067	0.0709	0.1024	0.1693	0.2008	0.0145	0.0112	0.006	0.0043	0.0024	0.0017	0.5	1	3	0
0.0788	0.1812	0.2638	0.8623	1.6063	2.6103	0.0263	0.0302	0.022	0.036	0.0224	0.0218	0.482	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.1024	0.1418	0.193	0	0	0	0.0043	0.002	0.0017	0.406	3	3	0
0	0	0.126	1.0315	1.0709	1.2323	0	0	0.0105	0.043	0.0149	0.0103	0.456	3	4	0
0	0	0	0.2284	0.3741	0.4134	0	0	0	0.0096	0.0052	0.0035	0.271	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0237	0.2048	1.2953	0	0	0	0.001	0.0029	0.0108	0.4683	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.63	0.7914	0.8741	0	0	0	0.0263	0.011	0.0073	0.324	1	3	0
0.0237	0.0355	0.0552	0.3071	0.9882	1.0434	0.0079	0.006	0.0046	0.0128	0.0138	0.0087	0.424	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0985	0.2914	0.5394	0	0	0	0.0042	0.0041	0.0045	0.299	2	3	0
0.0237	0.0237	0.0709	0.1969	0.3938	0.689	0.0079	0.004	0.006	0.0083	0.0055	0.0058	0.4248	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	1.5394	3.5591	0	0	0	0	0.0214	0.0297	0.42	1	2	0
0	0.004	0.0434	1.2441	4.1063	4.9922	0	0.0007	0.0037	0.0519	0.0571	0.0417	0.453	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.1339	0.2245	0	0	0	0	0.0019	0.0019	0.3216	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0079	1.6812	3.9331	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0234	0.0328	0.429	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.4134	0.6575	0.9056	0	0	0	0.0173	0.0092	0.0076	0.407	2	1	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0434	1.8583	2.0867	0	0	0.0007	0.0019	0.0259	0.0174	0.363	1	3	0
0	0.0158	0.1142	0.3504	0.4371	0.752	0	0.0027	0.0096	0.0146	0.0061	0.0063	0.5081	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.0276	0.1693	0.4607	1.5512	0	0.0007	0.0023	0.0071	0.0064	0.013	0.371	5	4	0
0.0788	0.1497	0.1497	0.193	0.8504	1.9607	0.0263	0.025	0.0125	0.0081	0.0119	0.0164	0.4924	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.0473	0.6063	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0007	0.0051	0.3055	1	2	0
0	0	0	0.0985	0.2166	0.3701	0	0	0	0.0042	0.0031	0.0031	0.4033	1	2	0
0	0	0.0827	0.2638	1.6378	2.7796	0	0	0.0069	0.011	0.0228	0.0232	0.4759	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.0315	0.0552	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0005	0.0005	0.3902	1	1	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0867	1.4213	2.7166	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0037	0.0198	0.0227	0.3862	2	1	0
0.0512	0.0867	0.1182	0.2756	0.7166	1.2008	0.0171	0.0145	0.0099	0.0115	0.01	0.0101	0.456	1	3	0
0	0	0.0158	0.2402	0.4646	0.7481	0	0	0.0014	0.0101	0.0065	0.0063	0.48	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.0276	0.0552	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0005	0.347	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.446	1	3	0
0.0276	0.1575	0.189	0.6221	1.2599	1.9449	0.0092	0.0263	0.0158	0.026	0.0175	0.0163	0.396	4	3	0
0	0	0	0.1063	0.689	1.315	0	0	0	0.0045	0.0096	0.011	0.386	1		0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0749	0.1339	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0011	0.0012	0.4113	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.6339	1.0237	1.3583	0	0	0	0.0265	0.0143	0.0114	0.4832	1	2	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.0434	0.067	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0007	0.0006	0.4183	3	1	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0355	0.063	0.0945	0	0	0.0007	0.0015	0.0009	0.0008	0.3483	1	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.1103	0.4134	1.1969	0	0	0.0007	0.0046	0.0058	0.01	0.329	1	4	0
0	0	0.0158	0.3859	0.4725	0.756	0	0	0.0014	0.0161	0.0066	0.0063	0.431	1	2	0
0	0	0.0276	0.0906	0.3819	0.3819	0	0	0.0023	0.0038	0.0054	0.0032	0.47	1	3	0
0.0237	0.0788	0.0867	0.1693	0.878	1.5158	0.0079	0.0132	0.0073	0.0071	0.0122	0.0127	0.419	1	4	0
0	0	0.0473	0.0906	0.6615	0.8898	0	0	0.004	0.0038	0.0092	0.0075	0.302	2	3	0
0.0197	0.0906	0.256	0.4449	0.8701	0.9725	0.0066	0.0151	0.0214	0.0186	0.0121	0.0082	0.285	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.0158	0.1575	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0003	0.0014	0.3812	1	2	0
0	0	0.0158	0.2756	2.4016	2.7008	0	0	0.0014	0.0115	0.0334	0.0226	0.504	1	2	0

0	0	0	0	0.067	0.2875	0	0	0	0	0.001	0.0024	0.4684	3	4	0
0	0	0.0473	0.2323	0.3938	1.2048	0	0	0.004	0.0097	0.0055	0.0101	0.396	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.4623	5	3	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.2087	0.563	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0029	0.0047	0.313	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.0237	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.37	1	3	0
0	0.0119	0.0158	0.2048	0.7875	1.2008	0	0.002	0.0014	0.0086	0.011	0.0101	0.5023	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.193	0	0	0	0	0	0.0017	0.3495	1	3	0
0.0158	0.1024	0.1339	0.5276	0.6575	0.7638	0.0053	0.0171	0.0112	0.022	0.0092	0.0064	0.3788	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0906	0.1536	0	0	0	0	0.0013	0.0013	0.3791	3	3	0
0.0315	0.0512	0.063	0.0867	0.1142	0.1182	0.0105	0.0086	0.0053	0.0037	0.0016	0.001	0.153	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.0276	0.2363	2.6339	2.752	0.0014	0.0007	0.0023	0.0099	0.0366	0.023	0.4282	1	3	0
0.0276	0.0355	0.0434	0.0512	0.5512	2.6418	0.0092	0.006	0.0037	0.0022	0.0077	0.0221	0.394	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.0552	0.0827	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0008	0.0007	0.3899	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.2087	0.5788	0	0	0	0	0.0029	0.0049	0.2773	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0276	0.1103	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.001	0.3797	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.3741	1.0945	1.5945	0	0	0	0.0156	0.0153	0.0133	0.292	5	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0158	0.2481	0.256	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0007	0.0035	0.0022	0.3212	1	3	0
0	0	0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.0473	0	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0003	0.0004	0.4781	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0473	0.0473	0.063	0	0	0	0.002	0.0007	0.0006	0.476	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.126	0	0	0	0	0	0.0011	0.406	4	3	0
0.0197	0.0197	0.0394	0.0394	0.2638	0.3426	0.0066	0.0033	0.0033	0.0017	0.0037	0.0029	0.391	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0552	0.5591	1.5	0	0	0	0.0023	0.0078	0.0125	0.388	2	1	0
0	0.0985	0.3386	0.4095	1.4331	1.752	0	0.0165	0.0283	0.0171	0.02	0.0146	0.497	1		0
0	0	0	0.0591	0.9174	1.315	0	0	0	0.0025	0.0128	0.011	0.3562	1	3	0
0.004	0.0237	0.0355	0.2166	0.5197	1.9686	0.0014	0.004	0.003	0.0091	0.0073	0.0165	0.313	5		0
0.0158	0.0473	0.0473	0.1615	0.3347	0.6339	0.0053	0.0079	0.004	0.0068	0.0047	0.0053	0.4962	1	3	0
0	0.126	0.126	0.2441	1.0591	1.7284	0	0.021	0.0105	0.0102	0.0148	0.0145	0.3946	3	4	0
0.067	0.2245	0.3544	0.7363	2.3544	2.9095	0.0224	0.0375	0.0296	0.0307	0.0327	0.0243	0.4106	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0355	0.1812	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0005	0.0016	0.312	1	4	0
0.2126	0.4686	1.0394	3.2914	4.8583	5.4489	0.0709	0.0781	0.0867	0.1372	0.0675	0.0455	0.074	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.5827	2.4371	0	0	0	0	0.0081	0.0204	0.293	1	3	0
0	0	0.004	0.4528	4.378	4.7284	0	0	0.0004	0.0189	0.0609	0.0395	0.4248	3	4	0
0.0079	0.3938	0.563	0.6575	0.8426	1.0591	0.0027	0.0657	0.047	0.0274	0.0118	0.0089	0.292	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0434	0.256	0.4528	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0019	0.0036	0.0038	0.502	1		0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.0709	0.5827	0	0	0	0.0012	0.001	0.0049	0.298	2	1	0
0.0079	0.0237	0.126	0.2284	1.2205	2.8623	0.0027	0.004	0.0105	0.0096	0.017	0.0239	0.423	1		0
0	0	0	0.126	0.2796	3.0788	0	0	0	0.0053	0.0039	0.0257	0	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0158	0.0276	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0003	0.0003	0.329	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0197	0.2087	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0003	0.0018	0.335	1	3	0
0	0	0.0355	0.5197	2.3938	6.6221	0	0	0.003	0.0217	0.0333	0.0552	0.4741	1	2	0
0.004	0.0237	0.0237	0.1418	0.567	2.315	0.0014	0.004	0.002	0.006	0.0079	0.0193	0.418	1		0
0	0	0	0.0552	0.2402	1.9961	0	0	0	0.0023	0.0034	0.0167	0.5015	1	3	0
0	0	0.0119	0.3386	0.3662	0.4567	0	0	0.001	0.0142	0.0051	0.0039	0.39	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.3701	1.4528	2.689	0	0	0	0.0155	0.0202	0.0225	0.364	1	4	0
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0158	0.0434	0.0709	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0007	0.0007	0.0006	0.307	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0512	0.252	0.2638	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0035	0.0022	0.4	1	3	0
0	0	0.0512	0.0512	0.2796	0.7756	0	0	0.0043	0.0022	0.0039	0.0065	0.417	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.1103	0.3189	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0016	0.0027	0.485	1		0

0	0	0.0749	0.1654	0.2008	0.9489	0	0	0.0063	0.0069	0.0028	0.008	0.498	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.0709	0.504	0.6182	0	0	0	0.003	0.007	0.0052	0.4944	1	4	0
0.004	0.1418	0.1418	0.315	0.6615	0.7363	0.0014	0.0237	0.0119	0.0132	0.0092	0.0062	0.5059	2	4	0
0.0394	0.0552	0.1812	0.3386	0.7599	1.2796	0.0132	0.0092	0.0151	0.0142	0.0106	0.0107	0.4071	2	4	0
0.0197	0.0197	0.0197	0.0197	0.0197	0.0197	0.0066	0.0033	0.0017	0.0009	0.0003	0.0002	0.222	1	2	0
0	0.004	0.004	0.1693	0.7087	0.7245	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0071	0.0099	0.0061	0.2312	2	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0197	0.8111	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0068	0.3923	1	3	0
0.1142	0.1221	0.1378	0.3938	1.5079	1.5552	0.0381	0.0204	0.0115	0.0165	0.021	0.013	0.408	2	2	0
0.0237	0.063	0.2402	0.5906	1.1733	1.4764	0.0079	0.0105	0.0201	0.0247	0.0163	0.0124	0.4551	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.2402	0	0	0	0	0	0.0021	0.361	2	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3503	1	4	0
0.1536	0.2126	0.9371	1.7205	2.1103	4.8662	0.0512	0.0355	0.0781	0.0717	0.0294	0.0406	0.511	1	3	0
0.0591	0.0788	0.0867	0.1182	1.6182	1.8898	0.0197	0.0132	0.0073	0.005	0.0225	0.0158	0.3721	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1339	0.1615	1.1733	0	0	0	0.0056	0.0023	0.0098	0.4	1	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.1851	0.3859	0.7126	0	0	0.0007	0.0078	0.0054	0.006	0.5015	3		0
0	0	0.0434	0.067	0.504	2.3268	0	0	0.0037	0.0028	0.007	0.0194	0.396	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0315	0.1142	0.2205	0	0	0	0.0014	0.0016	0.0019	0.4224	1	3	0
0.004	0.0158	0.063	0.126	0.4331	0.5552	0.0014	0.0027	0.0053	0.0053	0.0061	0.0047	0.465	1	2	0
0	0.0276	0.0276	0.13	0.1851	0.3898	0	0.0046	0.0023	0.0055	0.0026	0.0033	0.4187	2	3	0
0.0276	0.0394	0.0867	0.1378	0.4528	0.7678	0.0092	0.0066	0.0073	0.0058	0.0063	0.0064	0.4475	2	1	0
0	0	0	0.626	1.5079	1.9686	0	0	0	0.0261	0.021	0.0165	0.4	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.7481	1.4174	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0104	0.0119	0.2291	1	4	0
0	0	0.0119	0.0119	0.1457	0.315	0	0	0.001	0.0005	0.0021	0.0027	0.472	1	3	0
0	0.1063	0.6418	0.9528	1.9922	3.3898	0	0.0178	0.0535	0.0397	0.0277	0.0283	0.424	1	3	0
0	0	0.0119	0.0119	0.2284	0.878	0	0	0.001	0.0005	0.0032	0.0074	0	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0827	0.1497	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0012	0.0013	0.471	1	1	0
0	0.004	0.0237	0.4922	1.8977	2.1378	0	0.0007	0.002	0.0206	0.0264	0.0179	0	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.0552	0.1497	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0008	0.0013	0.3318	1	3	0
0.0434	0.1103	0.2205	1.1575	2.1182	2.1339	0.0145	0.0184	0.0184	0.0483	0.0295	0.0178	0.4968	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.2599	2.3504	3.0473	0	0	0	0.0109	0.0327	0.0254	0.411	2	3	0
0	0.0197	0.3189	0.4882	1.3977	1.5119	0	0.0033	0.0266	0.0204	0.0195	0.0126	0.4351	1	3	0
0.0355	0.0749	0.126	0.1339	0.2087	1.4528	0.0119	0.0125	0.0105	0.0056	0.0029	0.0122	0.4811	3	3	0
0.2441	0.4174	0.4371	0.4646	0.5079	0.9646	0.0814	0.0696	0.0365	0.0194	0.0071	0.0081	0.49	1	3	0
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.1536	0.1812	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0022	0.0016	0.495	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.13	0.315	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0019	0.0027	0.4992	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.0276	0.0434	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0004	0.4202	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.0237	0.4686	0.63	0	0	0	0.001	0.0066	0.0053	0.233	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0591	0.0749	0	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0007	0.3605	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0552	0.1497	0	0	0	0	0.0008	0.0013	0.414	2	3	0
0.0355	0.1418	0.3071	1.0276	2.193	2.2678	0.0119	0.0237	0.0256	0.0429	0.0305	0.0189	0	2	1	0
0.0158	0.0237	0.0276	0.1733	0.7796	1.1615	0.0053	0.004	0.0023	0.0073	0.0109	0.0097	0.507	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.504	1.3386	1.7126	0	0	0	0.021	0.0186	0.0143	0.352	1	3	0
0.1339	0.256	0.4213	0.9686	2.4528	3.1575	0.0447	0.0427	0.0352	0.0404	0.0341	0.0264	0.419	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0394	2.8583	3.756	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0397	0.0313	0.3639	1	3	0
0.0985	0.315	0.3583	0.5	1.756	2.8977	0.0329	0.0525	0.0299	0.0209	0.0244	0.0242	0.227	4	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.0394	0.0394	0	0	0	0	0.0006	0.0004	0.441	1	4	0
0.0158	0.0276	0.1024	0.1103	0.3111	0.5867	0.0053	0.0046	0.0086	0.0046	0.0044	0.0049	0.227	1	4	0
0.1654	0.3544	0.7245	0.9331	2.3583	3.9213	0.0552	0.0591	0.0604	0.0389	0.0328	0.0327	0.4227	1	3	0

0	0	0.063	0.315	1.2756	1.7166	0	0	0.0053	0.0132	0.0178	0.0144	0.3463	2	4	0
0	0.0079	0.2323	0.7363	0.8741	1.1536	0	0.0014	0.0194	0.0307	0.0122	0.0097	0.227	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0591	0.0788	0.0985	0	0	0	0.0025	0.0011	0.0009	0.498	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.0473	0.2245	0.3701	0	0	0	0.002	0.0032	0.0031	0.4013	4	4	0
0	0	0.0355	0.0512	0.0512	0.0512	0	0	0.003	0.0022	0.0008	0.0005	0.4634	1	4	0
0	0.0158	0.0709	0.0906	0.4646	1.0945	0	0.0027	0.006	0.0038	0.0065	0.0092	0.459	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.4213	0.5394	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0059	0.0045	0.369	2	1	0
0.1221	0.1418	0.1418	0.2678	1.1733	1.2638	0.0407	0.0237	0.0119	0.0112	0.0163	0.0106	0.328	1	3	0
0	0	0.004	0.063	5.8229	6.9371	0	0	0.0004	0.0027	0.0809	0.0579	0.4873	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0197	0	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.3296	6	3	0
0.0158	0.0315	0.0512	0.063	0.4016	1.0276	0.0053	0.0053	0.0043	0.0027	0.0056	0.0086	0.502	1		0
0	0	0	0.1024	0.1457	0.1851	0	0	0	0.0043	0.0021	0.0016	0.4208	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.0434	0.0906	0.3583	0.693	0.0014	0.0007	0.0037	0.0038	0.005	0.0058	0.5107	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0315	0.063	0.1221	0	0	0	0.0014	0.0009	0.0011	0.3132	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0315	0	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.3531	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.3938	1.6733	3.5079	0	0	0	0.0165	0.0233	0.0293	0.5	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.4843	1.1063	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0068	0.0093	0.4781	5	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0276	0	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.23	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0197	1.1103	4.0867	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0155	0.0341	0.5028	1		0
0	0	0	0.0434	0.189	1.3347	0	0	0	0.0019	0.0027	0.0112	0.421	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.0315	0.3071	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0026	0.302	1	3	0
0.0237	0.0276	0.0276	0.063	0.1418	0.1654	0.0079	0.0046	0.0023	0.0027	0.002	0.0014	0.261	1		0
0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0.252	0.626	0.9252	0.0027	0.002	0.001	0.0105	0.0087	0.0078	0.305	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.1733	0.7048	0	0	0	0	0.0025	0.0059	0.4221	1		0
0	0	0	0.0985	0.3504	0.6024	0	0	0	0.0042	0.0049	0.0051	0.398	1		0
0	0	0.1851	0.3386	1.0315	1.4607	0	0	0.0155	0.0142	0.0144	0.0122	0.382	1	3	0
0.0591	0.2481	0.5315	1.1497	1.693	1.693	0.0197	0.0414	0.0443	0.048	0.0236	0.0142	0.3151	1	3	0
0.0158	0.0237	0.0237	0.0315	2.567	3.2835	0.0053	0.004	0.002	0.0014	0.0357	0.0274	0.406	3	3	0
0.0119	0.0355	0.1457	0.6536	1.3938	1.8504	0.004	0.006	0.0122	0.0273	0.0194	0.0155	0.373	1	2	0
0.0237	0.126	0.3544	0.5	4.1615	8.5788	0.0079	0.021	0.0296	0.0209	0.0578	0.0715	0.5167	1		0
0.0434	0.0434	0.0749	0.1103	0.1536	0.5394	0.0145	0.0073	0.0063	0.0046	0.0022	0.0045	0.345	1	3	0
0	0	0.0473	0.1457	0.6024	0.7048	0	0	0.004	0.0061	0.0084	0.0059	0.413	1	3	0
0.0749	0.193	0.2796	0.3701	0.5945	0.6812	0.025	0.0322	0.0233	0.0155	0.0083	0.0057	0.442	1	1	0
0	0	0.0079	0.2796	0.3544	0.8583	0	0	0.0007	0.0117	0.005	0.0072	0.2753	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0158	0.0749	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0007	0.34	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0.1733	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0005	0.0002	0.0015	0.358	2	4	0
0	0	0.0552	0.1024	1.7126	1.7835	0	0	0.0046	0.0043	0.0238	0.0149	0.404	3	2	0
0	0	0	0.0237	0.752	0.9607	0	0	0	0.001	0.0105	0.0081	0.4811	1	3	0
0	0	0.3504	1.5867	3.2166	3.3662	0	0	0.0292	0.0662	0.0447	0.0281	0.3981	1	3	0
0	0.0158	0.0591	0.0827	0.2048	13.6654	0	0.0027	0.005	0.0035	0.0029	0.1139	0.4067	4	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.6103	0.8623	0	0	0	0	0.0085	0.0072	0.345	1		0
0.0079	0.0079	0.067	0.5276	1.3544	1.378	0.0027	0.0014	0.0056	0.022	0.0189	0.0115	0.497	2	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.0355	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0003	0.3925	1	1	0
0.0237	0.0237	0.0827	0.1339	0.1772	0.3898	0.0079	0.004	0.0069	0.0056	0.0025	0.0033	0	2	3	0
0.0394	0.0473	0.0906	0.1103	0.6969	1.7087	0.0132	0.0079	0.0076	0.0046	0.0097	0.0143	0.5069	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.0394	0.2678	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0006	0.0023	0.4135	1	3	0
0.1142	0.2441	0.4252	0.5788	0.815	1.1733	0.0381	0.0407	0.0355	0.0242	0.0114	0.0098	0.429	1	4	0
0.0197	0.0197	0.0788	0.1182	0.256	0.5473	0.0066	0.0033	0.0066	0.005	0.0036	0.0046	0.4617	1	1	0

0	0	0	0.0158	0.1693	0.5119	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0024	0.0043	0.4428	1	1	0
0	0.0394	0.0394	0.6851	0.8426	1.0079	0	0.0066	0.0033	0.0286	0.0118	0.0084	0.3245	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.1024	0.4016	1.1221	0	0	0	0.0043	0.0056	0.0094	0.492	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0158	0.0394	0.1103	1.5749	4.4252	0.0027	0.0027	0.0033	0.0046	0.0219	0.0369	0.3894	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.13	0.4252	0.7323	0	0	0	0.0055	0.006	0.0062	0.413	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.0079	0.256	4.0394	4.4882	0.0014	0.0007	0.0007	0.0107	0.0562	0.0375	0.243	1		0
0	0	0	0.0945	1.0434	2.0434	0	0	0	0.004	0.0145	0.0171	0.4533	1	3	0
0	0.0119	0.067	0.2126	1.0276	1.0512	0	0.002	0.0056	0.0089	0.0143	0.0088	0.5055	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.6142	1.7993	0	0	0	0	0.0086	0.015	0	2	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.3032	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0026	0.3667	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.0276	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0003	0.374	2	3	0
0	0	0.1536	0.315	0.567	0.5709	0	0	0.0128	0.0132	0.0079	0.0048	0.395	5	3	0
0.1182	0.2205	0.2796	0.4174	0.6969	1.3032	0.0394	0.0368	0.0233	0.0174	0.0097	0.0109	0.327	1	3	0
0	0	0.0512	0.3071	0.3859	2.5827	0	0	0.0043	0.0128	0.0054	0.0216	0.418	1		0
0	0.0355	0.0394	0.1063	0.3308	1.0276	0	0.006	0.0033	0.0045	0.0046	0.0086	0.4972	1	1	0
0.0355	0.067	0.067	0.1654	0.63	1.7875	0.0119	0.0112	0.0056	0.0069	0.0088	0.0149	0.4492	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.3386	0.9174	1.3032	0	0	0	0.0142	0.0128	0.0109	0.4264	5	3	0
0.378	0.7875	1.4292	2.7756	4.1969	4.4882	0.126	0.1313	0.1191	0.1157	0.0583	0.0375	0.283	1	4	0
0	0	0.0434	0.3938	1.4646	1.8386	0	0	0.0037	0.0165	0.0204	0.0154	0.4207	2	3	0
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0197	0.2363	0.941	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0009	0.0033	0.0079	0.39	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0867	0.2717	0.315	0.9686	2.4646	0.004	0.0145	0.0227	0.0132	0.0135	0.0206	0.428	1	2	0
0.1182	0.126	0.1772	0.3268	0.9764	1.1654	0.0394	0.021	0.0148	0.0137	0.0136	0.0098	0.507	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.4016	0.4016	0	0	0	0	0.0056	0.0034	0.4832	5	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.0591	0.1221	0.5591	1.6969	0.0014	0.0007	0.005	0.0051	0.0078	0.0142	0.285	4	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.0079	0.2953	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0025	0.3682	1	3	0
0.004	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0906	0.1142	0.0014	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0013	0.001	0.4373	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.0197	0.0906	0.8623	1.3268	0.0014	0.0007	0.0017	0.0038	0.012	0.0111	0.42	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.193	0.4449	0.6733	0	0	0	0.0081	0.0062	0.0057	0.306	1	3	0
0	0	0.0158	0.5315	0.5709	0.7678	0	0	0.0014	0.0222	0.008	0.0064	0.395	2	3	0
0	0.0079	0.5158	0.689	1.6772	2.3189	0	0.0014	0.043	0.0288	0.0233	0.0194	0.4781	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1378	0.3662	0.5749	0	0	0	0.0058	0.0051	0.0048	0	2	3	0
1.193	1.9134	2.0197	2.3701	2.6851	3.2953	0.3977	0.3189	0.1684	0.0988	0.0373	0.0275	0.3561	1	4	0
0	0	0.0119	0.1536	0.6497	2.4961	0	0	0.001	0.0064	0.0091	0.0209	0.4838	1	3	0
0.1103	0.2481	0.2678	0.6063	1.0945	1.3229	0.0368	0.0414	0.0224	0.0253	0.0153	0.0111	0.4896	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.189	0.752	1.4292	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0105	0.012	0.419	2	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3609	1	3	0
0	0	0.1063	0.4016	3.189	3.441	0	0	0.0089	0.0168	0.0443	0.0287	0.49	1	3	0
0	0.0473	0.0473	0.3701	1.2993	2.0079	0	0.0079	0.004	0.0155	0.0181	0.0168	0.423	1		0
0.0394	0.1812	0.7481	0.8386	1.5945	1.8859	0.0132	0.0302	0.0624	0.035	0.0222	0.0158	0.495	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0827	0.1733	0	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0015	0.3305	1		0
0.0158	0.0434	0.067	0.315	1.1418	1.5867	0.0053	0.0073	0.0056	0.0132	0.0159	0.0133	0.415	1	3	0
0.004	0.0355	0.0473	0.2284	0.7678	1.2717	0.0014	0.006	0.004	0.0096	0.0107	0.0106	0.414	5	3	0
0	0	0	0.063	0.7166	1.2126	0	0	0	0.0027	0.01	0.0102	0	2	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0158	0.13	0.1536	0	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0019	0.0013	0.269	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.2717	0.3308	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0038	0.0028	0.3711	1		0
0	0.004	0.004	0.0197	0.1772	0.252	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0009	0.0025	0.0021	0.3254	1	4	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.8308	1.4213	1.7717	2.5119	0.0027	0.0014	0.0693	0.0593	0.0247	0.021	0.5065	1		0
0.0079	0.0945	0.1142	0.4174	2.0552	2.3426	0.0027	0.0158	0.0096	0.0174	0.0286	0.0196	0.4005	1	3	0

0.004	0.0158	0.0788	0.1851	0.815	0.9292	0.0014	0.0027	0.0066	0.0078	0.0114	0.0078	0.4171	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.3426	0.9134	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0048	0.0077	0.3901	1	4	0
0	0.004	0.0355	0.0867	0.1497	0.9567	0	0.0007	0.003	0.0037	0.0021	0.008	0.51	1		0
0	0	0	0.189	0.5434	0.5709	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0076	0.0048	0.501	1	3	0
0.0434	0.2245	0.63	2.3701	3.5552	3.7087	0.0145	0.0375	0.0525	0.0988	0.0494	0.031	0.4135	1	3	0
0	0	0.0158	0.2048	2.2048	2.7166	0	0	0.0014	0.0086	0.0307	0.0227	0.203	1	4	0
0	0	0.0315	0.0749	0.8623	2.4056	0	0	0.0027	0.0032	0.012	0.0201	0.4105	2	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.3583	0.4016	0	0	0	0	0.005	0.0034	0.437	2	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.13	0.3308	0	0	0	0	0.0019	0.0028	0.4435	1	4	0
0.0079	0.0355	0.0355	0.0512	0.126	0.3583	0.0027	0.006	0.003	0.0022	0.0018	0.003	0.294	2	4	0
0	0.0512	0.1103	0.5434	1.6654	2.1063	0	0.0086	0.0092	0.0227	0.0232	0.0176	0.48	1	4	0
0	0.0197	0.0867	0.2638	0.5276	0.9292	0	0.0033	0.0073	0.011	0.0074	0.0078	0.3835	1	3	0
0	0.0079	0.1142	0.4016	1.6733	1.9607	0	0.0014	0.0096	0.0168	0.0233	0.0164	0.494	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0276	0.0788	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0007	0.3791	1		0
0.004	0.0237	0.0237	0.1339	1.1575	2.4843	0.0014	0.004	0.002	0.0056	0.0161	0.0208	0.3791	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0512	0.063	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0008	0.0006	0.338	4	4	0
0.0197	0.0237	0.0237	0.0552	0.4804	0.8504	0.0066	0.004	0.002	0.0023	0.0067	0.0071	0.404	1		0
0	0.004	0.004	0.067	0.1024	0.2953	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0028	0.0015	0.0025	0.4071	1	4	0
0.0237	0.0434	0.0906	0.1063	0.2717	0.5237	0.0079	0.0073	0.0076	0.0045	0.0038	0.0044	0.411	3	3	0
0.0237	0.0867	0.1497	0.3859	3.3701	3.9922	0.0079	0.0145	0.0125	0.0161	0.0469	0.0333	0.1735	1	4	0
0	0.004	0.004	0.1142	0.3544	0.3741	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0048	0.005	0.0032	0.4183	2	4	0
0	0	0.004	0.1024	0.8229	0.9489	0	0	0.0004	0.0043	0.0115	0.008	0.413	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0552	1.9056	2.1812	0	0	0	0.0023	0.0265	0.0182	0.392	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1142	0.6497	0.7481	0	0	0	0.0048	0.0091	0.0063	0.404	1		0
0	0	0.0749	0.1024	0.1103	0.2166	0	0	0.0063	0.0043	0.0016	0.0019	0.452	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.004	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.4395	1	3	0
0.3032	0.5237	0.5985	0.689	0.7323	1.2363	0.1011	0.0873	0.0499	0.0288	0.0102	0.0104	0.418	1	1	0
0	0.0119	0.0119	0.0709	1.2363	4.2126	0	0.002	0.001	0.003	0.0172	0.0352	0.4303	1		0
0	0	0.0473	0.63	0.8347	1.4567	0	0	0.004	0.0263	0.0116	0.0122	0.419	1	1	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0119	0.063	1.0355	1.4016	0.0027	0.0014	0.001	0.0027	0.0144	0.0117	0.4251	1	3	0
0	0	0.0355	0.0827	0.1497	0.4252	0	0	0.003	0.0035	0.0021	0.0036	0.5041	1		0
0.0473	0.126	0.2796	0.8504	1.6812	2.693	0.0158	0.021	0.0233	0.0355	0.0234	0.0225	0.4428	4	3	0
0.0591	0.1142	0.3859	0.5827	0.7284	4.0276	0.0197	0.0191	0.0322	0.0243	0.0102	0.0336	0.4286	1	2	0
0.0709	0.193	0.2796	0.2835	0.7993	1.9882	0.0237	0.0322	0.0233	0.0119	0.0112	0.0166	0.4121	3	1	0
0	0	0.9764	1.8504	3.5473	4.4567	0	0	0.0814	0.0771	0.0493	0.0372	0.3675	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.283	2	3	0
0.0355	0.0434	0.1142	1.1339	1.3583	2.1575	0.0119	0.0073	0.0096	0.0473	0.0189	0.018	0.424	1	3	0
0	0.067	0.1182	0.2323	1.1851	1.6969	0	0.0112	0.0099	0.0097	0.0165	0.0142	0.485	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.1221	1.2048	3.1772	4.2441	0	0.0007	0.0102	0.0502	0.0442	0.0354	0.4701	3	2	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0788	0.7166	1	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0033	0.01	0.0084	0.3865	2	3	0
0	0.0158	0.0197	0.2953	0.378	0.5552	0	0.0027	0.0017	0.0124	0.0053	0.0047	0.42	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.3544	0.6812	0	0	0	0.0009	0.005	0.0057	0.38	1	3	0
0.8938	1.5552	2.0355	3.5315	4.4725	4.8268	0.298	0.2592	0.1697	0.1472	0.0622	0.0403	0.5105	2	3	0
0.0788	0.2166	0.9371	1.2441	2.563	3.3819	0.0263	0.0361	0.0781	0.0519	0.0356	0.0282	0.311	1	3	0
0	0.0079	0.0276	0.0473	0.1969	0.2756	0	0.0014	0.0023	0.002	0.0028	0.0023	0.4004	3	1	0
0	0	0.1851	0.378	1.1182	1.5473	0	0	0.0155	0.0158	0.0156	0.0129	0.437	2	3	0
0.0473	0.2126	0.8426	1.126	1.2835	1.9528	0.0158	0.0355	0.0703	0.047	0.0179	0.0163	0.371	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.1024	0.1182	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0015	0.001	0.474	1	4	0

0	0	0.3426	1.3741	2.2481	2.4489	0	0	0.0286	0.0573	0.0313	0.0205	0.494	1	1	0
0	0.0394	0.0473	0.2756	1.0788	1.1418	0	0.0066	0.004	0.0115	0.015	0.0096	0.479	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.5119	0.6378	1.2599	0	0	0	0.0214	0.0089	0.0105	0.4121	1	3	0
0.0158	0.0237	0.0591	0.1418	0.7953	1.3859	0.0053	0.004	0.005	0.006	0.0111	0.0116	0.309	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0119	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.4497	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.5	1.1536	2.004	0	0	0	0.0209	0.0161	0.0167	0.4606	1	3	0
0	0	0.0552	0.189	0.9449	1.1497	0	0	0.0046	0.0079	0.0132	0.0096	0.362	5	3	0
0.004	0.0197	0.2402	0.2402	0.7875	1.4174	0.0014	0.0033	0.0201	0.0101	0.011	0.0119	0.5031	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.2717	1.8544	2.2481	0	0	0	0.0114	0.0258	0.0188	0.505	1		0
0.0119	0.0394	0.1182	0.1536	0.2914	0.4961	0.004	0.0066	0.0099	0.0064	0.0041	0.0042	0.3723	1	3	0
0	0.0119	0.0158	0.1654	0.3898	0.563	0	0.002	0.0014	0.0069	0.0055	0.0047	0.485	1		0
0.0276	0.0512	0.063	0.1339	0.3504	1.4449	0.0092	0.0086	0.0053	0.0056	0.0049	0.0121	0.266	1		0
0.0079	0.0119	0.0276	0.1103	0.1378	0.2363	0.0027	0.002	0.0023	0.0046	0.002	0.002	0.3716	1		0
0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0512	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0005	0.2696	3	3	0
0.0197	0.0355	0.0591	0.0827	0.7048	1.0788	0.0066	0.006	0.005	0.0035	0.0098	0.009	0.204	2	3	0
0.315	0.315	0.315	0.4764	1.0158	1.0158	0.105	0.0525	0.0263	0.0199	0.0142	0.0085	0	1		0
0.0158	0.0158	0.0867	0.1969	0.8386	0.878	0.0053	0.0027	0.0073	0.0083	0.0117	0.0074	0.3561	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.3386	0.6772	1.004	0	0	0	0.0142	0.0095	0.0084	0.074	1	3	0
0.0749	0.0749	0.0906	0.256	0.8544	1.6103	0.025	0.0125	0.0076	0.0107	0.0119	0.0135	0	1	2	0
0.0552	0.0552	0.0552	0.126	0.3111	0.6182	0.0184	0.0092	0.0046	0.0053	0.0044	0.0052	0.503	2	3	0
0	0.004	0.0276	0.13	0.2835	0.3859	0	0.0007	0.0023	0.0055	0.004	0.0033	0.5046	1	3	0
0	0	0.004	0.4016	0.9567	1.3229	0	0	0.0004	0.0168	0.0133	0.0111	0.23	1		0
0.0473	0.0867	0.0906	0.1221	0.4016	0.5434	0.0158	0.0145	0.0076	0.0051	0.0056	0.0046	0.4122	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0434	0.0434	0.0434	0	0	0	0.0019	0.0007	0.0004	0.4169	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.189	0.6142	0.7087	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0086	0.006	0.405	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.4686	1.2205	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0066	0.0102	0.4645	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0	0	0	0.001	0.0004	0.0002	0.4737	2	4	0
0	0	0.004	0.126	0.8111	1.256	0	0	0.0004	0.0053	0.0113	0.0105	0.432	1	3	0
0.0237	0.2126	0.2323	0.256	0.5906	0.6772	0.0079	0.0355	0.0194	0.0107	0.0083	0.0057	0.287	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.1733	0.3032	0.9882	0	0	0	0.0073	0.0043	0.0083	0.3111	1	3	0
0	0	0.0158	0.3189	0.6378	1.9725	0	0	0.0014	0.0133	0.0089	0.0165	0.182	3	4	0
0	0	0	0.1063	0.4843	0.9528	0	0	0	0.0045	0.0068	0.008	0.332	1	1	0
0	0.063	0.063	0.5552	0.9607	2.3465	0	0.0105	0.0053	0.0232	0.0134	0.0196	0.4815	4	4	0
0	0	0	0.063	0.4095	0.8386	0	0	0	0.0027	0.0057	0.007	0.344	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.44	1	3	0
0.067	0.1103	0.126	0.4764	1.067	1.4725	0.0224	0.0184	0.0105	0.0199	0.0149	0.0123	0.418	3	1	0
0	0.0119	0.0276	0.1378	0.3504	0.4489	0	0.002	0.0023	0.0058	0.0049	0.0038	0.463	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.0512	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0005	0.2838	2	1	0
0.004	0.004	0.0119	0.3268	1.1457	2.1457	0.0014	0.0007	0.001	0.0137	0.016	0.0179	0.477	6	3	0
0	0	0.4607	1.5709	3.9095	4.2008	0	0	0.0384	0.0655	0.0543	0.0351	0.4585	1	1	0
0.0079	0.0119	0.9489	2.2441	2.6615	4.3347	0.0027	0.002	0.0791	0.0936	0.037	0.0362	0.2932	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.1063	0.252	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0015	0.0021	0.4073	2	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0473	2.563	3.4331	0	0	0.0007	0.002	0.0356	0.0287	0.4581	1	3	0
0.0552	0.1772	0.3938	0.567	1.0512	1.1654	0.0184	0.0296	0.0329	0.0237	0.0146	0.0098	0.4023	2		0
0	0	0.1418	0.5945	0.9489	1.6378	0	0	0.0119	0.0248	0.0132	0.0137	0.51	1	3	0
0	0	0.1024	0.1969	0.9016	1.3898	0	0	0.0086	0.0083	0.0126	0.0116	0.4196	1		0
0	0	0.0119	0.0591	0.6733	1.4843	0	0	0.001	0.0025	0.0094	0.0124	0.4005	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.0119	0.0591	0.8189	1.0119	0.0014	0.0007	0.001	0.0025	0.0114	0.0085	0.37	1	3	0

0.004	0.004	0.0158	0.063	0.4804	1.3741	0.0014	0.0007	0.0014	0.0027	0.0067	0.0115	0	1	0	
0.0315	0.13	0.1733	0.3819	0.9882	1.5197	0.0105	0.0217	0.0145	0.016	0.0138	0.0127	0.4695	1	3	0
0.004	0.0827	0.2638	0.5709	0.9252	1.8583	0.0014	0.0138	0.022	0.0238	0.0129	0.0155	0.3891	1	0	
0.0119	0.0119	0.3701	0.8819	3.6812	4.7441	0.004	0.002	0.0309	0.0368	0.0512	0.0396	0.4857	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.004	0.0119	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	0.294	2	3	0
0	0.0276	0.0473	0.1733	0.3465	0.9134	0	0.0046	0.004	0.0073	0.0049	0.0077	0.5094	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0867	0.2126	0.5552	0	0	0	0.0037	0.003	0.0047	0.467	2	1	0
0	0.004	0.063	0.3623	1.0197	1.4961	0	0.0007	0.0053	0.0151	0.0142	0.0125	0.5063	3	0	
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.324	1	3	0
0.0552	0.0709	0.1378	0.3347	1.0788	2.0552	0.0184	0.0119	0.0115	0.014	0.015	0.0172	0.4534	4	4	0
0.0276	0.0788	0.256	0.3426	0.6457	1.0827	0.0092	0.0132	0.0214	0.0143	0.009	0.0091	0	2	3	0
0.004	0.0079	0.0591	0.2756	0.7796	1.0512	0.0014	0.0014	0.005	0.0115	0.0109	0.0088	0.388	1	3	0
0.0197	0.1024	0.1024	0.4174	1.0945	1.8032	0.0066	0.0171	0.0086	0.0174	0.0153	0.0151	0.4183	3	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0945	1.1693	1.3308	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.004	0.0163	0.0111	0.497	3	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0512	0	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.4681	4	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.315	0.5394	0	0	0	0	0.0044	0.0045	0.244	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.0079	0.4134	1.13	1.689	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0173	0.0157	0.0141	0.493	2	1	0
0	0	0.0079	0.6103	1.2835	1.3701	0	0	0.0007	0.0255	0.0179	0.0115	0.493	1	3	0
0.0473	0.0473	0.0945	0.3189	1.252	2.7875	0.0158	0.0079	0.0079	0.0133	0.0174	0.0233	0.2291	1	1	0
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.6693	2	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0093	0.0167	0.427	1	4	0
0.0079	0.0788	0.0827	0.1182	0.7638	1.0591	0.0027	0.0132	0.0069	0.005	0.0107	0.0089	0.3202	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.4143	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.5552	2.4252	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0078	0.0203	0.378	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.4487	2	4	0
0	0	0.0906	0.3977	0.4567	1.7087	0	0	0.0076	0.0166	0.0064	0.0143	0.4655	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0709	0.2166	0.8032	0	0	0	0.003	0.0031	0.0067	0.4686	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.0119	0.1733	0.4449	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0025	0.0038	0.251	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0434	0.1536	0	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0013	0.3713	1	0	
0	0	0	0.2914	1.2756	2.0473	0	0	0	0.0122	0.0178	0.0171	0.3086	1	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0119	0.3308	0.5394	0	0	0.0007	0.0005	0.0046	0.0045	0.392	2	3	0
0	0.0119	0.0158	0.2166	1.1418	1.315	0	0.002	0.0014	0.0091	0.0159	0.011	0.3613	5	3	0
0	0	0	0.0709	0.3662	1.7993	0	0	0	0.003	0.0051	0.015	0.3815	2	1	0
0	0	0.0276	0.1024	0.4922	0.7048	0	0	0.0023	0.0043	0.0069	0.0059	0.511	4	3	0
0	0	0.004	0.8977	2.8386	3.9449	0	0	0.0004	0.0375	0.0395	0.0329	0.5131	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0945	0.193	0.7205	2.4095	4.3071	0.0027	0.0158	0.0161	0.0301	0.0335	0.0359	0.516	3	3	0
0	0.0315	0.1103	0.3032	0.6103	0.9174	0	0.0053	0.0092	0.0127	0.0085	0.0077	0.5052	1	3	0
0	0	0.0827	0.4095	1.1733	6.4489	0	0	0.0069	0.0171	0.0163	0.0538	0.365	1	1	0
0.0315	0.1221	0.2205	0.815	1.5906	1.5906	0.0105	0.0204	0.0184	0.034	0.0221	0.0133	0.474	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	1.5906	2.4213	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0221	0.0202	0.351	1	4	0
0	0	0.1772	0.6851	2.2126	3.3623	0	0	0.0148	0.0286	0.0308	0.0281	0.5106	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0276	0.0827	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0007	0.4786	2	0	
0	0	0	0.5276	1.563	2.0512	0	0	0	0.022	0.0218	0.0171	0.497	1	3	0
0.1063	0.126	0.1615	1.1221	2.0237	2.1851	0.0355	0.021	0.0135	0.0468	0.0282	0.0183	0.493	1	3	0
0.0197	0.0197	0.063	0.2008	0.5552	1.0512	0.0066	0.0033	0.0053	0.0084	0.0078	0.0088	0.4961	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0945	0.3111	0.7481	0	0	0	0.004	0.0044	0.0063	0.441	1	3	0
0	0.0473	0.0552	0.2717	0.8111	1.7875	0	0.0079	0.0046	0.0114	0.0113	0.0149	0.503	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.126	0	0	0	0	0	0.0011	0.33	2	3	0
0.0079	0.0315	0.1733	0.6654	3.7914	4.6378	0.0027	0.0053	0.0145	0.0278	0.0527	0.0387	0.4941	1	3	0

0	0	0.0119	0.0512	0.0867	0.3426	0	0	0.001	0.0022	0.0013	0.0029	0.408	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.0001	0.4771	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.3426	0.4686	1.2638	0	0	0	0.0143	0.0066	0.0106	0.506	3		0
0	0	0	0.1103	6	6.0749	0	0	0	0.0046	0.0834	0.0507	0.3157	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	3.7205	5.1693	0	0	0	0	0.0517	0.0431	0.369	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.0276	0.0276	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0004	0.0003	0.432	1		0
0	0	0	0.1497	0.7166	0.8465	0	0	0	0.0063	0.01	0.0071	0.3948	4	3	0
0	0	0.1615	1.5945	2.5827	2.7796	0	0	0.0135	0.0665	0.0359	0.0232	0.4869	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.0315	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0003	0.459	1		0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.462	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.1063	1.2048	1.7284	0	0	0	0.0045	0.0168	0.0145	0.4741	1	4	0
0	0.0158	0.0827	0.1693	0.6536	1.5788	0	0.0027	0.0069	0.0071	0.0091	0.0132	0.348	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.0867	0.378	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0013	0.0032	0.398	3	4	0
0	0.004	0.004	0.0394	0.1063	0.189	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0017	0.0015	0.0016	0.367	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0119	0.0158	0.2441	1.0394	1.3544	0.004	0.002	0.0014	0.0102	0.0145	0.0113	0.408	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0591	0.1536	0	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0013	0.479	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.1693	0.4646	0.8308	0	0	0	0.0071	0.0065	0.007	0.4174	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.0394	0.4961	0.6024	0.7402	0	0.0007	0.0033	0.0207	0.0084	0.0062	0.423	1		0
0	0.0237	0.0315	0.4449	6.7914	8.2638	0	0.004	0.0027	0.0186	0.0944	0.0689	0.4828	3	3	0
0	0	0.0788	0.6063	1.4764	2.5591	0	0	0.0066	0.0253	0.0206	0.0214	0.45	1	4	0
0.3504	0.6418	1.126	2.067	3.8071	4.7323	0.1168	0.107	0.0939	0.0862	0.0529	0.0395	0.3801	1	4	0
0.0749	0.1615	0.193	0.6575	1.2323	1.3268	0.025	0.027	0.0161	0.0274	0.0172	0.0111	0.4989	1		0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.2914	0.7363	0.7363	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0122	0.0103	0.0062	0.4154	1	1	0
0.0119	0.0119	0.0119	0.3819	2.9804	3.7717	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.016	0.0414	0.0315	0.5	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1024	0.9489	2.0276	0	0	0	0.0043	0.0132	0.0169	0.275	1	3	0
1.3583	2.9016	4.1772	5.7126	7.1812	7.2875	0.4528	0.4836	0.3481	0.2381	0.0998	0.0608	0.362	1	3	0
0.004	0.0788	0.1339	0.3308	0.4174	0.5276	0.0014	0.0132	0.0112	0.0138	0.0058	0.0044	0.488	2	3	0
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.3938	0.9174	1.2441	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0165	0.0128	0.0104	0.4221	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.0276	0.0276	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0004	0.0003	0.4036	1	3	0
0.0552	0.0749	0.1221	0.6693	1.315	1.5985	0.0184	0.0125	0.0102	0.0279	0.0183	0.0134	0.336	4	1	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.2245	0.2245	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0032	0.0019	0.3386	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.29	1	3	0
0	0.0158	0.0788	0.3504	1.5197	2.3426	0	0.0027	0.0066	0.0146	0.0212	0.0196	0.307	1		0
0	0	0	0.5276	0.8071	0.8308	0	0	0	0.022	0.0113	0.007	0.337	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0394	1.3189	2.5434	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0184	0.0212	0.3266	2	4	0
0.0237	0.1457	0.2363	0.2402	0.3229	0.6142	0.0079	0.0243	0.0197	0.0101	0.0045	0.0052	0.409	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.189	0.5591	1.2835	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0078	0.0107	0.432	1	3	0
0	0.0079	0.3741	1.252	1.3662	1.4961	0	0.0014	0.0312	0.0522	0.019	0.0125	0.3946	3	3	0
0	0.0394	0.1339	0.4292	0.441	0.441	0	0.0066	0.0112	0.0179	0.0062	0.0037	0.444	3	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.2796	0.567	0	0	0	0	0.0039	0.0048	0.321	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.1575	0.1575	0	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0014	0.391	3	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.6063	0	0	0	0	0	0.0051	0.388	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.4016	0.6221	1.1812	0	0	0	0.0168	0.0087	0.0099	0.3891	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.4725	1.1063	2.2481	3.2599	0	0.0007	0.0394	0.0461	0.0313	0.0272	0.2963	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.0709	0.0867	0.1024	0	0	0	0.003	0.0013	0.0009	0.285	1	3	0
0	0	0.0197	0.0827	0.2993	0.4292	0	0	0.0017	0.0035	0.0042	0.0036	0.342	1		0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.24	1	3	0
0.1024	0.1851	0.4095	0.8229	2.193	2.8859	0.0342	0.0309	0.0342	0.0343	0.0305	0.0241	0.3641	2	1	0

0.2087	0.2914	0.3032	0.5079	0.8426	1.4134	0.0696	0.0486	0.0253	0.0212	0.0118	0.0118	0	1	3	0
0	0.0355	0.1024	0.1142	0.1182	0.1418	0	0.006	0.0086	0.0048	0.0017	0.0012	0.352	1		0
0.0473	0.1339	0.1418	0.2756	0.441	0.8662	0.0158	0.0224	0.0119	0.0115	0.0062	0.0073	0.47	1	3	0
0.0237	0.0591	0.1969	0.7205	1.7835	3.2087	0.0079	0.0099	0.0165	0.0301	0.0248	0.0268	0.3661	3	3	0
0	0.0749	0.0749	0.1615	0.1615	0.1615	0	0.0125	0.0063	0.0068	0.0023	0.0014	0.395	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0473	0.441	0.5276	0	0	0	0.002	0.0062	0.0044	0.5105	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0197	0.13	0.2402	1.0473	0.0027	0.0014	0.0017	0.0055	0.0034	0.0088	0.452	6	4	0
0	0	0.004	0.0512	0.3741	1.7402	0	0	0.0004	0.0022	0.0052	0.0146	0.4001	3	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.274	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0552	0.1812	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0008	0.0016	0.2495	1	2	0
0	0	0	0.0552	0.0552	0.067	0	0	0	0.0023	0.0008	0.0006	0.4839	3		0
0.9174	0.9331	1.1418	1.4567	2.8662	3.8544	0.3058	0.1556	0.0952	0.0607	0.0399	0.0322	0.408	1	3	0
0.0552	0.0709	0.189	0.8701	1.7717	2.0315	0.0184	0.0119	0.0158	0.0363	0.0247	0.017	0.3516	1		0
0	0	0.2008	0.2363	0.7245	0.7835	0	0	0.0168	0.0099	0.0101	0.0066	0	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.7402	2.0867	0	0	0	0	0.0103	0.0174	0.3862	1	3	0
0.063	0.1142	0.193	0.3623	1.2756	1.9331	0.021	0.0191	0.0161	0.0151	0.0178	0.0162	0.4251	5	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.252	2	3	0
0	0	0.1969	0.252	0.3819	0.8623	0	0	0.0165	0.0105	0.0054	0.0072	0.5053	4	4	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.2441	0.4567	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0034	0.0039	0.359	1	3	0
0	0	0.0119	0.0355	0.1103	0.1851	0	0	0.001	0.0015	0.0016	0.0016	0.4656	1	3	0
0.0749	0.1182	0.2087	0.2126	0.3583	0.5394	0.025	0.0197	0.0174	0.0089	0.005	0.0045	0.3273	1	3	0
0	0.0079	0.1536	0.6221	1.3938	2.4528	0	0.0014	0.0128	0.026	0.0194	0.0205	0.4928	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.4843	1.0197	0	0	0	0	0.0068	0.0085	0.4271	1	4	0
0	0	0.0237	0.0906	0.4331	1.1812	0	0	0.002	0.0038	0.0061	0.0099	0.503	3	3	0
0.004	0.0158	0.126	0.3544	2.13	5.3189	0.0014	0.0027	0.0105	0.0148	0.0296	0.0444	0.4441	4	3	0
0.067	0.1536	0.2284	0.2875	0.8465	1.1182	0.0224	0.0256	0.0191	0.012	0.0118	0.0094	0.43	3	1	0
0.0197	0.0197	0.0197	0.0355	0.2048	0.3544	0.0066	0.0033	0.0017	0.0015	0.0029	0.003	0.3561	2	3	0
0	0	0.0355	0.0473	0.5237	0.9725	0	0	0.003	0.002	0.0073	0.0082	0.367	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0945	0.1142	0.2717	1.126	1.9331	0.0027	0.0158	0.0096	0.0114	0.0157	0.0162	0.319	1	4	0
0.0276	0.0434	0.0867	0.1024	0.1654	0.5	0.0092	0.0073	0.0073	0.0043	0.0023	0.0042	0.4133	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.2008	0.7717	2.3229	0	0	0	0.0084	0.0108	0.0194	0.3441	1		0
0	0.0158	0.0434	0.063	0.063	0.0945	0	0.0027	0.0037	0.0027	0.0009	0.0008	0	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	2.5552	4.4882	0	0	0	0	0.0355	0.0375	0.4288	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0591	0	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.295	1		0
0	0	0.0237	0.5985	1.0591	1.7441	0	0	0.002	0.025	0.0148	0.0146	0.3891	1	3	0
0.2796	0.5591	1.1693	1.8465	4.5827	6.6142	0.0932	0.0932	0.0975	0.077	0.0637	0.0552	0.5175	4	3	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.6024	0.6182	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0084	0.0052	0.4913	4	4	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0591	0.4804	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0009	0.0041	0.494	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0434	0.0434	0	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.4503	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0552	0.0591	0.1497	0	0	0	0.0023	0.0009	0.0013	0.3574	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.5158	1.8268	0	0	0	0	0.0072	0.0153	0.494	2	1	0
0.0197	0.0552	0.1063	0.4174	2.252	2.8426	0.0066	0.0092	0.0089	0.0174	0.0313	0.0237	0.4165	1	1	0
0.0119	0.0315	0.1024	0.5749	1.4686	1.5434	0.004	0.0053	0.0086	0.024	0.0204	0.0129	0.4192	2	1	0
0.0749	0.1063	0.4646	0.5867	0.6418	1.0906	0.025	0.0178	0.0388	0.0245	0.009	0.0091	0.322	1		0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.1418	0.3701	0	0	0	0.0007	0.002	0.0031	0.4255	1	3	0
0.0237	0.0434	0.1024	0.2796	0.752	4.5119	0.0079	0.0073	0.0086	0.0117	0.0105	0.0376	0.4134	1		0
0.0197	0.0394	0.063	0.3347	1.2363	1.756	0.0066	0.0066	0.0053	0.014	0.0172	0.0147	0	1		0

0	0	0	0	0.2402	0.8583	0	0	0	0	0.0034	0.0072	0.393	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.6024	0.9016	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0084	0.0076	0.369	1	4	0
0.0749	0.1339	0.1378	0.2678	0.5394	2.063	0.025	0.0224	0.0115	0.0112	0.0075	0.0172	0.498	1	3	0
0.0394	0.0512	0.13	1.1733	1.4725	2.0906	0.0132	0.0086	0.0109	0.0489	0.0205	0.0175	0.397	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.0709	0.0709	0	0	0	0.0017	0.001	0.0006	0.3531	1	3	0
0.004	0.0079	0.0552	0.3544	1.4764	2.2678	0.0014	0.0014	0.0046	0.0148	0.0206	0.0189	0.5154	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0315	0.0315	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0003	0.466	1		0
0	0	0.0985	1.0867	1.4843	2.2323	0	0	0.0083	0.0453	0.0207	0.0187	0.4467	1	4	0
0.0749	0.1457	0.2166	1.1733	1.9489	2.2323	0.025	0.0243	0.0181	0.0489	0.0271	0.0187	0.5022	1		0
0.0315	0.0749	0.1575	0.2166	0.5512	1.13	0.0105	0.0125	0.0132	0.0091	0.0077	0.0095	0.187	1	1	0
0	0.004	0.0512	0.0512	0.1142	0.4331	0	0.0007	0.0043	0.0022	0.0016	0.0037	0.398	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.1182	0.7245	0.9056	0.9567	0.0014	0.0007	0.0099	0.0302	0.0126	0.008	0.452	1	3	0
0.0197	0.1339	0.2953	0.5079	1.8071	4.5591	0.0066	0.0224	0.0247	0.0212	0.0251	0.038	0.3078	1	3	0
0	0	0.0197	0.0512	1.5276	1.8583	0	0	0.0017	0.0022	0.0213	0.0155	0.3661	2	1	0
0	0	0.004	1.1575	2.3308	3.3544	0	0	0.0004	0.0483	0.0324	0.028	0.3739	1	1	0
0	0.004	0.3347	0.5158	1.3229	1.3741	0	0.0007	0.0279	0.0215	0.0184	0.0115	0.404	1	3	0
0.2402	0.3977	0.5	0.941	1.752	2.3308	0.0801	0.0663	0.0417	0.0393	0.0244	0.0195	0.508	2	3	0
0.1812	0.256	0.256	0.2717	0.5355	1.626	0.0604	0.0427	0.0214	0.0114	0.0075	0.0136	0.295	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0237	0.1457	0.6812	0	0	0	0.001	0.0021	0.0057	0.473	2	4	0
0	0.0197	0.0867	0.1142	0.7953	1.1182	0	0.0033	0.0073	0.0048	0.0111	0.0094	0.3285	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.067	0.0827	0.1063	0	0	0	0.0028	0.0012	0.0009	0.4183	1		0
0	0	0.063	0.8701	2.6063	2.9961	0	0	0.0053	0.0363	0.0362	0.025	0.416	1	1	0
0	0	0.0237	0.0552	0.2126	0.3426	0	0	0.002	0.0023	0.003	0.0029	0.427	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2697	4	3	0
0	0.0276	0.126	0.3189	0.5158	0.6693	0	0.0046	0.0105	0.0133	0.0072	0.0056	0.4104	1	3	0
0.0197	0.0237	0.067	0.4567	0.8032	1.8032	0.0066	0.004	0.0056	0.0191	0.0112	0.0151	0.28	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.3898	4.3032	6.6339	0	0	0	0.0163	0.0598	0.0553	0.5155	1	3	0
0	0.0119	0.0158	0.0197	0.378	2.4252	0	0.002	0.0014	0.0009	0.0053	0.0203	0.508	1	3	0
0.0119	0.1063	0.1063	0.1063	0.3111	0.3268	0.004	0.0178	0.0089	0.0045	0.0044	0.0028	0.3513	2	3	0
0.0079	0.0158	0.0237	0.0394	0.2481	0.7008	0.0027	0.0027	0.002	0.0017	0.0035	0.0059	0	3	3	0
0	0.0079	0.0749	0.2953	0.8662	1.563	0	0.0014	0.0063	0.0124	0.0121	0.0131	0.368	6		0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0512	0	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.443	2		0
0	0	0	0.2048	0.878	1.3032	0	0	0	0.0086	0.0122	0.0109	0.509	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1182	0.8662	1.0158	0	0	0	0.005	0.0121	0.0085	0.266	1	3	0
0	0.0119	0.0119	0.3938	0.9252	1.7087	0	0.002	0.001	0.0165	0.0129	0.0143	0.3623	2	1	0
0	0.0079	0.1221	0.1378	0.3071	0.9056	0	0.0014	0.0102	0.0058	0.0043	0.0076	0.4986	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.1457	8.9016	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0021	0.0742	0.5139	3	4	0
0	0	0.004	0.2953	1.3583	2.8268	0	0	0.0004	0.0124	0.0189	0.0236	0.494	2	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.7284	0.941	1.4489	1.8938	0.0014	0.0007	0.0607	0.0393	0.0202	0.0158	0.414	1	3	0
0	0	0.0119	0.3308	0.4961	0.7441	0	0	0.001	0.0138	0.0069	0.0063	0.337	1	3	0
0	0	0.0197	0.315	0.5512	0.8819	0	0	0.0017	0.0132	0.0077	0.0074	0.4206	4		0
0.0197	0.0315	0.0315	0.0788	0.126	0.2048	0.0066	0.0053	0.0027	0.0033	0.0018	0.0018	0.442	4	4	0
0	0.0119	0.0237	0.1024	0.5	1.2599	0	0.002	0.002	0.0043	0.007	0.0105	0.4282	1	3	0
0.0158	0.0237	0.0394	0.1418	0.4134	0.5355	0.0053	0.004	0.0033	0.006	0.0058	0.0045	0.5109	1	3	0
0	0.0079	0.0237	0.3819	1.1772	1.2993	0	0.0014	0.002	0.016	0.0164	0.0109	0.421	1		0
0	0.0158	0.0473	0.0867	0.9725	1.2875	0	0.0027	0.004	0.0037	0.0136	0.0108	0.378	1	3	0
0	0	0.0473	0.0591	0.1221	0.1693	0	0	0.004	0.0025	0.0017	0.0015	0.3428	2		0
0	0	0.004	0.0119	0.2914	0.3741	0	0	0.0004	0.0005	0.0041	0.0032	0.424	1	3	0

0	0	0.0512	0.4331	3.4213	4.2756	0	0	0.0043	0.0181	0.0476	0.0357	0.5168	2	0
0.0197	0.0355	0.0355	0.0473	0.0827	0.0906	0.0066	0.006	0.003	0.002	0.0012	0.0008	0.2083	2	3 0
0.1182	0.2087	0.256	0.4095	0.4882	0.5	0.0394	0.0348	0.0214	0.0171	0.0068	0.0042	0.4613	2	1 0
0.0552	0.1063	0.1221	0.2245	0.6851	0.7599	0.0184	0.0178	0.0102	0.0094	0.0096	0.0064	0.401	1	0
0.0119	0.0512	0.1339	0.252	0.6851	1.5158	0.004	0.0086	0.0112	0.0105	0.0096	0.0127	0.5105	1	3 0
0	0	0.0119	0.2323	1.6733	2.9449	0	0	0.001	0.0097	0.0233	0.0246	0.4999	1	3 0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0788	0.2284	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0011	0.002	0.4592	1	1 0
0	0.0473	0.1378	0.2323	0.9489	2.0827	0	0.0079	0.0115	0.0097	0.0132	0.0174	0.378	4	4 0
0	0	0	0.3189	1.3071	1.3071	0	0	0	0.0133	0.0182	0.0109	0.318	1	3 0
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.0119	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0001	0.408	1	3 0
0	0	0	0.0709	0.2205	1.4331	0	0	0	0.003	0.0031	0.012	0.384	1	0
0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.0197	0.2323	0.567	0.0053	0.0027	0.0014	0.0009	0.0033	0.0048	0.3923	1	3 0
0	0	0.0158	0.1536	1.9371	2.0788	0	0	0.0014	0.0064	0.027	0.0174	0	1	3 0
0.0237	0.0434	0.0434	0.0434	0.378	0.4607	0.0079	0.0073	0.0037	0.0019	0.0053	0.0039	0.404	1	3 0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.369	4	1 0
0	0	0.0906	1.2481	2.1182	2.63	0	0	0.0076	0.0521	0.0295	0.022	0.28	1	3 0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2875	1	0
0.004	0.0394	0.256	0.8662	2.0985	3.3662	0.0014	0.0066	0.0214	0.0361	0.0292	0.0281	0.3118	1	0
0	0	0	0.2126	0.4371	0.6733	0	0	0	0.0089	0.0061	0.0057	0.4121	1	3 0
0	0.004	0.0315	0.0394	0.3111	0.378	0	0.0007	0.0027	0.0017	0.0044	0.0032	0.436	2	0
0	0	0	0.1024	0.4134	0.9213	0	0	0	0.0043	0.0058	0.0077	0.332	1	0
0	0	0	0.0867	0.7402	1.1615	0	0	0	0.0037	0.0103	0.0097	0.4831	2	3 0
0.0276	0.0394	0.0512	0.3859	1.6654	3.9252	0.0092	0.0066	0.0043	0.0161	0.0232	0.0328	0.4156	1	3 0
0	0	0	0.0749	0.5473	1.1378	0	0	0	0.0032	0.0077	0.0095	0.3253	1	3 0
0.004	0.0158	0.0158	0.0867	1.2205	1.4056	0.0014	0.0027	0.0014	0.0037	0.017	0.0118	0.489	1	1 0
0	0	0.0827	0.3229	0.4134	0.6615	0	0	0.0069	0.0135	0.0058	0.0056	0.12	1	3 0
0.2796	0.3111	0.5158	0.8898	5.126	5.1969	0.0932	0.0519	0.043	0.0371	0.0712	0.0434	0.5093	2	4 0
0	0	0	0.7402	2.6024	4.0197	0	0	0	0.0309	0.0362	0.0335	0.442	2	3 0
0	0	0	0.4016	0.7402	0.9449	0	0	0	0.0168	0.0103	0.0079	0.288	2	3 0
0	0	0.0709	0.1103	0.4331	1.2599	0	0	0.006	0.0046	0.0061	0.0105	0.506	1	1 0
0	0	0	0	0.2284	0.8071	0	0	0	0	0.0032	0.0068	0.506	2	0
0	0	0.0079	0.126	0.563	1.067	0	0	0.0007	0.0053	0.0079	0.0089	0.393	1	3 0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0237	0.0945	0.8701	0.9686	0.0027	0.0014	0.002	0.004	0.0121	0.0081	0.4081	1	4 0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.0945	0.1142	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0014	0.001	0.4985	1	1 0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.0945	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0008	0.3451	1	3 0
0	0.004	0.004	0.6142	2.1851	2.1851	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0256	0.0304	0.0183	0.296	1	1 0
0	0	0	0.2245	0.2363	0.4252	0	0	0	0.0094	0.0033	0.0036	0.2674	1	0
0	0	0.0276	0.0512	0.7126	1.0197	0	0	0.0023	0.0022	0.0099	0.0085	0.2631	1	1 0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.0355	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0003	0.4	1	3 0
0.0434	0.0512	0.0985	0.4764	1.3623	1.8898	0.0145	0.0086	0.0083	0.0199	0.019	0.0158	0.5116	1	3 0
0	0	0.0079	0.0119	0.4252	0.8229	0	0	0.0007	0.0005	0.006	0.0069	0.5019	1	1 0
0	0	0.0119	0.1378	0.5158	0.5473	0	0	0.001	0.0058	0.0072	0.0046	0.3431	1	4 0
0.0552	0.3426	0.4607	0.8386	4.7402	5.7402	0.0184	0.0571	0.0384	0.035	0.0659	0.0479	0.429	3	3 0
0	0	0	0.0197	1.8977	2.3071	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0264	0.0193	0.487	1	3 0
0	0	0	0.0237	0.0591	0.4567	0	0	0	0.001	0.0009	0.0039	0.3221	1	3 0
0	0	0	0.0945	0.3662	0.6063	0	0	0	0.004	0.0051	0.0051	0.4681	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3891	1	0
0	0	0.0079	0.2205	0.3977	0.4449	0	0	0.0007	0.0092	0.0056	0.0038	0.4231	1	3 0

0	0	0	0.0906	0.441	0.5434	0	0	0	0.0038	0.0062	0.0046	0.293	4	3	0
0.0394	0.1063	1.13	1.2008	2.1024	2.193	0.0132	0.0178	0.0942	0.0501	0.0292	0.0183	0.327	3	3	0
0	0.004	0.0985	0.2441	2.063	3.2599	0	0.0007	0.0083	0.0102	0.0287	0.0272	0.498	4		0
0	0	0.0079	0.0119	0.0591	0.4331	0	0	0.0007	0.0005	0.0009	0.0037	0.373	2		0
0	0.0197	0.0906	0.1457	0.2441	0.4961	0	0.0033	0.0076	0.0061	0.0034	0.0042	0.4383	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0434	0.4331	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0007	0.0037	0	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.2717	0.7875	1.2599	0	0	0	0.0114	0.011	0.0105	0.4929	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.2441	0.4095	0.8623	0	0	0	0.0102	0.0057	0.0072	0.4509	1	3	0
0.004	0.0394	0.063	0.1536	0.4567	0.5906	0.0014	0.0066	0.0053	0.0064	0.0064	0.005	0.297	1	3	0
1.1103	1.1378	1.1654	1.256	1.9567	2.4292	0.3701	0.1897	0.0972	0.0524	0.0272	0.0203	0.359	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.126	0.7756	0	0	0	0	0.0018	0.0065	0.471	1	3	0
0	0.0119	0.0315	0.0394	0.0394	0.0473	0	0.002	0.0027	0.0017	0.0006	0.0004	0.3431	2		0
0.0197	0.0512	0.1182	0.6615	2.4686	3.4252	0.0066	0.0086	0.0099	0.0276	0.0343	0.0286	0.4862	1	3	0
0	0	0.1497	2.6024	3.7796	4.3544	0	0	0.0125	0.1085	0.0525	0.0363	0.2503	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.1024	0.3544	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0015	0.003	0	2	3	0
0.0591	0.1103	0.1339	0.5276	0.6457	0.9056	0.0197	0.0184	0.0112	0.022	0.009	0.0076	0.4811	1	4	0
0	0.0237	0.0237	0.4567	0.563	0.7638	0	0.004	0.002	0.0191	0.0079	0.0064	0.496	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.2205	0.504	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0031	0.0042	0.079	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0434	0.2048	1.2796	1.2875	2.4607	0.004	0.0073	0.0171	0.0534	0.0179	0.0206	0.357	1		0
0	0	0.004	0.1575	0.5394	0.815	0	0	0.0004	0.0066	0.0075	0.0068	0.3785	1		0
0.0355	0.0591	0.063	0.063	0.3938	0.5591	0.0119	0.0099	0.0053	0.0027	0.0055	0.0047	0.4936	6	4	0
0	0	0	0.0867	0.3504	0.3898	0	0	0	0.0037	0.0049	0.0033	0.39	1	3	0
0.0827	0.0827	0.2166	0.3623	0.5512	2.4371	0.0276	0.0138	0.0181	0.0151	0.0077	0.0204	0.4272	1	3	0
0	0.0158	0.0315	0.0355	0.063	8.4567	0	0.0027	0.0027	0.0015	0.0009	0.0705	0.3619	2	3	0
0	0.004	0.0355	0.0906	0.3859	1.1536	0	0.0007	0.003	0.0038	0.0054	0.0097	0.4056	3	4	0
0	0	0	0.0119	0.0788	0.4567	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0011	0.0039	0.494	3	3	0
0	0	0.0237	1.3111	3.0434	3.4016	0	0	0.002	0.0547	0.0423	0.0284	0.4328	1	1	0
0.0079	0.0197	0.0197	0.2953	0.6378	1.7756	0.0027	0.0033	0.0017	0.0124	0.0089	0.0148	0.3687	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.0197	0.2638	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0003	0.0022	0.4993	2	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.371	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0355	0.1654	0.4252	1.256	2.067	0.0027	0.006	0.0138	0.0178	0.0175	0.0173	0.312	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.0355	0.1339	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0005	0.0012	0.3497	3	4	0
0	0	0.004	0.0591	0.8465	1.1378	0	0	0.0004	0.0025	0.0118	0.0095	0.5094	1	4	0
0	0.0119	0.1103	0.2638	2.4371	2.7402	0	0.002	0.0092	0.011	0.0339	0.0229	0.3903	6	4	0
0	0	0.004	0.7599	2.4213	3.1221	0	0	0.0004	0.0317	0.0337	0.0261	0.31	1	3	0
0	0	0.0276	0.4882	1.1536	2.1103	0	0	0.0023	0.0204	0.0161	0.0176	0.504	1		0
0	0.0237	0.1693	0.3268	0.9528	1.7678	0	0.004	0.0142	0.0137	0.0133	0.0148	0.432	3	4	0
0.0512	0.0788	0.1103	0.3583	4.5434	9.9134	0.0171	0.0132	0.0092	0.015	0.0632	0.0827	0.3578	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0552	1.2166	1.2166	0	0	0	0.0023	0.0169	0.0102	0.5068	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.1063	0.2441	0.5079	0	0	0	0.0045	0.0034	0.0043	0.3772	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0158	0.5276	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0044	0.3778	3		0
0	0.004	0.0079	0.067	0.0788	0.1418	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0028	0.0011	0.0012	0.3052	2	4	0
0.0434	0.0552	0.2993	0.4095	1.004	1.5945	0.0145	0.0092	0.025	0.0171	0.014	0.0133	0.4382	5	1	0
0	0	0	0.1142	0.1575	0.4095	0	0	0	0.0048	0.0022	0.0035	0.499	1		0
0	0	0	0.0119	0.0473	0.1615	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0007	0.0014	0.269	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.6063	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0051	0.4481	2	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.1497	0.1575	0	0	0	0	0.0021	0.0014	0	1	3	0
0.0079	0.067	0.1142	0.252	1.0276	1.1063	0.0027	0.0112	0.0096	0.0105	0.0143	0.0093	0.049	2		0

0.0079	0.0709	0.1024	0.3583	0.7599	0.8229	0.0027	0.0119	0.0086	0.015	0.0106	0.0069	0.307	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.1221	0.2363	0.252	0	0	0	0.0051	0.0033	0.0021	0.454	1	3	0
0.2678	1.0434	1.067	1.1615	1.4843	1.7599	0.0893	0.1739	0.089	0.0484	0.0207	0.0147	0.411	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.2638	0.3859	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0037	0.0033	0.4417	4	4	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0276	0.0315	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0004	0.0003	0.427	2	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.1103	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.001	0.469	2	1	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0355	0.0749	0.2087	0	0	0.0007	0.0015	0.0011	0.0018	0.3703	6		0
0	0	0	0.0945	0.378	0.4764	0	0	0	0.004	0.0053	0.004	0.238	1	3	0
0	0	0.0473	0.0867	0.3032	0.3465	0	0	0.004	0.0037	0.0043	0.0029	0.404	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.004	0.004	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.0001	0.451	5	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.4646	1.7048	0	0	0	0	0.0065	0.0143	0.215	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0788	0.2008	0.2087	0	0	0	0.0033	0.0028	0.0018	0.4521	4	3	0
0	0.004	0.004	0.5434	0.6221	0.693	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0227	0.0087	0.0058	0.415	1		0
0	0	0.004	0.1969	0.1969	0.3308	0	0	0.0004	0.0083	0.0028	0.0028	0.3847	1		0
0	0	0.0315	0.3623	1.4764	1.7796	0	0	0.0027	0.0151	0.0206	0.0149	0.5037	3	1	0
0.0197	0.0237	0.0237	0.1536	0.5197	0.9174	0.0066	0.004	0.002	0.0064	0.0073	0.0077	0.451	2	3	0
0.1575	0.3189	0.7835	0.9686	1.315	1.3623	0.0525	0.0532	0.0653	0.0404	0.0183	0.0114	0	4	3	0
0	0	0	0.0749	0.4804	0.8071	0	0	0	0.0032	0.0067	0.0068	0.488	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.126	0.6969	0.7717	0	0	0	0.0053	0.0097	0.0065	0.362	1		0
0	0	0.0079	0.1221	0.4292	0.441	0	0	0.0007	0.0051	0.006	0.0037	0.387	1	1	0
0	0.193	0.4882	0.8229	1.6812	2.7048	0	0.0322	0.0407	0.0343	0.0234	0.0226	0.4305	2	4	0
0	0.004	0.0709	0.2441	0.4804	1.2756	0	0.0007	0.006	0.0102	0.0067	0.0107	0.4255	2	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0197	0	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.262	2	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0079	0.4686	0.6497	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0004	0.0066	0.0055	0	1		0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0119	0.0749	0.1497	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0005	0.0011	0.0013	0.181	1	4	0
0	0	0.004	0.0591	0.7402	0.9764	0	0	0.0004	0.0025	0.0103	0.0082	0.259	1	3	0
0.1418	0.2323	0.2717	0.6654	0.6733	0.7008	0.0473	0.0388	0.0227	0.0278	0.0094	0.0059	0.3761	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.252	1.1693	2.6142	0	0	0	0.0105	0.0163	0.0218	0.386	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.1969	0.2481	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0028	0.0021	0.2081	4	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.0985	0.1103	0	0	0	0	0.0014	0.001	0.406	4	4	0
0	0	0.0394	0.2599	0.5237	0.8701	0	0	0.0033	0.0109	0.0073	0.0073	0.393	1	3	0
0.0237	0.0434	0.0749	0.1497	0.3465	0.3465	0.0079	0.0073	0.0063	0.0063	0.0049	0.0029	0.3968	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.1221	0.1693	0.4016	0	0	0	0.0051	0.0024	0.0034	0.341	6	1	0
0	0.0276	0.0552	0.1536	0.6536	1.4922	0	0.0046	0.0046	0.0064	0.0091	0.0125	0.345	1		0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3891	5	3	0
0	0	0	0.3071	0.8386	0.9174	0	0	0	0.0128	0.0117	0.0077	0.4993	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0985	0.2205	0.2205	0	0	0	0.0042	0.0031	0.0019	0	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0552	0.0709	0	0	0	0	0.0008	0.0006	0.3531	5	3	0
0.004	0.0119	0.0119	0.0119	0.256	0.9607	0.0014	0.002	0.001	0.0005	0.0036	0.0081	0.4121	1	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0197	0.0434	0.3347	0	0	0.0007	0.0009	0.0007	0.0028	0.4255	4	3	0
0.004	0.0276	0.2599	0.3308	1.2875	1.5473	0.0014	0.0046	0.0217	0.0138	0.0179	0.0129	0.511	1	3	0
0	0	0.1851	0.7205	1.9843	3.2363	0	0	0.0155	0.0301	0.0276	0.027	0.4515	2	1	0
0	0	0	0.0434	0.9371	2.0512	0	0	0	0.0019	0.0131	0.0171	0.451	1	4	0
0	0	0.1024	0.1693	1.3819	1.6378	0	0	0.0086	0.0071	0.0192	0.0137	0.459	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.1969	0.7323	1.7008	2.9528	0	0.0007	0.0165	0.0306	0.0237	0.0247	0.4454	3	1	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.063	0.0945	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0009	0.0008	0.3962	1	4	0
0.0434	0.1339	0.2796	0.4095	4.6221	5.0355	0.0145	0.0224	0.0233	0.0171	0.0642	0.042	0.429	1		0
0	0	0	0.3898	0.9528	1.3701	0	0	0	0.0163	0.0133	0.0115	0.5069	1	3	0

0	0	0	0.0473	0.9686	1.7875	0	0	0	0.002	0.0135	0.0149	0.3336	1	4	0
0.0237	0.0394	0.0945	0.752	2.1733	2.3938	0.0079	0.0066	0.0079	0.0314	0.0302	0.02	0.441	1		0
0.0079	0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.1182	0.1182	0.0027	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0017	0.001	0.4366	3	3	0
0.1497	0.3741	0.6536	0.7166	1.3268	1.6772	0.0499	0.0624	0.0545	0.0299	0.0185	0.014	0.419	2	3	0
0.252	0.3583	0.3701	0.4567	0.5237	0.752	0.084	0.0598	0.0309	0.0191	0.0073	0.0063	0.357	1	4	0
0	0	0	1.004	2.6772	9.7914	0	0	0	0.0419	0.0372	0.0816	0.5148	1	1	0
0	0	0.1339	0.1457	0.1654	0.1772	0	0	0.0112	0.0061	0.0023	0.0015	0.479	5	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.1733	0.4843	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0025	0.0041	0.444	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0237	0.0237	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0004	0.0002	0.4473	1	1	0
0.0394	0.5355	1.2166	2.0079	2.5591	3.1615	0.0132	0.0893	0.1014	0.0837	0.0356	0.0264	0.507	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1182	3.2205	4.004	0	0	0	0.005	0.0448	0.0334	0.3937	3	3	0
0.0788	0.0945	0.0945	0.1851	0.2284	0.256	0.0263	0.0158	0.0079	0.0078	0.0032	0.0022	0.36	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0.0197	0.0197	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.0002	0.362	1	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.1378	0.3189	0.4764	0	0	0.0007	0.0058	0.0045	0.004	0.4681	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.13	0.7599	1.2914	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0055	0.0106	0.0108	0.271	3	1	0
0.13	0.3504	0.626	1.5788	9.0827	9.2835	0.0434	0.0584	0.0522	0.0658	0.1262	0.0774	0.5182	1	1	0
0.2323	0.2717	0.3662	0.6221	0.7166	0.7323	0.0775	0.0453	0.0306	0.026	0.01	0.0062	0.268	1		0
0	0	0	0.0749	0.2638	0.6615	0	0	0	0.0032	0.0037	0.0056	0.361	5		0
0	0	0	0	0.0867	0.3623	0	0	0	0	0.0013	0.0031	0.4603	1	3	0
0.004	0.0985	0.0985	0.1575	1.3583	1.815	0.0014	0.0165	0.0083	0.0066	0.0189	0.0152	0.291	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0394	0.0394	0.1142	0.3426	0.0027	0.0014	0.0033	0.0017	0.0016	0.0029	0	6	4	0
0.0276	0.0512	0.0867	0.1772	0.378	0.5355	0.0092	0.0086	0.0073	0.0074	0.0053	0.0045	0.4122	1	1	0
0.1772	0.3465	0.4489	0.4764	0.5434	2.3111	0.0591	0.0578	0.0375	0.0199	0.0076	0.0193	0.423	1		0
0.0315	0.1654	0.7717	1.504	2.4607	2.5197	0.0105	0.0276	0.0644	0.0627	0.0342	0.021	0.4983	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.0119	0.0315	0.189	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0005	0.0016	0.484	1		0
0	0	0	0.2245	1.1536	1.3741	0	0	0	0.0094	0.0161	0.0115	0.5038	4	1	0
0	0	0.0079	6.4174	7.6536	8.6812	0	0	0.0007	0.2674	0.1063	0.0724	0.3728	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0473	0.0552	0.1182	0	0	0	0.002	0.0008	0.001	0.4343	1		0
0.0709	0.1103	0.13	0.1654	0.8623	1.4882	0.0237	0.0184	0.0109	0.0069	0.012	0.0125	0.477	3		0
0	0.0079	0.0709	0.1182	2.5906	2.8032	0	0.0014	0.006	0.005	0.036	0.0234	0.4021	1	1	0
0.0276	0.0552	0.1339	0.3386	0.6378	1	0.0092	0.0092	0.0112	0.0142	0.0089	0.0084	0	5	3	0
0	0.0709	0.0985	0.1733	0.2638	0.3229	0	0.0119	0.0083	0.0073	0.0037	0.0027	0.328	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0237	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0002	0.254	2		0
0	0	0	0	1.5906	1.693	0	0	0	0	0.0221	0.0142	0.477	1	1	0
0.0197	0.0315	0.0709	0.0709	0.5867	0.8071	0.0066	0.0053	0.006	0.003	0.0082	0.0068	0.5022	2	3	0
0	0	0.0591	0.1536	1.1142	1.7166	0	0	0.005	0.0064	0.0155	0.0144	0.4415	5	3	0
0	0	0.256	0.6024	1.4804	1.7835	0	0	0.0214	0.0251	0.0206	0.0149	0.489	5	3	0
0	0.0315	0.1772	0.4607	3.0827	4.7166	0	0.0053	0.0148	0.0192	0.0429	0.0394	0.4581	3	3	0
0.0315	0.0473	0.063	0.1182	2.0867	3.0315	0.0105	0.0079	0.0053	0.005	0.029	0.0253	0.511	1	3	0
0.1024	0.1182	0.1182	0.1969	0.2796	0.2796	0.0342	0.0197	0.0099	0.0083	0.0039	0.0024	0.4463	1	3	0
0.0355	0.0434	0.0434	0.0434	0.4725	0.7638	0.0119	0.0073	0.0037	0.0019	0.0066	0.0064	0.301	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0473	0.5434	3.9489	0	0	0	0.002	0.0076	0.033	0.4078	1	1	0
0.0237	0.0434	0.1221	0.4213	0.5709	0.6418	0.0079	0.0073	0.0102	0.0176	0.008	0.0054	0.4032	1	3	0
0	0	0.0473	0.1851	0.8032	1.5237	0	0	0.004	0.0078	0.0112	0.0127	0.4949	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.1575	0.2205	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0022	0.0019	0.216	3	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.497	1	3	0
0	0	0.0591	0.5158	0.6063	0.878	0	0	0.005	0.0215	0.0085	0.0074	0.4124	3	4	0
0	0	0.4016	0.7008	1.3032	1.4843	0	0	0.0335	0.0292	0.0181	0.0124	0.3661	2	3	0

0.0552	0.0552	0.0788	0.5158	2.2481	2.8347	0.0184	0.0092	0.0066	0.0215	0.0313	0.0237	0.5119	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0119	0.0237	0.0394	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0004	0.0004	0.466	3	3	0
0.0119	0.0276	2.3504	4.8032	5.63	7.4646	0.004	0.0046	0.1959	0.2002	0.0782	0.0623	0.4184	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.1063	0.5079	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0015	0.0043	0.4634	1	1	0
0	0	0.0079	0.6142	2.3977	2.9843	0	0	0.0007	0.0256	0.0334	0.0249	0.4681	2	3	0
0.0434	0.063	0.1221	0.3426	1.3111	1.6457	0.0145	0.0105	0.0102	0.0143	0.0183	0.0138	0.503	4	4	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.2166	7.2993	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0031	0.0609	0.3518	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1063	0.1536	0.2363	0	0	0	0.0045	0.0022	0.002	0.4774	1	1	0
0.0276	0.256	0.4213	2.2087	6.7599	8.5	0.0092	0.0427	0.0352	0.0921	0.0939	0.0709	0.4277	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0158	0.0276	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0003	0.0003	0.414	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.2166	0.3977	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0031	0.0034	0.3802	4	3	1
0.3819	0.4922	0.5197	0.6418	1.4725	4.6024	0.1273	0.0821	0.0434	0.0268	0.0205	0.0384	0.5148	5	1	1
0	0.0158	0.2638	0.693	1.1182	3.1221	0	0.0027	0.022	0.0289	0.0156	0.0261	0.507	1	4	1
0.0079	0.0158	0.0237	0.2048	1.4252	1.4646	0.0027	0.0027	0.002	0.0086	0.0198	0.0123	0.4265	4	4	1
0	0.0158	0.1575	0.2717	3.6615	4.1772	0	0.0027	0.0132	0.0114	0.0509	0.0349	0.4178	1		1
0.0119	0.0591	0.1063	0.189	0.4449	1.7441	0.004	0.0099	0.0089	0.0079	0.0062	0.0146	0.439	1	3	1
0.2441	0.5827	1.3859	2.6142	4.9213	6.0473	0.0814	0.0972	0.1155	0.109	0.0684	0.0504	0.3896	3	3	1
0	0	0	0.1969	0.4607	2.441	0	0	0	0.0083	0.0064	0.0204	0.4255	4	4	1
0	0	0	0.6182	1.7087	1.8662	0	0	0	0.0258	0.0238	0.0156	0.4996	5	3	1
0	0.0394	0.0552	0.0552	0.4567	1.0985	0	0.0066	0.0046	0.0023	0.0064	0.0092	0.3809	2	3	1
0.13	0.2875	0.9489	4.8544	7.7796	8.4016	0.0434	0.048	0.0791	0.2023	0.1081	0.0701	0.3851	6	3	1
0	0.0315	0.0709	0.0788	0.0788	0.1851	0	0.0053	0.006	0.0033	0.0011	0.0016	0.5084	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.0197	0.0512	0.2284	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0008	0.002	0.483	5	4	1
0.0591	0.2166	0.504	1.6063	2.5197	4.126	0.0197	0.0361	0.042	0.067	0.035	0.0344	0.3583	4	4	1
0.0197	0.0473	0.0473	0.1457	0.4882	1.0788	0.0066	0.0079	0.004	0.0061	0.0068	0.009	0.497	6	3	1
0	0	0.0197	0.1024	0.6457	0.8819	0	0	0.0017	0.0043	0.009	0.0074	0.348	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.0473	1.1575	1.5	0	0	0	0.002	0.0161	0.0125	0.486	6	4	1
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	2.2284	2.8583	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.031	0.0239	0.478	1	1	1
0	0	0.0237	0.0552	0.4449	1.1339	0	0	0.002	0.0023	0.0062	0.0095	0.3725	5	3	1
0.0158	0.0276	0.0591	0.4646	1.0552	1.1693	0.0053	0.0046	0.005	0.0194	0.0147	0.0098	0.504	5	4	1
0.2048	1.0473	2.3583	3.3308	4.4686	5.0985	0.0683	0.1746	0.1966	0.1388	0.0621	0.0425	0.5082	4	3	1
0	0	0.0788	0.8426	1.6378	2.563	0	0	0.0066	0.0352	0.0228	0.0214	0.473	3	4	1
0	0	0	0.2087	0.815	1.0394	0	0	0	0.0087	0.0114	0.0087	0.443	4	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.0473	0.0473	0	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0	5	1	1
0.1182	1.315	1.6812	4.7205	6.2245	6.7796	0.0394	0.2192	0.1401	0.1967	0.0865	0.0565	0.5	5	3	1
0	0.0197	0.0276	0.2599	0.4134	0.6812	0	0.0033	0.0023	0.0109	0.0058	0.0057	0.497	2	3	1
0	0.0276	0.067	0.2245	0.8583	1.0079	0	0.0046	0.0056	0.0094	0.012	0.0084	0.3684	4	1	1
0.063	0.1812	0.2481	0.756	1.5552	3.7875	0.021	0.0302	0.0207	0.0315	0.0216	0.0316	0.5123	4	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0867	0.1063	0.3504	1.2875	0.0014	0.0033	0.0073	0.0045	0.0049	0.0108	0.4259	6	4	1
0.004	0.0158	0.1615	0.5709	6.8189	6.8898	0.0014	0.0027	0.0135	0.0238	0.0948	0.0575	0.416	1	3	1
0.0158	0.0749	0.5119	1.1182	4.6497	5.8071	0.0053	0.0125	0.0427	0.0466	0.0646	0.0484	0.4289	4	1	1
0.0079	0.0355	0.0512	0.063	0.5237	0.5237	0.0027	0.006	0.0043	0.0027	0.0073	0.0044	0.446	5	4	1
0.0827	0.2599	0.63	1.5985	3.1024	3.815	0.0276	0.0434	0.0525	0.0667	0.0431	0.0318	0.3665	4	1	1
0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.0197	0.0394	0.004	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0003	0.0004	0.411	6	3	1
0.2087	0.3071	0.5749	1.8347	2.1575	2.3859	0.0696	0.0512	0.048	0.0765	0.03	0.0199	0.496	4	3	1
0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.0197	0.0394	0.004	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0003	0.0004	0.411	6	3	1
0.3347	0.7402	1.1339	1.3268	1.5473	1.6024	0.1116	0.1234	0.0945	0.0553	0.0215	0.0134	0.232	3	4	1
0	0	0	0	1.3189	1.6142	0	0	0	0	0.0184	0.0135	0.5024	5	4	1

0	0	0	0.3189	0.5276	3.9016	0	0	0	0.0133	0.0074	0.0326	0.4624	6	3	1
0.0512	0.0709	0.1536	0.5827	2.3347	4.815	0.0171	0.0119	0.0128	0.0243	0.0325	0.0402	0.502	5	1	1
0.3623	1.2402	2.2756	4.5315	5.7048	6.2441	0.1208	0.2067	0.1897	0.1889	0.0793	0.0521	0.5162	2	4	1
0.0119	0.0512	0.0985	0.1969	0.6851	0.7284	0.004	0.0086	0.0083	0.0083	0.0096	0.0061	0.382	4	4	1
1.2048	1.9567	2.3938	3.8111	6.563	11.9449	0.4016	0.3262	0.1995	0.1588	0.0912	0.0996	0.3713	6	3	1
0.0315	0.1969	0.5552	1.378	2.9174	3.3544	0.0105	0.0329	0.0463	0.0575	0.0406	0.028	0.4153	4	3	1
0.0276	0.0315	0.0315	1.0985	3.256	4.1103	0.0092	0.0053	0.0027	0.0458	0.0453	0.0343	0.4297	4	3	1
2.8544	4.1812	5.5434	6.5394	7.1142	7.8229	0.9515	0.6969	0.462	0.2725	0.0989	0.0652	0.4718	4	1	1
0.1221	0.2796	0.7284	1.2993	2.9252	3.8544	0.0407	0.0466	0.0607	0.0542	0.0407	0.0322	0.4251	4	3	1
0.0158	0.3111	1.1339	1.4646	1.9725	2.3544	0.0053	0.0519	0.0945	0.0611	0.0274	0.0197	0.3926	2	3	1
0.0197	0.0197	0.0197	0.067	2.8308	3.0355	0.0066	0.0033	0.0017	0.0028	0.0394	0.0253	0.5161	1	3	1
0.0315	0.0906	0.8071	1.0591	1.4016	1.6221	0.0105	0.0151	0.0673	0.0442	0.0195	0.0136	0.413	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.2599	0.2599	0.2638	0	0	0	0.0109	0.0037	0.0022	0.4083	1	3	1
0	0.1615	0.7756	7.5079	12.7678	12.8741	0	0.027	0.0647	0.3129	0.1774	0.1073	0.383	3	3	1
1.1536	2.3977	3.7323	4.3859	12.6418	12.8426	0.3846	0.3997	0.3111	0.1828	0.1756	0.1071	0.4987	5	4	1
0.0276	0.0945	0.7875	1.8662	2.4056	2.5276	0.0092	0.0158	0.0657	0.0778	0.0335	0.0211	0.4713	4	3	1
0.0158	0.0276	0.0591	0.4646	1.0552	1.1693	0.0053	0.0046	0.005	0.0194	0.0147	0.0098	0.504	5	4	1
0	0.0197	0.0906	0.4056	2.2245	2.3544	0	0.0033	0.0076	0.0169	0.0309	0.0197	0.351	1	3	1
0	0	0	0.4607	0.4686	0.4922	0	0	0	0.0192	0.0066	0.0042	0.5	1	3	1
0.193	0.2914	0.3111	0.4567	1.6615	3.2008	0.0644	0.0486	0.026	0.0191	0.0231	0.0267	0	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0512	0.2599	0.6103	0.8386	1.6733	0.004	0.0086	0.0217	0.0255	0.0117	0.014	0.303	1	1	1
0.0079	0.0788	0.0788	0.5197	1.0315	1.3268	0.0027	0.0132	0.0066	0.0217	0.0144	0.0111	0.42	5	3	1
0	0.0158	0.3583	0.7481	2.1733	2.2441	0	0.0027	0.0299	0.0312	0.0302	0.0188	0.508	6	4	1
0.0315	0.0945	0.0985	0.7048	9.8544	11.9567	0.0105	0.0158	0.0083	0.0294	0.1369	0.0997	0.5191	4	4	1
0.0079	0.3623	0.9882	6.7756	11.4528	11.6575	0.0027	0.0604	0.0824	0.2824	0.1591	0.0972	0.3791	3	3	1
0	0.004	0.1851	0.6142	2.4449	2.8938	0	0.0007	0.0155	0.0256	0.034	0.0242	0.5024	5	4	1
0	0	0.0197	0.3465	7.0394	14.3623	0	0	0.0017	0.0145	0.0978	0.1197	0.4293	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.004	1.1969	2.2048	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0167	0.0184	0.4025	5	4	1
0.0119	0.0591	0.1536	0.5158	5.3701	8.5	0.004	0.0099	0.0128	0.0215	0.0746	0.0709	0.3132	4	3	1
0.7048	1.3898	2.3111	2.5512	3.0945	4.63	0.235	0.2317	0.1926	0.1063	0.043	0.0386	0.5074	4	3	1
0.0434	0.4371	0.7481	0.9174	2.7087	3.5709	0.0145	0.0729	0.0624	0.0383	0.0377	0.0298	0.334	2	3	1
0.0237	0.0906	0.1182	0.3701	1.9371	3	0.0079	0.0151	0.0099	0.0155	0.027	0.025	0.4293	4	3	1
0.1851	0.2953	0.8268	1.1812	2.8938	4.5276	0.0617	0.0493	0.0689	0.0493	0.0402	0.0378	0.511	5	3	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.063	0.2008	9.2953	13.063	0.0027	0.0014	0.0053	0.0084	0.1292	0.1089	0.5175	5	4	1
0	0.0158	0.2638	0.693	1.1182	3.1221	0	0.0027	0.022	0.0289	0.0156	0.0261	0.507	1	4	1
0	0	0	0.0119	0.0473	0.1693	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0007	0.0015	0.345	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.2481	0.4489	0.7008	0	0	0	0.0104	0.0063	0.0059	0.41	4	3	1
0.0315	0.0394	0.0512	0.3111	1.3386	3.8819	0.0105	0.0066	0.0043	0.013	0.0186	0.0324	0.4954	5	4	1
0.004	0.063	0.1812	0.5197	1.3426	2.4213	0.0014	0.0105	0.0151	0.0217	0.0187	0.0202	0.3613	2	4	1
0.2048	0.6221	0.8701	2.1536	4.3111	5.6418	0.0683	0.1037	0.0726	0.0898	0.0599	0.0471	0.4199	1	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0197	0.0276	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0003	0.0003	0.495	4	3	1
0.067	0.1733	0.3741	2.1221	5.878	6.1812	0.0224	0.0289	0.0312	0.0885	0.0817	0.0516	0.506	5	4	1
0	0.0355	0.1654	0.6378	1.9804	2.1182	0	0.006	0.0138	0.0266	0.0276	0.0177	0.369	6	3	1
0	0	0	0.5945	1.3426	1.626	0	0	0	0.0248	0.0187	0.0136	0.4075	5	4	1
0.1654	0.3741	0.8662	1.504	2.7796	3.567	0.0552	0.0624	0.0722	0.0627	0.0387	0.0298	0.3759	4	1	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0197	0.189	0.5945	1.0985	0.0014	0.0033	0.0017	0.0079	0.0083	0.0092	0.506	3	3	1
0.0197	0.1851	1.3662	2.9252	3.1733	3.2835	0.0066	0.0309	0.1139	0.1219	0.0441	0.0274	0.338	1	3	1
0	0	0.067	0.0827	0.6103	1.5788	0	0	0.0056	0.0035	0.0085	0.0132	0.426	6	4	1

0.0079	0.0079	0.0434	0.2756	2.8623	5.1063	0.0027	0.0014	0.0037	0.0115	0.0398	0.0426	0.5139	5	3	1
0	0	0	0.2875	0.6615	0.9016	0	0	0	0.012	0.0092	0.0076	0.4213	1	4	1
0.0355	0.0827	0.1693	0.3308	1.2796	1.3465	0.0119	0.0138	0.0142	0.0138	0.0178	0.0113	0.404	5	4	1
0	0.1221	2.3308	6.7717	6.815	6.9804	0	0.0204	0.1943	0.2822	0.0947	0.0582	0.336	6	3	1
0.1378	0.1497	0.1812	0.3859	2.9725	4.7245	0.046	0.025	0.0151	0.0161	0.0413	0.0394	0.517	6	3	1
0	0.004	0.1378	0.5827	4.8662	5.0473	0	0.0007	0.0115	0.0243	0.0676	0.0421	0.3492	6	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.1575	1.4843	0	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0124	0.4947	4	3	1
0.2441	0.4725	4.9371	10.7599	12.3544	13.6772	0.0814	0.0788	0.4115	0.4484	0.1716	0.114	0.3975	1	1	1
0.0473	0.0749	0.1103	0.1812	1.3938	2.3859	0.0158	0.0125	0.0092	0.0076	0.0194	0.0199	0.397	1		1
0.004	0.0315	0.0906	0.5119	1.4804	2.5906	0.0014	0.0053	0.0076	0.0214	0.0206	0.0216	0.421	3	4	1
0.0827	0.1221	0.2441	2.4292	3.8347	4.0473	0.0276	0.0204	0.0204	0.1013	0.0533	0.0338	0.3761	1	3	1
0.2245	0.9922	3.2363	5.0315	5.5985	6.6536	0.0749	0.1654	0.2697	0.2097	0.0778	0.0555	0.4221	3	4	1
0.0591	0.2166	0.504	1.6063	2.5197	4.126	0.0197	0.0361	0.042	0.067	0.035	0.0344	0.3583	4	3	1
0.4686	1.3229	1.5985	2.9371	3.7599	4.5906	0.1562	0.2205	0.1333	0.1224	0.0523	0.0383	0.361	6	3	1
0.0197	0.0197	0.0197	0.189	0.9646	2.2363	0.0066	0.0033	0.0017	0.0079	0.0134	0.0187	0.428	6	4	1
0.3111	1.0355	1.6221	2.3623	4.3701	4.7914	0.1037	0.1726	0.1352	0.0985	0.0607	0.04	0.4562	6	3	1
0.0079	0.0355	0.3859	1.189	1.7284	2.2796	0.0027	0.006	0.0322	0.0496	0.0241	0.019	0.4056	4	4	1
0.0827	0.1969	0.7245	1.8308	4.126	6.252	0.0276	0.0329	0.0604	0.0763	0.0574	0.0521	0.4193	2	4	1
0.3859	1.1536	4.6024	9.8544	14.0276	15.7835	0.1287	0.1923	0.3836	0.4106	0.1949	0.1316	0.2615	6	3	1
0	0.004	0.0394	0.063	1.7756	3.8741	0	0.0007	0.0033	0.0027	0.0247	0.0323	0.253	6	4	1
0.1142	0.2993	0.6418	1.4528	3.0315	3.8623	0.0381	0.0499	0.0535	0.0606	0.0422	0.0322	0.306	4	3	1
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.8071	1.8544	2.7402	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0337	0.0258	0.0229	0.4273	6	3	1
0.5473	1.0434	2.0158	5.0276	8.2953	8.6536	0.1825	0.1739	0.168	0.2095	0.1153	0.0722	0.4189	4	4	1
0	0.004	0.0079	0.2756	2.5276	3.2875	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0115	0.0352	0.0274	0.4013	1	1	1
0	0	0	0.504	0.8583	2.0985	0	0	0	0.021	0.012	0.0175	0.5	5	4	1
0.0119	0.0473	0.1536	0.567	7.5197	7.6693	0.004	0.0079	0.0128	0.0237	0.1045	0.064	0.5183	6	3	1
0.0355	0.0434	0.1024	1.626	3.0394	6.8741	0.0119	0.0073	0.0086	0.0678	0.0423	0.0573	0.515	3	1	1
0	0.004	0.2284	0.378	1.8111	2.6575	0	0.0007	0.0191	0.0158	0.0252	0.0222	0.3182	3	3	1
0.067	0.189	0.2953	0.7363	4.3623	4.5709	0.0224	0.0315	0.0247	0.0307	0.0606	0.0381	0.4906	4	3	1
0.0197	0.0985	0.6142	2.0079	8.3071	10.315	0.0066	0.0165	0.0512	0.0837	0.1154	0.086	0.3558	6	3	1
0.004	0.0315	0.0749	0.2599	5.0355	7.3898	0.0014	0.0053	0.0063	0.0109	0.07	0.0616	0.4663	4	3	1
0.0276	0.1654	0.2914	0.5315	4.1142	5.5315	0.0092	0.0276	0.0243	0.0222	0.0572	0.0461	0.429	2	3	1
0.0237	0.0749	0.1497	0.5237	2.6812	3.0237	0.0079	0.0125	0.0125	0.0219	0.0373	0.0252	0.369	1	4	1
0	0	0	0.1851	2.3859	6.0749	0	0	0	0.0078	0.0332	0.0507	0.5037	6	3	1
0.2323	0.2835	0.626	1.6772	1.8504	2.0985	0.0775	0.0473	0.0522	0.0699	0.0257	0.0175	0.4423	6	4	1
0	0.1063	0.7402	1.8032	8.2205	12.4528	0	0.0178	0.0617	0.0752	0.1142	0.1038	0.5179	5	4	1
0.0119	0.0473	0.1536	0.567	7.5197	7.6693	0.004	0.0079	0.0128	0.0237	0.1045	0.064	0.5183	6	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0197	0.189	0.5945	1.0985	0.0014	0.0033	0.0017	0.0079	0.0083	0.0092	0.506	4	3	1
0.0119	0.3071	0.3268	0.3347	1.2953	2.689	0.004	0.0512	0.0273	0.014	0.018	0.0225	0.5029	5	1	1
0.067	0.2678	2.0079	5.0867	5.4213	5.5	0.0224	0.0447	0.1674	0.212	0.0753	0.0459	0.4864	1	3	1
0.315	0.9095	1.9134	7.4843	8.1142	8.4134	0.105	0.1516	0.1595	0.3119	0.1127	0.0702	0.41	5	4	1
0	0.0079	0.0158	0.0158	1.4449	2.1575	0	0.0014	0.0014	0.0007	0.0201	0.018	0.342	4	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.5552	2.3111	0	0	0	0	0.0078	0.0193	0.474	2	3	1
0	0.0709	0.0709	0.1654	0.3898	1.0276	0	0.0119	0.006	0.0069	0.0055	0.0086	0.502	5	3	1
0.0158	0.0709	0.3544	0.7284	1.2441	1.3623	0.0053	0.0119	0.0296	0.0304	0.0173	0.0114	0.493	5	4	1
0.0315	0.1378	0.4725	0.8701	2.1536	2.3032	0.0105	0.023	0.0394	0.0363	0.03	0.0192	0.5181	6	3	1
0.13	0.1969	0.2599	0.3032	0.6851	0.8308	0.0434	0.0329	0.0217	0.0127	0.0096	0.007	0.396	1	3	1
0	0.0158	0.0158	0.0394	1	1.6063	0	0.0027	0.0014	0.0017	0.0139	0.0134	0.4563	1	3	1

0	0.0079	0.1182	0.2323	2.5394	4.0119	0	0.0014	0.0099	0.0097	0.0353	0.0335	0.3564	2	3	1
0.067	0.1575	0.3386	5.8268	8.1182	8.6103	0.0224	0.0263	0.0283	0.2428	0.1128	0.0718	0.4768	5	3	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.0552	1.4528	2.1497	2.3229	0.0027	0.0014	0.0046	0.0606	0.0299	0.0194	0.4715	5	3	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.0237	0.2717	2.3898	4.4056	0.0027	0.0014	0.002	0.0114	0.0332	0.0368	0.5163	4	3	1
0.3111	1.0355	1.6221	2.3623	4.3701	4.7914	0.1037	0.1726	0.1352	0.0985	0.0607	0.04	0.4562	6	3	1
0	0.0197	0.0276	0.2599	0.4134	0.6812	0	0.0033	0.0023	0.0109	0.0058	0.0057	0.497	4	3	1
0.3938	0.8819	1.5315	1.6536	1.8583	2.941	0.1313	0.147	0.1277	0.0689	0.0259	0.0246	0.4831	4	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.0276	0.0906	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0008	0.242	6	3	1
0.0355	0.1497	1.1378	1.689	4.2166	7.5158	0.0119	0.025	0.0949	0.0704	0.0586	0.0627	0.4228	6	4	1
0.2245	0.5906	1.0788	1.6851	7.5394	8.7953	0.0749	0.0985	0.0899	0.0703	0.1048	0.0733	0.5188	4	3	1
0.0276	0.0315	0.1969	0.9607	3.4252	4.5552	0.0092	0.0053	0.0165	0.0401	0.0476	0.038	0.4846	5	4	1
0.063	0.0906	0.1024	0.3347	0.7441	5.2953	0.021	0.0151	0.0086	0.014	0.0104	0.0442	0.41	1	3	1
0.0788	0.1418	0.2717	0.9213	1.9252	2.8819	0.0263	0.0237	0.0227	0.0384	0.0268	0.0241	0.404	6	4	1
0.004	0.0197	0.3308	1.5079	3.815	3.8308	0.0014	0.0033	0.0276	0.0629	0.053	0.032	0.276	1	3	1
0	0.0867	0.315	0.6536	6.504	10	0	0.0145	0.0263	0.0273	0.0904	0.0834	0.5163	4	1	1
0.0119	0.193	1.3189	1.6497	3.6969	5.2284	0.004	0.0322	0.11	0.0688	0.0514	0.0436	0.27	6	4	1
0	0	0	0	0.3071	4.6575	0	0	0	0	0.0043	0.0389	0.4334	5	3	1
0.1536	0.3032	1.1615	3.0591	4.6536	5.189	0.0512	0.0506	0.0968	0.1275	0.0647	0.0433	0.5147	6	3	1
0.0079	0.0158	0.0355	0.2481	7.5906	7.626	0.0027	0.0027	0.003	0.0104	0.1055	0.0636	0.4294	5	1	1
0.3859	1.1536	4.6024	9.8544	14.0276	15.7835	0.1287	0.1923	0.3836	0.4106	0.1949	0.1316	0.2615	6	3	1
0	0.0079	0.2599	1.0512	3.1457	5.8583	0	0.0014	0.0217	0.0438	0.0437	0.0489	0.429	2	4	1
0.0827	0.2599	0.63	1.5985	3.1024	3.815	0.0276	0.0434	0.0525	0.0667	0.0431	0.0318	0.3665	4	1	1
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0119	0.5709	1.1457	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0005	0.008	0.0096	0.484	5	3	1
0.0315	0.0945	0.1339	0.563	1.4331	2.6851	0.0105	0.0158	0.0112	0.0235	0.02	0.0224	0.4323	6	3	1
0.7481	1.4174	1.8701	2.5906	3.0237	3.9331	0.2494	0.2363	0.1559	0.108	0.042	0.0328	0.4999	4	3	1
0.1615	0.2245	0.5355	0.7441	1.4882	2.4725	0.0539	0.0375	0.0447	0.0311	0.0207	0.0207	0.344	5	4	1
0.1182	0.1615	0.2284	1.3977	4.4252	4.6615	0.0394	0.027	0.0191	0.0583	0.0615	0.0389	0.438	5	3	1
0.4843	1.3504	2.8111	6.563	15.6063	17.193	0.1615	0.2251	0.2343	0.2735	0.2168	0.1433	0.4815	4	3	1
1	1.9686	2.4567	3.1851	4.8662	5.6142	0.3334	0.3281	0.2048	0.1328	0.0676	0.0468	0.4584	3	3	1
0.0276	0.315	2.0749	8.9252	11.3741	11.9961	0.0092	0.0525	0.173	0.3719	0.158	0.1	0.3129	2	4	1
0.0591	0.063	0.063	0.0906	8.1182	8.6733	0.0197	0.0105	0.0053	0.0038	0.1128	0.0723	0.518	5	3	1
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0119	0.5709	1.1457	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0005	0.008	0.0096	0.484	5	3	1
0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.0434	0.0552	0.0985	0.0079	0.004	0.002	0.0019	0.0008	0.0009	0.423	3	3	1
0.0197	0.0985	0.6142	2.0079	8.3071	10.315	0.0066	0.0165	0.0512	0.0837	0.1154	0.086	0.3558	6	3	1
0.2245	0.3544	0.4764	0.9252	4.4725	5.7599	0.0749	0.0591	0.0397	0.0386	0.0622	0.048	0.3787	3	3	1
0	0	0	0.3111	1.378	1.8898	0	0	0	0.013	0.0192	0.0158	0.424	1	3	1
0	0.0985	0.0985	0.1812	0.9213	1.2245	0	0.0165	0.0083	0.0076	0.0128	0.0103	0.297	1	3	1
0.0276	0.0945	0.1969	0.7126	1.8032	7.6536	0.0092	0.0158	0.0165	0.0297	0.0251	0.0638	0.5152	5	3	1
0	0.0079	0.1182	0.2323	2.5394	4.0119	0	0.0014	0.0099	0.0097	0.0353	0.0335	0.3564	2	3	1
0.6575	1.0315	1.3583	2.0749	2.5158	3.2323	0.2192	0.172	0.1132	0.0865	0.035	0.027	0.492	3	3	1
0	0.0985	0.0985	0.1812	0.9213	1.2245	0	0.0165	0.0083	0.0076	0.0128	0.0103	0.297	1	3	1
0.0709	0.1221	0.2796	1.1024	1.9646	2.8819	0.0237	0.0204	0.0233	0.046	0.0273	0.0241	0.3762	5	4	1
0.0079	0.0788	0.0788	0.5197	1.0315	1.3268	0.0027	0.0132	0.0066	0.0217	0.0144	0.0111	0.42	5	3	1
0.0867	0.1693	0.5827	1.5355	5.3977	5.9489	0.0289	0.0283	0.0486	0.064	0.075	0.0496	0	4	1	1
0	0	0.0079	0.0276	0.0276	0.0355	0	0	0.0007	0.0012	0.0004	0.0003	0.3451	2	3	1
0.7126	1.0079	1.0197	1.0355	2.1457	2.2008	0.2376	0.168	0.085	0.0432	0.0299	0.0184	0	5	1	1
0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.0827	4.0512	4.7402	0.0053	0.0027	0.0014	0.0035	0.0563	0.0396	0.416	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0158	0.0276	0.067	1.4528	2.9016	0.004	0.0027	0.0023	0.0028	0.0202	0.0242	0.4742	5	3	1

0.0591	0.1221	0.2796	0.5827	2.4489	3.5197	0.0197	0.0204	0.0233	0.0243	0.0341	0.0294	0.223	6	3	1
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0119	0.5709	1.1457	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0005	0.008	0.0096	0.484	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.0197	0.9607	1.4843	0.004	0.0027	0.0014	0.0009	0.0134	0.0124	0.401	2	1	1
0.4095	0.6654	0.8977	1.7245	2.752	6.1418	0.1365	0.1109	0.0749	0.0719	0.0383	0.0512	0.427	3	4	1
0	0.0355	0.1654	0.6378	1.9804	2.1182	0	0.006	0.0138	0.0266	0.0276	0.0177	0.369	6	3	1
0.0119	0.0591	0.1536	0.5158	5.3701	8.5	0.004	0.0099	0.0128	0.0215	0.0746	0.0709	0.3132	4	3	1
0.504	0.8662	1.5276	2.693	4.63	5.2245	0.168	0.1444	0.1273	0.1123	0.0644	0.0436	0.4226	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.0158	0.4095	5.756	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0057	0.048	0.5133	1	3	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.0394	1.1142	6.2008	11.8465	0.0027	0.0014	0.0033	0.0465	0.0862	0.0988	0.3792	3	3	1
0	0	0	0.1457	1.4607	1.5749	0	0	0	0.0061	0.0203	0.0132	0.4196	1	1	1
0.067	0.2599	0.6733	2.0158	5.1457	6.4882	0.0224	0.0434	0.0562	0.084	0.0715	0.0541	0.3977	2	3	1
0.3386	0.5512	1.2087	1.3701	2.1812	8.6063	0.1129	0.0919	0.1008	0.0571	0.0303	0.0718	0.5143	5	3	1
0.004	0.0197	0.0197	0.189	0.5945	1.0985	0.0014	0.0033	0.0017	0.0079	0.0083	0.0092	0.506	4	3	1
0.0394	0.0434	0.4292	0.6339	1.3701	1.9686	0.0132	0.0073	0.0358	0.0265	0.0191	0.0165	0.451	6	3	1
0.0237	0.1142	0.1693	0.2284	3.4725	4.441	0.0079	0.0191	0.0142	0.0096	0.0483	0.0371	0.45	4	3	1
0	0	0	0.504	1.3386	2.3111	0	0	0	0.021	0.0186	0.0193	0.4133	4	4	1
0.0276	0.0906	0.441	1.2008	1.9371	2.2441	0.0092	0.0151	0.0368	0.0501	0.027	0.0188	0.393	4	3	1
0	0	0.0079	0.1339	0.756	1.9449	0	0	0.0007	0.0056	0.0105	0.0163	0.428	3	4	1
0	0	0	0.3189	1.3071	1.3071	0	0	0	0.0133	0.0182	0.0109	0.318	1	3	0
0	0	0.0355	0.0827	0.1497	0.4252	0	0	0.003	0.0035	0.0021	0.0036	0.5041	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0237	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0002	0.254	2		0
0	0	0.0158	0.1536	1.9371	2.0788	0	0	0.0014	0.0064	0.027	0.0174	0	1	3	0
0.0197	0.0237	0.067	0.4567	0.8032	1.8032	0.0066	0.004	0.0056	0.0191	0.0112	0.0151	0.28	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.4843	1.0197	0	0	0	0	0.0068	0.0085	0.4271	1	4	0
0	0	0.0197	0.0827	0.3623	3.2245	0	0	0.0017	0.0035	0.0051	0.0269	0.3522	2	3	0
0	0	0.0119	0.0276	0.8898	2.3898	0	0	0.001	0.0012	0.0124	0.02	0.502	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0119	0.0749	0.1497	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0005	0.0011	0.0013	0.181	1	4	0
0.0276	0.0788	0.0788	0.0906	0.3032	1.0434	0.0092	0.0132	0.0066	0.0038	0.0043	0.0087	0.502	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0512	0.0552	0	0	0	0	0.0008	0.0005	0	2	4	0
0	0	0.0119	0.2323	1.6733	2.9449	0	0	0.001	0.0097	0.0233	0.0246	0.4999	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.3544	0.6812	0	0	0	0.0009	0.005	0.0057	0.38	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.063	0.7166	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0009	0.006	0.3186	2	1	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0.1733	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0005	0.0002	0.0015	0.358	2	4	0
0	0	0.1575	0.2481	1.7205	3.3308	0	0	0.0132	0.0104	0.0239	0.0278	0.3117	1	4	0
0.004	0.004	0.0591	0.1221	0.5591	1.6969	0.0014	0.0007	0.005	0.0051	0.0078	0.0142	0.285	4	4	0
0.0355	0.0434	0.1103	0.1378	0.5237	1.0985	0.0119	0.0073	0.0092	0.0058	0.0073	0.0092	0.293	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1221	0.2363	0.252	0	0	0	0.0051	0.0033	0.0021	0.454	1	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0119	0.3308	0.5394	0	0	0.0007	0.0005	0.0046	0.0045	0.392	2	3	0
0	0	0.0355	0.0906	0.2402	0.7993	0	0	0.003	0.0038	0.0034	0.0067	0.4967	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0434	0.2048	1.2796	1.2875	2.4607	0.004	0.0073	0.0171	0.0534	0.0179	0.0206	0.357	1		0
0	0	0	0.3426	0.9095	4.6142	0	0	0	0.0143	0.0127	0.0385	0.4384	5		0
0.0079	0.189	0.2008	0.2441	0.7638	2.2481	0.0027	0.0315	0.0168	0.0102	0.0107	0.0188	0.34	1	1	0
0.004	0.0119	0.1497	0.1851	0.815	1.4607	0.0014	0.002	0.0125	0.0078	0.0114	0.0122	0.482	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0315	0.063	0.1221	0	0	0	0.0014	0.0009	0.0011	0.3132	1	3	0
0.3032	0.5237	0.5985	0.689	0.7323	1.2363	0.1011	0.0873	0.0499	0.0288	0.0102	0.0104	0.418	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0827	0.1733	0.3544	0	0	0	0.0035	0.0025	0.003	0.306	2	3	0
0.0197	0.1339	0.2953	0.5079	1.8071	4.5591	0.0066	0.0224	0.0247	0.0212	0.0251	0.038	0.3078	1	3	0
0	0	0.0788	0.0788	0.1812	0.1812	0	0	0.0066	0.0033	0.0026	0.0016	0.273	1	3	0

0	0	0	0.1339	0.1615	1.1733	0	0	0	0.0056	0.0023	0.0098	0.4	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.0001	0.4771	1	3	0
0	0.0119	0.3977	0.4607	0.6693	1.0945	0	0.002	0.0332	0.0192	0.0093	0.0092	0.371	2		0
0	0	0	0.0709	0.3662	1.7993	0	0	0	0.003	0.0051	0.015	0.3815	2	1	0
0	0	0.0749	0.1654	0.2008	0.9489	0	0	0.0063	0.0069	0.0028	0.008	0.498	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.0709	0.3662	1.7993	0	0	0	0.003	0.0051	0.015	0.3815	2	1	0
0	0	0	0.0749	0.3662	0.4528	0	0	0	0.0032	0.0051	0.0038	0.2963	1	4	0
0	0	0	1.004	2.6772	9.7914	0	0	0	0.0419	0.0372	0.0816	0.5148	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.3426	0.9134	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0048	0.0077	0.3901	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.2245	0.2363	0.4252	0	0	0	0.0094	0.0033	0.0036	0.2674	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0906	0.1536	0	0	0	0	0.0013	0.0013	0.3791	3	3	0
0	0	0	0.1142	0.2993	4.7599	0	0	0	0.0048	0.0042	0.0397	0.38	1	1	0
0	0.0512	0.1103	0.5434	1.6654	2.1063	0	0.0086	0.0092	0.0227	0.0232	0.0176	0.48	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.1063	0.1418	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0015	0.0012	0.331	2		0
0	0	0.0591	0.1536	1.1142	1.7166	0	0	0.005	0.0064	0.0155	0.0144	0.4415	5	3	0
0	0	0	0.1575	1.067	1.4292	0	0	0	0.0066	0.0149	0.012	0.492	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.2284	0.3741	0.4134	0	0	0	0.0096	0.0052	0.0035	0.271	1	4	0
0	0.004	0.2717	0.3189	1.1457	1.1851	0	0.0007	0.0227	0.0133	0.016	0.0099	0.475	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.1615	0	0	0	0	0	0.0014	0.3791	1	1	0
0	0	0.0394	0.0394	0.0788	0.5197	0	0	0.0033	0.0017	0.0011	0.0044	0.414	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.0355	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0003	0.3925	1	1	0
0.0119	0.0237	0.0512	0.2008	0.2875	1.063	0.004	0.004	0.0043	0.0084	0.004	0.0089	0.42	1		0
0.0552	0.0552	0.0552	0.126	0.3111	0.6182	0.0184	0.0092	0.0046	0.0053	0.0044	0.0052	0.503	2	3	0
0.0591	0.1812	0.1812	0.189	0.3504	0.8741	0.0197	0.0302	0.0151	0.0079	0.0049	0.0073	0.34	1	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0119	0.3308	0.5394	0	0	0.0007	0.0005	0.0046	0.0045	0.392	2	3	0
0	0.004	0.004	0.315	0.4016	0.8859	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0132	0.0056	0.0074	0.4256	1		0
0.0079	0.0079	0.067	0.5276	1.3544	1.378	0.0027	0.0014	0.0056	0.022	0.0189	0.0115	0.497	2	4	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.0394	0.1654	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0006	0.0014	0.432	1	3	0
0.0434	0.0591	0.13	0.315	1.4882	2.6418	0.0145	0.0099	0.0109	0.0132	0.0207	0.0221	0.424	1	1	0
0	0.0119	0.0119	0.3938	0.9252	1.7087	0	0.002	0.001	0.0165	0.0129	0.0143	0.3623	2	1	0
0.0237	0.0591	0.1969	0.7205	1.7835	3.2087	0.0079	0.0099	0.0165	0.0301	0.0248	0.0268	0.3661	3	3	0
0.1024	0.1851	0.4095	0.8229	2.193	2.8859	0.0342	0.0309	0.0342	0.0343	0.0305	0.0241	0.3641	2	1	0
0	0.0237	0.0276	0.5158	0.941	1.2756	0	0.004	0.0023	0.0215	0.0131	0.0107	0.408	1	3	0
0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.0197	0.2323	0.567	0.0053	0.0027	0.0014	0.0009	0.0033	0.0048	0.3923	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0315	0.1142	0.2205	0	0	0	0.0014	0.0016	0.0019	0.4224	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0749	0.0749	0	0	0	0	0.0011	0.0007	0.341	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0394	2.8583	3.756	0	0	0	0.0017	0.0397	0.0313	0.3639	1	3	0
0.0276	0.2441	0.2717	0.3662	0.7796	1.1772	0.0092	0.0407	0.0227	0.0153	0.0109	0.0099	0.429	1	3	0
0.0158	0.0237	0.0237	0.0237	0.2678	0.3347	0.0053	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.0038	0.0028	0.331	1	3	0
0.0749	0.1615	0.193	0.6575	1.2323	1.3268	0.025	0.027	0.0161	0.0274	0.0172	0.0111	0.4989	1		0
0	0.0119	0.0158	0.0158	0.1063	0.1536	0	0.002	0.0014	0.0007	0.0015	0.0013	0.3991	1	3	0
0.1103	0.2481	0.2678	0.6063	1.0945	1.3229	0.0368	0.0414	0.0224	0.0253	0.0153	0.0111	0.4896	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0237	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0002	0.254	2		0
0	0.0709	0.1457	0.441	1.0079	1.2166	0	0.0119	0.0122	0.0184	0.014	0.0102	0.404	1	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.1378	0.3189	0.4764	0	0	0.0007	0.0058	0.0045	0.004	0.4681	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.4016	0.6221	1.1812	0	0	0	0.0168	0.0087	0.0099	0.3891	1	3	0
0.0434	0.0945	0.189	0.5237	3.4449	4.1103	0.0145	0.0158	0.0158	0.0219	0.0479	0.0343	0.517	1	3	0
0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.1536	0.1812	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0022	0.0016	0.495	1	4	0

0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0.0276	0.0749	0.0945	0.0027	0.002	0.001	0.0012	0.0011	0.0008	0.2985	1	1	0
0	0	0.3426	1.3741	2.2481	2.4489	0	0	0.0286	0.0573	0.0313	0.0205	0.494	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0315	0.0315	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0003	0.466	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.3032	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0026	0.3667	1	3	0
0.0158	0.067	0.1142	0.3032	0.9764	1.2914	0.0053	0.0112	0.0096	0.0127	0.0136	0.0108	0.4679	1	4	0
0.0237	0.126	0.3544	0.5	4.1615	8.5788	0.0079	0.021	0.0296	0.0209	0.0578	0.0715	0.5167	1		0
0	0	0.0119	0.0119	0.0473	0.0473	0	0	0.001	0.0005	0.0007	0.0004	0.3784	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.0355	0.0355	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0003	0.331	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0119	0.0158	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0002	0.0002	0.3291	1	3	0
0.0197	0.0552	0.1063	0.4174	2.252	2.8426	0.0066	0.0092	0.0089	0.0174	0.0313	0.0237	0.4165	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.1024	0.3544	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0015	0.003	0	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.4016	1.4331	1.6654	0	0	0	0.0168	0.02	0.0139	0.241	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.063	0.1772	0.2481	0	0	0	0.0027	0.0025	0.0021	0.4021	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1103	0.378	0.5237	0	0	0	0.0046	0.0053	0.0044	0.4933	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.0945	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0008	0.3451	1	3	0
0.0315	0.0512	0.063	0.0867	0.1142	0.1182	0.0105	0.0086	0.0053	0.0037	0.0016	0.001	0.153	1	3	0
0.2402	0.3977	0.5	0.941	1.752	2.3308	0.0801	0.0663	0.0417	0.0393	0.0244	0.0195	0.508	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.0237	0.0591	0.4567	0	0	0	0.001	0.0009	0.0039	0.3221	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.0001	0.431	2	1	0
0	0	0.004	0.0079	0.4725	0.7402	0	0	0.0004	0.0004	0.0066	0.0062	0.498	1	1	0
0	0	0.0119	0.13	0.4489	0.4528	0	0	0.001	0.0055	0.0063	0.0038	0.4433	1		0
0.0158	0.0315	0.0709	0.0749	0.1378	0.3308	0.0053	0.0053	0.006	0.0032	0.002	0.0028	0.392	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.0709	0.2678	0	0	0	0.0017	0.001	0.0023	0.407	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0001	0.4099	1	4	0
0	0.004	0.4725	1.1063	2.2481	3.2599	0	0.0007	0.0394	0.0461	0.0313	0.0272	0.2963	2	3	0
0.1378	0.4449	0.6654	0.6693	0.7205	0.7245	0.046	0.0742	0.0555	0.0279	0.0101	0.0061	0.477	1	4	0
0.0276	0.0434	0.0867	0.1024	0.1654	0.5	0.0092	0.0073	0.0073	0.0043	0.0023	0.0042	0.4133	1	3	0
0.0079	0.189	0.1969	0.2008	0.256	0.3977	0.0027	0.0315	0.0165	0.0084	0.0036	0.0034	0.287	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0394	0.189	0.9489	1.2245	7.1536	0.0027	0.0066	0.0158	0.0396	0.0171	0.0597	0.416	1		0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.0394	0.2678	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0006	0.0023	0.4135	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0119	0.3701	0.8819	3.6812	4.7441	0.004	0.002	0.0309	0.0368	0.0512	0.0396	0.4857	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.295	1		0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.6024	0.9016	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0084	0.0076	0.369	1	4	0
0	0.0119	0.126	0.3347	1.256	1.3426	0	0.002	0.0105	0.014	0.0175	0.0112	0.471	3	3	0
0.0237	0.1063	0.2402	0.2756	0.7441	1.3819	0.0079	0.0178	0.0201	0.0115	0.0104	0.0116	0.304	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.4016	0.4016	0	0	0	0	0.0056	0.0034	0.4832	5	3	0
0	0.004	0.004	0.0079	0.0394	0.0434	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0004	0.0006	0.0004	0.3504	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0512	0.252	0.2638	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0035	0.0022	0.4	1	3	0
0.0355	0.1418	0.3071	1.0276	2.193	2.2678	0.0119	0.0237	0.0256	0.0429	0.0305	0.0189	0	2	1	0
0.0079	0.0945	0.193	0.7205	2.4095	4.3071	0.0027	0.0158	0.0161	0.0301	0.0335	0.0359	0.516	3	3	0
0	0.0158	0.1142	0.3504	0.4371	0.752	0	0.0027	0.0096	0.0146	0.0061	0.0063	0.5081	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.0237	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.37	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0197	0.13	0.2402	1.0473	0.0027	0.0014	0.0017	0.0055	0.0034	0.0088	0.452	6	4	0
0	0	0	0.252	1.1693	2.6142	0	0	0	0.0105	0.0163	0.0218	0.386	1	4	0
0	0.0119	0.126	0.3347	1.256	1.3426	0	0.002	0.0105	0.014	0.0175	0.0112	0.471	3	3	0
0.0749	0.193	0.2796	0.3701	0.5945	0.6812	0.025	0.0322	0.0233	0.0155	0.0083	0.0057	0.442	1	1	0
0.004	0.0394	0.1851	0.3308	0.9016	1.3898	0.0014	0.0066	0.0155	0.0138	0.0126	0.0116	0.387	1	1	0
0	0.0158	0.0197	0.2953	0.378	0.5552	0	0.0027	0.0017	0.0124	0.0053	0.0047	0.42	1	3	0

0.1182	0.2205	0.2796	0.4174	0.6969	1.3032	0.0394	0.0368	0.0233	0.0174	0.0097	0.0109	0.327	1	3	0
0.0945	0.1103	0.1103	0.2875	0.9489	1.0512	0.0315	0.0184	0.0092	0.012	0.0132	0.0088	0.306	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0119	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.493	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.252	2	3	0
0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0512	0	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0002	0.0005	0.2696	3	3	0
0.0709	0.193	0.2796	0.2835	0.7993	1.9882	0.0237	0.0322	0.0233	0.0119	0.0112	0.0166	0.4121	3	1	0
0	0	0.004	0.063	5.8229	6.9371	0	0	0.0004	0.0027	0.0809	0.0579	0.4873	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0158	0.0158	0.0158	0.1182	0.1182	0.0027	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0017	0.001	0.4366	3	3	0
0	0	0.1103	0.1142	0.2205	0.3623	0	0	0.0092	0.0048	0.0031	0.0031	0.3561	4	1	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.24	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.0473	0.3111	1.7914	2.8701	0.0014	0.0007	0.004	0.013	0.0249	0.024	0.4618	1	1	0
0	0.0276	0.0315	0.1693	0.189	0.4489	0	0.0046	0.0027	0.0071	0.0027	0.0038	0.3778	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0001	0.4099	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0315	0	0	0	0	0	0.0003	0.3531	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0158	0.0197	0.2638	0	0	0	0.0007	0.0003	0.0022	0.4993	2	4	0
0.004	0.004	0.0079	0.0315	0.1339	0.3898	0.0014	0.0007	0.0007	0.0014	0.0019	0.0033	0.492	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.6024	0.6182	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0084	0.0052	0.4913	4	4	0
0.193	0.2993	0.3898	0.6575	3.2835	5.878	0.0644	0.0499	0.0325	0.0274	0.0457	0.049	0.3416	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0276	0.2205	0.504	0	0	0	0.0012	0.0031	0.0042	0.079	1	3	0
0.252	0.3583	0.3701	0.4567	0.5237	0.752	0.084	0.0598	0.0309	0.0191	0.0073	0.0063	0.357	1	4	0
0	0	0.0119	0.3308	0.4961	0.7441	0	0	0.001	0.0138	0.0069	0.0063	0.337	1	3	0
0	0.004	0.0079	0.063	0.5827	0.7402	0	0.0007	0.0007	0.0027	0.0081	0.0062	0.4662	1		0
0	0	0	0.3701	1.4528	2.689	0	0	0	0.0155	0.0202	0.0225	0.364	1	4	0
0.0079	0.0237	0.5197	2.0985	2.9686	3.0394	0.0027	0.004	0.0434	0.0875	0.0413	0.0254	0.3611	1	3	0
0	0.0394	0.1339	0.4292	0.441	0.441	0	0.0066	0.0112	0.0179	0.0062	0.0037	0.444	3	3	0
0.0158	0.1024	0.1339	0.5276	0.6575	0.7638	0.0053	0.0171	0.0112	0.022	0.0092	0.0064	0.3788	1	1	0
0	0	0.0512	0.3071	0.3859	2.5827	0	0	0.0043	0.0128	0.0054	0.0216	0.418	1		0
0.0276	0.0434	0.0867	0.1024	0.1654	0.5	0.0092	0.0073	0.0073	0.0043	0.0023	0.0042	0.4133	1	3	0
0.004	0.0276	0.2599	0.3308	1.2875	1.5473	0.0014	0.0046	0.0217	0.0138	0.0179	0.0129	0.511	1	3	0
0	0.0119	0.3977	0.4607	0.6693	1.0945	0	0.002	0.0332	0.0192	0.0093	0.0092	0.371	2		0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3891	5	3	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.1575	0.2205	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0022	0.0019	0.216	3	3	0
0	0	0.0276	0.0906	0.3819	0.3819	0	0	0.0023	0.0038	0.0054	0.0032	0.47	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.6339	1.0237	1.3583	0	0	0	0.0265	0.0143	0.0114	0.4832	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.126	0	0	0	0	0	0.0011	0.33	2	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0394	0.0394	0.1142	0.3426	0.0027	0.0014	0.0033	0.0017	0.0016	0.0029	0	6	4	0
0	0.1063	0.6418	0.9528	1.9922	3.3898	0	0.0178	0.0535	0.0397	0.0277	0.0283	0.424	1	3	0
0.004	0.004	0.0276	0.2363	2.6339	2.752	0.0014	0.0007	0.0023	0.0099	0.0366	0.023	0.4282	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.1182	0.7166	1.0985	1.2166	0.0027	0.0014	0.0099	0.0299	0.0153	0.0102	0.336	1		0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3891	5	3	0
0	0	0.1024	0.1693	1.3819	1.6378	0	0	0.0086	0.0071	0.0192	0.0137	0.459	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0512	0.252	0.2638	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0035	0.0022	0.4	1	3	0
0.0158	0.0473	0.0473	0.1615	0.3347	0.6339	0.0053	0.0079	0.004	0.0068	0.0047	0.0053	0.4962	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0434	0.9371	2.0512	0	0	0	0.0019	0.0131	0.0171	0.451	1	4	0
0	0	0	0.2126	0.4371	0.6733	0	0	0	0.0089	0.0061	0.0057	0.4121	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0709	0.2638	0	0	0	0	0.001	0.0022	0.3561	1	1	0
0	0	0.1103	0.1142	0.2205	0.3623	0	0	0.0092	0.0048	0.0031	0.0031	0.3561	4	1	0
0	0.0079	0.0709	0.1182	2.5906	2.8032	0	0.0014	0.006	0.005	0.036	0.0234	0.4021	1	1	0

0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0.0276	0.0749	0.0945	0.0027	0.002	0.001	0.0012	0.0011	0.0008	0.2985	1	1	0
0	0	0.3426	1.3741	2.2481	2.4489	0	0	0.0286	0.0573	0.0313	0.0205	0.494	1	1	0
0	0	0	0	0.0315	0.0315	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0003	0.466	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.0119	0.3032	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0026	0.3667	1	3	0
0.0158	0.067	0.1142	0.3032	0.9764	1.2914	0.0053	0.0112	0.0096	0.0127	0.0136	0.0108	0.4679	1	4	0
0.0237	0.126	0.3544	0.5	4.1615	8.5788	0.0079	0.021	0.0296	0.0209	0.0578	0.0715	0.5167	1		0
0	0	0.0119	0.0119	0.0473	0.0473	0	0	0.001	0.0005	0.0007	0.0004	0.3784	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.0355	0.0355	0	0	0	0	0.0005	0.0003	0.331	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.004	0.0119	0.0158	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0002	0.0002	0.3291	1	3	0
0.0197	0.0552	0.1063	0.4174	2.252	2.8426	0.0066	0.0092	0.0089	0.0174	0.0313	0.0237	0.4165	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.1024	0.3544	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0015	0.003	0	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.4016	1.4331	1.6654	0	0	0	0.0168	0.02	0.0139	0.241	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.063	0.1772	0.2481	0	0	0	0.0027	0.0025	0.0021	0.4021	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.1103	0.378	0.5237	0	0	0	0.0046	0.0053	0.0044	0.4933	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.0945	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0008	0.3451	1	3	0
0.0315	0.0512	0.063	0.0867	0.1142	0.1182	0.0105	0.0086	0.0053	0.0037	0.0016	0.001	0.153	1	3	0
0.2402	0.3977	0.5	0.941	1.752	2.3308	0.0801	0.0663	0.0417	0.0393	0.0244	0.0195	0.508	2	3	0
0	0	0	0.0237	0.0591	0.4567	0	0	0	0.001	0.0009	0.0039	0.3221	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0079	0.0119	0.0119	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.0001	0.431	2	1	0
0	0	0.004	0.0079	0.4725	0.7402	0	0	0.0004	0.0004	0.0066	0.0062	0.498	1	1	0
0	0	0.0119	0.13	0.4489	0.4528	0	0	0.001	0.0055	0.0063	0.0038	0.4433	1		0
0.0158	0.0315	0.0709	0.0749	0.1378	0.3308	0.0053	0.0053	0.006	0.0032	0.002	0.0028	0.392	1	1	0
0	0	0	0.0394	0.0709	0.2678	0	0	0	0.0017	0.001	0.0023	0.407	1	2	0
0	0	0	0	0.0079	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0.0002	0.0001	0.4099	1	4	0
0	0.004	0.4725	1.1063	2.2481	3.2599	0	0.0007	0.0394	0.0461	0.0313	0.0272	0.2963	2	3	0
0.1378	0.4449	0.6654	0.6693	0.7205	0.7245	0.046	0.0742	0.0555	0.0279	0.0101	0.0061	0.477	1	4	0
0.0276	0.0434	0.0867	0.1024	0.1654	0.5	0.0092	0.0073	0.0073	0.0043	0.0023	0.0042	0.4133	1	3	0
0.0079	0.189	0.1969	0.2008	0.256	0.3977	0.0027	0.0315	0.0165	0.0084	0.0036	0.0034	0.287	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0394	0.189	0.9489	1.2245	7.1536	0.0027	0.0066	0.0158	0.0396	0.0171	0.0597	0.416	1		0
0	0	0	0.0197	0.0394	0.2678	0	0	0	0.0009	0.0006	0.0023	0.4135	1	3	0
0.0119	0.0119	0.3701	0.8819	3.6812	4.7441	0.004	0.002	0.0309	0.0368	0.0512	0.0396	0.4857	1	4	0
0	0	0	0	0	0.0079	0	0	0	0	0	0.0001	0.295	1		0
0	0	0	0.0355	0.6024	0.9016	0	0	0	0.0015	0.0084	0.0076	0.369	1	4	0
0	0.0119	0.126	0.3347	1.256	1.3426	0	0.002	0.0105	0.014	0.0175	0.0112	0.471	3	3	0
0.0237	0.1063	0.2402	0.2756	0.7441	1.3819	0.0079	0.0178	0.0201	0.0115	0.0104	0.0116	0.304	1		0
0	0	0	0	0.4016	0.4016	0	0	0	0	0.0056	0.0034	0.4832	5	3	0
0	0.004	0.004	0.0079	0.0394	0.0434	0	0.0007	0.0004	0.0004	0.0006	0.0004	0.3504	1	3	0
0	0	0	0.0512	0.252	0.2638	0	0	0	0.0022	0.0035	0.0022	0.4	1	3	0
0.0355	0.1418	0.3071	1.0276	2.193	2.2678	0.0119	0.0237	0.0256	0.0429	0.0305	0.0189	0	2	1	0
0.0079	0.0945	0.193	0.7205	2.4095	4.3071	0.0027	0.0158	0.0161	0.0301	0.0335	0.0359	0.516	3	3	0
0	0.0158	0.1142	0.3504	0.4371	0.752	0	0.0027	0.0096	0.0146	0.0061	0.0063	0.5081	1	3	0
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.0237	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0002	0.37	1	3	0
0.0079	0.0079	0.0197	0.13	0.2402	1.0473	0.0027	0.0014	0.0017	0.0055	0.0034	0.0088	0.452	6	4	0
0	0	0	0.252	1.1693	2.6142	0	0	0	0.0105	0.0163	0.0218	0.386	1	4	0
0	0.0119	0.126	0.3347	1.256	1.3426	0	0.002	0.0105	0.014	0.0175	0.0112	0.471	3	3	0
0.0749	0.193	0.2796	0.3701	0.5945	0.6812	0.025	0.0322	0.0233	0.0155	0.0083	0.0057	0.442	1	1	0
0.004	0.0394	0.1851	0.3308	0.9016	1.3898	0.0014	0.0066	0.0155	0.0138	0.0126	0.0116	0.387	1	1	0
0	0.0158	0.0197	0.2953	0.378	0.5552	0	0.0027	0.0017	0.0124	0.0053	0.0047	0.42	1	3	0

0.0473	0.0827	0.126	0.4528	1.2638	1.9489	0.0158	0.0138	0.0105	0.0189	0.0176	0.0163	0.5126	1	3	1
0.0394	0.0788	0.1339	0.3071	1.0867	1.6221	0.0132	0.0132	0.0112	0.0128	0.0151	0.0136	0.5132	5	3	1
0.315	0.6536	1.7402	3.2756	3.8189	4.878	0.105	0.109	0.1451	0.1365	0.0531	0.0407	0.5146	5	3	1
0	0	0.3386	0.3544	1.756	2.2087	0	0	0.0283	0.0148	0.0244	0.0185	0.3618	1	1	1
0	0.0079	0.0158	0.0158	0.689	0.9095	0	0.0014	0.0014	0.0007	0.0096	0.0076	0.393	6	3	1
0.004	0.0158	0.0591	0.3701	4.878	7.0709	0.0014	0.0027	0.005	0.0155	0.0678	0.059	0.4155	5	1	1
0	0.0079	0.1772	0.2048	1.3032	1.6733	0	0.0014	0.0148	0.0086	0.0181	0.014	0.469	4	3	1
0.004	0.1024	0.2087	0.2205	1.2835	1.563	0.0014	0.0171	0.0174	0.0092	0.0179	0.0131	0.341	5	4	1
0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0512	0.3662	0.5158	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0022	0.0051	0.0043	0.321	4	3	1
0.3819	0.5158	0.8819	2.3268	7.193	15.4056	0.1273	0.086	0.0735	0.097	0.1	0.1284	0.43	4	3	1
0.1497	0.2205	0.3859	0.5473	3.7284	5.5276	0.0499	0.0368	0.0322	0.0229	0.0518	0.0461	0.514	3	1	1
0.0788	0.63	0.6654	0.6851	2.4292	3.1378	0.0263	0.105	0.0555	0.0286	0.0338	0.0262	0.4548	5	3	1
0.0276	0.1024	0.2008	0.9961	3.3741	3.6339	0.0092	0.0171	0.0168	0.0416	0.0469	0.0303	0.5153	5	3	1
0.0749	0.2048	0.2953	0.7638	1.6575	2.5906	0.025	0.0342	0.0247	0.0319	0.0231	0.0216	0.5083	6	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.1142	0.3583	0	0	0	0	0.0016	0.003	0.487	6	3	1
0	0	0.1103	1.5709	3.563	4.6024	0	0	0.0092	0.0655	0.0495	0.0384	0.5169	6	3	1
0.0158	0.0512	0.2875	0.3898	2.8071	4.5315	0.0053	0.0086	0.024	0.0163	0.039	0.0378	0.5168	6	3	1
0.1378	0.1497	0.1812	0.3859	2.9725	4.7245	0.046	0.025	0.0151	0.0161	0.0413	0.0394	0.517	6	3	1
0.0276	0.0355	0.2363	0.3544	3.0158	4.5788	0.0092	0.006	0.0197	0.0148	0.0419	0.0382	0.5172	5	3	1
0.0394	0.1536	0.5	0.7914	2.878	4.5079	0.0132	0.0256	0.0417	0.033	0.04	0.0376	0.517	6	3	1
0	0	0.0906	0.6024	2.9134	3.9331	0	0	0.0076	0.0251	0.0405	0.0328	0.4169	4	3	1
0	0	0.0906	0.8583	3.2205	5.3071	0	0	0.0076	0.0358	0.0448	0.0443	0.423	4	3	1
0.0119	0.0906	0.13	0.3426	2.9213	4.6142	0.004	0.0151	0.0109	0.0143	0.0406	0.0385	0.4121	1	3	1
0	0	0.0394	0.1339	1.7245	2.7402	0	0	0.0033	0.0056	0.024	0.0229	0.4131	6	4	1
0.004	0.0119	0.0237	0.0552	0.7993	1.4056	0.0014	0.002	0.002	0.0023	0.0112	0.0118	0	4	1	1
0.2678	0.5945	2.2756	3.5394	4.4371	4.4646	0.0893	0.0991	0.1897	0.1475	0.0617	0.0373	0.4596	4	3	1
0.0591	0.1024	1.1221	3.6497	4.6221	4.878	0.0197	0.0171	0.0936	0.1521	0.0642	0.0407	0.3854	5	3	1
0.0197	0.5079	1.5709	2.4252	2.6339	2.6851	0.0066	0.0847	0.131	0.1011	0.0366	0.0224	0.335	1	3	1
0.0237	0.2087	0.7756	2.4686	3.4174	3.6103	0.0079	0.0348	0.0647	0.1029	0.0475	0.0301	0.5031	4	4	1
0.3859	0.7284	1.1772	1.6536	2.1418	2.2875	0.1287	0.1214	0.0981	0.0689	0.0298	0.0191	0.36	4	4	1
0.3386	0.815	1.5119	1.9764	2.6693	2.8032	0.1129	0.1359	0.126	0.0824	0.0371	0.0234	0.392	4	4	1
0.0788	0.256	0.9607	2.1772	2.7441	2.941	0.0263	0.0427	0.0801	0.0908	0.0382	0.0246	0.3602	4	4	1
0.0079	0.0119	0.3819	1.752	2.7008	2.8544	0.0027	0.002	0.0319	0.073	0.0376	0.0238	0.4833	4	4	1
0.0788	0.1812	0.5237	0.7914	3.0315	3.4961	0.0263	0.0302	0.0437	0.033	0.0422	0.0292	0.3684	4	4	1
0.004	0.0276	0.0945	0.2087	1.9016	2.4725	0.0014	0.0046	0.0079	0.0087	0.0265	0.0207	0.331	4	4	1
0	0	0.0079	0.1221	0.5079	2.0394	0	0	0.0007	0.0051	0.0071	0.017	0.355	3	3	1
0	0	0.1103	0.6615	2.6969	5.7756	0	0	0.0092	0.0276	0.0375	0.0482	0.4167	6	3	1
0	0.0158	0.3111	0.8583	4.4095	7.0315	0	0.0027	0.026	0.0358	0.0613	0.0586	0.5158	6	3	1
0	0	0.0473	0.8347	2.2087	6.2953	0	0	0.004	0.0348	0.0307	0.0525	0.4652	6	3	1
0.004	0.0473	0.4922	0.9804	4.6812	6.2953	0.0014	0.0079	0.0411	0.0409	0.0651	0.0525	0.4645	6	3	1
0.13	0.2875	0.9489	4.8544	7.7796	8.4016	0.0434	0.048	0.0791	0.2023	0.1081	0.0701	0.3851	6	3	1
0.1497	0.5749	1.5512	2.8623	10.0119	12.5985	0.0499	0.0959	0.1293	0.1193	0.1391	0.105	0.4001	6	4	1
0.0512	0.2008	1.2993	2.5749	9.5591	12.6497	0.0171	0.0335	0.1083	0.1073	0.1328	0.1055	0.4011	6	3	1
0.0276	0.0945	0.7875	1.8662	2.4056	2.5276	0.0092	0.0158	0.0657	0.0778	0.0335	0.0211	0.4713	4	3	1
0.0276	0.0945	0.7875	1.8662	2.4056	2.5276	0.0092	0.0158	0.0657	0.0778	0.0335	0.0211	0.4713	4	3	1
0.1024	0.4213	1.3111	2.252	2.7284	2.8662	0.0342	0.0703	0.1093	0.0939	0.0379	0.0239	0.4636	5	3	1
0.0867	0.1063	0.1457	0.193	0.3071	0.3426	0.0289	0.0178	0.0122	0.0081	0.0043	0.0029	0.344	5	3	1
0.004	0.0079	0.2402	1.4922	2.1457	2.3189	0.0014	0.0014	0.0201	0.0622	0.0299	0.0194	0.4713	4	3	1

0.0079	0.0079	0.0552	1.4528	2.1497	2.3229	0.0027	0.0014	0.0046	0.0606	0.0299	0.0194	0.4715	5	3	1
0	0.0197	0.1615	0.1654	0.8662	2.8898	0	0.0033	0.0135	0.0069	0.0121	0.0241	0.4803	5	3	1
0	0.004	0.2914	0.689	2.4961	3.5906	0	0.0007	0.0243	0.0288	0.0347	0.03	0.3561	1	3	1
0.067	0.189	0.2953	0.7363	4.3623	4.5709	0.0224	0.0315	0.0247	0.0307	0.0606	0.0381	0.4906	4	3	1
0.3898	0.8111	1.2638	2.0906	6.756	7.8268	0.13	0.1352	0.1054	0.0872	0.0939	0.0653	0.5173	6	3	1
0.2008	0.2914	0.4882	0.6693	1.0315	1.1812	0.067	0.0486	0.0407	0.0279	0.0144	0.0099	0.5065	4	3	1
0.004	0.2441	0.3504	0.7678	2.6575	4.6693	0.0014	0.0407	0.0292	0.032	0.037	0.039	0.292	2	3	1
0	0.0473	0.0906	0.0906	1.3544	2.004	0	0.0079	0.0076	0.0038	0.0189	0.0167	0.4069	3	3	1
0.0276	0.0985	0.2678	0.3504	1.9095	2.6654	0.0092	0.0165	0.0224	0.0146	0.0266	0.0223	0.512	6	3	1
0.0827	0.189	0.4056	0.6024	2.9528	3.5749	0.0276	0.0315	0.0338	0.0251	0.0411	0.0298	0.3666	5	3	1
0.0512	0.0867	0.13	0.3268	1.4882	3.5906	0.0171	0.0145	0.0109	0.0137	0.0207	0.03	0	1	1	1
0	0.004	0.0315	0.1693	0.2087	0.2087	0	0.0007	0.0027	0.0071	0.0029	0.0018	0.4286	4	3	1
0	0	0	0	0.0237	0.0355	0	0	0	0	0.0004	0.0003	0.287	4	4	1
0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0079	0.0355	0.0394	0.0027	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0005	0.0004	0.225	4	4	1
0	0	0.0158	0.0158	0.0237	0.0276	0	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0003	0.222	3	4	1
0	0	0.0158	0.0158	0.0237	0.0276	0	0	0.0014	0.0007	0.0004	0.0003	0.222	2	1	1
0	0.0119	0.0276	0.0276	0.0276	0.0355	0	0.002	0.0023	0.0012	0.0004	0.0003	0.3454	4	3	1
0	0	0.0079	0.0276	0.0276	0.0355	0	0	0.0007	0.0012	0.0004	0.0003	0.3451	2	3	1
0.0197	0.0434	0.0473	0.0473	0.0473	0.0552	0.0066	0.0073	0.004	0.002	0.0007	0.0005	0.444	4	3	1
0	0	0.0158	0.0197	0.063	0.0906	0	0	0.0014	0.0009	0.0009	0.0008	0.421	5	3	1
0.0237	0.0355	0.067	0.0709	0.0749	0.1812	0.0079	0.006	0.0056	0.003	0.0011	0.0016	0.4452	1	3	1
0.0473	0.1812	0.6339	0.9843	1.8977	2.3977	0.0158	0.0302	0.0529	0.0411	0.0264	0.02	0.4143	4	3	1
0.8938	1.4174	2.3189	3.2678	5.13	8.9371	0.298	0.2363	0.1933	0.1362	0.0713	0.0745	0.3551	2	3	1
0.3504	0.7205	1.9292	4.1654	8.378	12.4292	0.1168	0.1201	0.1608	0.1736	0.1164	0.1036	0.3665	2	3	1
0.4528	1.0867	1.8071	3.7638	9.3623	13.4882	0.151	0.1812	0.1506	0.1569	0.1301	0.1125	0.3695	2	3	1
0.8819	1.4174	2.2835	3.2126	4.9056	8.5945	0.294	0.2363	0.1903	0.1339	0.0682	0.0717	0.516	6	3	1
0.2441	0.5827	1.3859	2.6142	4.9213	6.0473	0.0814	0.0972	0.1155	0.109	0.0684	0.0504	0.3896	3	3	1
0.067	0.2599	0.6733	2.0158	5.1457	6.4882	0.0224	0.0434	0.0562	0.084	0.0715	0.0541	0.3977	2	3	1
0.193	0.2953	0.6851	2.0276	5.2402	6.4371	0.0644	0.0493	0.0571	0.0845	0.0728	0.0537	0.3993	2	3	1
0.2363	0.4134	0.8544	2.2638	5.3701	6.4961	0.0788	0.0689	0.0712	0.0944	0.0746	0.0542	0.3933	1	3	1
0.256	0.4764	1.0867	2.7638	6.3662	7.8229	0.0854	0.0794	0.0906	0.1152	0.0885	0.0652	0.3893	4	1	1
0.2008	0.4567	0.9528	2.6103	6.4725	7.9331	0.067	0.0762	0.0794	0.1088	0.0899	0.0662	0.3896	2	3	1
0.1654	0.2402	0.5276	1.2008	5.3662	6.4804	0.0552	0.0401	0.044	0.0501	0.0746	0.0541	0.4111	4	3	1
0.0709	0.3741	0.9134	2.2323	5.1969	6.4252	0.0237	0.0624	0.0762	0.0931	0.0722	0.0536	0.285	4	3	1
0.1142	0.1969	0.5394	2.126	7.7756	8.6497	0.0381	0.0329	0.045	0.0886	0.108	0.0721	0.4745	5	4	1
0.0591	0.2166	0.504	1.6063	2.5197	4.126	0.0197	0.0361	0.042	0.067	0.035	0.0344	0.3583	4	4	1
0.0119	0.0237	0.8189	0.9095	1.7363	2.2363	0.004	0.004	0.0683	0.0379	0.0242	0.0187	0.493	4	3	1
0.0788	0.3544	0.5158	0.563	0.9686	1.0473	0.0263	0.0591	0.043	0.0235	0.0135	0.0088	0.4781	1	3	1
0.0906	0.1733	0.2993	1.3859	9.1497	10.2284	0.0302	0.0289	0.025	0.0578	0.1271	0.0853	0	4	4	1
0	0.004	0.0394	0.063	1.7756	3.8741	0	0.0007	0.0033	0.0027	0.0247	0.0323	0.253	6	4	1
0.0237	0.0355	0.1221	0.7323	1.126	1.2363	0.0079	0.006	0.0102	0.0306	0.0157	0.0104	0.375	4	2	1
0.1103	0.5276	0.9134	1.5276	3.1182	3.3268	0.0368	0.088	0.0762	0.0637	0.0434	0.0278	0.385	5	3	1
0.0119	0.0119	0.0394	0.1615	0.2245	0.2756	0.004	0.002	0.0033	0.0068	0.0032	0.0023	0.4791	3	1	1
1.8308	2.5788	6.7323	10.5119	12.004	12.13	0.6103	0.4298	0.5611	0.438	0.1668	0.1011	0.383	3	3	1
0.1969	0.7441	2.4449	7.5079	11.815	12.2126	0.0657	0.1241	0.2038	0.3129	0.1641	0.1018	0.4531	4	1	1
0.1969	0.6142	2.2638	7.2481	10.5276	10.8583	0.0657	0.1024	0.1887	0.3021	0.1463	0.0905	0.4561	4	1	1
1.0394	1.8544	2.8071	4.4843	4.9804	5.0355	0.3465	0.3091	0.234	0.1869	0.0692	0.042	0.39	3	3	1
0.3544	0.5158	0.7166	0.8189	1.1063	1.1851	0.1182	0.086	0.0598	0.0342	0.0154	0.0099	0.459	4	3	1

APPENDIX I

Artificial Intelligence Tools Used.

Tool Used	Purpose	Prompt/Activity	Results	Location
Gemini 2.5	For the automatic report generation feature of the application	<p>Generate a comprehensive risk assessment report for a potential landslide.</p> <p>The report should be structured, professional, and easy for a non-expert to understand.</p> <p>Your analysis should consider all the environmental data given to you by the system.</p> <p>Conclude with a clear risk level (e.g., Low, Moderate, High, Critical) and a list of actionable recommendations for Local Government Units (LGUs) and residents.</p> <p>**DISCLAIMER:**</p> <p>This report is based on the available data and predictive models. Ground conditions can change rapidly. Furthermore, this report was made using the gemini model. This assessment should be used as a guide for disaster preparedness and mitigation and not as a substitute for on-site engineering and geological assessments.</p>	Generation of a landslide report based on the given variables	Application: Automatic Report Generation

Chat GPT	<p>To ensure the needed number of sentences on each paragraph</p> <p>To ensure that the paragraph would be understandable and easy to read</p>	<p>Expand the paragraph to generate more sentences</p> <p>Make the structure of this paragraph better and coherent</p>	<p>Generation of sentences on to at least 3 sentences per paragraph</p> <p>A paragraph that contains the same meaning and content as the original but is better understood and is more coherent</p>	<p>Chapter III, section 3.3.4, 3.4 and Chapter V, section 5.1.2, 5.2.2, 5.2.3, 5.3.4, 5.4.1 and Chapter VI, section, 6.1.3.2</p> <p>Chapter I, section 1.4.2, 1.4.4, 1.5, 1.5.2, 1.5.3 and Chapter II, section 2.2.2, 2.2.3, 2.4, 2.7 and Chapter III, section 3.2, 3.3.1 and Chapter V section 5.1, 5.1.1, 5.2, 5.2.1, 5.4 and Chapter VI, section, 6.1.2, 6.2.3</p>
----------	--	--	---	---

APPENDIX J

Product Logo.

The Two Steps Ahead logo forms a symbolic reflection of our mission, method, and our team. In seeing the big picture, you see the shoe which represents a step forward toward preparedness. It showcases the idea that through our system, communities stay two steps ahead of possible landslide occurrences through timely forecasting. The two mountains rising above the shoe form the core visual of the logo. They signify both the landscapes we aim to protect and the steep terrains where landslide occurrences are common. Inside the shoe are the three trees, which symbolizes our team members. Just as trees make the earth stable reducing the landslide impacts, our team forms the foundation of Two Steps Ahead, the figures behind the development of this forecasting tool making it more stable and usable. Lastly, the four sticks represent the four key variables. Like shoelaces securing a shoe, they bind the system together to create a unified and dependable forecasting tool.

APPENDIX K

Team Logo.

The Red Rams logo forms the representation of our identity, purpose, and the spirit that strengthens our team. The bold red color of the ram represents fierceness, alertness, and passion. These are qualities that mirror us in remaining active, responsive, and committed in facing any difficult challenges that lie ahead. The ram, which stands as the central figure, signifies strength, resilience, and determination, much like how we navigate arduous tasks and technical obstacles with focus and dedication. The curved horn represents our eagerness to step back and see the bigger picture before moving forward, which shows that deep preparation is important in setting our ideas toward a successful launch. The ram facing right, symbolizes forward momentum. It reflects our journey from zero resources to continuous rebuilding and improvement. These elements create the Red Rams logo, a unified symbol of our perseverance, mindset, and a vision of moving forward continuously as a team.

APPENDIX L

Product Poster.

Two Steps Ahead

RANDOM FOREST IN FORECASTING RAIN-INDUCED LANDSLIDES

Problem Statement

Landslides, primarily triggered by rainfall, are a significant and unpredictable hazard that undermines key **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 11 and 15)**. This study uses the random forest model which improves landslide forecasting by integrating rainfall and environmental variables, achieving strong, reliable performance on unseen data. This highlights that a successful predictive solution depends on a multi-faceted approach combined with optimizing the model well.

SDG 11

SDG 15

Methodology

The methodology follows a clear sequence: First, data is collected and preprocessed. This prepared data is then used to train and validate the random forest model and used for statistical analysis. Finally, the validated model would then be integrated to the Two Steps Ahead web application.

Findings of the Study

Landslides in the study area are primarily triggered by prolonged rainfall, emphasizing the role of rainfall duration over intensity. However, the model reveals that soil moisture is the most dominant risk factor, elevating landslide odds more than 11-fold. Steeper slopes also significantly increase the risk, but to a lesser extent. The combination of saturated soil on steep terrain presents the highest level of hazard.

IMPACT OF ENVIRONMENTAL VARIABLES

Environmental variables have a significant impact on the probability of a landslide. Steeper terrain, for instance, increases the likelihood by a factor of 2.7. The type of soil is also a key factor, as some types increase susceptibility while others can reduce it. However, the most critical element is soil moisture, with very wet soil dramatically increasing the chance of a landslide by 11.7 times.

2.7x
HIGHER RISK
Significant Increase

1.2x
HIGHER RISK
Slight Increase

11.7x
HIGHER RISK
Very Significant Increase

IMPACT OF RAINFALL VARIABLES

Long duration rainfall is a much more significant predictor of landslides than short duration, intense rainfall. They are not primarily caused by sudden, brief downpours. Instead, they are the result of the ground becoming more progressively saturated and unstable over several days.

1.4x

1.4x

1.4x

1.5x

1.6x

1.7x

Conclusion

The Random Forest Model was **HIGHLY EFFECTIVE** at predicting landslides. Moreover, A combined model using both rainfall and environmental variables significantly outperformed models that used only one set of variables. The combined model achieved an **Accuracy of up to 91%**.

91%

Recommendations

Model accuracy may be enhanced through the incorporation of additional datasets such as land use, geology, and geomorphology.

Compare the current model with other machine learning algorithms to identify the optimal approach that balances accuracy with interpretability

The model can be further improved by developing a more comprehensive landslide inventory that has better quality, quantity, and accuracy.

Developed by: **RED Rams**
Ranmie Montecalvo Erik Agaban Daniel Lamaton

APPENDIX M

Product Packaging.

APPENDIX N

Grammarly Results.

APPENDIX O

Turnitin Results.

REFERENCES

A. Books

- {AE2021} Alpaydin, E. (2021). Machine learning. MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/13811.001.0001>
- {CD2014} Coghlan, D., & Brydon-Miller, M. (2014). The SAGE encyclopedia of action research (Vols. 1-2). London: SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446294406>
- {FY1996} Freund, Y., & Schapire, R. E. (1996, July). Experiments with a new boosting algorithm. In *icml* (Vol. 96, pp. 148-156).
- {GF2022} Guzzetti, F., Gariano, S. L., Peruccacci, S., Brunetti, M. T., & Melillo, M. (2022). Rainfall and landslide initiation. In Elsevier eBooks (pp. 427–450). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-822544-8.00012-3>
- {JA2024} Jaafari, A. (2024). An overview of triggering and causing factors of landslides. In Disaster risk reduction (pp. 25–45). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-4680-4_2
- {PS2019} Pradhan, S. P., Vishal, V., & Singh, T. N. (Eds.). (2019). Landslides: Theory, practice and modelling. Springer International Publishing. ISBN: 978-3-319-77376-6
- {PV2018} Profillidis, V. A., & Botzoris, G. N. (2018). Statistical methods for transport demand modeling. In Elsevier eBooks (pp. 163–224). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-811513-8.00005-4>
- {ZZ2021} Zhou, Z.-H. (2021). Machine Learning. Springer Nature. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-1967-3>

B. Articles

- {AC2021} Abancó, C., Bennett, G. L., Matthews, A. J., Matera, M. a. M., & Tan, F. J. (2021). The role of geomorphology, rainfall and soil moisture in the occurrence of landslides triggered by 2018 Typhoon Mangkhut in the

Philippines. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 21(5), 1531–1550.
<https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-21-1531-2021>

- {AC2024} Abancó, C., Asurza, F. A., Medina, V., Hürlimann, M., & Bennett, G. L. (2024). Modelling antecedent soil hydrological conditions to improve the prediction of landslide susceptibility in typhoon-prone regions. *Landslides*, 21(7), 1531–1547. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10346-024-02242-8>
- {AH2010} Abdi, H., & Williams, L. J. (2010). Tukey’s honestly significant difference (HSD) test. *Encyclopedia of research design*, 3(1), 1-5.
- {AR2006} Adler, R., Hong, Y., & Huffman, G. (2006). An experimental global monitoring system for rainfall-triggered landslides using satellite remote sensing information. NTRS - NASA Technical Reports Server. Retrieved from:
<https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20070017889/downloads/20070017889.pdf>
- {AH2019} Al-Najjar, H. A., Kalantar, B., Pradhan, B., & Saeidi, V. (2019, October). Conditioning factor determination for mapping and prediction of landslide susceptibility using machine learning algorithms. In *Earth Resources and Environmental Remote Sensing/GIS Applications X* (Vol. 11156, pp. 97-107). SPIE. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2532687>
- {AT2023} Atlan, T. (2023, December 12). Spatial data: Definition, types, examples, use cases & more! Atlan. <https://atlan.com/spatial-data/>
- {AT2023} Belcic, I., & Stryker, C. (2024, December 26). Supervised Learning. *What is supervised learning?* <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/supervised-learning>
- {BM2016} Beroya-Eitner, M. (2016). Landslides in the Philippines: Geo-physical controls, triggers, and examples. ResearchGate. Retrieved from:
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344538329_Landslides_in_the_Philippines_Geo-Physical_Controls_Triggers_and_Examples
- {BL2001} Breiman, L. (2001). Random forests. *Machine Learning*, 45(1), 5–32. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010933404324>
- {BM2024} Broquet, M., Cabral, P., & Campos, F. S. (2024). What ecological factors to integrate in landslide susceptibility mapping? An exploratory review of current trends in support of eco-DRR. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 22, 100328. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pdisas.2024.100328>
- {CS2022} CW. Authother (2022, March 16). Significance and use of Post-hoc Analysis studies. <https://www.cwauthors.com/article/significance-and-use-of-post-hoc-analysis-studies>

- {CY2021} Cheng, Y., Yu, T., & Son, N. (2021). Random forests for landslide prediction in Tsengwen River Watershed, central Taiwan. *Remote Sensing*, 13(2), 199. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13020199>
- {CZ2020} Chang, Z., Du, Z., Zhang, F., Huang, F., Chen, J., Li, W., & Guo, Z. (2020). Landslide Susceptibility Prediction Based on Remote Sensing Images and GIS: Comparisons of Supervised and Unsupervised Machine Learning Models. *Remote Sensing*, 12(3), 502. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12030502>
- {DM2024} De Moraes, M. A., Filho, W. M. M., Mendes, R. M., Bortolozo, C. A., Metodiev, D., De Andrade, M. R. M., Egas, H. M., Mendes, T. S. G., & Pampuch, L. A. (2024). Antecedent precipitation index to estimate soil moisture and correlate as a triggering process in the occurrence of landslides. *International Journal of Geosciences*, 15(1), 70–86. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ijg.2024.151006>
- {DN2005} Dendukuri, N., & Reinhold, C. (2005). Correlation and regression. *American Journal of Roentgenology*, 185(1), 3–18. <https://doi.org/10.2214/ajr.185.1.01850003>
- {ES2007} Evans, S. G., Guthrie, R. H., Roberts, N. J., & Bishop, N. F. (2007). The disastrous 17 February 2006 rockslide-debris avalanche on Leyte Island, Philippines: A catastrophic landslide in tropical mountain terrain. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 7(1), 89–101. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-7-89-2007>
- {GM2008} Geertsema, M., Highland, L., & Vaugeouis, L. (2008). Environmental impact of landslides. In Springer eBooks (pp. 589–607). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-69970-5_31
- {GD2023} Gómez, D., García, E. F., & Aristizábal, E. (2023). Spatial and temporal landslide distributions using global and open landslide databases. *Natural Hazards*, 117, 25–55. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-023-05848-8>
- {GF2006} Guzzetti, F. (2006). Landslide hazard and risk assessment (Doctoral dissertation, Universitäts-und Landesbibliothek Bonn). <https://bonndoc.ulb.uni-bonn.de/xmlui/handle/20.500.11811/2644>
- {GF2007} Guzzetti, F., Peruccacci, S., Rossi, M., & Stark, C. P. (2007). Rainfall thresholds for the initiation of landslides in central and southern Europe. *Meteorology and Atmospheric Physics*, 98(3–4), 239–267. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00703-007-0262-7>
- {HF2022} Huang, F., Chen, J., Liu, W., Huang, J., Hong, H., & Chen, W. (2022). Regional rainfall-induced landslide hazard warning based on landslide

susceptibility mapping and a critical rainfall threshold. *Geomorphology*, 408, 108236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2022.108236>

- {HH2018} Hong, H., Kornejady, A., Soltani, A., Termeh, S. V. R., Liu, J., Zhu, A., Hesar, A. Y., Ahmad, B. B., & Wang, Y. (2018). Landslide susceptibility assessment in Anfu County, China: Comparing different statistical and probabilistic models considering the new topo-hydrological factor (HAND). *Earth Science Informatics*, 11(4), 605–622. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12145-018-0352-8>
- {HO2013} Hungr, O., Leroueil, S., & Picarelli, L. (2013). The Varnes classification of landslide types: An update. *Landslides*, 11(2), 167–194. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10346-013-0436-y>
- {JJ2023} Jones, J. N., Bennett, G. L., Abancó, C., Matera, M. a. M., & Tan, F. J. (2023). Multi-event assessment of typhoon-triggered landslide susceptibility in the Philippines. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 23(3), 1095–1115. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-23-1095-2023>
- {JM2023} Jemec Auflič, M., Bezak, N., Šegina, E., Frantar, P., Gariano, S. L., Medved, A., & Peternel, T. (2023). Climate change increases the number of landslides at the juncture of the Alpine, Pannonian and Mediterranean regions. *Scientific reports*, 13(1), 23085. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-50314-x>
- {JK2024} Jisoo, K., Wan, B., Gao, Z., Zhou, S., Chen, H., & Shen, H. (2024). Research on machine learning forecasting and early warning model for rainfall-induced landslides in Yunnan Province. *Dental Science Reports*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-64679-0>
- {KD2010} Kirschbaum, D. B., Adler, R., Hong, Y., Hill, S., & Lerner-Lam, A. (2010). A global landslide catalog for hazard applications: method, results, and limitations. *Natural Hazards*, 52(3), 561–575. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-009-9401-4>
- {KM2020} Kuradusenge, M., Kumaran, S., & Zennaro, M. (2020). Rainfall-induced landslide prediction using machine learning models: The case of Ngororero District, Rwanda. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(11), 4147. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17114147>
- {LD2010} Lane, D. (2010). Tukey's honestly significant difference (hsd). In *Encyclopedia of research design* (Vol. 0, pp. 1566-1570). SAGE Publications, Inc., <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412961288.n478>
- {LE2020} Leonarduzzi, E., & Molnar, P. (2020). Deriving rainfall thresholds for landsliding at the regional scale: daily and hourly resolutions, normalisation,

and antecedent rainfall. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 20(11), 2905–2919. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-20-2905-2020>

- {LY2016} Le Bissonnais, Y. (2016). Aggregate stability and assessment of soil crustability and erodibility: I. Theory and methodology. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 67(1), 11–21. https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.4_12311
- {LB2019} Lim, B., Arik, S. O., Loeff, N., & Pfister, T. (2019). Temporal fusion transformers for interpretable multi-horizon time series forecasting. arXiv (Cornell University). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1912.09363>
- {LY2021} Liu, Y., Deng, Z., & Wang, X. (2021). The effects of rainfall, soil type, and slope on the processes and mechanisms of rainfall-induced shallow landslides. *Applied Sciences*, 11(24), 11652. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app112411652>
- {LL2020} Lombardo, L., Opitz, T., Ardizzone, F., Guzzetti, F., & Huser, R. (2020). Space-time landslide predictive modeling. *Earth Science Reviews*, 209, 103318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2020.103318>
- {MM2018} Marjanović, M., Krautblatter, M., Abolmasov, B., Đurić, U., Sandić, C., & Nikolić, V. (2018). The rainfall-induced landsliding in Western Serbia: A temporal prediction approach using Decision Tree technique. *Engineering Geology*, 232, 147–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enggeo.2017.11.021>
- {MB2018} Mirus, B. B., Becker, R. E., Baum, R. L., & Smith, J. B. (2018). Integrating real-time subsurface hydrologic monitoring with empirical rainfall thresholds to improve landslide early warning. *Landslides*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10346-018-0995-z>
- {NR2021} Naskar, R., Chowdhury, A., Sharma, M. C., & De, S. K. (2021). Rapid climate change and anthropogenic impact on landslides in South Sikkim, India. *Journal of Indian Geomorphology*. ISSN 2320-0731
- {NC2021} Ng, C. W. W., Yang, B., Liu, Z. Q., Kwan, J. S. H., & Chen, L. (2021). Spatiotemporal modelling of rainfall-induced landslides using machine learning. *Landslides*, 18(7), 2499–2514. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10346-021-01662-0>
- {NN2023} Nocentini, N., Rosi, A., Segoni, S., & Fanti, R. (2023). Towards landslide space-time forecasting through machine learning: The influence of rainfall parameters and model setting. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2023.1152130>
- {ND2017} Nolasco-Javier, D., & Kumar, L. (2017). Deriving the rainfall threshold for shallow landslide early warning during tropical cyclones: A case study in

- northern Philippines. *Natural Hazards*, 90(2), 921–941. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-017-3081-2>
- {PP2019} Probst, P. (2019). Hyperparameters, tuning, and meta-learning for Random Forest and other machine learning algorithms. Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München.
- {SS2018} Segoni, S., Piciullo, L., & Gariano, S. L. (2018). *A review of the recent literature on rainfall thresholds for landslide occurrence*. *Landslides*, 15(8), 1483–1501. doi:10.1007/s10346-018-0966-4
- {TF2022} Tehrani, F. S., Calvello, M., Liu, Z., Zhang, L., & Lacasse, S. (2022). Machine learning and landslide studies: Recent advances and applications. *Natural Hazards*, 114(2), 1197–1245. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-022-05423-7>
- {TA2022} Tiwari, A. (2022). Supervised learning: From theory to applications. In *Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning for EDGE Computing* (pp. 23-32). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-824054-0.00026-5>
- {TA2015} Trigila, A., Iadanza, C., Esposito, C., & Scarascia-Mugnozza, G. (2015). Comparison of logistic regression and random forests techniques for shallow landslide susceptibility assessment in Giampilieri (NE Sicily, Italy). *Geomorphology*, 249, 119–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2015.06.001>
- {UB2008} Utley, B. C., & Wynn, T. M. (2008). Cohesive soil erosion: Theory and practice. *World Environmental and Water Resources Congress 2008*. [https://doi.org/10.1061/40976\(316\)289](https://doi.org/10.1061/40976(316)289)
- {VC2008} Van Westen, C. J., Castellanos, E., & Kuriakose, S. L. (2008). Spatial data for landslide susceptibility, hazard, and vulnerability assessment: An overview. *Engineering Geology*, 102(3–4), 112–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enggeo.2008.03.010>
- {WS2021} Wang, S., Zhuang, J., Zheng, J., Fan, H., Kong, J., & Zhan, J. (2021). Application of Bayesian hyperparameter-optimized random forest and XGBoost model for landslide susceptibility mapping. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 9, 712240. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2021.712240>
- {WL2018} Wu, L., Zhang, L., Zhou, Y., Xu, Q., Yu, B., Liu, G., & Bai, L. (2018). Theoretical analysis and model test for rainfall-induced shallow landslides in the red-bed area of Sichuan. *Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the Environment*, 77, 1343-1353. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10064-017-1126-0>

- {XJ2019} Xie, J., Uchimura, T., Chen, P., Liu, J., Xie, C., & Shen, Q. (2019). A relationship between displacement and tilting angle of the slope surface in shallow landslides. *Landslides*, 16(6), 1243–1251. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10346-019-01135-5>
- {ZJ2015} Zêzere, J., Vaz, T., Pereira, S., Oliveira, S., Marques, R., & Garcia, R. (2015). Rainfall thresholds for landslide activity in Portugal: A state of the art. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 73, 2917-2936. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-014-3672-0>

C. Websites

- {AK2024} A, K. (2024, November 16). Understanding T-Statistic, F-Statistic, and P-Value in statistical analysis. Medium. <https://kishanakbari.medium.com/understanding-t-statistic-f-statistic-and-p-value-in-statistical-analysis-562463988bdc>
- {AW2024} AWS Amazon. (2024). What is hyperparameter tuning? <https://aws.amazon.com/what-is/hyperparameter-tuning/>
- {BA2023} Bhandari, A. (2023). Confusion matrix in machine learning. Analytics Vidhya. <https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/articles/confusion-matrix-in-machine-learning>
- {BN2024} Bressler, N. (2024, June 10). How to Check the Accuracy of Your Machine Learning Model. Deepchecks. Retrieved from <https://www.deepchecks.com/how-to-check-the-accuracy-of-your-machine-learning-model/>
- {BY2024} BYJUS. (2024, July 2). Types of soil - Sandy soil, clay soil, silt soil, and loamy soil. <https://byjus.com/biology/types-of-soil/>
- {CV2024} Chugani, V. (2024, June 21). *A Comprehensive Guide to K-Fold Cross Validation*. Datacamp. Retrieved December 3, 2025, from <https://www.datacamp.com/tutorial/k-fold-cross-validation>
- {CW1991} Critchley, W., & Siegert, K. (1991). A manual for the design and construction of water harvesting schemes for plant production. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. <https://www.fao.org/4/u3160e/u3160e05.htm>

- {ES2024} Earth Science Week. (2024). Soil moisture. <https://www.earthsciweek.org/resources/classroom-activities/soil-moisture/>
- {FK2024} Fabro, K. A. (2024, December 27). *Landslide in Philippines mining town kills nearly 100, prompts calls for action*. Mongabay Environmental News. <https://news.mongabay.com/2024/02/landslide-in-philippines-mining-town-kills-nearly-100-prompts-calls-for-action/>
- {GA2024} Gad, A. F., & Skelton, J. (2024, August 28). Evaluating deep learning models: The confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, and recall. DigitalOcean. www.digitalocean.com/community/tutorials/deep-learning-metrics-precision-recall-accuracy#accuracy-precision-and-recall
- {GC2021} Grand Canyon University. (2021, October 29). 5 Qualitative research designs and research methods. *GCU*. <https://www.gcu.edu/blog/doctoral-journey/5-qualitative-research-designs-and-research-methods>
- {G2025a} GeeksforGeeks. (2025, February 28). *Cross validation in machine learning*. GeeksforGeeks. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/cross-validation-machine-learning/>
- {G2025b} GeeksforGeeks. (2025, February 3). *Logistic regression in machine learning*. GeeksforGeeks. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/understanding-logistic-regression/>
- {G2025c} GeeksforGeeks. (2025, July 23). How to interpret odds ratios in logistic regression. GeeksforGeeks. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/machine-learning/how-to-interpret-odds-ratios-in-logistic-regression/>
- {G2024a} GeeksforGeeks. (2024, January 22). *OneWay ANOVA*. GeeksforGeeks. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/one-way-anova/>
- {G2024b} GeeksforGeeks. (2024, July 12). Random Forest algorithm in machine learning. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/random-forest-algorithm-in-machine-learning/>
- {G2023} GeeksforGeeks. (2023, December 7). Hyperparameter tuning. www.geeksforgeeks.org/hyperparameter-tuning
- {G2021} GeeksforGeeks. (2021, January 22). Hyperparameters of random forest classifier. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/hyperparameters-of-random-forest-classifier/>

- {G2024} Geoportal Philippines. (2024, November). Geoportal PH. <https://www.geoportal.gov.ph/>
- {GS2009} Glen, S. (2009). *F Statistic / F Value: Simple Definition and Interpretation*. Statistics How To. <https://www.statisticshowto.com/probability-and-statistics/f-statistic-value-test/>
- {GC2024} Google Cloud. (2024). What is supervised learning? <https://cloud.google.com/discover/what-is-supervised-learning>
- {IB2024} IBM. (2024). What is Random Forest? <https://www.ibm.com/topics/random-forest>
- {JA2024} Jain, A. (2024, February 6). A comprehensive guide to performance metrics in machine learning. Medium. medium.com/@abhishekjainindore24/a-comprehensive-guide-to-performance-metrics-in-machine-learning-4ae5bd8208ce
- {SN2023} Sharma, N. (2023, June 6). Understanding and applying F1 Score: AI evaluation essentials with hands-on coding example. Arize. arize.com/blog-course/f1-score
- {SA2024} Fiveable. (2024). Slope angle. library.fiveable.me/key-terms/geophysics/slope-angle
- {SD2024} *THE 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development*. (n.d.). <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
- {TD2024} Fiveable. (n.d.). Temporal data - (Intro to Visual Thinking) - Vocab, definition, explanations. Fiveable. <https://library.fiveable.me/key-terms/introduction-to-visual-thinking/temporal-data>
- {UN2017} UNISDR. (2017). *Words into Action Guidelines: National Disaster Risk Assessment - Hazard Specific Risk Assessment - Landslide Hazard and Risk Assessment*. https://www.unisdr.org/files/52828_03landslidehazardandriskassessment.pdf
- {US2017} U.S. Geological Survey. (2017). *What is a landslide and what causes one?* U.S. Department of the Interior. Retrieved February 19, 2025, from <https://www.usgs.gov/faqs/what-a-landslide-and-what-causes-one>
- {VC2024} Visual Crossing. (2024). Visual Crossing weather data. <https://www.visualcrossing.com/weather-data>

- {VM2023} Vivekanandan, M. (2023, August 17). Hyperparameters of Random Forests. LinkedIn.
<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/hyperparameters-random-forests-madhavan-vivekanandan>
- {WH2019} World Health Organization (WHO). (2019, November 26). Landslides. Retrieved from https://www.who.int/health-topics/landslides#tab=tab_1
- {WA2024} WINDY.APP. (2024). What is the total accumulated precipitation? <https://windy.app/blog/what-is-total-accumulated-precipitation.htm>
- {ZA2022} Zubair, A. M. (2022, November 30). Experimental research: Design, types & process. Department of Peace and Conflict Studies, University of Dhaka. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367044021_Experimental_Research_Design-types_process

D. Tools and APIs

- {BO2025} Bootstrap. Retrieved From: <https://getbootstrap.com/>
- {FL2025} Flask — Flask Documentation (3.1.x). Retrieved From: <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/stable/>
- {JU2025} Jupyter Notebook. Retrieved From: <https://jupyter.org/>
- {MA2025} MapBox | Maps, navigation, search, and data. Retrieved From: <https://www.mapbox.com/>
- {OM2025} Open-Meteo. Retrieved From: <https://open-meteo.com/>
- {OS2025} OpenStreetMap. Retrieved From: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/#map=5/13.03/121.77>
- {QG2009} QGIS Development Team (2009). QGIS Geographic Information System. Open Source Geospatial Foundation Project. Retrieved From: <http://qgis.osgeo.org>
- {SC2025} Scikit-Learn. Retrieved From: <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>

CURRICULUM VITAE

Name : ERIK A. AGABON
ORCID : 0009-0009-5030-4081
Program of Study : Bachelor of Science in Computer Science
Date of Birth : April 15, 2004
Contact Details : erikagabon125@gmail.com
Areas of Interest : Cyber Security, AI, Project Manager

Name : DANIEL JUN S. LAMATON
ORCID : 0009-0005-4045-6365
Program of Study : Bachelor of Science in Computer Science
Date of Birth : December 5, 2003
Contact Details : lamatond444@gmail.com
Areas of Interest : Project Manager, AI, Data Science

Name : RANMIE G. MONTECALVO
ORCID : 0009-0007-4078-9594
Program of Study : Bachelor of Science in Computer Science
Date of Birth : February 7, 2003
Contact Details : ranmiem@gmail.com
Areas of Interest : Web Development, AI, Mobile Development